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**Social, environmental and ethical
factors in engineering design
theory: a post-positivist approach**

Terence Love

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Department of Mechanical and Materials Engineering

University of Western Australia

**Social, environmental and ethical factors
in engineering design theory: a post-
positivist approach**

Terence Love B.A. (Hons) Engineering

**This thesis is presented for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy
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Department of Mechanical and Materials Engineering

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Abstract

This research investigated how social, environmental and ethical factors can be better included in theories of engineering design. The research focused on designing as an essentially human activity via consideration of the epistemological and ontological issues involved in constructing coherent design theory. The research investigations led to a clearer understanding of the roles of ontology, epistemology and methodology in design research and this clarification enabled the construction of a post-positivist approach to engineering design theory that better includes social, environmental and ethical factors alongside the existing products of scientific engineering design research. Other contributions to knowledge that emerged from the research process and which underpin the conclusions include; clarification of the terminology and basic concepts of design research and engineering design research, historical reviews of ways that the terms 'design' and 'design process' have been used in the literature of engineering design research and design research in the period 1962–1995, clarification of the role of disciplinary structure in the development of coherent design theories, the development of conceptual tools and perspectives for the epistemic, critical and meta-theoretical analysis of engineering design theory, and the development of a new meta-theoretical structure that offers the basis for unifying the theories and disciplinary structures of design research and engineering design research.

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Declaration by Candidate

In submitting this thesis for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy of the University of Western Australia the author acknowledges help from the individuals listed previously and from the authors of sources acknowledged throughout the text, but states that this thesis is entirely his own work.

Contributions to knowledge

The author claims the following contributions to knowledge:

1. The development of a post-positivist research position which enables the inclusion of human aspects of designing that can not be adequately addressed under the dominant positivist perspectives of engineering design research, but which does not exclude well justified positivist or scientific research findings.
2. Significant additional clarification of the epistemological and ontological foundations of engineering design theory.
3. The development of a coherent set of definitions that better differentiates between primary concepts of engineering design research, engineering design theory and design research.
4. The development of a new meta-theoretical perspective based on constructivism and critical analysis that enables several problems of engineering design theory, relating to the roles of human valuing and the relative nature of human understanding and cognition, to be analysed more satisfactorily.
5. The development of a new meta-theoretical hierarchical structure that enables the classification of elements of engineering design theory according to their level of abstraction. This structure aids the analysis and validation of engineering design theory, and helps define the relationships between different theories and metaphors of design.
6. Useful clarification of the role of the disciplinary structure of engineering design research in the formulation of engineering design theory.
7. Proposals for a disciplinary structure for engineering design research, based on the meta-theoretical relationship between theories of design at different levels of abstraction, whose external bounds align with other more established disciplines. This proposed disciplinary structure results in more straightforward relationships between the purpose of the discipline, its ontology and epistemology, its research perspectives, and its theories.

8. The development of the core of a human-centred basis for engineering design theory that resolves many of the problems with including social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory.
9. Development of a coherent framework of engineering design theory with the following benefits and characteristics:
 - It provides a more coherent and justifiable description of the activity of designing.
 - It establishes a philosophically more rigorous basis for the development of design theories, methods, techniques and aids.
 - It incorporates epistemologically well justified knowledge embedded in previous engineering design theory.
 - It provides a theoretical basis for the development of design practices and design methods in which social, environmental and ethical factors can be included in creative design activities.
 - It is based on post-positivist theories of knowledge.
 - Its ontological basis is that of designing as an intrinsically human activity like thinking or feeling.
 - It provides a well bounded version of design theory in which most of the activities previously considered to be part of design are relocated back to their original fields of study.
 - It places the intelligence of design in humans rather than in external processes or objects.
 - It is validated as theory by its coherence with other well-justified theory.
 - It is based on the premise that human's internalised management of information is essentially qualitative.

- It assumes the intrinsic inseparability of human values, assumptions, and biases from the activity of designing.
- It provides an epistemologically better justified theoretical means of approaching the design of technology for different societies and cultures because it includes, and allows, different human values, relating to social, environmental and ethical factors, into engineering design theory.
- It allows designing to be viewed as both an essentially unobjectifiable human internal process, and an observable, objectified external activity.

1. Introduction

1.1 *Background to research*

Research into engineering design has extended in many directions since its early focus on the theories and methods of systematic design which led to the formation of the Design Research Society in the UK, the Workshop-Design-Konstruktion (WDK) group in Germany and the Design Methods Group in the United States (Gregory 1966a; Jones and Thornley 1964a; Pahl and Beitz 1984). In the period from that time to the present, a variety of research avenues has been explored, and the pattern of these explorations – in design research in general and engineering design research in particular – has been laid out in thematic and conceptual taxonomies and reviews (see, for example, Cross 1984b, 1991, 1993, 1996; Dorst and Dijkhuis 1995; Franz 1994; Jones 1970; Konda et al 1992; Reich 1994; Ullman 1992). Since the mid-1980s, in spite of the wide variety of investigative approaches that are appropriate to design research, engineering design research has become dominated by an information-processing perspective on design which is supported by the extensive research that has been undertaken in the areas of artificial intelligence and computerised expert systems (Court 1995; Dasgupta 1991, 1992; Dixon 1987; Eder 1989; Gero 1991b; Pitts 1981; Reich 1992, 1994a, 1995; Rhodes and Smith 1989; Visser 1995; Wong and Shriram 1993; Yoshikawa 1985c). This focus on computerised information-based theories of design has proved useful in addressing many issues related to the technical aspects of problem-solving in designing, but, by giving privilege to perspectives that are efficient at addressing technical, quantifiable issues, it has led to a neglect of the non-technical, qualitative, human aspects of designing.

The qualitative aspects of designing are important because they are central to any attempt to produce a coherent design theory that includes humans and their condition (Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Dilnot 1982; Franz 1994; Reich 1994, 1995). Qualitative issues lie at the heart of any theory of creative cognition based on human values. They also provide the human value-laden context within which designed artefacts are intended to be used, and which design theories must include in the way they address the evaluation of both emerging partial designs and completed designs (Hamlyn 1990; Petroski 1992; Oxman 1996; Soufi and Edmonds 1996).

The problem addressed in this research is how engineering design theory might better include social, environmental and ethical considerations – the three primary qualitative aspects of human designing. The research focused on theory relating to the cognitive aspects of designing as undertaken by human designers, and did this without assuming that qualitative matters can be represented by quantified equivalents. The research was grounded in the practical problem of identifying how designers can improve the ways that information about social, environmental and ethical issues influences their designing. The current lack of design methods that provide a satisfactory means of including these issues points to the necessity of investigating how qualitative considerations can be addressed in engineering design theory. This analysis of engineering design theory points, in its turn, to the limitations of the positivist epistemological and ontological assumptions of engineering design theory as the roots of the research problem. Consequently it implies that the research problem may be resolved by building engineering design theory on different epistemological and ontological foundations. Therefore, undertaking this research depends on the application of different ontological and epistemological assumptions than those underpinning the positivist perspective that is dominant in the literature of engineering design research. What was undertaken in this research was nothing less than a re-envisioning of engineering design theory; a change of ontological and epistemological perspective for engineering design research from the purely positivist to a post-positivist perspective which includes the understanding that human reality is relatively valued, interpreted and individually constructed. This change in perspective is necessary in order to adequately include and address those issues that are central to resolving the research problem.

The main conceptual thread in this thesis is the analyses of the epistemological and ontological foundations of engineering design research and theory. Undertaking these analyses led to the development of a new analytical tool, a meta-theoretical perspective, and, in consequence, to a new meta-theoretical means of classifying design theory in terms of an hierarchy of abstractions. This meta-theoretical way of classifying design theory provides the basis for a theoretically radical means of comparing and contrasting existing theories and their conceptual elements. Alongside this main thread is a secondary supporting thread relating to resolving

conceptual and terminological confusion in design research that has been widely acknowledged from its inception but has not yet been addressed successfully (Hollins 1994; Lewis 1964; O'Doherty 1964; Pugh 1990; Ullman 1992). This conceptual and terminological confusion causes considerable problems for design researchers because it leads to difficulties of discussion, analysis and synthesis due to the lack of agreement on fundamental concepts and the use of terms in different ways by different design researchers. The post-positivist and meta-theoretical perspectives used in this research provide a means of circumnavigating and resolving much of this confusion.

1.2 Research problem and research questions

This thesis is grounded in the practical question, 'How can social, environmental and ethical matters be better included in designing?' Discussion of this practical problem leads into the realms of design theory where the problem must be expressed in theoretical terms and concepts. It is this theoretical aspect of the practical problem on which this research is focused. In Chapter 2, the practical problem is refined and the following research problem is defined in terms of the theories and concepts of engineering design research.

Can social, environmental and ethical matters be better included in theories about designing engineering artefacts by applying a post-positivist perspective ?

The literature of engineering design research is then reviewed in relation to the research problem, and from this review emerge five research questions that represent the essence of the research problem and which must be satisfactorily addressed for its resolution:

- 1. How can design theories be evaluated and compared?*
- 2. What are the implications of including human values in theories of human design cognition?*
- 3. What are the implications of using post-positive perspectives for research and theory-building in the area of engineering design cognition?*
- 4. What are the theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors?*

5. *How do designers use information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors?*

These research questions are addressed using the post-positivist and meta-theoretical perspectives developed in Chapter 3. It is concluded that developing improvements to the way social, environmental and ethical factors are included in theories of engineering design requires a human-centred focus to the theoretical foundations of engineering design theory. This focus also resolves many otherwise intractable problems of engineering design theory and leads to a disciplinary structure for engineering design research which comports better with other disciplines.

1.3 Justification for the research

Six main reasons for this research are outlined below. Each of them is discussed in more detail elsewhere in the thesis (see later this chapter and Chapters 2, 3 and 5). Firstly, there is widespread public concern about social, environmental and ethical issues in relation to technology. The magnitude and ubiquitousness of this public concern indicate that there is a need for further work in this area. Secondly, research in this area offers the possibility of clarifying the relationship between the internal subjective contexts of theories of designing (i.e. cognition), and the external contexts (i.e. social, environmental and ethical factors). Design theory that does not take adequate account of these internal and external contexts is technical theory or engineering theory rather than design theory. Hence, the research problem is central to developing a coherent theory of engineering design. Thirdly, previous attempts to include social, environmental and ethical issues in engineering design theory have not been successful. Fourth, the potential benefits of the approach, research methodology and theoretical perspectives used in this research have not been explored previously in the field of engineering design research. Fifth, the proposal in this thesis to bring both the external contexts of engineering design and theories of internal human design cognition into engineering design theory offers the possibility of developing a more coherent foundation for establishing fundamental concepts of engineering design theory and a better structured discipline of engineering design. Sixth, improving the effectiveness of transfer of technology to developing countries necessitates a means of including in engineering design theory the different norms of

human values in relation to social, environmental and ethical issues that are found in other cultures.

1.3.1 Public concern about social, environmental and ethical matters

There have been many changes to both the natural world and the ways in which human beings exist in the world due to the use of technology. Some of these changes have not been beneficial, and there is a considerable body of public and academic criticism of the ways that social, environmental and ethical issues have been addressed in relation to technological innovation (see for example, Beder 1990; Bellini 1987; Gasparski 1979; Illich 1974; Jonas 1982; Kostelanetz 1973; Meadows et al 1974; Pacey 1983; Papanek, 1984; Rapp 1989; Willoughby 1990). This widespread criticism gives support to the need for further research as to how engineering designers might better include social, environmental and ethical factors in their work. This thesis is intended to resolve some of the epistemological issues that stand in the way of the development of appropriate theories of designing in which social, environmental and ethical factors are included at least as fully as technical and economic factors.

1.3.2 Centrality of the research problem to engineering design and its context

Technology springs from the discipline of engineering. The final technical specifications of technological artefacts are defined in the design departments of industrial concerns. Thus, criticisms of technology are criticisms of the way that engineering is practised, and criticisms of the way social, environmental and ethical factors are included in engineering as a whole, are, in the main, directed towards engineering design practice. Design practice, however, is not a static phenomenon, nor are theories about how designers design well defined or well agreed upon (see for example, Coyne 1990c, 1991b; Dasgupta 1991, 1992; Hollins and Pugh 1989; Holt, Radcliffe and Schoorl 1985; Oxman 1990; Pugh 1982, 1990; Reich 1992). On the technical side, designers are now able to design artefacts which were impossible only a few years ago, and design them faster. Design related research is responsible for many of these changes. However, these improvements in the technical potential of engineering designers have not been matched by similar improvements in how designers understand, integrate and evaluate social, environmental and ethical factors in their work. Gasparski (1979) has argued that the adverse social, environmental and ethical consequences of technology are due to failures of design and

design research: that they have been 'caused by the failure of design and the knowledge of designing, the grasp of the essence of design, to keep pace with the changes of everyday life'. This view is supported by other researchers who have argued that research relating to the design of engineered artefacts has focused on the engineering and technical aspects of designs rather than the everyday, human aspects relating to how the designs change the world and human circumstances (Beder 1989, 1990, 1993a, 1993b; Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Papanek 1984; Singer 1995).

The importance of the research problem addressed in this thesis is that it lies at the intersection between research into engineering, research into designing and research into the social, environmental and ethical consequences of engineering design (see chapter 2). In Chapters 2 and 3, it is argued that social, environmental and ethical factors lie closer to the epistemological heart of designing in general, and designing engineering artefacts in particular, than technical concerns. The centrality of the research problem to research into engineering design is argued in Chapter 2 where the potential of the findings of this thesis to fundamentally influence the development of all three of the above areas of research is discussed. In Chapter 5, the centrality is evidenced in terms of the implications of the research findings for the development of a more coherent discipline of engineering design research and the unification of engineering design theory.

1.3.3 Attempts to address the research problem have so far not been successful.

Institutionally, there has been a world-wide concerted effort to reduce the adverse social, environmental and ethical impacts of technology, and to limit the use of technology where its social, environmental or ethical consequences are considered to be unacceptable by prevailing opinions. Examples of these institutional and legislative initiatives are Health and Safety standards, government legislated Environmental Protection Agencies (EPAs), environmental and social impact assessments conducted by EPAs and others, Codes of Practice and Codes of Ethics for engineering and other professionals, and national and international standards for different aspects of artefact design. Behind and supporting each of these, lie national and international laws which govern the common day-to-day relationships between humans, and

which are intended to guide and prescribe human actions. In spite of all these efforts, the use of technology has continued to create adverse social, environmental and ethical consequences – consequences that the above legislative and administrative systems were apparently developed to avoid (Beder 1993; Bunge 1989; Canter 1996; Fookes 1992; Jonas 1982; Martin and Schinzinger 1983; Papanek 1984).

One reason that social, environmental and ethical factors have not yet been satisfactorily addressed in engineering design is that theoretical and practical efforts relating to these matters have been focused mainly on technically completed designs (Beder 1993a, 1993b; Benn 1974; Ozbekhan 1974; Pacey 1983; Spencer 1991; Wallace and Burgess 1995). That is, the emphasis has been on the evaluation of the social, environmental and ethical issues after the specification of a solution to a problem has been completed with respect to technical and economic criteria. One explanation of this is that this is what engineering designers are required to do. This explanation is supported by the descriptions of the design process found in undergraduate texts on engineering design, and by the methodology and legal structures that underpin the two main formal processes in this area: environmental impact assessment and social impact assessment (Canter 1996; Ertas and Jones 1993). Inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors at this point is too late in the design process. They need to be included earlier, both in design practice and also in design theory. Further, the need to include these social, environmental and ethical issues at the very earliest stages in the evolution of a design implies that research into engineering design should focus on the details of creative human design cognition.

1.3.4 Methodology and theoretical perspective used in this research have been neglected

Cross (1992) suggested that resolving the research problems of the sort addressed in this research requires a 'successful simplifying paradigm of design thinking'. The essence of the arguments that are presented in Chapters 2 and 3 is that previous 'simplifying paradigms of design thinking' have failed because they have attempted to conceptualise designing as a mechanistic process. This observation is supported by those design epistemologists who argue that the mechanistic, deterministic, scientific and positivist outlooks that define the dominant

theoretical perspectives on design research are insufficient for addressing many aspects of engineering design (see Coyne 1990a, 1991b; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1993; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992; Daley 1982; Franz 1994; Petroski 1992; Reich 1994). Most simplifying paradigms of engineering have assumed that the role of design research is to find a design theory that would deterministically relate a particular design 'problem' with a particular design 'solution'. This assumption is widespread in the literature, but its clearest expression can be found in the early conferences on design and in discussions of theory about designing computer software and hardware (see, for example, Dasgupta 1991; Gregory 1996a; Jones and Thornley 1963).

The assumption of many researchers that the main aim of design research is to identify or create deterministic theory precludes the possibility of conceptualising designing as a dynamic entity where design activity events may sometimes be considered as designing, and sometimes not. One such dynamic definition of design is that 'designing depends on the attitude that the designer brings to the activity'. In other words, that designing only happens when the designer is 'designing' rather than addressing a problem using some other cognitive means (Thomas and Carroll 1979). Another dynamic definition is that 'designing is dealing with the as yet unknown'. Hence, the first time that an individual designer creates a design solution it is designing, but successive actualisations of the same solution are not designing. With both of these dynamic views of design, if a deterministic relationship can be established between problem and solution, then moving from problem to solution is no longer designing because design activity has become routine.

The emphasis in the field on positivist scientific determinism has also meant that many areas of research that are potentially relevant to design research have either been neglected or have been inappropriately quantified and then included as if they were technical (Crane 1989). In the field of systems research, it has become necessary to look beyond positivism and include the qualitative contexts of designed systems. For example, Flood (1990, 1995) has argued that a philosophical review of systems research is necessary to reflect the new understandings offered by the alternative post-positivist outlooks, and Singer (1995) has similarly argued that the inclusion of social concerns in management theories is now well justified. These changes in the

field of systems research have implications for engineering design research for two reasons. Firstly, there is an historically intimate theoretical dependence of engineering design research on systems research, and secondly, the engineering design process is frequently viewed as a business decision-making system (Coplin 1989; Love 1995).

What is needed is a reformulation of the theoretical foundations of engineering design theory so that it can include the factors and issues which are part and parcel of designing but which are better expressed qualitatively. The post-positivist approach proposed in this research is widely accepted in other disciplines, and its adoption is encouraged by design epistemologists, yet it has been neglected so far in mainstream engineering design research and theory-making.

1.3.5 Usefulness of potential applications of this research

This research offers the possibility of developing improvements to engineering design research in several ways, not least by answering the widespread criticism that it is difficult to compare, contrast and critically analyse different theories and concepts because of the lack of adequate epistemological foundations, fundamental concepts and well defined terminology (Daley 1982; Dilnot 1982; O'Doherty 1963; Pugh 1990; Ullman 1992). Hence, resolving the focal issues of this research is likely to be of use in resolving other major problems in design theory, particularly problems relating to the role of human valuing and the relative nature of human understanding and cognition. The main benefits of this research are:

1. It offers the opportunity of resolving conflicts and removing inadequacies that are at the root of the problems of engineering theory and terminology through its focus on the epistemological and ontological foundations of engineering design theory.
2. It has the possibility not only of addressing the social, environmental and ethical aspects of engineering design more adequately, but also of doing this without contradicting well justified scientifically-based theories of engineering design.
3. It clarifies the bounds and structure of the discipline of engineering design by addressing ontological and epistemological issues which help define the relationships between engineering design and its disciplinary neighbours.

4. The theories and concepts developed as a result of this research improve the coherence between the concepts, theories and research perspectives of engineering design research and other disciplines.

1.3.6 Summary of justification for investigating this research problem

To restate: the main justifications for this research are that:

1. There is widespread public concern about the ways that social, environmental and ethical matters are addressed, or fail to be addressed, in the process of creating technology.
2. Research into social, environmental and ethical aspects is central to the establishment of coherent engineering design theory.
3. Attempts to include social, environmental and ethical matters by using a positivist, technical perspective have not so far been adequate or successful.
4. Alternative perspectives to positivism have been neglected in engineering design research, and these perspectives offer means of addressing many of the problems associated with positivist attempts to include social, environmental and ethical matters into engineering design theory.
5. Applying post-positivist perspectives to issues relating to design cognition and the human context of designed artefacts offers a means of improving both the foundations of engineering design theory and the structure of the discipline of engineering design research.

1.4 Methodology and Theoretical Perspective

The primary means of addressing the research problem in this thesis is through investigating and clarifying its epistemology and ontology. These ontological and epistemological investigations have been undertaken in two stages,

1. Clarification of the definitions and relationships between the different concepts relating to epistemological and ontological analysis (such as 'methodology', 'theoretical

perspective', 'theoretical structure', 'paradigm', 'method', 'theory'), and the ways they are used in this thesis. This is necessary because of variations in the use of basic terms in this area (Indurkha 1992; Phillips 1987; Stegmüller 1976).

2. The separation of the different epistemological and ontological situations relating to 'the research and thesis', 'the problem' and 'the problem context'. This separation is necessary to avoid confusion between different epistemological and ontological analyses and to avoid conflation of conclusions across conceptual divides. The epistemological situations are different for the researcher (the theoretical position applied during this research), the subject of research (concepts and theories of engineering design research), and the research context (designers and their cognition, and the representation of social, environmental and ethical matters).

The terms and concepts relating to research in this area, the structure and dynamics of theory-making, are not widely agreed (see for example, Feyerabend 1975; Guba 1990a; Indurkha 1992; Popper 1976; Rosen 1980; Stegmüller 1976). One of the outcomes of this research is the development of a semantic structure that positions different epistemological terms and their different interpretations. In particular, it has been necessary in this research to clarify the differences between the ideas of 'methodology' and 'theoretical perspective'. Put simply for the purpose of this section, 'methodology' guides 'what to do' and 'theoretical perspective' guides 'how to think or theorise'. Thus, taken together, 'methodology' and 'theoretical perspective' form the bulk of the epistemological and ontological foundations of any research and theorising.

After clarifying the definitions and relationships between different terms and concepts relating to the epistemological and ontological analysis of theory, the next step was to draw boundaries between different parts of the research. The main boundaries that were used were between:

1. The methodology and theoretical perspective that guide this research and thesis.
2. The methodologies and theoretical perspectives that are applied, in this thesis, to the analysis of the work of other researchers.

3. The methodologies and theoretical perspectives that are implicit in the engineering design research and engineering design theory that is discussed in this research.
4. The methodologies and theoretical perspectives used by engineering designers.

Making these boundaries explicit has been an important aid in this research because much of the literature in this area has used terminology and conceptual content which masks important differences both in reality and theory. The main gains from establishing the above boundaries have been:

- Identification of the necessity for separate analyses for each of the areas of this research.
- Understanding that different theoretical approaches are appropriate to the circumstances found in each of the areas of this research.
- Avoidance of the inappropriate use of concepts and arguments that belong to epistemologically different circumstances.
- Avoidance of the inappropriate conflation of conclusions drawn from one area of research into another.

The detailed discussions of the terms and concepts relating to the epistemological and ontological analysis of theory, and the structural boundaries in this research are found in Chapter 3.

1.4.1 Methodology and theoretical perspective used in this research: a pragmatic constructivist meta-theoretical perspective underpinning a critical methodology

A pragmatic critical constructivist perspective was chosen as the theoretical basis for this research. This perspective is particularly appropriate in this context because it provides the conceptual space necessary for investigating matters relating to designing in which due consideration of individual constructions and interpretations of reality is essential and paramount (Guba 1990a; Reich 1994a). The relativity of truth, validation and evaluation within a constructivist framework leads in turn to the need for a critical methodology (Feyerabend 1975; Franz 1994; Guba 1990a; Indurkha 1992; Reason and Rowan 1981a; Reich 1994a, 1994b;

Rosen 1980). In addition, this research must have a meta-theoretical stance because it involves epistemological and ontological analysis of the foundations of engineering design theory *qua* theory (Stegmüller 1976). In addition, a meta-theoretical approach and a critical methodology are needed to circumnavigate the widespread confusion within engineering design research about concepts and terminology, and the lack of adequate definition of foundational concepts. A critical methodology is the most appropriate means of referring to the work of other researchers in these circumstances and a meta-theoretical perspective offers a means of clarifying the theoretical and terminological confusion (Dixon 1987,1989; Hollins 1994; Suh 1990; Ullman 1992).

The application of the above pragmatic critical constructivist perspective and critical methodology led to two new research techniques in this area:

1. A meta-theoretical perspective for use in decomposing theories into their contributions at different levels of conceptual abstraction.
2. A meta-theoretical hierarchical taxonomy that classifies elements of engineering design theories according to their relationship to the activity of designing rather than to the characteristics of the designed object.

This latter hierarchy, used in combination with the meta-theoretical perspective, provides a means to quickly and easily identify the contributions of different design concepts and theories. It offers a simple means of identifying and resolving many of the problems implicit in existing theory in this field. In addition, the hierarchy provides the basis of a new disciplinary structure for the field of engineering design research. This new structure has three advantages; its focus is on the structure of design, design theory and design research rather than engineering theory and engineering research, it avoids the manifold problems associated with the domain-based structure that is echoed in library classifications such as the Dewey call system (see Appendix 3), and it offers a means of establishing design research as academically separate from the subject domains whose information is used by designers.

1.4.2 Use of critical analysis in this thesis

The critical methodology of this thesis is applied to the subject matter for several purposes.

Again it is necessary to separate these roles to avoid unnecessary conflation. The main roles of the critical methodology are in:

- Textual analysis
- Semantic analysis
- Conceptual analysis
- Meta-theoretical analysis

Practically, this research involves analysing the research and theories of others which are communicated by textual means. The textual analyses of the work of design researchers raises many semantic issues (Hollins 1994; Ullman 1992) to which the critical methodology can be applied in turn. Once semantic issues are resolved to the level that theories and concepts become clarified, then the critical methodology can be applied to compare, contrast and validate those theories and concepts. At this stage the critical methodology is used for *conceptual analysis*. What remains unaddressed is the validity and appropriateness of the foundations in which the theories and concepts are grounded: the epistemic and ontological concerns. The critical methodology is used meta-theoretically to analyse how a subject is researched and theorised about and how those theories are validated.

1.4.3 Summary of issues of methodology and theoretical perspective

There are several aspects to the methodology of this research. In short these are:

- Definitions and structure of epistemological and ontological concepts.
- The separation of the analyses relating to 'the research', 'the research problem', and 'the research context', that is,
 - The methodology and theoretical perspective that guide this research and thesis

- The methodologies and theoretical perspectives that are applied in this thesis to the analysis of the work of other researchers
 - The methodologies and theoretical perspectives that are implicit in the engineering design research and engineering design theory that is discussed in this research
 - The methodologies and theoretical perspectives used by engineering designers
- The choice of a pragmatic constructivist meta-theoretical perspective and a critical methodology for this research.
 - The application of the critical methodology across textual, semantic, conceptual and meta-theoretical analyses.

A detailed discussion and justification of the above points is found in Chapter 3.

1.5 Outline of this thesis

This thesis follows the recommended five chapter PhD structure of Perry (1996). The five chapters are:

1. Introduction
2. Literature review
3. Theoretical position
4. Research findings
5. Conclusions and implications

Perry's structure has been used for three reasons; firstly, because it was devised with the intention of satisfying the main concerns voiced by PhD examiners; secondly, because it accords with general guidelines for reporting research; and thirdly, because it matches well with contemporary advice on the PhD writing process (Bjelland 1990; *Degree of Doctor of Philosophy*

Handbook 1993; Langrish 1993; Lindsay 1995; Perry 1996; Phillips and Pugh 1987; *Style Manual* 1994).

The five main chapters of the thesis are followed by,

- List of references
- Appendix 1: Annotated bibliography of definitions of the term 'design' 1962–1995.
- Appendix 2: Annotated bibliography of definitions of the term 'design process' 1962–1995.
- Appendix 3: List of Dewey Call Numbers relating to literature of design research and engineering design research.
- Appendix 4: DesignWeb Researchers' Database 1996 [on-line].
- Appendix 5: Four lists of the characteristics and skills of human engineering designers.

1.5.1 Chapter 1 - Introduction

This first chapter provides an overview of the thesis. It outlines the background to the research problem, the research questions that are investigated, the justification for this research and issues of methodological and theoretical perspective.

The description of the structure of the thesis, this section, is followed by the final three sections, (1.6 to 1.8). In section 1.6, the terminological issues relating to this area of research are introduced along with the definitions of terms used in this thesis. In section 1.7, the way that this research has been delimited is described along with the key assumptions that form the basis of the way that this research is formulated. Section 1.8 concludes Chapter 1.

1.5.2 Chapter 2 - Research Issues that ensue from the literature

The second chapter establishes the basis of the research in detail with respect to the relevant literature. Chapter 2 starts from the broad area in which the practical problem is grounded, clarifying and defining the practical problem as a research problem. This clarification leads, in turn, to the specific research questions that bound and define the research. Alongside this evolution of the practical problem into research questions, the relevant literature in the parent

disciplines is reviewed and structured. As part of this review and structuring of the literature, several models are developed to classify the literature in this field in order to facilitate its analysis. The classificatory structures developed in this chapter set the ground for the new, formally defined classificatory methods which are developed in Chapter 3.

1.5.3 Chapter 3 - Theoretical perspective and methodology

In Chapter 3, the details of the theoretical perspectives and research methodologies used in this research are developed and justified. It is in this chapter that the core of this research is described and that the research problem is addressed by clarifying the philosophical basis for asking the research questions. A substantial part of the contributions to new knowledge of this thesis are developed in this chapter. These contributions consist of:

- A new way of structuring the concepts and terminology in the field of epistemological and ontological analysis (also called the analysis of alternative research paradigms or alternative research methodologies (Guba 1990a; Reich 1994a))
- A new approach to analysing the epistemological and ontological foundations of design theories
- The development of a new technique for meta-level analysis of theoretical and conceptual relationships
- The development of a new way of structuring existing knowledge and theories of engineering design research.

The theoretical perspective and its associated methodology is the theoretical equivalent of a practical experimental technique in which the above developments form the theoretical means for addressing the research questions. The results of the research follow directly from asking the research questions from this theoretical perspective.

1.5.4 Chapter 4 - Analysis of textual and conceptual data

The textual and conceptual data generated by this research are the answers to the research questions when asked from the theoretical perspective developed in Chapter 3. These answers follow directly from the theoretical perspective and the questions with the minimum of

analysis, investigation or discussion. This phenomenon, of the results being simply and immediately consequent on the clarification of the theoretical foundations of the research questions, has been previously noted by Dilnot (1982).

In Chapter 4, the answers to the research questions are presented. The discussion of the implications of the findings of this research for their wider context is left until Chapter 5.

1.5.5 Chapter 5 - Conclusions and wider implications

In the final chapter, the research is reviewed and the results of Chapter 4 are summarised and analysed both with respect to the research problem and its wider theoretical contexts. The theoretical implications for the disciplines of engineering design research and design, and the unification of engineering design theory, are presented along with the practical implications that relate to engineering design practice and the training of engineering designers. The contributions to knowledge that originate in this research are identified and suggestions are made for the direction of further research in this area.

1.6 Terminology and definitions

Before embarking on the detail of this research project, it is necessary to define and clarify some of the terms that are used in this thesis. Using the existing terminology of engineering design research is problematical for several reasons. Firstly, the purpose of this thesis is to clarify some of the fundamental concepts in this field, and hence it presumes the possibility that some existing definitions are unsuitable. Secondly, there are wide variations of meaning in the terminology used by design researchers. Thirdly, what is drawn out later is that the validity of research into engineering design, and the way that concepts and theories have been analysed in the literature, have been adversely influenced by the terminology that has been used. Fourth, there is confusion between the terminology and concepts of engineering, engineering design and engineering design research. Fifth, the subjects of this research are the different theories and foundations of engineering design research, and hence the analytical terminology used must be sufficient to avoid confusion between the analyses and what is analysed. These problems of terminology in design research have been raised directly and indirectly by several prominent design researchers (French 1985; Jones 1970; Hollins 1994; Lewis 1963; O'Doherty

1963; Reich 1994a, 1994b; Ullman 1992; Wray 1992). Additional evidence of fundamental terminological problems is the wide variety of definitions of design and design process found in Appendices 1, 2, 3 and 4.

Despite the obvious need for clear definitions of fundamental concepts, little attention has been paid to semantic and terminological exactitude in design research. New terms have not been developed to support new concepts. Instead, the meanings of existing terms have been changed or extended, or multiple meanings have been attributed to them. This lack of terminological precision, consistency and structure presents design researchers with problems in comparing, contrasting and analysing existing design theories, and the clarification and resolution of semantic and conceptual issues is an ongoing theme throughout this thesis. The problem is addressed in several steps:

- A review of existing definitions of the terms 'design' and 'design process'.
- The establishment of a temporary working definition of design.
- A definition of the role of engineering design research, and the separation of the roles of engineering, engineering design and engineering design research.
- The separation of the terminology of engineering, engineering design and engineering design research.
- The definition of key terms about engineering, engineering design and engineering design research from a perspective of engineering design research.
- The definition of key terms that relate to research methodology and theoretical perspective.

1.6.1 Review of definitions of 'design' and 'design process'

The literature of engineering design and design research from the period 1962–1995 was reviewed as a basis for understanding the detail of the terminological problems relating to definitions of the terms 'design' and 'design process'. The outcomes of this review of the literature are the annotated bibliographies of Appendices 1 and 2, and the distilled overviews

and definitions of terminology that follow in the main text. Appendices 1 and 2 show that the terms 'design' and 'design process' have had many different definitions, and most of these are poorly justified, inconsistent, or contain epistemological contradictions.

1.6.2 A working definition of 'design'

The word 'design' has been used in many ways, but only recently (in the 1950s and 1960s) have the processes, concepts and methods involved in designing come under widespread scrutiny in the industrialised western world (Jones 1970). This scrutiny has led to the development of new design theories, concepts and methods, along with a range of disciplines and subdisciplines dedicated to design research. Each of these developments has been based on some idea of design or designing, but without a concerted effort to clarify and agree on a universal definition of the term design. In fact, as O'Doherty (1963) claimed, 'design' has been used as a catch-all term that has effectively defined a null set of meanings by its universality. This wide range of meanings which has been attributed to it across different subject domains, topics, concepts and levels of abstraction has caused many problems which are discussed in detail later in Chapter 3. Grammatically, the term 'design' is found in the literature as a noun, verb, adjective and adverb, and each of these presents a range of different semantic problems.

- As a **noun** – for example, 'the *design* of the Eiffel Tower'.
- As a **verb** – for example, 'vehicle engineers *design* cars'.
- As an **adjective** – for example, 'a *design* problem'.
- As an **adverb** – for example, '*design* computing'.

There is little controversy over the use of 'design' as a noun to refer to some sort of specification of a designed object or the object itself. This sort of definition, however, refers only to objects in the public realm. For research involving the internal subjective realms of designers the definition of 'design' becomes less well agreed. For example, it is not evident in research into design emergence whether the definition of design refers to all of the thought in a designers head that is to do with the manufacturing specification of an artefact, or only that part which emerges in some publicly available specification (see, for example, Soufi and Edmonds 1996).

The 'de-facto' basis for the majority of definitions of design is the idea of design as a process (see Appendix 2). In spite of the underlying unity of this process definition, almost all those who define design define it differently (see Appendix 1). Although almost all definitions of design are a response to the unstated question 'what is design?', what is ignored by many researchers is the idea of designing as a human *act*, and in consequence most definitions describe design as some sort of process that relates what went on before the act of designing to the situation afterwards. Dilnot (1982) pointed out that this basis for defining 'design' means that the activity of designing disappears from the theoretical scene. The purpose of defining 'design' has changed: the intention was to make a definition about the activity, and the result was a definition that was concerned only with associated peripheral phenomena; that is, the design problem and the design that resolves it. In other words, the perspective has changed from design research to some other research perspective, and in most cases it becomes engineering research, research into information processes, research into artificial intelligence, or applied physical research.

In the design research literature, the explicit definition of design as a verb is much less common than its definition as a noun. Instead, 'design' as a verb, is implicitly defined by its definition as a noun. For example, Hubka (1985) defined design (noun) as,

A process in which the designed [sic] problem (based on demands) is transformed into a description of technical systems (technical product).

In this case, implicit in the definition of the noun 'design' is the definition that the verb 'to design' means to 'to transform'. It is at this point that Dilnot's (1982) paradox comes into play: the discussion by Hubka about 'designing' refers to the information and knowledge about the problem and the description of technical systems, that is, the solution rather than the human creative act of designing. Therefore, the focus has been tacitly changed from one of philosophical or psychological inquiry about the activity of designing into an inquiry about the objects being designed.

There are some researchers who have viewed designing primarily as an activity, but their activity-based definitions lead to much the same conclusion as the definition of Hubka above

(Chakrabarti and Bligh 1994; Lawson 1993; Thomas and Carroll 1979). For example, Chakrabarti and Bligh (1994) regard designing as,

the activity of transforming the functional requirements of a design into a solution concept or concepts for fulfilling requirements.

As with the noun definition, the practical consequence of these activity-based definitions is a change of focus from research which attempts to reveal something about the human creative act, to research that reveals relationships between the physical properties of the problem and its solution.

Similarly, the adjectival and adverbial usage of the term 'design', not surprisingly, follow the same path as the noun definition of design, and are defined by the way that they are used to connect concepts and activities to the theories of design. For example, 'design' as an adjective in *design management* is defined through the definition of *design management* as 'management in the context of design'.

The few exceptions to Dilnot's rule which avoid the trap of attempting to undertake design research through the perspectives of engineering or other disciplines, and which avoid the language of the designed object, do not lead to precise, useful, bounded definitions of design. For example, Petroski (1992) focuses on the human aspect, but his definition does not provide adequate guidance for a structure of design theory,

engineering design is an endeavour of, by, and for human beings. In both principle and practice it has incontrovertibly human characteristics no understanding of engineering design can be expected to be complete without an appreciation of its uniquely human dimensions and attributes . . .

Similarly, Thomas and Carroll (1979) focused on the role of human cognition and tied their definition of design to the attitude or intent of the designer, suggesting that design happens when a problem-solver 'views his/her problem or acts as though there is some ill-definedness in the goals, initial conditions or allowable transformation'. This perspective on design depends on ontological and epistemological assumptions that are implicit in the description, but neither

the description nor the assumptions lead to a usefully defined and bounded foundation for design theory.

Coyne and Snodgrass (1993) made the following statements about design and design research,

Clearly it is designers that design.

Design is not a rule-based or symbol processing activity

An understanding of design should begin with the experience of design.

Each of these contributions helps avoid Dilnot's trap but each in itself contributes only a little to a definition of design, and then only by laying the grounds for the development of a definition. The problems of scope and precision in a definition of design that has a well justified epistemological foundation have not yet been overcome: to quote Duggan (1970) 'engineering design is a complex activity which is not easy to define comprehensively.'

This leaves the problem of defining design for the purpose of this research because, at this stage, what is needed is a 'working' definition of design that enables the research and thesis to continue. What is necessary is a definition that includes the mainstream positions about how design has been perceived so far. This definition must be wide enough to include all that is included by other researchers but, if it is to have some utility, it must be tight enough to exclude what is not obviously associated with design. The problem here is to avoid, on one hand, O'Doherty's (1963) charge of creating a definition that includes everything and hence defines nothing and, on the other hand, to avoid defining design so tightly that it limits the possibility of exploring new areas of conceptualisation that might lead to a better definition of design, or that excludes what other researchers have included and thus precludes discussion of their work.

This problem of scope and precision of the definition of design is not a new one in design research; it was discussed in detail by Jones (1970). Jones came to his own definition of design as 'initiating man-made things'. To get to this definition he started from a definition of design that was based on public perceptions of design before the modern interest in researching into design, that is, when designing was intimately connected with craft. Jones claimed that prior to

the advent of design research, design was defined in terms of designers' social and commercial roles, that is, 'it was sufficient to know that designing was what engineers, architects, industrial designers and others did in order to produce the drawings needed by their clients and by manufacturers'. Jones' early definition is appropriate here because this thesis focuses on the roots of engineering design theory and part of its purpose is to define 'designing' in an epistemologically better justified manner. This, in a sense, is a similar search to that which would have been appropriate at the commencement of research into design at the time of Jones' discussion.

The working definition of design that is used in this thesis is based on Jones' definition, but it places Jones' definition within a framework that assumes that designing is different from other activities. Therefore, the definition of design that is used in this thesis is,

Design – what engineering and other designers do to initiate change in human-made things that distinguishes them from, for example, engineers.

1.6.3 Definitions: engineering and technology

Engineering is often considered synonymous with technology, but there are differences between engineering and technology that are significant for research into engineering design, particularly for this research, because it spans from the use of engineering principles in design across to the social, environmental and ethical implications of technology. Both Willoughby (1990) and Pacey (1983) have attempted to clarify the terminology in this area, and there is substantial agreement between both their definitions and the analyses that support them. Willoughby offered a more extended and critically detailed technological terminology than Pacey, but Pacey provided an additional socio-cultural perspective along with a semantic correlation between 'technology', 'society' and 'environment'. The definitions of Willoughby and Pacey have been adapted for use in this thesis and these adapted definitions are given below:

Technology – an ensemble of artefacts intended to function as relatively efficient means. That is, an intentional group of artificial elements that are intended to function in a particular way for a particular purpose.

Technological – a term used to qualify all operations, activities, situations and phenomena which involve technology.

Technical – used as an adjective or adverb, to qualify human or non-human phenomena dedicated to efficient, rational, instrumental, specific, precise and goal-oriented operations.

Technicity – a term used to denote the factor or quality itself which makes something technical. Technicity is a defining feature of technology, but technology may involve other features besides technicity.

Technique – denotes a human skill which involves a significant technical element.

Technological science – a phrase used to denote either the scientific study of technology, or scientific practice which involves a significant amount of technology.

Whilst Willoughby defined ‘Technology-practice’ as denoting all things technological, Pacey has widened that definition so that it parallels the socio-cultural perspective of ‘medical practice’ (as described by, for example, Grbych 1996; Illich 1988). It is in Pacey’s sense of ‘technology-practice’ that it is possible to discuss the technology-practice of a country, a culture or a business organisation. The idea of a culturally based technology-practice is important for engineering design research as it offers a means of testing the coherency of engineering design theory with developments in the social sciences. In Pacey's terms,

Technology-practice – means the whole activity associated with the production and use of technology including its basis in technical knowledge, its organisation and its cultural aspects.

Pacey’s concept of ‘practice’ and his definition has been used in this thesis. His definition of technology-practice forms the basis of a similar concept of ‘engineering-practice’ that is described later.

‘Engineering’ is in common use as a noun, a verb, an adjective and an adverb. It has been widely used to denote both craft and scientific methods for the production of technologies. In this thesis, following the conventions of Willoughby and Pacey, the following definitions are used:

Engineering – as a *noun* refers to the discipline of engineering (verb).

Engineering – as a *verb* denotes the activity of producing technology, or an activity related to the production of technology.

Engineering – as an *adjective* and *adverb* qualifies activities and practices which lead to technology being produced.

Engineering research – research into engineering issues that results in engineering theory.

Engineering theory – one of many theories that engineering designers, that is, those practising engineering design, use to gain further information about the likely behaviour of designed artefacts, for example, theories about machine dynamics, behaviour of materials and kinematics.

Engineering-practice – the activity of producing technology, including its basis in technical knowledge, its organisation and its cultural aspects.

Engineering science – the scientific study of engineering and the scientific practices by which technology is produced. Engineering science is used in engineering practice.

1.6.4 Definitions: engineering design research

The definitions of engineering design and engineering design research that are used in this thesis follow on directly from the definitions of design and engineering given earlier, that is:

Engineering design – the activity of designing technological artefacts.

Engineering design research – research that investigates the activity of designing technological artefacts.

The next issue that needs addressing concerns the overlapping terminology of engineering, engineering design and engineering design research. The definitions that are chosen for this thesis must improve linguistic clarity rather than add to the confusion. Engineers, engineering designers and engineering design researchers have different perspectives on engineering design and this leads to differences in the definitions given to the term ‘engineering design theory’.

The main focus of many engineers and engineering designers is on engineering calculations and, for them, the term 'engineering design theory' refers to mathematically expressed theories such as the kinematics of mechanisms, theories relating to structural integrity, and theories about the dynamics of fluids. The focus of other engineering designers, however, is on the design problem and the artefact being designed. For these engineering designers, the term 'engineering design theory' refers to theory relating to the characteristics of the designed object. This latter view is indicated by the ways that industrial designers, automotive designers and architects discuss, analyse and theorise about their designs (see, for example, Baljon 1997; Hillier and Penn 1994; Reich, Konda, Monarch, Levy and Subrahmanian 1996; Tovey 1997, 1992a, 1992b). Engineering design researchers that focus on the activity of designing, however, are theorising about that activity and, for them, an 'engineering design theory' is a theory about the *activity* of designing engineering artefacts.

These three meanings of 'engineering design theory' can be reduced to,

- An engineering theory.
- A theory about the designed object.
- A theory about designing.

All of these meanings of 'engineering design theory' are found in engineering design research, perhaps because of the historic origins of this discipline in engineering (see, for example, Beck 1966; Duggan 1970; Eder 1966; Himmelblau 1974; Jones 1970; Wong 1974).

In this research, the first two meanings of 'engineering design theory' above present problems because one of the tasks of engineering design researchers is to identify and classify the different types of knowledge and information which engineering designers use, and engineering theories and theories about designed artefacts are parts of this knowledge or information base (Court 1995). The terminological complexity of engineering design research, and this thesis in particular, is reduced by avoiding use of the term 'engineering design theory' as engineering theory or theories about engineering artefacts. Consequently, the definition of

engineering design theory used in this thesis builds on the definitions of design and engineering derived earlier.

Engineering design theory and **theory of engineering design** – a theory about the activity of designing as it relates to designing engineering artefacts and seen from a perspective of engineering design research.

1.6.5 Definitions: design research

In the above sections, terms were defined that are fundamental to research into engineering design, but research into the design of engineering artefacts also depends on the terminology and theories of the generic field of design research, and this field presents its own terminological difficulties. In this section, key terms of design research that relate to this thesis are defined in the following areas:

- Philosophical terminology
- Problem terminology
- Domain terminology
- Disciplinary terminology

1.6.5.1 Definitions: philosophical terminology

The term 'design theory' has had many meanings, partly because of its incorporation of the term 'design' and also because the combination of the two generic terms 'design' and 'theory' has led to it being applied to many subjects and from a variety of theoretical perspectives. It has been in widespread use by engineers to mean 'engineering theories which engineering designers use'. It was the name given to a subject area in mathematics in which mathematical 'designs' are analysed; it has been used by designers to mean theorising about artefacts, and it has been used by design researchers to refer to theorising about design (Dasgupta 1992; Hughes and Piper 1985). This semantic diversity has given rise to several difficulties in the area of engineering design research. For example, when a particular 'design theory', drawn from the field of Design Theory in Mathematics, was adapted into the field of design research it led to a

particular mathematical model about the characteristics of a design problem and its solution being inappropriately privileged with the title of 'General Design Theory' (Reich 1995).

The following definitions of 'design theory' and its equivalent 'theory of design' have been chosen to align with the semantic and conceptual framework established by the terms that have been defined in this thesis so far, and to avoid the terminological difficulties of design research.

Design theory and **theory of design** – are used in this thesis to mean 'a theory about the activity of designing and its associated knowledge' as seen from a perspective of research into designing. In addition, 'design theory' is a subdiscipline of design research.

These definitions of 'design theory' accord with general usage in the design research literature where the two meanings are sometimes typographically differentiated by differences in capitalisation as shown in the following examples,

- *Engineering Design Theory* is the title of a disciplinary or sub-disciplinary classification or field of research into design.
- An *engineering design theory* is a theory about the activity of designing engineering artefacts.

In this sense, *design theories* are studied in the subdiscipline of *Design Theory*. Where it has been necessary, in this thesis, to refer to the mathematically privileged meaning of design theory, an appropriate indication is provided in the text.

The term 'general design theory' is used in this thesis to refer to theories that claim to encompass all aspects of the activity of designing. 'General Design Theory' (GDT) is, however, already in use in the fields of design research and engineering design research to refer to a scientific and mathematical theory of design first devised by Yoshikawa (1981) which was originally intended to provide a basis for developing computer aided engineering design systems (Reich 1995; Tomiyama 1994). It is claimed by Tomiyama (1994) that GDT extends beyond being a design theory and that 'it is a theory about design knowledge or even knowledge in general' but the arguments presented later in this thesis, in Chapters 2 and 3, along with the critique of GDT by Reich (1995), contradict Tomiyama's views on the scope of

GDT. The phrase 'general design theory' and its equivalent 'general theory of design' are used in this thesis as follows,

General design theory and **general theory of design** – has been used in this thesis to mean a theory of design that is complete, that is, a theory that brings together particular individual design theories and defines the relationships between them into a system that has been epistemologically and ontologically well justified, and which integrates well with wider human knowledge.

The phrase 'design concept' has also been used in many different ways in the field of design research, for example:

- It has been used to refer to the *concepts* which a designer holds in mind while designing
- It is a term applied to the *representation* of thoughts in a 'design', for example, the 'design concept' that underpins a particular engineering drawing.
- It has been used to refer to the *actualised embodiment* of ideas in an artefact, that is the 'design concept' behind a particular physical device.

The application of 'design concept' in the above three epistemologically different circumstances indicates a lack of attention to the epistemological role of the idea of a concept in the development of theory, that is, the relationship between concepts and theories. From the perspective of design research as research into the activity of designing, theories about designing are based on concepts about designing, that is, 'design theories', theories about designing, are built up from 'design concepts', concepts about the activity of designing. The definition of design concept used in this thesis, therefore, is based on the role of design concepts as a basis for theory-making in design research, that is,

Design Concept – a concept about the activity of designing

The terms 'design methods' and 'design methodology' have been used synonymously in the literature of design research (Cross 1984d). Cross drew attention to this early confusion between method and methodology and inferred that the study of 'design methodology' was tacitly

undertaken by those theorists and researchers involved in the design methods movement when they took into account those aspects of method development which would be more properly categorised as 'methodological'. This implies that there are two histories of design methods and design methodology. The first history, explicitly reported by Cross (1984b) and Franz (1994) has the study of design methods starting in the 1950's and being followed by the development of the study of design methodology in the late 1970's. The second history, implicit in Cross' analysis, is that the study of design methods and methodology proceeded concurrently.

The phrases 'design method' and 'design methodology' are differentiated in this thesis. The definitions that are given below are chosen to accord with the use of each phrase in the design research literature, with the terminology defined in previous sections, with epistemological analysis and with common language.

Design method – refers to 'a method used by a designer to manipulate information'.

Design methodology – is used here in two ways, first to mean an 'an arrangement of design methods', secondly to refer to the 'study of design methods', for example, 'the field of design methodology'.

The phrase, 'design philosophy' has previously been used to describe the study of philosophical questions relating to design. Design philosophy has, however, historically intimate connections with the study of design methods, that is, the definition of the phrase 'design philosophy' has effectively become limited to the philosophical study of design methods and design methodologies (Cross 1984b, 1984c, 1993). This de facto definition of design philosophy has strongly influenced the framework within which philosophical issues relating to design have been considered, and contradicts the idea of design research as research into designing because its focus is on techniques for designing rather than the activity of design itself (Coyne and Snodgrass 1992a). This means that 'design philosophy' is not a suitable title for the philosophical study of all aspects of design theory because theories related to design and the concepts associated with them cover a wider range of issues than the methods, methodologies and techniques of design. The phrase 'design philosophy' will be avoided in this thesis.

The phrase 'philosophy of design' has often been used interchangeably with 'design philosophy', but where philosophy and design research are brought together, 'philosophy of design' is a more useful overarching term because it refers to the field where epistemological and ontological questions relating to design theory are addressed along with matters of meta-theory, for example: 'What, in general, is design?', 'What are the characteristics of a valid theory of design?', 'What are the characteristics of a theory of objects being designed?', 'How might a theoretical design concept be tested for coherency with other concepts?' and 'Should a theory of objects be part of design theory?' Philosophy of design is used in this thesis to refer to such philosophical enquiry and also to the scholarly activity in which theories pertaining to design are proposed and validated. In this sense, the 'philosophy of design' has a role in the disciplinary structure of design research similar to that of the 'philosophy of science' in the natural sciences. The definition of 'philosophy of design' used in this thesis complies with the above analyses, that is,

Philosophy of design – that subdiscipline or field which concerns itself with ontological, epistemic and structural issues relating to theorising about the activity of designing.

1.6.5.2 Definition: problem terminology

In line with the mathematical terminology of 'well' and 'ill' conditioned solutions, design researchers have referred to 'well' and 'ill' defined *problems*, and 'well' and 'ill' structured *problems* (see, for example, Rittel 1972a; Rittel and Webber 1973, 1984). In the literature about design problems, the terms 'defined' and 'structured' are often used interchangeably, but in this research a distinction is made between them. Well-defined and well-structured problems lead to possibilities for automating designing, and conversely investigating how designers address ill-defined or ill-structured problems presents some of the greatest difficulties for design researchers (Thomas and Carroll 1979).

Well-defined and ill-defined problems – refers to whether the description of the problem is complete and sufficient enough to establish whether a particular solution satisfies that problem.

Well-structured and ill-structured problems—refers to whether the problem has an internal structure that is coherent and well-defined and whether the problem fits within a structure of specific design knowledge that is likely to lead routinely to a solution.

Thus, a design problem can be well-defined, yet ill-structured, but it is unlikely that a problem can be ill-defined and well-structured.

1.6.5.3 Definitions: domain terminology

The term 'domain' is used to relieve the terminological complexity when the analyses and theories of design research refer to disciplines associated with either the designed artefact or the subject knowledge used by the designer, for example, the domains of engineering, electronics, and hydraulics, because it releases terms such as 'subject' or 'field' for other purposes. This is especially useful when analyses span combinations of design activity, design process, disciplines, methods, methodologies and design knowledge. The domain terminology also offers the means of differentiating between those concepts and theories of design that depend on particular domain technicity and those that are defined independently. For example, the designing of chemical plant is domain dependent because it depends on specific information relating to chemical processes and industrial plant, and, in this sense, the skills and activities of designing chemical plant are not identical to the skills and activities involved in designing (say) racing car engines. In contrast, research into creativity is in most cases domain independent because creative activity is unique to an individual and can happen in any domain.

In this thesis, the 'domain' terminology defined below agrees with its widespread use in the design research literature.

Domain— is the term used to refer to the subject area that the designed artefact would conventionally be classified in, or the discipline that is most significant as a source of information for the designer, for example: engineering, electronics, hydraulics, thermodynamics.

Domain dependent— is used to refer to those design theories and concepts that depend on information or designerly skills of disciplines related to the design problem, the design analyses or the designed solution.

Domain independent – refers to design theories and concepts that are not dependent on the particular information or skills that are grounded in the disciplines related to the design problem, design analyses or the designed solution.

1.6.5.4 Definitions: disciplinary terminology

The 20th century scrutiny of design and design processes has led to the formation of several fields or sub-disciplines concerned with the study of designing which are distinct from the disciplines or domains in which designing takes place. New titles for these domain independent fields of design research have been coined almost yearly, but there is little agreement on either their precise definition, or on the precise areas of scholarly endeavour which they describe. For example, in 1979, Archer rhetorically asked what had become of the subdiscipline of Design Methodology, and answered himself by listing nine of the main subdisciplines of design research in the late 1970s.

Design Methodology is alive and well, and living in the bosom of its family: design history, design philosophy, design criticism, design epistemology, design modelling, design measurement, design management and design education.

Archer indicated that sub-disciplinary titles had changed in this early period and, as a result of these changes, 'design methodology is found under the name of design research'. Since that time, new titles for these subdisciplines of design research have been coined almost yearly. Some of Archer's sub-disciplinary categories have declined in popularity, and others are still in contemporary use, but there is little agreement on either their precise definition, or on the precise areas of scholarly endeavour which they describe. Nearly twenty years after Archer's comments, the subdisciplines of design research have still not stabilised (Cross 1997). In January 1997, Cross reported on a preliminary internal review by the Design Research Society of keywords from papers published in *Design Studies* from 1992 to 1995 – these would be expected to represent the sub-disciplinary and conceptual categories of design research. Over 200 different keywords had been used across 96 papers and out of this selection, 170 were used only once and a further 28 were used only twice. Further evidence of the lack of agreement about the sub-disciplinary categories of design research is evidenced also by the predominance of lightly

populated categories in a database of design researchers' areas of research interest (*DesignWeb Researchers' Database* 1996). Both the review of keywords in *Design Studies* and the categories of the *DesignWeb Researchers' Database* point to the sub-disciplinary structure of design research being fragmented and confused.

The choice of key terms that are discussed and defined in this section is guided by their relevance to this research and their importance in clarifying the analysis of disciplinary issues relevant to resolving the research problem. The majority of the terms are domain independent. In many cases, associated domain dependent sub-disciplinary titles can be found by prefixing a domain name, for example, 'engineering design history' is one of the domain dependent aspects of 'design history'. The six sub-disciplinary terms whose usage is analysed in this section are,

- Design History
- Design Studies
- Design Research
- Design Thinking
- Design Science
- Science of Design

The term 'design history' has two meanings in the literature,

- The historically based classification and interpretation of designed artefacts, design methods and design cultures which have developed in different cultures over time.
- The history of the conceptual development of a particular designed artefact.

The first is sometimes called 'design studies'. Perhaps because of the massive amount of material involved, practitioners in this area consider themselves to have only begun to touch the surface of this work, and as recently as 1992, Margolin claimed that,

As an academic subject, design history received a strong impetus in the early 1970's, and yet there is still little that can gain recognition for the subject as a solid field of study.

The term 'design history' is also used to describe the history of a designed artefact's development in which the different partial conceptualisations and other milestones of designing, which a designer, or group of designers, have evolved on the way towards a final artefact description, are catalogued into a conceptual history. The use of this meaning of 'design history' has received recent impetus from two directions; research focusing on analysing design activity from a protocol perspective and research based on information transformation perspectives (see, for example, Akin and Lin 1995; Court 1995; Nagy, Ullman and Deiterrich 1992; Waldron and Waldron 1988; Wong and Shriram 1993; Visser, 1995).

The term, 'design studies' has been used in the literature of design research to refer to anything to do with the study of design. This is its use as the title of the journal of the Design Research Society and this is the sense in which it is used in this thesis.

The term 'design research' has been used as an umbrella term to cover all investigations into the activities of designers, concepts related to the field of design, and the relationships between design and other disciplines. The significance and all-encompassing nature attributed to the term 'design research' is seen in its use in the name of the Design Research Society . In this thesis. 'design research' is used to mean research into the *activity* of designing and this differentiates . the meaning of the term 'design research' from the all encompassing 'design studies' which refers to the study of *anything* to do with design.

The term 'design thinking' concerns the cognitive aspects of designing. In 1992, Akin deconstructed the concept of design thinking and defined 'design thinking' as 'the totality of cognitive activities that occur during designing'. This resulted in Akin separating the design thinking that is thinking about the design problem and its solution from the design thinking that is thinking about designing, i.e. he separated designing from research into designing in the manner proposed earlier in this thesis. He also separated 'thinking' from other neurological activities associated with designing. That is Akin's definition of 'design thinking' excludes,

- All thinking that is done whilst not designing
- All thinking about designing
- The neurological activities that occur during designing but which are not 'thinking'

Akin avoided a naive mechanistic perspective on design cognition by viewing *design thinking* as a combination of *design reasoning* and *design intuition*. By defining it in this manner Akin brought creativity into mechanistic information-processing theories of design through the theories of cognitive science. The weakness of Akin's model, however, is its separation of thinking from human feelings, motivations and values by including intuition in a model of thinking that is separated from associated neurological activities. This precludes Akin's model from including the human aspects of designing and any biologically based explanation of that human behaviour. In short, Akin's theory of design thinking follows the usual line through Dilnot's paradox, and results in a theory of design cognition based on information about the design problem and its physical solution.

At this early stage of this research it is clear that it is necessary to include the 'human aspects' of designing in theories of creative design cognition, but whether it is best to include feelings and other aesthetic aspects of creative and evaluative processes into a definition of 'design thinking', or to define design thinking in some complete and coherent manner that is concerned only with conscious thoughts is not clear. What is clear, however, is that it is essential not to semantically conflate or confuse the two definitions.

The terms 'design science' and 'the science of design' have both had a variety of different meanings attributed to them in the literature, and they have frequently been used interchangeably (Cross 1993). Many researchers have taken them to be synonymous with 'design research', 'design theory' and 'design philosophy' (Dixon 1987, 1989; Eder 1995; Finger 1991; Hongo 1985; Hubka 1985; Hubka and Eder 1988, 1990; Suh 1990). In 1985, Hubka gave over-riding privilege to design science in research into engineering design arguing that 'Design Science is the most complete area of engineering design covering the whole field of problems' and Hubka and Eder (1990) extended this claim reporting that,

*An attempt is being made, under the collective title of design science, to build up an integral system of logically related insights and knowledge that should contain **complete** [emphasis added] knowledge about and for designing.*

The essence of these claims by Hubka and Eder and other researchers who view design research as a scientific process identical or very similar to physical research, has been widely challenged (see, for example, Coyne 1991b; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992a, 1992b; Cross 1989; Dasgupta 1991; Duggan 1970; Franz 1994; French 1988; Guba 1990a, Jones 1970; Phillips 1987, 1990; Pugh 1990; Rosen 1980; Wray 1992). The arguments against using science as the primary model for design research focus on the limitations of the scope of the scientific perspective: in essence, science is unable to address adequately many of the fundamental aspects of research into designing. What many designers and design researchers have emphasised is that designing as a subject of research is fundamentally different from research into either purely physical phenomena or purely rational cognition, and that a research perspective is needed that can address those human aspects of designing that lie outside the ambit of science. In addition, Coyne and Snodgrass (1991, 1992a) have argued that it is not only inappropriate for a purely scientific paradigm to be the dominant basis of design research, it is also inappropriate for it to be used as a conceptual bridge between theories of design research and the development of improved design practice.

Cross, in 1993, reviewed the conceptual and terminological status of both 'design science' and the 'science of design'. He demonstrated the confusion around the use of the two terms, but concluded that it was possible to separate their meanings in a way that might be widely agreed upon in the field. This is because 'design science' and 'science of design' have mainly been used in the design research literature to;

- Describe the activity of designing as seen from a scientific perspective.
- Indicate a scientific set or subset of research into design.

On this basis Cross suggested the following definitions that would clarify these differences:

'Design science' refers to an explicitly organised, rational and wholly systematic approach to design: not just the utilisation of the scientific knowledge of artefacts, but design also in some sense as a scientific activity itself.

and

The 'science of design' refers to that body of work which attempts to improve our understanding of design through scientific (systematic, reliable) methods of investigation.

Cross' definitions are used in this thesis unless otherwise stated.

1.6.6 Definitions: theoretical analysis

A variety of terms and concepts have been used in this thesis in relation to the analysis and discussion of the structure and dynamics of theory-making, and the formulation of design related analyses. The key terms are defined as follows:

Abstraction – A mental construct or concept which enables the identification, communication and manipulation of an idea or pattern of ideas. Each abstraction has a verbal or literal identifier such as: 'red', 'hydrodynamic theory', 'concept'.

Æsthetic – the definition used in this thesis goes beyond the *Webster Comprehensive Dictionary* (1986) definition of 'pertaining to beauty', and includes the internal human activities, perception and values that enable beauty to be perceived. In this sense, æsthetics is an epistemological and ontological precursor to ethics and theory. This position on æsthetics aligns with other research in this area that extends beyond positivism (see, for example, Coyne 1997; Croce 1959; Dewey c1933,1959; Feyerabend 1974; Guba 1990a; Holt 1997; Kenny 1994; Ryle 1949, 1979; Schön 1983, 1987, 1992; Scruton 1994; Stolterman 1994; Vivante 1980).

Critical Analysis – A philosophically-based technique used to criticise, compare and contrast the structure and meanings of abstractions and the relationships between them.

Epistemology – refers to the relationship between theory and ontology ('the study of knowledge and truth' (*Webster Comprehensive Dictionary* 1986); 'the study of the nature of

knowledge and justification' (*The Cambridge Dictionary of Philosophy* 1995)). Epistemology also provides the bridge between ontology and research methodology because epistemology is the study of how reality is represented by theory that has been created as a result of research method.

Epistemological perspective – the way that the relationship between reality and theory is defined for a particular analysis or theoretical proposal.

Ethics – the 'philosophy of morals' (*Webster's Comprehensive Dictionary* 1986); 'the philosophical study of morality' (*The Cambridge Dictionary of Philosophy*). In this thesis the focus is on the human internal processes by which 'right and wrong', and 'good and bad' are differentiated by individuals rather than the properties of the objects or concepts that make them, for example, good or bad. In this sense, ethical propositions are theories (moral theories) and, like other theories, are epistemologically dependent on aesthetic foundations and justification.

Meta – Is used here to mean above, higher or transcending in a theoretical sense (*Webster Comprehensive Dictionary* 1986). The term, 'meta' is normally used to refer to the elevated conceptual position used for analysis or criticism, for example, **meta**-cognition is the cognitive position needed to be able to watch and discuss normal cognition.

Meta-theory – a theory that organises and defines patterns of relationships between concepts and theories at a lower level of abstraction.

Meta-theoretical hierarchy – The classification of theoretical elements into different levels of abstraction in a similar manner to that used in defining systemic or holonic models of systems and sub-systems.

Meta-theoretical position – A level of abstraction which provides the concepts and theories that enable the analysis and classification of theories, concepts and arguments at lower levels of abstraction.

Meta-theoretical analysis – An analytical technique whose subjects are theory and theory-making and whose focus is on theories, concepts, analyses and critiques as theoretical

abstractions rather on what they represent. Meta theoretical analysis is a technique for identifying and clarifying the epistemological relationships between particular theories, concepts, analyses and critiques and for testing the validity and coherency of both the theories, concepts, analyses and critiques and their relationships.

Meta-theoretical perspective – an epistemological perspective that focuses on the meta-theoretical aspects of relationships between theoretical elements, arguments and analyses.

Metaphor – A description of a phenomenon or set of concepts and conceptual relationships to which it does not literally apply. A useful way of grouping abstractions around a familiar concept. The idea of metaphoric representation may also be seen as a framework within which individuals or groups conceive reality and that both bounds and guides their thoughts, actions and the theories which they develop (Coyne 1990a, 1990c, 1991b; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992a; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992; Indurkha 1992; Stegmüller 1976).

Methodological perspective – the research perspective, based on the ‘world view’ and the assumed means of representing reality in theory, that guides the choice of research methodology.

Ontology – the study of the human assumptions and values about existence (‘the study of being and existence’ (*Webster Comprehensive Dictionary* 1986)). The adjective ‘ontological’ refers to that aspect of a subject concerning human assumptions and values.

Ontological Perspective – the assumptions, beliefs and collections of human values that together form a human view of what existence is. In Reich’s (1994a) terms, a ‘world view’.

Privilege – the use of a term or concept in a ‘special’ manner such that it is ‘assumed as given’ and is not open to critical analysis. The guiding metaphors or paradigms of theory-making define which terminology and concepts are privileged (Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin, 1992). The dependence of theory on privileged concepts and terminology means that a challenge to the semantic privilege attributed to a term or concept is a challenge to the overarching metaphor or theoretical framework in which it is used.

Research method – a collection of research techniques

Research methodology – the study of research methods or a collection of methods

Research technique – an elemental research action

Theoretical Framework – the complete theoretical basis of a particular research project which includes both the theoretical perspective and the choice of methodologies, methods and techniques.

Theoretical Perspective – the combination of ontological, epistemological and methodological perspectives.

In this thesis, a distinction is made between *information* and *knowledge*. Information is taken to be the representation of knowledge outside an individual, and knowledge is something internal to an individual. Information is in the wider arena: it is potentially objective. Knowledge, however, is internalised. Information consists of facts and opinions; knowledge accrues in an individual after judging and weighing information and experience. Information can exist without human presence, but knowledge requires a human being to know it. In short,

Information – is the representation of knowledge in the public domain.

Knowledge – is all or part of an individual's accumulation of interpreted, weighed and judged information and experience.

The distinction between information and knowledge is important as it assists in the differentiation of engineering design theories, concepts, and theoretical and philosophical perspectives.

The term 'factors' is used in this thesis in a similar manner to its use in the phrase 'technical factors', where 'technical factors' are those matters that influence a potential design (Norman 1992). This is similar to the use of the term 'factors' by Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian (1992) in their proposals for shared memory as a unifying theme for design research and practice. The reason that the term 'factors' is used in this way in the phrase 'social, environmental and ethical factors', is to avoid unnecessarily presuming the epistemological

status of social, environmental and ethical factors as information or knowledge. This is an important issue because the creation of new thought is a central concern of this thesis and there is no agreed model of influences on the creation of new thought or ideas. Hence, to *presume* that the influences on creative thought are best represented in theory by the concepts of 'knowledge' or of 'information' is to give uncritical privilege to models of creative thinking represented as a means operating on knowledge or information. The use of the term 'factor' offers an easier discussion of the epistemological issues surrounding 'knowledge' and 'information'.

Not all engineering design researchers have acknowledged the above terminological and conceptual difficulties, or agreed with the conventions used here, and this has sometimes caused difficulties in quotation. Where this has occurred, a comment is made in the thesis to clarify meanings. For example, the terminological difficulty presented by Yoshikawa's claim that his mathematical theory is *the* 'general design theory' will be addressed in this thesis by writing either 'Yoshikawa's general design theory' or the abbreviation 'GDT'.

1.7 Delimitations of scope and key assumptions

The research was delimited both practically and theoretically as follows.

1.7.1 Practical delimitations

The scope of the literature reviewed was bounded by language and availability in that it was restricted to English language texts, journals and translations available through the University of Western Australia and the international inter-library loan service.

1.7.2 Theoretical delimitations

The research problem was addressed in terms of theory and with a primary focus on design cognition. Theoretically, the research perspective and methodology were aimed at the foundations of engineering design theory. Secondary issues concerned semantic and conceptual confusion in the literature, and developing new structures for epistemological and ontological analysis. Design research touches on many other disciplines, particularly in the area of philosophy and cognition. In choosing which material to use, the concepts and literature that were referred to in these associated areas were bounded pragmatically to that which would resolve whichever problem was in focus.

1.7.3 Key assumptions

This research has been founded on several key assumptions:

- That social, environmental and ethical issues can be better addressed in engineering design research than at present.
- That including social, environmental and ethical issues needs to be a core concern of any attempt to develop engineering design theory that is coherent with a wide range of well justified human knowledge.
- That design is fundamentally a human activity.
- The term 'design' defines something different from other terms that describe other aspects of human activity.
- That the terminological and conceptual confusion in design research means that any new research in this area needs to pay particular attention to issues of epistemology and ontology.
- That the epistemological and ontological foundations of design theories should be coherent with the definition of design that underpins those theories and with other well-justified human knowledge.

1.8 Conclusion

This chapter has laid the foundations for the thesis. Having introduced the research problem and research questions, and justified the research, it was necessary to present clear definitions and state the delimitations and assumptions on which this research was based. Next, it is necessary to explore the research problem in terms of the existing literature, and to define the questions that form the detailed basis of this research. This is done in the next chapter.

2. Literature review

2.1 Introduction

Chapter 1 introduced the practical problem that underlies this research and laid the foundations for the thesis. In this chapter, the description of the practical problem is first transformed into a theoretically defined research problem, and then the literature relating to addressing the research problem is reviewed. This review leads to the definition of the research questions that form the basis of this research.

Identifying and defining the research *questions* is commenced by first classifying the literature into 'background' and 'focal' literature, as recommended by Phillips and Pugh (1987). Then the research *problem* is positioned, in the manner suggested by Perry (1996), relative to both the wider body of background knowledge and to its immediate focal field of inquiry (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Perry's model of relationships between research problem, research questions and disciplinary context

The final definitions of the research questions, whose answers enable the research problem to be addressed, are consequent on the analysis and investigation of the immediate disciplinary and conceptual context of the research problem in the concluding sections of this chapter.

Graphical models are used in this review of literature to clarify and add structure to the different aspects of the analyses of the literature. This is necessary because of the problems presented by the combination of cross-disciplinary terminology, the complexity of the

relationships between the different fields, disciplines and perspectives involved in the study of design, and the terminological problems of design research and engineering design research referred to in Chapter 1.

2.2 Overarching disciplinary contexts of the research problem

The practical aim of this research is to address the problem,

How can social, environmental and ethical matters, be better included in designing?

The consequences of resolving this problem lie in practical changes to designers' activities.

Researching and resolving the problem, however, lies in the realm of design theory. This research focuses on updating design theory in this area to take account of advances in research into alternative foundations of theory-making. Hence, the research question addressed in this thesis is,

Can social, environmental and ethical matter be better included in theories about designing engineering artefacts by applying a post-positivist perspective?

2.2.1 Parent fields of the research problem

The theoretical position from which this research is undertaken lies outside the disciplinary areas of the research problem. The theoretical position of the researcher, and the source of the theoretical tools used in this research, are mainly drawn from the field of philosophy of knowledge. This philosophical basis is necessary to include those philosophical aspects of the disciplines that relate to the practical aspects of the research problem.

The research problem is grounded in five parent fields:

- Engineering
- Design research
- Social aspects of technology
- Environmental aspects of technology
- Ethical aspects of technology

For brevity, the latter three are combined together into 'social, environmental and ethical aspects of technology'. The issues relating to the research problem lie in the area of overlap between the three fields of engineering, design research and the social, environmental and ethical impacts of technology represented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Centrality of research area in relation to parent fields of research problem.

Figure 2 illustrates the centrality of the area of the research problem relative to its parent fields. It is necessary, however, to clarify which aspects of the literature of these parent fields provides a background to the research problem, which areas are focal, and which areas of literature are not immediately relevant. The relationships between the parent fields and the research problem are better illustrated in Figure 3. This figure is a topological transformation of Figure 2 that emphasises the linkages between disciplines and the research problem rather than the overlaps of knowledge between the main disciplines.

Figure 3: Centrality of social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory

In this thesis, the research problem is considered in the context of theories about design cognition, and consequently the disciplines in the upper half of Figure 3 are more relevant to the central research area than those disciplines in the lower half of the figure. The literature of engineering research is directed towards modelling the physical behaviour of artefacts rather than the cognitive environment in which the specifications of artefacts are created, and thus is peripheral to this research. Research into the social, environmental and ethical aspects of engineering research focuses more on the ethics of engaging in particular aspects of engineering research, for example, the commercialisation of research into medical and food technologies such as artificial human conception and genetic modification of plants and animals. Neither of these disciplinary perspectives is of direct relevance to the formulation of theories of design cognition which are the essence here. The delimitations and assumptions of this research defined in Chapter 1 mean that the literature concerning ‘research into social, environmental

and ethical issues’ is also not of direct relevance because its main focus is the *consequences* of particular technological implementations, as is evident from the focus in the field on ‘environmental impacts’ and ‘social impacts’.

The purpose of this research is to improve the social, environmental and ethical consequences of technology and its design by improving design theory related to how the consequences of technology influence designers as described in section 1.3. Hence, the sources of literature that are of primary interest are found in the fields of design research and engineering design research. This means that, although the central area of interest is related to all of the above six fields, only the literatures of the fields design research, engineering design research and social, environmental and ethical aspects of design research are of direct significance. Thus, the ‘background’ and ‘focal’ literature structure of this research is as illustrated in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4 The disciplinary context of the background and focal literature

2.2.1.1 Literatures of design research, engineering design research and the social, environmental and ethical aspects of design research

It is first necessary to clarify some issues about the background literature relating to this research, and about the relationships between the background disciplines to the research problem. First, the terms ‘design research’ and ‘engineering design research’ are primarily used

in this section in the senses that are most commonly found in the literature. For example, 'design research' is used by the Design Research Society's Journal *Design Studies*, to mean 'design research in engineering, architecture, products and systems' (see also, for example, the goals of the Design Research Society and the aims of the journal *Research in Engineering Design*) (*Design Studies* 1996a; Durling 1996b; Finger, 1991)). Secondly, the literature on the social, environmental and ethical aspects of design research is not discussed here separately from the literatures of design research and engineering design research because it is effectively subsumed into them. Third, the extensive overlap between research into design and research into engineering design has meant that research and theories relating to design research are frequently referenced to texts, conference proceedings and journals that are predominantly associated with engineering design research and vice versa.

The explanation for the overlap of the literatures of 'design research' and 'engineering design research' is found in the history of the development of research into these areas. The modern English language literature of design research is grounded in an academic tradition that started in the English speaking world in the 1950s. The Design Research Society, founded after the Conference on Design Methods in 1962, has been the main bearer of this tradition, particularly in the UK. In North America, the Design Methods Group, founded at the University of Waterloo in Canada in 1966, has a similar role with similar interests and methodologies (Jones and Thornley 1963; Pahl and Beitz 1984). The Design Research Society publishes *Design Studies*, the electronic *DRS_News* and the *Design Research Newsletter*, and the Design Methods Group publishes the *DMG Newsletter*. Researchers associated with these organisations are responsible for the majority of the literature in both fields. Although the scope of design research extends, in theory, beyond the design of technical objects to the role of design in Art, both of these English language research streams have been characterised by a focus on technical artefacts designed for commercial purposes (Cross 1984d, 1993).

Predating the above two English language traditions is the German research into systematic design. The German approach originated in the 19th century and is firmly based on a scientific deterministic hierarchical model of design process (Pahl and Beitz 1984; Matousek 1963). Associated with this systematic approach is the development of the VDI 2221 German Standard

design guidelines, the publications of the German WDK design research group founded by W. E. Eder and V. Hubka, and the International Conferences on Engineering Design (ICED) organised by the WDK group (Eder 1981; Hubka and Eder 1981; Pahl and Beitz 1984; VDI 2221 1985; Wallace 1987). This German systematic approach emphasises procedural methods of designing and is founded on the intention that design research will result in a science of design. This systematic and scientific research perspective focuses on the artefact and problem characteristics rather than the activity of designing, and provides a strong contrast to the traditional style of design research dating back at least to Vitruvius that involves bringing together insights from a variety of disciplinary sources (Cross 1993; Dasgupta 1992). In Cross' (1995) terms, the systematic tradition focuses on 'research *for* design' rather than 'research *into* design'.

In addition to the English and German literature of design research and engineering design research are the occasional translated publications from the former USSR colonies. These translations indicate the existence in the former USSR colonies of research programs focusing on systematic methods of addressing design problems in a similar manner to the WDK group and on research into the praxiological nature of designing, that is aimed at clarifying the issues surrounding the duality of theory and practice in design (see, for example, Altshuller 1984; Gasparski 1979; Stupniker 1994; Tempczyk 1986).

In all of the above research histories, the origins of the academic interest in researching into design is found in the development of mathematical methods for complex decision-making and the applications of the newly coined 'systems' perspectives (Love 1995). During the 1960s, the application of theories of systems and cognitive science to the more technical design disciplines led to a dream that a way might be found to automate designing and to the start of interest in research into design by academics and commercial organisations. In 1970, Jones reported on the development of several theories of design from which the human designer had been completely removed: design had become conceived as a process that related problem and solution. At the same time, 'design research' had become 'research into how satisfactory solutions might be deterministically identified and defined' and 'engineering design research' had become well

established as ‘research into technical and theoretical tools to help designers choose and evaluate design attributes’ (Beck 1966; Duggan 1970; Eder 1966; Himmelblau 1974; Wong 1974).

There are three trends evident in the development of the literatures of design research and engineering design research. Firstly, the literature of both design research and engineering design research is dominated by research aimed at automating some or all aspects of designing in the more technical domains (Coyne and Snodgrass 1993). Secondly, both literatures emphasise the role of science as a paradigm with differing levels of support for the idea that the aim of research into design is the establishment of a design science or science of design. These differences relating to the role of science are illustrated in Table 1 below, where the column concerning design research is based on the role that *Design Studies* defines for itself, and the column relating to engineering design research is drawn from statements made by prominent researchers in engineering design (*Design Studies*, 1996b; Dasgupta 1992; Dixon 1987; Hubka and Eder 1990; Pugh 1990). Thirdly, ‘design research’ has been reduced in scope to refer only to research into designing artefacts associated with scientifically based technologies, and this appears to be due to the lack of formal attention that has been paid to research into the less technical design domains especially the Arts (Newbury 1996; Allison, 1995; Cross, 1995).

Design Research	Engineering Design Research
Discussion and development of the theoretical aspects of design including its methodology and values	Design science is ‘an integral system of logically related insights and knowledge that should contain complete knowledge about and for designing.’ (Hubka and Eder 1990)
An understanding of design from comparison of its application in all areas, including engineering, architecture, planning and industrial design	‘Design researchers are viewed as a single communicating community searching for <i>scientific</i> theories of engineering design; that is, theories that can be tested by formal methods of hypothesis testing.’ (Dixon 1987)
New developments, techniques, knowledge and applications in the practice of design	‘Explanations of design process must satisfy the programmatic aims of science.’ (Dasgupta 1992)
Design education: how design techniques may be taught, the approach to ill-defined problems and the impact of new technologies	Engineering design research is the ‘Interaction between design process research and applied engineering research.’ (Pugh 1990)

Table 1 Science in design research and engineering design research

Whilst these trends clarify the roles of design research and engineering design research, the complexity of the issues involved in research into or for design, and the terminological

problems referred to in Chapter 1, have led to substantial overlaps between the disciplines. In addition, the boundaries between design research and engineering design research are made more complex by the overlapping claims about the scope of each discipline that can be inferred from Table 1. From the perspective of design research, topics addressed in engineering design research are either subsumed within design research, or relate to engineering rather than design. From the viewpoint of many engineering design researchers, however, *all* design research is completely subsumed within a science of design that is based on similar scientific principles to those used in engineering analysis.

These differences in outlook mean that there is a substantial overlap in the literature of both disciplines in terms of the topics that are addressed. More importantly, however, it means that the activity of designing engineering artefacts is rarely viewed as a human activity with all that that entails. This is because from the perspective of engineering, engineering design research is seen as research into a technical process, and from the perspective of design research, engineering design research is a subdiscipline that investigates the peculiarities of designing in the domain of engineering. In both disciplines, the literature relating to how theories of engineering design include social, environmental and ethical considerations reflects these assumptions that design can be scientifically modelled as an ahuman process.

To recap,

- Research into the social, environmental and ethical aspects of design research is embedded in the literatures of design research and engineering design research.
- Both design research and engineering design research are based on systems theory and the theories of cognitive science.
- Both design research and engineering design research are mainly concerned with the design of artefacts associated with the more technical domains and this has led to substantial overlaps in the literature.
- The literature of design research is less dominated by scientism than the literature of engineering design research.

- Researchers involved in both design research and engineering design research lay claim to their perspective encompassing all and every aspect of research into design.
- Both design research and engineering design research are mainly focused at automating design and hence are concerned with developing a human design theory that is suited to that end.

The above analysis of the background literature in design research, engineering design research and social, environmental and ethical aspects of design research outlines their content and relationships as seen from a general perspective. The perspective of this research, however, is defined by the way social, environmental and ethical factors are incorporated into theories about human design cognition, and hence it is necessary to review how the background literature relates to this perspective.

Firstly, the overlapping characteristics of the literatures of design research and engineering design research mean that identifying the literature relating to a particular specialism is not as straightforward as the above general analysis might imply. For example, the dichotomy between the human-centred and a human perspectives on design does not result in a clear separation of the literature and, in fact, much of the literature relating to the development of mechanistic and deterministic a human theories of designing also contradictorily implies or states that design is an essentially human activity (see Chapter 3 and Appendix 1). There is an imbalance in which the majority of the literature focuses on the artefactual design solution at the expense of research into the human side of designing. Analogically, it is as if research into English literature ignored issues of aesthetics, semantics and truth and focused only on grammar, punctuation, logic and syntax. This imbalance in the literature means that many of the references that are relevant to this thesis are found in literature whose primary focus is only distantly connected to it. Secondly, issues concerning social, environmental and ethical factors are more particularly concerned with theories of design cognition than theories of the characteristics of objects. This is because what is needed is to extend theory in this area of engineering design research beyond the simple quantisation of social, environmental and ethical factors as technical factors so that it also encompasses how designers include these

factors in their partial and internal conceptualisations and evaluations. Publications relating to design cognition are mainly found in the literature of design research. Thirdly, the analytical tools that are utilised in this research for investigating engineering design cognition originate in the field of philosophy, but the issues surrounding their choice and the epistemological detail of their use that are discussed in Chapter 3 are based mainly on the literature of design research. Fourthly, the problems associated with disciplinary structure, referred to in Chapter 1, have meant that Dewey and similar library classification systems do not contain a specific classification structure for the literature of design research and engineering design research (see Appendix 3). Consequently, the literature of engineering design research and design research is unevenly distributed across libraries and has mainly been classified according to the domain of interest of its purchaser. This presents difficulties of both location and access for research in this area.

In summary, the main source of background literature for this research is to be found in the literature associated with the discipline of design research, but, because the disciplines of design research and engineering design research do not translate to unique library classifications, this gives rise to difficulties in identifying and obtaining relevant texts.

The above difficulties associated with a lack of appropriate library classifications which in turn are based on problems with the structure and bounds of relevant disciplines means that the background and focal literatures of this thesis cannot be easily and uniquely identified from electronic catalogue searches undertaken within a particular domain. Therefore, the literature for this review has been drawn from the contents of the journals *Design Studies* and *Research in Engineering Design*, along with the texts found by manual library catalogue searches across many domains and from related bibliographic references.

2.2.2 Research problem and the literature

The discussion of issues relating to the social, environmental and ethical aspects of designing is rare in the design research and engineering design research literature and, in general, these discussions only come to light when one of them is focal to a design problem. For examples, the environmental implications of leaded motor fuel, the social implications of high rise housing, or

the ethical implications of armament design. The focus remains, however, on the problem and its solution, and in general what is addressed in the engineering design research literature is 'How can the social/environmental/ethical side of this particular design problem be satisfactorily resolved?'. In this thesis the focus is moved from the design problem to the theories and assumptions that underpin how design problems are viewed. That is, what is being investigated in this thesis are alternative post-positivist paradigms and perspectives that might form a new basis for engineering design research and theories of engineering design.

Social, environmental and ethical considerations are especially important to reviewing the basis of design research and formulating theory about designing because designing is an activity that is socially, environmentally and ethically situated (Coyne, Rosenman, Radford, Balachandran and Gero 1990; Dilnot 1982; Gasparski 1979; Konda,, Monarch, Sargent, Subrahmanian 1992; Simon 1981). This is a key point in this thesis and it, and its implications, are discussed in detail in Chapters 3, 4 and 5. What viewing designing as a socially, environmentally and ethically situated activity implies is an inversion of the accepted relationship between theories concerning the social, environmental and ethical aspects of design and theories of design. The argument is that:

- Designing is a human activity that is socially purposeful and is intended to result in changes to social situations, for example, by making money for its sponsors.
- Designers do this by modifying environments with their designs, not only because of manufacturing inefficiencies, but also because designers intend to create new artefacts and technologies that change the user's environment.
- The activity of designing is grounded in ethical judgements by designers and others about design solutions and social and environmental problems associated with both of the two points above.

If the above argument is accepted, then theories of designing would be expected to be derived from, and evaluated with respect to, research and theories relating to the social, environmental and ethical situation of designing. What has happened instead is that, in most of the literature,

the social, environmental and ethical aspects of designing have been assigned a minor role in theories whose primary purpose is to define the physical relationships between a scientifically defined problem and its technically defined solution. Most research into designing results in theories of designing as an ahuman process and this means that social, environmental and ethical factors are dealt with in this context as information – preferably quantified – and the implications for human design cognition are lost (Court 1995; Dorst and Dijkhuis 1995; Joseph 1996; Oxman 1995). There are exceptions. For example, Dilnot (1982) has drawn out in detail the argument against the primacy of the technical perspective in design research with respect to design and society. Recent work by Coyne and Snodgrass (1991, 1992a, 1992b, 1993), Reich (1994a, 1995) and Franz (1994) and other researchers who espouse a constructed or phenomenological view of reality have this alternative human-based view of design research implicit in their arguments. From these perspectives any theory of the technical must reduce to one about individual human circumstance with the concomitant implications concerning social, environmental and ethical consideration. Similarly, but more distantly, the argument for reversing the privilege given to object-based engineering design theory is implicit in the work of Cross, Cross and Glynn (1986) on hemispheric brain specialisation and ‘designerly ways of knowing’. Finally, implicit support for this inversion of the relationship between the theories about the social, environmental and ethical aspects of design and human-based theories of design is found distributed throughout the works of researchers who view designing as an essentially human activity and whose research reflects this focus (see, for example, Cross and Cross, 1995; Goldschmidt 1995; Peng 1994; Reich et al. 1996; Sharrock and Anderson 1994; Wong and Shriram 1993).

The idea that design is essentially a human process is rarely explicitly stated in the design literature, but is more often implicit in either the topic being discussed or in the detail of analyses. Design research was founded on the disciplines of architecture, industrial design and to some extent the craft design traditions (Alexander 1979, 1964, 1963; Archer 1979, 1965; Broadbent 1973, 1966; Jones 1970; Jones and Thornley 1963). In each of these disciplines the idea of a ‘designer as creative genius’ was dominant and this has carried through, albeit as a minor strand of the literature, into contemporary design research (Roy 1993; Coyne And Snodgrass

1992b; Tovey 1992a, 1992b; Buchanan 1990). The idea of design as a human activity is also strongly implicit in theories relating to 'human error in designing', 'participatory design', 'design for the user', 'designer as "prosumer"', 'computer supported co-operative work', 'design thinking' and the research into design that uses protocol analysis as its research method (see, for example, de Bont, Schoormans and Wessel 1992; Bowers 1991; Cross and Cross, 1995; Goldschmidt 1995; Gunther 1992; Krouwel 1992; Magee 1987; Peng 1994; Petroski 1991, Reich et al. 1996; Sharrock and Anderson 1994; Sonnenwald 1996; Stewart 1992; Tang and Leifer 1991; Toffler 1990; Wong and Shriram 1993).

2.3 Immediate disciplinary and conceptual context of the research problem

In section 2.2, the way that the disciplines of design research and engineering design research provide a general background to the research problem was discussed. The conceptual background to the research problem now needs to be exposed in sufficient detail to draw out the research questions that must be answered to address the research problem. This section starts that process by exploring the immediate context of the research problem.

The breadth and depth of concepts and theories about design have been mapped out in a variety ways, but some of these mappings are more appropriate to domains other than engineering, for example, to Graphic Art or Sculpture. Significant overviews of concepts and theories of design research are those on:

- Design methods (see, for example, Chandrasekaran 1990; Cross 1984d, 1989, 1993; Jones 1970; Pahl and Beitz 1984; Rittel and Webber 1984, 1974, 1973, 1972; Ullman 1992).
- Types of design research (see, for example, Cross 1995).
- Design theories (see, for example, Cross 1993; Hubka and Eder 1990; Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Ullman 1992).
- Design research methodologies and issues of epistemology and ontology (see, for example, Coyne and Snodgrass 1992; Franz 1994; Reich 1994).

The conceptual mappings or overviews that are discussed in the following have been chosen because they represent the main aspects of research into design that has a technological or engineering focus. These overviews and taxonomies of the literature and the design research effort coexist, however, with the ubiquitous classification by domain and subdomain, echoed in how design research and design theory is catalogued in libraries (Appendix 3). There are several explanations for the dominance of the domain based taxonomies of design research, but it will be argued later, in Chapters 3, 4, and 5, that one of the most important reasons for the failure of proposals for a structure of design theory that is not based on domains is the lack of attention to epistemological assumptions in design research, especially where those assumptions relate to design cognition.

2.3.1 Theoretical approaches to design research: Overviews, taxonomies and classifications

It is necessary to bound this research by defining which aspects of the literature are not addressed by this review. In this thesis, the research problem is viewed in terms of theory-making and conceptualisation and this means that the study of the history of design methods lies outside its scope. Similarly, the study of the relationships between particular design methods is not considered here in detail. In spite of these general exclusions, some concepts that originated in design methods research are useful for developing design theory, for example, the ideas of classifying designing in terms of its 'wickedness' or its novelty are useful in separating activities that are 'pure' design from associated routine activities (Love 1996a, 1996b; Pahl and Beitz 1984; Rittel and Webber 1984, 1974, 1973, 1972).

In this section, six different classifications of the concepts and theories of research relating to design are reviewed with the intention of establishing the historical backdrop of the developments of design theory for the theoretical investigations of this research. The six classification systems are,

- Hubka and Eder's (1990) taxonomy of design research.
- Ullman's (1992) taxonomy of design research in mechanical engineering.
- Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian's (1992) taxonomy of design research.

- Cross' (1995, 1993 and 1984b) historical reviews of the literature relating to research into design, design science and science of design.
- Franz' (1994) taxonomy of design research in the domain of architecture.
- Reich's (1994) layered taxonomy of research methodology in engineering design research.

Hubka and Eder's (1990) taxonomy of design focuses on design knowledge and is based on a paradigm of research and theory-making that is drawn exclusively from the natural sciences. Their scientific perspective on design depends on the activity of designing being adequately described by theories of information processing and the structure of their taxonomy reflects this assumption, see Figure 5.

Figure 5 Taxonomy of Design Science (Hubka and Eder 1990)

In 1992, Ullman proposed an hierarchical taxonomy or, rather, a set of hierarchical frameworks to classify design research in the mechanical domain. The top level of this taxonomy is reproduced in Figure 6 below. The purpose of Ullman's taxonomy is to classify design methods and tools and it is set firmly in the context of establishing a design science. The taxonomy differentiates between research relating to an artefactual view of design and research relating to

design process, and, unusually, includes a category for classifying research into design environment, that is, the environment in which a design is created.

Figure 6 Taxonomy of Mechanical Design (Ullman 1992)

Ullman put forward the above model for classifying design methods and tools in the domain of mechanical engineering, but it is clear that it has wider application. What Ullman achieved was to separate many aspects of research into design that were commonly conflated, and in doing this the structure of his taxonomy draws attention to several aspects of design research that are often overlooked, for example design environment and individual designers' backgrounds.

According to Ullman, one of the main purposes of his taxonomy was to provide a basis to avoid the problems associated with the lack of terminological and conceptual agreement in design research and to support the critical analysis of theories and research results. It is clear that he has separated and differentiated between overlapping areas and concepts, and in this his taxonomy provides a useful tool for the deconstruction of design theory. What he has not addressed, however, is how alternative ontological and epistemological perspectives change the basis for design research and hence, change his taxonomic structure. Ullman's taxonomy provides a well developed taxonomic 'snapshot' of a positivist perspective of engineering design research which although initially grounded in his research into mechanical engineering design is likely to apply to most engineering design (Nagy, Ullman and Deiterrich 1992).

Ullman's taxonomy of design method shares many features with Hubka and Eder's (1990) taxonomy of design science. The main differences between the two taxonomies are due to their

difference in purpose. Hubka and Eder aimed to classify design knowledge whereas Ullman's purpose was to classify means of design assistance. The similarities between the two taxonomies extend to detail, for example, Ullman's environmental category is paralleled in Hubka and Eder's taxonomy by a combination of their 'current fields' and 'general' knowledge classifications.

Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian (1992) derived a graphically structured taxonomy indicating the relationships between different elements of research into the design of technology (see Figure 7). Their taxonomy is important because it encompasses all aspects of design theory and it situates designing in a social, environmental and ethical context. The universal scope of this taxonomy, therefore, extends beyond the taxonomies of Hubka and Eder and Ullman whose foci are limited to design knowledge and design aids.

Figure 7 'Shared Memory' taxonomy of design research (Konda et al 1992)

The position of Konda et al that underpins their taxonomy parallels the arguments used in this thesis for focusing on design theory qua theory rather than its content, and in terms of viewing design as a socially, environmentally and ethically situated phenomenon. They take a social constructivist perspective on design, and in this sense view designing as an activity undertaken

between humans. This position leads naturally to the concept of 'shared memory' in which the focus of design theory expands to include all the shared human knowledge that is contextual to the creation and implementation of a design. This concept provides the underlying basis for their classification of design theories and research and the basis of their proposals that shared memory is suited as a unifying theme for design research and practice.

For Konda et al, the idea of 'shared memory' has two roles: On one hand it offers the means of introducing a constructed view of reality into design research and provides a basis for enabling design research to move beyond its positivist beginnings so that it may encompass the implications of the social constructionist perspectives on knowledge. On the other hand, it keeps design theory tightly connected with the mathematically computerisable informatic perspectives of engineering design research. The 'shared memory' proposals are important because they are a milestone in the acceptance, by one of the main groups of artificial intelligence based researchers, that the non-technical human aspects of designing are what differentiate design from engineering and that it is necessary to address issues relating to the construction and interpretation of reality by designers and researchers alike.

The findings of Konda et al are important but not central to this thesis because their post-positivist perspective is tied to social constructivism, and therefore, leads to a structuralist outlook whereby the activity of designing is described in terms of the structural constraints defined by social and cultural considerations. This research is also post-positivist, but its central focus is on theory relating to individuals' design cognition because the aim of this research is to investigate the best way to express in theory how individual engineering designers' cognitions are influenced by non-technical external factors.

In 1993, Cross took an overview of design theory and design research in a way that followed on from his review of a decade before (Cross 1984b). Both reviews used the same categories, but differed in their focus. In 1984, Cross' focus was on the history of research into design methods and methodology, whereas, in 1993, his emphasis was on the details of the relationship between scientific research and design research and the implications this has for design theory. In both overviews, rather than using conceptual structures in the manner of Ullman or Hubka and

Eder, Cross classified design research into themes that were almost identical for both 1984 and 1993. In 1993, the themes he proposed that represented the main streams of design research were:

- The development of design methods.
- The management of the design process.
- The structure of design problems.
- The nature of design activity.
- The philosophy of design method.

These themes are coherent with the taxonomies of both Ullman (1992) and Konda et al (1992) in the following ways,

- Themes 1 and 3 refer to artefactual matters.
- Themes 2 and 4 refer to design process.
- Theme 5 is essentially part of the epistemological consideration that is necessary for establishing a coherent research methodology.

What is omitted from Cross' overview is any explicit reference to research into the environment of designing, but this is not surprising in view of its paucity in the literature.

Two years later, in 1995, Cross suggested a three-fold classification of 'types' of design research.

These were:

- Research *into* design
- Research *for* design
- Research *through* design

In Cross' terms, 'research *into* design' includes all aspects of investigations of the design activity, processes, knowledge. Its purpose is to increase knowledge about designing. 'Research *for* design' is that research intended to assist designers or to improve design outcomes in some

other way. Research aimed at the development of design methods is an example of research *for* design. 'Research *through* design' refers to research that necessarily occurs in the course of designing. That is, 'research *through* design' occurs when a sculpture, or a dance, or a design of whatever sort not only represents itself, or a solution to a problem, but also represents the inquiry – the research – that led to its appearance.

Cross' categorising razor cuts the field of design research in a way that is important from several standpoints. Firstly, Cross' classification outlook is important because it clarifies and differentiates between different types of research in terms of the *purpose* for which it was undertaken. This is useful because the field until recently has overlooked the ways that the reasons for doing research influence not only on what research is undertaken, but how it is undertaken. Cross' classifications bring these issues of purpose to the fore and open the way for further clarification of the assumptions that underpin particular theories and concepts.

Secondly, Cross' three classifications reflect the differences between the work of those involved in domain-independent research, domain-dependent research and practitioner-focused research. Finally, Cross' classifications inadvertently illustrate an endemic problem in the design theory literature relating to the way that different design research perspectives can result in apparently contradictory conclusions. An example of this is that classifying this thesis according to Cross' categories at first implies that the research that underpins it is primarily 'research *into* design'. This research is, however, intended to be useful to designers, which means that it might also be viewed as 'research *for* design'. In addition, because this research and thesis have been designed – in Schon's (1984) sense of 'design as a process of enquiry' – it is also 'research *through* design'. The implication of the above example is that the usefulness of Cross' classifications are at least partially neutralised by the multiplicity of purposes to which design research can be applied.

The ephemerally changing 'Design Web' taxonomy (a 1997 version of which is listed in Appendix 4) contrasts with the above carefully derived taxonomies and reviews of design research (see *DesignWeb Researchers' Database* 1997). The taxonomy of design research contained in the *DesignWeb Researchers' Database* is defined moment to moment as design researchers enter their areas of interest onto a World Wide Web database held at the University of Bath in the UK.

It appears that the *DesignWeb Researchers' Database* includes an experimental classificatory system that is used to structure a database of design researchers' areas of interest as design research keywords. As additional researchers add their interests, the taxonomic structure is changed to reflect the new input. The structure of the 1997 *DesignWeb* taxonomy in Appendix 4 is dominated by research relating to information for designers, design science and artificial intelligence, which is perhaps to be expected since those who put entries in *DesignWeb* are likely to be familiar with computers. The taxonomy of *DesignWeb* is not reviewed in detail here because of its ephemerality and because of its experimental purpose. Its value, however, is that it reflects a composite of researchers' preferences as to what they would like the structure of design research to be like in the conceptual vicinity of their particular research interests.

Design methods, design knowledge, theories about artefact definition, theories about design cognition and models of design process have all been well addressed by design researchers. The epistemological considerations that theory-making about design depends upon, however, have been relatively neglected (Coyne and Snodgrass 1992, 1993; Franz 1994; Reich 1994a). This means that those researchers who focus on the ontological and epistemological foundations of design theories are in a position of trying to bring the field of design research up to date with contemporary advances in these philosophically based areas. Coyne and Snodgrass, Franz and Reich concur that design theory has been inappropriately dominated by a positivist perspective, and in consequence, a major emphasis of their taxonomies is to provide a structure to guide the development of new design theory that is based on post-positivist perspectives, rather than classifying existing design theory, methods or knowledge.

Franz (1994) developed her taxonomy of all design research from within the domain of architecture. Franz' research is significant in terms of research into engineering design because architecture, like engineering design is a technical discipline that is socially, environmentally and ethically situated and, perhaps more importantly, the field of architecture provides many of the foundational concepts of design research on which engineering design research draws. Franz' taxonomy separated the technical, conceptual and philosophical aspects of design research, and divided the literature into the following categories:

- Technically oriented research (systematic frame of reference)
- Technically oriented research (computational frame of reference)
- Technically oriented research (management frame of reference)
- Conceptually oriented research (psychological frame of reference)
- Conceptually oriented research (person-environment frame of reference)
- Philosophically oriented research (epistemological frame of reference)
- Philosophically oriented research (ontological frame of reference)

This taxonomy of Franz has many similarities with Cross' (1984b, 1993) themes and with Ullman's (1992) taxonomy of mechanical design. Her separation of design research into 'technical', 'conceptual' and 'philosophical' orientations aligns with the terminological structure developed in Chapter 1, where 'engineering theory' includes most of the 'technical' aspects of design research; 'engineering design theory' parallels 'conceptually oriented research'; and 'the philosophy of design' is equivalent to Franz' 'philosophically oriented research'. The main difference in the first category is that Franz' 'technically oriented research' also includes research relating to the management of engineering design. What is evident in both Franz' taxonomy and the terminology defined in Chapter 1 is a concept of meta-theoretical 'layers' where the theories and concepts in any one layer are informed by and inform the layers above and below them. This idea of layers is developed further in Chapter 3 to provide a methodology for deconstructing design theories and, in Chapter 5, the layered model of Chapter 3 is used together with the findings from the research questions to sketch out a new structure for design theory and the discipline of design research.

In 1994, Reich suggested a different taxonomy of research methodology that also had a layered structure. In this layered model, Reich focused on theories as theoretical entities in their own right rather than on the objects to which theories refer (see Table 2)..

Layer	Examples
World views	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practicism • Scientism
Research heuristics (sources of theories or hypotheses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive science • Decision science • Formal methods • Human-centred • Software engineering • Systems science
Specific issues (evaluation or goodness criteria)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal representation • Parsimony • Practical relevance

Table 2: A layered model of research methodology (Reich 1994a)

Reich's layered model formalises a view of theory similar to that which underlies Kuhn's concept of 'paradigms' because it locates theory within a ground of research methodology and beliefs (Kuhn 1962; Stegmüller 1976). In essence, Reich is arguing that the choice of concepts and theories for any thesis or investigation, and their validity, depend on the background assumptions that underpin the research. That is, theories and concepts that arise in a research project depend on:

- The researchers' beliefs about the world and about knowledge.
- The belief systems espoused by the academic disciplines through which the research task is approached.
- The choice of methodology and specific methods that are used in the research.

In Table 2, these beliefs, assumptions and choices are coalesced into 'world views', 'Research heuristics' and 'specific issues'. In Reich's layered model, each 'World view' defines and bounds the available choice of 'research heuristic', and each 'research heuristic' then, in its turn, influences which 'specific issues' become relevant in research method.

The above section broadly reviews the immediate context of the research problem using a selection of overviews and taxonomies of design research drawn from the literature. To summarise this review:

- The overviews of design research and the taxonomies of design theory of the researchers presented here are substantially coherent with each other with the exception of some aspects of the taxonomy of design knowledge proposed by Hubka and Eder (1990) that depend on an exclusively scientific perspective in a way that is argued against by Reich (1994a), Franz (1994) and Coyne and Snodgrass.
- The main foci of design research in the literature are:
 1. The designed object (artefactual view)
 2. The design process (process view)
- There is agreement that design related human and environmental issues are a part of design research although the literature is sparse.
- Ontological and epistemological aspects of design research and design theory need addressing more adequately, and post-positivist perspectives need to be applied to design research to replace the positivist or rationalist perspectives that inappropriately underpin many existing design theories.
- The layered deconstruction of research methodology which underlies much of the above literature is valuable because it points beyond methodology to the need to investigate the role of the assumptions and foundations of design research which are relevant to deconstructing engineering design theory to resolve the research problem in this thesis.
- Because this thesis is concerned with improving the way that social, environmental and ethical factors are incorporated into theories of design cognition, research relating to prescriptive methods or design aids is peripheral to the main task and is not considered here in detail.

2.3.2 Research problem and its immediate theoretical contexts

In the previous section, the broad theoretical context of the research problem was explored, particularly in terms of the theoretical assumptions that underpin any research into design. In this section, the theoretical contexts of three aspects of the research problem are investigated:

- Matters of ontology and epistemology relating to the validity and coherence of engineering design theory. These issues are important because it is necessary that any new theory is based on adequate foundations, and also because there are problems with the ontological and epistemological foundations of design research and engineering design research as identified in this chapter and Chapter 1.
- Theories of design cognition. This aspect of engineering design theory is important because the research problem is addressed in terms of *theory* and *designers' internal processes*.
- The representation of social, environmental and ethical matters in theoretical terms and concepts. This is necessary because the research problem is addressed in the realm of *theory*.

The literature relating to these three aspects of the research problem are reviewed in more detail in the following sections.

2.3.2.1 *Matters of ontology and epistemology relating to the validity and coherence of engineering design theory*

The most prolific writing relating to the philosophical foundations of design research and design theory has come from Coyne and his associates (Coyne 1991b, 1990a, 1990c; Coyne and Snodgrass 1993, 1992a, 1991; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992; Newton and Coyne 1992). This literature emphasises the role of metaphor in design research and theory-making and points towards positivism as a limiting factor in the quality of design research. More specifically, Coyne and associates identify the 'rationalist' aspects of positivism that are to be challenged, although they do not spell out the relationship between positivism and rationalism in detail. Coyne and associates have chosen to argue against 'rationalism' in design research, perhaps because of the emphasis on 'rationality' in research into artificial intelligence and design, but

many of their criticism apply to both positivism and rationalism, and the demise of rationalism brings the demise of positivism due to positivism's necessary reliance on rationality. For example, in *Problem Setting Within Prevalent Metaphors of Design*, Coyne and Snodgrass (1992) explored the implications of rationalist and post-rationalist perspectives on problem regimes in design theory. They use the six categories of problem first defined by Alexander (1964) in his *Notes on the Synthesis of Form*:

- Coping with complexity.
- Being systematic.
- Enabling communication.
- Enabling the processing of information.
- Formulating methods and models.
- Capturing knowledge.

Coyne and Snodgrass claimed that these problem regimes were created and defined in the discipline of design research as a consequence of researchers' dependence on a rationalist basis for research and theory making. They argued that many problems of design research are pseudo-problems, consequential to rationalist epistemologies and created by the choice of metaphor which have been used to represent the activity of design and which, in consequence, disappear or are transformed when different metaphors are applied.

What Coyne and Snodgrass have done is to interpose an additional layer in the picture of the relationship between design research and its theories. They argued that the problems, solutions and theories of design research are not objectively found, and by bringing attention to the role of metaphor, Coyne and Snodgrass have dispelled the claim to obviousness of design problems. Coyne and Snodgrass claimed that different metaphors result in different problems and different sorts of solutions, that is, the claim that the agreement in the field about the range of problems that design researchers 'see' are a direct consequence of researchers' dependence on positivism, scientism, and more specifically, rationalism, as the source of their ontological and

epistemological assumptions. Consequently, Coyne and Snodgrass argued it is necessary for post-rationalist metaphors to replace the existing dominance of the metaphors of rationalism, positivism and scientism.

In Coyne and Snodgrass' view, metaphors of design based on post-rationalist perspectives change the disciplines of design research in two ways. Firstly, they cast doubt on the validity of many existing design theories. Secondly, they point to problems of relativity in establishing positions from which to theorise or research: in Coyne and Snodgrass words 'Postrationalism is characterised by an impermanent set of metaphors'. They suggest that the way forward is through deconstructing and re-examining existing concepts and theory using a critical methodology.

Coyne and Snodgrass' conclusions align with those of Franz (1994) about the problems of design research and who also suggested critical methods as the way forward in resolving those problems that are founded in ontological and epistemological issues. This is in spite of using a different analytical approach to Coyne and Snodgrass and originating her inquiries in the field of architecture rather than artificial intelligence. From her position in architectural design research she noted that philosophical inquiry in design research has been limited to 'a meagre collection of epistemological and ontological studies' and claimed that this is due to four positivist assumptions:

- The conception of the world as atomistic.
- The conception of research as primarily prescriptive and interventionist.
- The conception of designing as rationalistic.
- The conception of design in purely physical or formal terms.

Franz claims that these assumptions have led to less than adequate design methods, but, more importantly, they underpin many of the difficulties concerning the inclusion of human and environmental issues in design theories. Essentially, she suggests that many of these difficulties can be overcome by changing from a dualist view of design to a dialectical view that designers and researchers exist in and as part of the world that they influence. This change from a dualist

perspective to one of dialectic has been expressed by Coyne (1991b) and Coyne and Snodgrass (1991) previously and they have come to similar conclusions. Its effect would probably be most radical in the research into design undertaken from a perspective of artificial intelligence because the literature, theory and concepts in this area depend heavily on dualism (Coyne and Snodgrass 1993). This change of view from dualism to dialecticism, of including the existential aspects of design cognition in design theory, requires different research methodologies and methods. Specifically, it requires theories and concepts to be relativistically validated via a critical methodology because research methodologies and methods that depend on assumptions of objective validity and truth are inappropriate in this theoretical arena.

The criticisms of existing design research and the proposals for changes to research practice made by Coyne and Snodgrass and Franz are also supported by Reich (1994). Reich explored the area of research methodology in the application of artificial intelligence theory in engineering design research. This area of engineering design research is significant because of late it has become possibly the largest area across all design research (Coyne and Snodgrass 1993). In exploring issues of research methodology, Reich drew attention to the importance of considering ontological and epistemological issues alongside methodological ones and to the importance of coherency between the ontological, epistemological and methodological foundations of a research project. In establishing the epistemological relationships between these three aspects of research, Reich developed the layered model of research methodology that was referred to in the previous section. The analyses that led to Reich's layered model imply an essentially pragmatic position: that different ontological, epistemological and methodological combinations are suited to different research situations with some combinations being fundamentally incompatible, for example, the combination of scientism and a human-centred perspective. Reich argued that the ontological and epistemological assumptions that have driven research methodology in the realm of artificial intelligence are flawed: an important issue because design research has come to align itself with the study of artificial intelligence theories as researchers attempt to automate design cognition. With respect to other matters of ontology and epistemology, Reich's position is similar to Coyne and Snodgrass and Franz. He proposed that more consideration should be given to moving design research beyond

its dependence on positivism and addressing theory, theory-making and research from post-positivist or post-rational perspectives. In particular, Reich emphasised what he referred to as *practicism*, a constructivist position drawn from the work of Guba (1990) and Reason and Rowan (1981). Also in line with Coyne and Snodgrass and Franz is the implicit assumption underlying Reich's discussions of the importance of ontological and epistemological considerations in resolving problems of theoretical validity and coherence in artificial intelligence research, and that advances in design theory and design research depend on the application of a critical methodology.

To summarise so far; researchers investigating the ontological, epistemological and methodological assumptions that design research and design theory are based on conclude:

- Post-positivist/post-rationalist epistemologies and ontologies provide better ways of addressing many of the issues that are central and fundamental to design research, especially issues relating to the interface between designers and reality that are either avoided, neglected or less than optimally addressed in research based on positivist or rationalist perspectives.
- That design research needs to be based on theoretical foundations that allow that reality is individually interpreted and constructed and hence, in many ways is relative and subjective rather than objective. Much of design theory has been inappropriately based on positivist and rationalist perspectives.
- The application of post-positivist /post rationalist perspectives necessitates the use of a critical methodology in design research. This is especially true for research that involves the study of the relative and interpreted nature of reality in design and the interpretation of design theories in this light, particularly those theories relating to design cognition,

If the above summary is combined with the problems of design research raised in Chapter 1, they define the problems of analysing existing design theories and developing new theory as follows:

- A lack of terminological agreement in the field.
- No established and widely agreed fundamental concepts.
- A lack of attention to epistemological and ontological issues which has lead to inadequate definition of terminology and under-justification of concepts and theories.
- The inappropriate application of positivist and rationalist perspectives in areas of investigation that may be more satisfactorily addressed from other theoretical vantage points.
- The neglect of issues relating to the essentially human nature of designing with all that that entails in terms of reality being individually interpreted and constructed.
- A shortage of well established literature, language and concepts relating to the application of post-positivist/post-rationalist epistemologies and ontologies in design research.
- Unresolved problems relating to the interpretation of existing design theories which have been proposed and accepted as established without being critically analysed in terms of their epistemological validity. This is especially relevant in the area of theories relating to design cognition.

The combination of the above problems means that establishing a coherent theoretical structure of engineering design research in terms of the existing theoretical perspectives is especially difficult because it cannot easily be achieved within the existing language and concepts of the field. What is needed first in this research is to identify an adequate means of analysing and validating design theories: in effect a means of deciding privilege in the different theoretical circumstances of engineering design research and design research (Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992). This issue of privilege and validation has precedence over other aspects of this inquiry because further analysis and theory-making depends on it. It raises the first research question,

Research question 1.

The wide ranging implications of this question have led to its discussion being distributed through this thesis. Different aspects of that discussion are found in Chapter 1, in justifying this research; in this chapter, Chapter 2; in Chapter 3, where the establishment of the theoretical framework of this research is undertaken; in Chapter 4, where the question is formally analysed; and in Chapter 5, where the analysis of the research question in Chapter 4 and its implications for resolving the research problem within its wider disciplinary context are discussed.

2.3.2.2 Theories of design cognition

The positivist information-processing idiom stands out as the most widely utilised perspective of research into design cognition. It is this information-processing view of design cognition that lies behind the ubiquitous ‘analysis’ – ‘synthesis’ – ‘evaluation’ (ASE) model of design process and which has led to the widespread assumption that design can be satisfactorily described as a rational problem-solving activity represented in terms of the informatic management of a world seen as patterns of information (see, for example, Bañares-Alcántara 1992, Bieniawski 1993; Chakrabarti and Bligh 1994; Chandrasekaran 1993; Court 1995; Coyne, Rosenman, Radford, Balachandran and Gero 1990; Culley, MacMahon and Court 1995; Dasgupta 1991; Visser 1992, 1996; Wong and Shriram 1993).

The literature relating to design cognition that focuses on designing by humans is substantially smaller than the above informatic literature. That is, the literature of design cognition rather unequally divides between what Cross, Dorst and Roozenburg (1992) have called ‘the “artificial” and “natural” intelligence of design’ which in this thesis are referred to as ‘artificial design cognition’ and ‘human design cognition’. In this thesis, because this research focuses on human design cognition, the balance of emphasis between the reviews of the literatures of ‘artificial design’ and ‘human design’ is reversed; a brief overview of the literature on artificial design cognition is followed by a more detailed review of the literature on human design

cognition. These reviews of the design cognition literature lead to the development of two more of the research questions that guide this thesis.

2.3.2.2.1 Artificial cognition

The informatic position on design cognition is reflected in the common perceptions of designing as 'problem solving' or 'satisfying requirements' (Dasgupta 1992; Wallace 1992; Simon 1981; Thomas and Carroll 1979; Newell and Simon 1972). Viewing designing as problem solving, in this manner, has been attractive to design researchers on three grounds. Firstly, because it brings the theories that have been derived from research relating to methods of scientific problem-solving and rational decision-making into engineering design theory and is thus coherent with the engineering background of many engineering design researchers. Secondly, a scientific, logically based theory of design problem-solving matches well with the development of a science of design. Thirdly, a logical model of designing offers a basis for computerising the engineering design process and thus gives rise to the conceptually and economically attractive possibility of automating designing.

The cognitive theories that are implicit in general 'artificial' design theories are not hidden; it is more that they are assumed rather than being discussed in detail (Akin 1992; Reich 1995, 1994a, 1992). For example, the 'General Design Theory' of Yoshikawa (1981) has no model of human design cognition. Instead it assumes that design cognition is a theoretical relationship between problem and solution characteristics that can be mathematically defined (Reich 1995; Tomiyama 1994). Similarly, in the 'Axiomatic Design Theory' of Suh (1990) the theoretical model of design cognition is reduced to a set of axioms for developing solution characteristics of relatively well-defined design problems. The concept of 'design science' implies a mechanistic model of design cognition because 'design science' is based on a scientific paradigm of design research that carries with it the assumptions of science and positivism and hence defines design cognition as an objective, deterministic and mechanistic process (see, for example, Cross 1993; Eder 1989; Dixon 1989; Finger 1991; Hubka 1985 and Hubka and Eder 1988 1990). The field of artificial intelligence has a variety of models or theories of design cognition because artificial intelligence and the associated models of design cognition have been based on one or more of the following: logic and 'fuzzy' logic theories, rationality and bounded rationality, linguistic grammars of

design attributes, biological models of connectionism, neural nets and genetic development theories. Artificial intelligence research provides sufficient theoretical basis for Oxman (1990) to suggest that creativity can be explained by a scientific theory that has knowledge defined in terms of precedents and procedures, and Hertz (1992) to build a general design theory on empiricism via logic although this latter is possibly positivism under a different name. The underlying characteristics of each of the models of design cognition associated with the above theories are defined by the overall aim that the models of design cognition are intended to be computerisable (Coyne 1990b; Coyne and Yokozawa 1992; Purcell, Mallen and Gourmain 1974).. Consequently, the main epistemological characteristics of artificial intelligence models of design cognition are that they are mechanistic, objectively deterministic, based on an information-processing paradigm and an assumption that all relevant knowledge can be adequately represented quantitatively.

An alternative slant on the role of artificial design cognition is offered by Tomiyama and Yoshikawa (1985) who claim that computer aided design systems give designers more time for thinking more deeply about the products. This is supported by Coyne and Snodgrass (1993) who in addition claim that the rationality that underpins artificial intelligence based research into CAD cannot address many aspects of human designing. What is implied by this is that artificial intelligence based theories of design cognition leading to CAD design solutions are *not* theories of human design cognition but instead are theories about those aspects of human cognitive design activity that can be mechanised and in this way are useful in freeing the human designer to undertake essentially human aspects of designing. This deconstruction of design activity into that which can be automated and that which cannot has been pointed to in Chapter 1 and earlier in this chapter, and is discussed further in Chapter 5.

Predating the above artificial intelligence theories are older models of artificial design process that were mainly developed in the 1950's and 1960's but are still in common use (see, for example, Ertas and Jones 1993). These older models of design process are based on concepts drawn from early systems theory and include the 'Analysis-Synthesis-Evaluation' feedback model, and the 'black box' and 'glass box' perspectives on design cognition (Jones 1970). Descriptions of designing in texts containing these early models of artificial design cognition

frequently refer to 'feeling', 'intuition' and 'insight' as essential aspects of designing, but the models of design cognition are mechanistic and positivist, and contain little that is adequate to address concerns about the individually interpretive basis of understanding and designers' creativity (see, for example, Alexander 1964; Asimow 1962; Gregory 1996a; Jones 1970; Jones and Thornley 1964a; Mann 1963; Matousek 1963; Roe, Soulis and Handa 1966).

2.3.2.2.2 Research into human design cognition

Many researchers have gone to great lengths to emphasise the difference between scientific activity and design activity (see, for example, Abel, 1981; Cathain, 1982; French, 1985; Joseph, 1996; Lyle, 1985; Sancar 1996; Tovey 1997, 1992b; Wray, 1992). In terms of design research, their arguments centre on the need to include in design theory those aspects of design activity that depend upon human internal activities such as cognition, judgement, creativity, valuing, feeling, guessing, intuiting and insight. Research into this essentially human side of design cognition is represented in the literature by four main fields,

- Models of design cognition that include an appreciative process parallel to a rational cognitive process (see, for example, Abel 1981; Bastick 1982; Dilnot 1982; Motard 1974; Porter 1988;; Schön 1984, Sneed (in Stegmuller 1976); Stegmuller 1976; Thomas and Carroll 1979; Weiskrantz 1987).
- Design cognition theory based on brain research (see, for example, Cross 1984d, 1990; Cross, Cross and Glynn 1986; Lera 1981a; Smets and Overbeeke 1994; Takala 1993; Ward 1984).
- Theories of cognition based on including the role of human values (see, for example, Alexander 1980; Bono (in Lawson) 1993; Cooper and Powell 1984; Cross 1984d; Dilnot 1982; Gordon 1961; Lera 1981b, 1983; Protzen 1980).
- The role of intuition and insight in theories of cognition (see, for example, Bastick 1982; Cross 1989, 1990; Davies 1985 (in Cross 1989); Davies and Talbot 1987; Glegg 1971; Rosen 1980; Simmonds (in Lera) 1983).

The individual literature relating to the above fields overlaps considerably, but in the main is bounded by the seven conceptual areas illustrated below in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Issues in human design cognition

In addition to the above four fields of literature of design cognition and the seven conceptual areas of Figure 8, is the study of the epistemological and ontological issues that underpin them (see, for example, Coyne 1990c; Coyne, Snodgrass 1991; Cross 1983, 1984c, 1991; Cross, Cross and Glynn 1986; Daley 1982; Davies and Talbot 1987; Franz 1994; Hamlyn 1990; Reich 1992, 1994a, 1994b, 1995; Reich et al 1996; Rosen 1980). There is substantial agreement between researchers about the human attributes that are important or essential for design cognition, and what emerges is a picture of human design cognition that is partly rational, partly intuitive and dependent upon designers' feelings (see, for example, the lists of characteristics and skills of Cross 1989; Eder 1995; Glegg 1971 and Neville and Crowe 1974 in Appendix 5).

The rational aspect of human design cognition has been subjected to considerable attention because it readily relates to the outlooks, theories and methodologies of the field of cognitive science (see, for example, Akin 1992; Baljon 1997; Chandrasekaran 1990; Dasgupta 1992; Faltings 1991; Gero 1991b; Hubka 1985; Newell and Simon 1972; Newell 1990; Ramscar, Lea and Pain 1996; Salminen and Verho 1989; Simon 1982; Soufi and Edmonds 1996; Visser 1991; Zeleny 1994). Of the non-rational aspects of design cognition, it is *intuition* and *feeling* that are most frequently referred to by both designers and design researchers alike. For example, Spencer-Chapman

(1993) believed that designers should aim to develop a *feel* for the relationships between engineering artefacts and social and natural systems, and repeated Ferguson's question of 'how we can foster the *intuitive feel* [emphasis added] for physical behaviour'. Similarly, Motard (1974) pointed to the importance of the role of feelings and experience in design cognition and the importance of biologically sensual aspects of design memory claiming that,

... an engineer would be hampered in his ability to design things if he had not experienced the material world first hand and distilled this experience through a kind of contemplation until it penetrated his entire being. The more perceptive the individual and the more sensitive, the more effective potentially, in the multidimensional pattern of design under constraints. Discovery and intuition might then have a physiological enhancement elicited from the fabric of the visual, aural and tactile experience and the 'feel' of physical situations.

In addition, both feeling and intuition are commonly associated with creativity, synthesis and understanding – all essential aspects of what marks designing as distinct from other human activities – and additionally, these 'intuitive' and 'feeling' aspects of designing are implicit in suggestions that design is both science and art (Deiter 1983; Eder 1995; Jones 1970; Matchett 1981; Wray 1992).

Some researchers have attempted to bridge the gap between the rational and non-rational aspects of human design cognition by suggesting that designers have particular ways of thinking that are different from 'normal' thinking. For example, Cross, Cross and Glynn (1986) have suggested that designers have 'designerly ways of thinking') and Goldschmidt (1994), Liu (1995) and Tovey (1992a) have pointed to the importance for designers of 'visual thinking'. These 'particular way of thinking' models of design cognition open the door to including other aspects of cognition than the purely logical and connect well with the work of those researchers who maintain that it is subconscious processes that are essential to explaining design cognition (see, for example, Davies 1995; Davies and Talbot 1987; Dorst 1995; Gasparski 1979; Glegg 1971; Jones 1971; Kern (quoted in Gregory 1981b); Lawson 1990, 1994; Purcell and Gero 1996; Soufi and Edmonds 1996; Stoltermann 1974).

In the main, however, where intuition or feeling has been included in theories of design cognition it has generally been via theories about the designed object or models of design process (see, for example, Akin and Akin 1996; Galle and Kovács 1996; Kolodner and Wills 1996; Lawson 1990, 1993, 1994; Liu 1996; Lloyd and Scott 1994). Epistemologically, these ways of including intuition, feeling and other non-rational aspects of human cognition are unsatisfactory because of their lack of scope and because they do not adequately include the essence of what it is for a human to design. Dilnot (1982) and Joseph (1996) have argued that viewing design cognition through either the designed object or through an ahuman definition of design process effectively moves the objects of research out of sight of the research method. In addition, Coyne and Snodgrass (1993), Franz (1994), Reich (1994a) and (1980) argued that scientific and positivist based design research is epistemologically insufficient for addressing many issues that are central to exploring the human aspects of design cognition. This means that those aspects of human design cognition involving intuition and feeling have either been ignored at the outset or addressed using research methods whose theoretical perspective is inappropriate.

Biologically based theories of design cognition that included intuition and feeling were proposed early in the history of design research. In 1970, Jones argued that designers are similar to artists, using 'the capacity of a skilled nervous system to respond quickly to an intuitively held picture of the real world . . . when they have to find their way through a number of alternatives while searching for a new and consistent pattern upon which to base their decisions.' By this proposal, Jones opened the theoretical foundation of design cognition to include research in neurology and the new field of psychoneurobiology. In a similar vein, Motard (1974) maintained that, 'design as a human activity includes *behavioural* [emphasis added] phenomena as well as cognitive inputs' and argued that good designers were good because they had 'the ability to *integrate experience* [emphasis added] as well as to generate conditions for experience to occur' and were also able to 'mature in their ability to condense states of knowledge into useful rules of thumb.' Motard argued that the raw material for internal patterns of thought comes from physiological experiencing and that the abstraction of this experience is then linked via cognition to the abstracted but also physiologically based

experience of others. Motard's is a sophisticated empirical view that avoids the more obvious epistemological and practical problems of biological determinism by its reference to cognitive abstraction. Had these biological proposals been adopted they would have connected well with the work of contemporary post-positivist and post-rationalist design researchers and the following three avenues of research into design cognition:

- The development of models of design cognition based on ideas of biological determinism. This option, developed via the field of artificial intelligence, has led to the development of connectionist, neural net and genetic algorithms of artificial design cognition (see, for example, Brown and Hwang 1993; Bullock et al 1995; Coyne et al 1990; Gero 1991b; Gero and Maher 1993; Hills 1995; Liu 1996; Newton And Coyne 1992; Woodbury 1992).
- The exploration of post-positivist epistemologies for design research (see, for example, Coyne 1990c, 1991b; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1992a, 1993; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992, Dilnot 1982; Dorst and Dijkhuis 1995; Franz 1994; Reich 1994).
- The exploration of research into similar problems in other disciplines, for example, left and right brain hemisphere research (Cross 1984d, 1990; Cross, Cross and Glynn 1986; Lera 1981a; Smets and Overbeeke 1994; Springer and Deutsch 1993; Ward 1984).

To summarise, researchers have explored several avenues investigating human design cognition across a variety of concept areas. There is substantial agreement in the field about the human attributes that contribute to human design cognition, but there are disagreements about the epistemological validity of some aspects of research in this area.

2.3.2.2.3 Discussion of the importance of theories of human design cognition

This section contains an overview of the epistemological merits of grounding this research in the research into human design cognition rather than artificial design cognition.

In spite of the explicit and implicit dominance of the informatic or 'artificial' basis of design research many researchers have had doubts about its adequacy as a basis for research into all

aspects of design cognition, particularly with respect to the role of humans in designing (see, for example, Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1992a, 1993; Cross 1992; Daley 1982; Dasgupta 1993; Dilnot 1982; Franz 1994; Glegg 1971; Hamlyn 1990; Lera, Cooper and Powell 1984; Newell 1990; Porter 1988; Reich 1994; Roozenburg 1992; Simon 1981, 1982; Stolterman 1994; Thomas and Carroll 1979). Cross (1992), supported by one of the first collections of papers on design thinking (Cross, Dorst and Roozenburg 1992), argued that design cognition had been inadequately addressed in the literature to that time, that is,

Those simplifying paradigms [of design thinking] which have been attempted in the past - such as viewing design simply as problem-solving, or information-processing, or decision-making, or pattern-recognition - have failed to capture the full complexity of design thinking.

This lack of adequacy or completeness of the artificial view of design cognition has been raised by other researchers presenting the following arguments,

- That the scientific, rational, informatic, problem-solving model of designing does not adequately address many aspects of the humanness of designers and theories of design cognition need to be able to address the vagaries of human intelligence, ignorance and intuition (Chakrabarti and Bligh, 1994; Glegg 1971; Lera, Cooper and Powell 1984; Petroski, 1992; Porter 1988; Simon 1981; Wong and Shriram, 1993).
- That the concept of abductive logic, used to underpin artificial intelligence models of artificial design cognition, is unsatisfactory and that a model of design cognition must replace it which includes 'innovative abduction' which cannot be expressed in formal logic (Roozenburg 1992).
- That designing is essentially a human activity, and when viewed as complex language-game or a Wittgensteinian 'form of life', it depends on other humans for its proper functioning (Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Liddament 1996).

- That the claims of Yoshikawa's General Design Theory and similar informatic theories to be complete theories of design were overstated in relation to human designing (Reich1995).
- That an hermeneutic approach to research into design cognition is necessary to address existential issues of meaning relating to human design cognition (Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1992a).
- That designing is not purely rational but depends also on intuitive considerations, for example, Glegg (1971) maintained that,

...we must beware of . . . regarding all design as a strictly logical exercise. It is no substitute for the inventive or the artistic... Logic is not enough; a sense of fitness of things is needed too.
- That theories of design cognition must adequately include qualitative design considerations, for example, Sharpe (1995) claimed that around 2500 million qualitative design decisions are made in designing an item of major plant and that this was approximately the same as the number of quantitative decisions.
- That design cognition cannot be adequately described from a rational verbal perspective because this perspective does not satisfactorily encompass the visual aspects of thinking. Tovey (1992a) offered objective evidence that automotive stylists have their own rich *visual* style of cognition accompanied by its own evolving language that enables the communication of that visual cognition
- That information-processing models of artificial design cognition ignore aspects of human functioning such as belief (Hamlyn, 1990), or make their adequate inclusion impossible (Newell, 1990). This is an important failing in terms of research into design cognition because theorising about designers' internalised processing of the validity of partially conceptualised creations is one of the most important issues which an information based model of designing would be expected to address and modelling all aspects of human cognitive process is necessary to that task.

- That intuition was a necessary aspect of the theoretical description of analysis and rational activities previously assumed to lie solely in the province of logic (Rosen 1980).
- That much of the theoretical inaccessibility of the intuitive aspects of cognition are connected with the widespread use of the 'central information-processing models' of thought and cognition that underpin theories of artificial design cognition (Hamlyn 1990).
- That issues of meaning and values underpin the problems of representation in theories of artificial cognition (Newell 1982, 1990). This means that the theoretical foundation of theories of design information and knowledge are challenged because they depend on a satisfactory theory of representation that cannot be construed using the same epistemological perspective.
- That design must be viewed primarily as a human activity rather than an ahuman process (Nakata 1996; Bieniawski 1993; Dasgupta 1993; Lawson 1993; Konda et al 1992; Petroski 1992; Piela, Katzenberg and McKelvey 1992; Ullman 1992; Cross 1984a, 1990; Ward 1984; Wilde 1983; Abel 1981; Thomas and Carroll 1979).
- That the focus on the designed object or the design process, common in research into artificial design cognition, leads to fundamental problems with respect to the validity of research methodology and the theory developed from it (Dilnot 1982).

Conceptually, the idea of 'artificial' intelligence assumes that there exists 'real' human intelligence. Likewise, 'artificial' models of designing, that are intended to automate design processes, depend upon an assumption of the existence of 'real' human designing. If this was not so, there would be no need to make the distinction that underlies the title of the journal *Artificial Intelligence in Engineering Design, Analysis and Manufacture*. The fact that the 'artificial' or mechanistic models of designing are theoretical *models* of an activity that exists in actuality has been overlooked in some research, and consequently models of designing and design process that have been created to simulate designing as an *artificial* process have come to be regarded as accurate representations of the *real* human activity. This confusion between the

artificial and the real has led to an assumption, implicit in much of the literature on design cognition, that human designing can be understood and represented by concepts and models relating to artificial design processes (Cross 1992).

Epistemologically, the study of human designing and the study of artificial design processes are theoretically different. One is the study of a human activity which has objectively observable and subjectively hidden aspects. The other is the study of a theoretical structure. In Popper's (1976) terms they lie in different 'worlds' of research and theory-making. By using models of artificial design process based on formalising the links between problem definitions and designed outcomes, the activity under study, *design cognition*, is opaquely reconceptualised from the realm of designing to the realm of the mechanical. This reconceptualisation means that designing, in this sense, cannot be automated because what is then referred to as 'designing' has become a determinable mechanical process. This latter point implies that theories created about automatic or routine design processes are not theories about *designing*, regardless of whether they are based on the techniques of artificial intelligence or any other body of knowledge.

A similar point was argued by Dilnot (1982) with respect to researchers' convergence on the designed object and the information transformations of a design process. He suggested that this way of viewing design through the design problem and its solution not only takes precedence over other perspectives, but results in the exclusion from investigation of other essential aspects of design cognition. One implication of Dilnot's argument is that, in a general theory of engineering design or a discipline of engineering design, the view of 'design as human activity' should have precedence over other design research outlooks, because the latter can be subsumed within the former but not vice versa.

The biological perspectives proposed by Bastick (1982), Jones (1970) and Motard (1974) offered a means of including human attributes alongside an informatic approach to design cognition by using biology as the theoretical interface between feeling and thinking. These biological perspectives on design cognition, based on the assumptions that design was a human activity and that human biology was part of the human process that led to the creation and conception

of designs, were well suited to being one of the cornerstones of human-centred theories of design.

Instead, alternative approaches more suited to computerisable theories of design have evolved where theoretical models of general biological and neurological process are used as a basis for the computerised synthetic deterministic development of design solutions to Well-defined and structured problems. This latter biological contribution relates to artificial design cognition rather than human design cognition and depends upon researchers giving privilege to a definition of design as 'an objectively determinable search process through solution space' in order that algorithms that imitate biology or neurology may be viewed as adequate means of mechanising the search for 'biologically determinable' solutions. Restricting the conceptual view of design to that of 'mechanically searching for solutions' means that issues concerning those essential aspects of human design and decision-making that relate to creativity, individually constructed realities and value judgements are neglected and remain unaddressed.

Value judgements and other human aspects of design cognition are excluded from the logical analysis that underpins many theories of artificial design cognition and creativity (see, for example, Alexander 1964; Altshuller 1984; Coyne, Newton and Sudweeks 1993; Hertz 1992; Liu 1996; Mitchell 1993). This exclusion of the human aspects of cognition gives rise to the problem of representation. Briefly, the problem of representation is the difficulty in establishing an adequate epistemology for theories that insist on objectivity and contain a circularity due to knowledge being derived from representation, and knowledge in its turn existing as a further representation. This issue of representation presents potentially insurmountable difficulties relating to the validation of core theories and concepts for those working in the fields of cognitive science and artificial intelligence. Newell (1982) identified the importance of the representation problem in the first presidential address of the American Association for Artificial Intelligence and it emerged again in Newell's later attempt to establish a comprehensive framework for a unified theory of artificial cognition (Newell, 1990). Theories of human design cognition that allow subjectivity and human values into the semantic aspect of cognition avoid those aspects of the representation problem that are present in theories of

artificial cognition because the problem of representation arises due to attempts to locate 'meaning' independently of individual human conceptualisation.

In addition to the epistemological problems of representation Rosen (1980) raised two other issues relating to the foundations of analysis that are relevant to theory-making about both artificial and human design cognition. Rosen pointed to intuition being epistemologically foundational in any explanation of creativity and synthesis and he implicated intuition, creativity and synthesis in activities which are commonly regarded as being rational or non-intuitive. After critically analysing the foundations of theories of analysis and synthesis, he concluded that intuition was fundamentally important to such theories because of its roles in:

- Justifying the closure which is necessary for validating theory (see also Walton 1996).
- Differentiating between creative activities and processes that can be routinised or formalised.
- Explaining activity which is not routine.

According to Rosen, intuition is dependent on individual human values, and this implies that it is essential to include human values in explanations and theories of analysis, synthesis and human judgement. Rosen's inclusion of intuition and human values as essential aspects of theories of analysis and creativity is directly and indirectly supported by a variety of viewpoints. For example:

- Hamlyn (1990) critically analysed the foundations of theories of cognition and concluded that intuition was an essential aspect of theories of design cognition and also that it is neither explained nor explicable in the rational and bounded rational views of cognition (Newell 1990; Simon 1982).
- Lai (1989) claimed that humans use an interpretive 'investigative strategy' for analytical problem solving.

- Rittel and Webber (1974) brought human values and intuition into design by arguing that the information needed to *understand* a problem depended upon one's idea for *solving* it.
- Dym (1994) included human values and intuition by arguing that design is a human activity or process with all that that entails about context and language.
- Stolterman (1994) claimed that there is objective evidence that designer's do not function rationally, and that it is the ideals and values of the designer that give a 'hidden rationality' to the design process.

The arguments that have been presented in this section point to artificial design cognition being epistemologically inadequate both in terms of representing design cognition in general and in its own concepts and methodology. In consequence, it is human design cognition that has been chosen to form the basis of this research. This choice of a human rather than an artificial focus has an additional benefit of assisting with circumnavigating the terminology problem discussed in Chapter 1. The terminology and theory from the tradition of engineering design research which relates directly to this human perspective is sparse, and researchers have tended to use the better-established concepts and terminology of other disciplines (Abel 1981; Davies and Talbot 1987; Lawson 1993; Schon 1984; Thomas and Carroll 1979; Ullman 1992).

Viewing design as a creative human activity that includes human values does not itself, however, lead to any easy theoretical solutions. Issues of human value give rise to problems in any theories of design cognition because of the difficulties associated with trying to explain. The consequences of individual designers having different underlying assumptions about reality, and how designers' values influence how they perceive both reality and their new conceptualisations (Magee, 1987; Protzen, 1980; Alexander, 1980). In addition, there are problems related to theorising about creativity because of the tautological difficulties in explaining the origin of new ideas (Hamlyn, 1990; Rosen, 1980).

The positivist information-processing basis for research into design cognition has depended on knowledge being represented as 'facts' that are objectively verifiable and independent of

human values. This separation of facts from values has been argued against by researchers who maintain that facts and values, and knowledge and values, are closely coupled and that theories of design must reflect this (see, for example, Coyne 1991; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1992a, 1992b; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992; Crane 1989; Dorst and Dijkhuis 1995; Margolis 1989; Pacey 1983; Reich 1994; Sargent 1994). Crane (1989) drew attention to the acceptance in philosophy of the demise of the fact-value dichotomy in the 1930s', and commented that this acceptance seems to have been slow to have been absorbed by the technical community. It is assumed in this thesis that facts and values are inseparable and, hence, it is inferred that there is a lack of credibility and completeness in the ontological and epistemological bases for theories of engineering design cognition that exclude human values and depend on facts and values being viewed as independent. These assumptions that facts and values are closely linked and that human values are a necessary part of theories of engineering design lead to the next research question.

Research Question 2:

What are the implications of including human values in theories of human design cognition?

To date, most researchers have used positivist methodologies and theories which present fundamental problems, as discussed earlier, because research into human design cognition involves many issues that are explicitly or implicitly excluded by the primary definitions of both positivism and science (Coyne and Snodgrass 1992b, 1993; Franz 1994; Guba 1990a; Reich 1994a, 1994b). The values issue is only one of the epistemological problems of positivist theories of design cognition which, when deconstructed, show weaknesses in the areas of intuition, cognitive styles, creative thought, meta-cognition, the role of feelings, individuation, evaluation, fixation, social influences on design, representation and perception (Akin and Akin 1996; Baljon

1997; Berger and Luckman 1987; Coyne 1990c, 1991b; Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1992a, 1992b, 1993; Crane 1989; Cross 1983, 1990; Cross and Cross 1995; Cross, Cross and Glynn 1986; Hamlyn 1990; Holt 1997; Indurkha 1992; Kitchener and Brenner 1990; Kolodner and Wills 1996; Newell 1982, 1990; Oxman 1995; Purcell and Gero 1996; Ramscar, Lee and Pain 1996; Rosen 1980; Sternberg 1990; Tovey 1997; Visser 1995). What is needed is a research perspective that provides an epistemologically adequate basis for including non-rational subjective aspects of cognition in researching and theorising about design, but without needing to reduce the cognitive phenomena into ahuman concepts and processes. This is particularly important for developing any general theory of design cognition where it is necessary for researchers to be able to theorise about those aspects of cognition that exist prior to a designer's conscious cognitive conceptualisation of a partial solution or 'design' and to take account of how the 'design' and its context are dealt with in 'fantasised design worlds' within designers' minds (Schon 1992; Schon and Wiggins 1992).

Several researchers have argued that it is epistemologically more appropriate to use post-positivist perspectives for research that focuses on design as a human activity because it is possible to include the subjective human considerations that the positivist perspectives cannot (Coyne 1991b; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992a, 1992b, 1993; Dorst and Dijkhuis 1995; Franz 1994; Guba 1990a; Harre 1981; Lincoln 1990; Phillips 1990; Popper 1976; Reason and Rowan 1981b; Reich 1994a, 1994b, Rowan and Reason 1981a; Schwandt, 1990). This research explores the use of post-positivist perspectives to address the research problem, and this leads to next research question.

Research Question 3:

What are the implications of using post-positive perspectives for research and theory-building in the area of engineering design cognition?

2.3.2.2.4 The representation of social, environmental and ethical matters in theories of design cognition

It has been argued earlier in this chapter and in Chapter 1 that social, environmental and ethical factors are central to developing an epistemologically satisfactory basis for theories of engineering design cognition. To summarise the position, design research needs to include social, environmental and ethical issues because of the role of design as definer of technology (Nicholls 1990; Wallace and Burgess 1995) and because the use of technology leads to,

- Changes in the *circumstances* of individuals and societies; if circumstances did not change then a particular technology would not have any utility.
- Changes in *attitudes* of individuals and societies; it is widely argued that technology changes users' attitudes by those involved in the study of technology transfer (see, for example, Harrison 1987; Illich 1974; Kipnis 1990; Klagge 1989; Mak 1995; Mamat 1991; Spencer 1991). In addition, the main purpose of some technology is to change users' attitudes and behaviour, and the technology is designed to those ends (Goggin 1994; Smets and Overbeeke 1994; and Woolley 1991).
- Changes to the underlying individual and societal *assumptions* that guide thoughts and actions (Benn 1974; Carpenter 1989; Frankel 1987; Margolis 1989; Norman 1992; Rapp 1989; Roszak 1974; Smets and Overbeeke 1995; Toffler 1973)

These issues are important in design research and the development of theories of design cognition because designers themselves are individuals affected by the technology they use, by the societies they live in, and by the activity of designing itself because thinking about new technology causes changes to an individual's attitudes and assumptions (Eno 1996; Margolis 1989; Schon 1983, 1987, 1992; Visser 1995). Hence, social, environmental and ethical issues are an important aspect of engineering design theory because of the ways that they necessarily influence engineering designers' cognition and the designs that they create. In this section, an overview is taken of the main themes concerning the inclusion of social, environmental and ethical matters in engineering design. The section concludes with a discussion of the characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors and presents additional research questions.

The conceptual topology of the study of social, environmental and ethical issues relating to technology is convoluted. The epistemological relationships between social and environmental concerns are confused and delineating a boundary between which issues relate to environmental effects of technology and which are best studied as social effects of technology is often difficult. This overlap and the difficulties that it presents is shown in, for example, the spread of topics in the contents list of *Social Impact* (Autumn 1992) and Fookes (1992) discussion of the New Zealand Resource Management Act.

The dominant view of the disciplinary relations in this area is that the study of the social effects of technology are subsumed within the study of the environmental effects of technology. This outlook may be because the study of the environmental effects of technology predates the study of its social effects: the time lag between the commencement of environmental and biophysical impact studies, and the study of socio-economic and cultural impacts was about six years in the United States and social factors were included because of an emphasis on 'secondary factors' in the 1973 National Environmental Protection Acts and Guidelines (Canter 1996). In Western Australia, the work of the Social Impact Unit was relayed via the Environmental Protection Authority to the State Government, which illustrates a similar dominance of environmental considerations over social ones (Social Impact, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 2). The minority view on the disciplinary relations between environmental and social concerns reverses the above situation and has the environmental effects of technology subsumed as part of the social effects of technology, and this is justified on the grounds that environmental changes cause human consequences by changing the human environment (see, for example, I. E. Aust. 1992). A more even handed position is reflected in the literature on the evaluation of program impacts where the effects of technology are partitioned into social and non-social environmental effects (Mohr 1988).

When ethical considerations are added to the above social and environmental relationships, the situation becomes more complex. Theories about ethical issues relating to technology have a reflexive epistemological relationship with the studies of the social and environmental effects of technology. Both social and environmental consequences of technology have an ethical aspect, yet the study of ethics is concerned with nothing other than social and environmental issues

because of its role as the study of the 'rightness' of human beings' actions. Ethical actions have external and/or internal consequences: if they are external, they affect the environment and hence, potentially, have social effects; and if the actions affect the actor internally, then, taken objectively, it is a social matter.' Hence, it is not clear whether social and environmental factors are a subset of ethical factors, or whether, by completely addressing the social and environmental consequences of technology, ethical analysis becomes redundant. Finally, in addition to these complexities, there is a temporal relationship between social, environmental and ethical matters that needs to be taken into account. Not only do social and environmental issues depend on ethical values, but, over time, ethical values themselves evolve within human societies, and these exist within, and are dependent on, a wider environmental ecology (Berger and Luckmann 1987).

The lack of clarity with respect to each of the terms 'social', 'environmental' and 'ethical' has led to a need to address this issue epistemologically in this research. In this thesis, the knowledge relating to social, environmental and ethical matters that are relevant to a particular design situation are viewed as *factors* which are similar to technical *factors* because they are influences on designers' cognition (see Chapter 1). Therefore, what is needed is epistemological clarification of the relationship between these social, environmental and ethical factors and the theories of engineering design cognition that are intended to include them. That is,

Research Question 4:

What are the theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors?

The last thirty or so years has seen increasing pressure on designers and the organisations which employ them to produce designs which reduce or avoid particular social and environmental effects. Design researchers have responded with Eco-Design, Life Cycle Analysis, Design for Recycling, Design for Environment, Sustainable Design and other research

and design methods that have been intended to improve the social, environmental and ethical consequences of technology (Chick 1997). Superficially, the philosophical basis of these new design developments appears to be clear, but on closer inspection it is a conceptual morass of different theoretical perspectives. For example, Hallen (1990) identified eight ethical ontological positions in relation to research concerning the environment that ranged from self-interested egoism, through the *grey green* outlooks of Bunge (1989), to the holism of the 'deep ecologists' or 'dark greens' (see, also Hollick 1995). Alongside these problems of ontological and epistemological perspective are terminological difficulties. For example, the definition of 'Ecodesign' that emerged from the 1994 Eco-Design Forum was,

Design which addresses all environmental impacts of a product throughout its complete life-cycle, without unduly compromising other criteria such as function, quality, cost and appearance (ECO2-IRN forum, 16th November 1994).

Underlying this definition was an understanding that a designer's consciousness of environmental issues influences their designing. The definition assumed that designers would have the 'right sorts of values', but the above definition does not preclude a designer consciously aiming to produce negative environmental impacts. Similar difficulties were noted by Brennan (1993) especially in relation to the number of meanings of the term 'sustainable' in circulation.

So far, engineering design theories have included social, environmental and ethical matters in one of the following ways:

- A design solution is first developed to satisfy technical constraints and it is then evaluated as to whether it satisfies social, environmental and ethical considerations. This is the most common perspective in the training of engineering designers and is represented in the methodology of environmental and social impact assessments (Booker 1962, Canter 1996; Ertas and Jones 1993; Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992).

- Social, environmental and ethical factors are quantified and included as if they are *technical* factors (Ertas and Jones 1993; Fenves and Grossman 1992; Piela, Katzenberg and McKelvey 1992; Otto and Antonsson 1994; Traub 1996)
- Social, environmental and ethical factors are reduced to the form of satisficing constraints. In terms of design theory, this perspective of bounding design solutions by quantifying social, environmental and ethical issues originated in the 1960s (Alexander 1963, 1964). The satisficing outlook on social, environmental and ethical factors is found in national and international technical standards that have social and environmental factors implicit in their specifications, and also in the guidance of national Environmental Protection Agencies where, for example, a requirement for good air quality might be reduced conceptually into a limitation on the proportion of sulphur dioxide that the air contains (Canter 1996).
- Social, environmental and ethical issues are included during the design process by recursively cycling through a design process model that divides the process into many interrelated parts (see, for example, the ‘Total Design’ model of design process of Pugh (1991)). In effect, this method brings social, environmental and ethical issues into the design process earlier than otherwise by using the above three methods at a micro level of designing.
- By bringing together the stake-holders in a design, informing them with quantitative data and allowing the design solution to evolve through a ‘political process’ (see, for example, Hollick 1993; Piela, Katzenberg and McKelvey 1992).

The underlying perspectives on how the social and environmental effects of technology are incorporated into models of design process are similar in all of the above except the last item. Practically, most perspectives assume a model of design cognition that depends on objectively quantifying the parameters of the design situation and then making decisions about these parameters by using a weighting method such as cost-benefit-risk or one of the more recent methods of magnitude scaling, multi-variable or multi attribute weighting that have been developed for use in multi-criteria optimisation (Crane 1989; Singer 1995; Zeleny 1994). The

model of design process that is based on the interactions between stakeholders being described in terms of political process explains the creation of a design via ideologies and publicly declared values. It does not, however, address issues concerning individual designers' cognition, particularly, how those quantitative and qualitative factors are brought together in creative cognition.

What each of the above situations illustrates is a lack of epistemological attention to the issues that underlie the representation of social, environmental and ethical matters in design theories. The epistemology of social, environmental and ethical issues in engineering design theory has been neglected in the literature of engineering design theory because the focus of mainstream positivist and post-positivist research has lain elsewhere. Positivist engineering design research has focused on artefact outcomes, engineering analyses, methods, knowledge, processes and techniques and from this positivist perspective, social, environmental and ethical matters are either quantified and included as if they were technical factors or are viewed as extraneous to the engineering design process. In both cases, the study of social, environmental and ethical factors is peripheral because the epistemological issues relating to the quantification of social, environmental and ethical factors are assumed to lie outside the province of engineers. In post-positivist engineering design research, the main themes have been:

- The application of post-positivist epistemologies from the Social Sciences.
- The establishment of arguments against positivist models of design cognition by exploring the weaknesses in the models of design cognition based on Cognitive Science.
- Bringing into design research the critical research perspectives of the post-positivist literature from the field of Philosophy of Knowledge.

Social, environmental and ethical factors are peripheral to each of the above post-positivist research directions, and the above analyses indicate that, for a variety of reasons, social, environmental and ethical factors have not been a significant concern of positivist and post-positivist engineering design research or design research.

It may be useful here to draw attention to a classification of research perspectives into what Phillips (1987) called 'hard headed' and 'soft headed'. The 'hard headed' perspective is positivist, based on quantitative information, and assumes that everything is amenable to mathematical representation. The 'soft headed' perspective has design as a human fundamentally unknowable activity. Ertas and Jones' (1993) outlook on social, environmental and ethical issues, whilst epistemologically unsophisticated, is 'hard headed' because their underlying epistemology is positivist. It contrasts with, for example, the 'soft headed' romantic metaphor of design described by Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin (1992). Potentially bridging both hard and soft headed approaches is the 'Total design' of Pugh (1991) which has a 'hard headed' line about technological matters but does not preclude the possibility of a more 'soft headed' approach to matters which cannot be managed in a 'hard headed' manner. One explanation of why the literature of engineering design research has been predominantly 'hard headed' is that there has been a shortage of alternative and more complex models of practical design that includes the human attributes. This has led to social, environmental and ethical factors being regarded as peripheral to the technical purpose of engineering (Beder 1989a, 1989b, 1990; Gregory 1981; Jonas 1982; Martin and Schinzinger 1983). As early as 1981, Gregory claimed that the lack of literature on design cognition relating to groups, organisations and social and environmental pressures was because of the shortage of alternative human models of design that could address human issues such as motivation, communication and negotiation. In other words, the technical emphasis in the design literature has led to a positivist perspective on social, environmental and ethical issues in engineering design cognition that is unable to incorporate the necessary values-based explanation of the cognition of human designers whose individual value systems are different and whose realities are relativistically constructed. Consequently, in this thesis, it is taken that the 'hard headed' outlook is inadequate for addressing social, environmental and ethical factors and this research explores the application of a 'soft' post-positivist perspective on engineering design cognition.

The above theoretical issues relating to social, environmental and ethical matters impinge on most engineers via the prescriptions of the professional engineering institutions (Beder 1990, Ertas and Jones 1993; Jonas 1982; Layton 1971; Martin and Schinzinger 1983). The guidelines

from professional institutions about how engineers should conduct themselves contain ethical advice on social and environmental issues in engineering (see, for example, *Code of Ethics*, I.E. Aust. 1988; *Environmental Principles for Engineers*, I. E. Aust., 1992; *Supplemental Charter and Byelaws*, I. E, Aust., 1991; *I.Mech.E.: Royal Charter, By-laws and Regulations for Voting* 1989). In the United States, most of the major engineering professions and professional institutions have adopted codes of ethics based on the code of ethics of the National Society for Professional Engineers (NSPE), and this trend has been followed by state legislators who have included some elements of the NSPE code in laws related to professional engineering registration (Ertas and Jones 1993; Martin and Schinzinger 1983). In Australia, in spite of close linkages with the United Kingdom, engineering institutions have in the main followed American engineering institutions in terms of their ethical codes. In the case of the Institution of Engineers Australia, which has a 'Code of Ethics' defined separately from its Royal Charter, its environmental code of practice, currently titled 'Environmental Principles for Engineers', was derived via the codes of ethics of the Institution of Professional Engineers, New Zealand, (I. E. Aust. 1988; 1991, 1992). In the UK, however, those institutions founded by Royal Charter are more likely to have their ethical strictures contained within their Royal Charter provisions (see, for example, I. Mech. E. 1989).

The contents of institutions' codes of social, environmental and ethical behaviour reflect the underlying assumptions and values of the institutions and the professional engineers that have joined them. This cultural gestalt of engineering institutions' ethical advice and prescriptions has been criticised by some researchers. For example, Jonas (1982) expressed concern that institutional prescriptions for professional engineering practice appeared to emphasise the ethics of professional relationships at the expense of social and environmental matters. His argument is supported by the environmental case studies of Caldwell, Hayes and MacWhirter (1976) and the historical overview of the American engineering institutions by Layton (1971). Beder (1990) claimed that there can be serious difficulties for engineers who attempt to satisfy professional engineering institutions' ethical requirements relating to social and environmental issues because of the pressures on individual engineers to be compliant with an employer's wishes. She points out the hegemonic difficulties for an individual engineer taking a stance

against their employers or other professionals on social, ethical or environmental grounds where there is no institutional or professional support for engineers and observes that action has been taken against engineers by professional institutions who have viewed an engineer's actions as a breach of professional ethics. In addition, Beder notes that the future employment prospects of an engineer who goes against an employer or other engineers are adversely affected. These analyses of Jonas and Beder of the practical and ontological difficulties of compliance with professional engineering institutions' advice on social, environmental and ethical matters are further supported by Layton's (1971) review of the institutional behaviour of engineers and Martin and Schinzinger's (1983) historical critiques of engineering ethics.

The issues raised by Beder, Jonas and Martin and Schinzinger relating to the underlying epistemological and ontological positions of engineering institutions are evident in the professional codes of the Institution of Engineers Australia (I. E. Aust.). The Institution of Engineers Australia has been chosen for this example because of the ready availability of its documentation rather than any assumption that its ethical position is less well considered than any other professional engineering institution. Historically, the professional engineering institutions have addressed social matters as a matter of priority and environmental matters as a consequence of the social emphasis which is in contrast to standards bodies concerned with environmental legislation and guidance who usually include social issues as a subset of environmental ones (Hollick 1995). In its *Environmental Principles for Engineers*, the I. E. Aust. (1992) indicates its intention that its engineers should attribute some ethical value to natural phenomena and give 'nature a standing which recognises maintenance of ecosystem independencies [sic] and diversity'. This potentially wide reaching definition of environmental ethics is then humanistically limited by the I. E. Aust, giving primacy to social ethics over environmental ethics as follows,

This [environmental ethic] does not accord nature an ethical standing similar to that of humans. Any recognition that all forms of nature have an inherent value unrelated to any utility would present new challenges to impact assessment and project evaluation.

The description has bounded the Institution's position on technological impact assessment and project evaluation by implying that design optimisation and decision-making methodologies should assume some criteria of human utility such as financial value and, in addition, the I. E. Aust. code of environmental practice has effectively excluded from consideration all arguments that insist on aspects of the environment having intrinsic worth.

The *Code of Ethics* of the I. E. Aust. (1988) avoids Jonas' concerns that institutions' advice to engineers emphasise professional and financial issues at the expense of social and environmental matters insisting that::

The responsibility of engineers for the welfare, health and safety of the community shall at all times come before their responsibility to the profession, to sectional or private interests, or to other engineers.

There is no indication, however, of the Institution providing any additional support for engineers who are disadvantaged by following its ethical directives and this leaves unanswered Beder's claims that such prescriptions are worthless.

Finally, the Institution requires that its members 'develop and promote a sustainability ethic'. There are problems with the terminology of this directive due to the lack of clarity about the exact meaning of 'sustainable' as noted by Brennan (1993) but, more importantly, the Institution gives no clear indication as to how 'developing and promoting a sustainability ethic' might be done by engineers whose training does not include any of the necessary conceptual skills or knowledge to enable them to embark on such a task (I.E.Aust. 1992).

The above discussions indicate that social, environmental and ethical issues are not conceptually well addressed in engineering design research and in the directives of professional institutions. More, the discussions point again to a shortage of epistemological analysis and a lack of conceptual and terminological clarity. For this research to address the research problem some of these epistemological and conceptual problems must be resolved first. Court (1995) has argued that the most crucial aspect of understanding designing and designers' behaviour is understanding how a designer uses information. Technical factors are easily expressed as quantitative information and because it is assumed in this thesis that social, environmental and

ethical *factors* influence designers' thoughts and behaviour in a similar way to technical factors, then it implies that social, environmental and ethical factors, like technical factors, should be seen as information. This position would fit well with the established quantitatively informatic view of design and with the design research literature that depends on the paradigms of Artificial Intelligence and Cognitive Science. To follow this direction, however, would be to go uncritically against the arguments that have been established earlier in this thesis that a positivist outlook on engineering design research is inadequate for addressing matters of design cognition relating to social, environmental and ethical factors. If social, environmental and ethical factors are to be included in design theory it is necessary to identify pertinent abstract characteristics about these factors which enable meaningful conceptualisation and communication. This argument is supported by Court (1995) who emphasised the extensive use of individual memory, knowledge and experience by engineering designers across all design activities and concluded that 'future research should also be directed to study the processes and developments involved in creating the memory/knowledge and experience of engineering designers'. It is necessary to have concepts, theory and terminology which enable the possibility of answers to epistemological questions such as, 'What are the implications for this conceptualisation of social factors of a deterministic theory of engineering design?'. It may be that social, environmental and ethical factors are best conceived of as information, but, by using a post-positivist research perspective, issues relating to human values, and the subjective aspects of designers' behaviour and thought can also be included. In other words, the post-positivist perspective provides a more complete basis for investigating how human designers include social, environmental and ethical factors in their designing rather than investigating how social, environmental and ethical factors can be included in models of artificial design cognition.

The above considerations lead to the final research question concerning engineering designers' use of social, environmental and ethical factors.

Research Question 5:

How do designers use information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors?

2.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, the background and focal literature that relates to the research problem has been reviewed. This has led to; the clarification of relationships between the background disciplines of the research problem; the identification of the need for satisfactory epistemological and ontological foundations for engineering design research and design research; and the identification of weaknesses in existing design theory, particularly with regard to cognition and social, environmental and ethical factors. In addition, the boundaries of the main conceptual areas of this research, (design theory, design cognition and the role of social, environmental and ethical factors) have been extended into areas that better relate to the human construction and interpretation of knowledge.

2.4.1 Summary list of research questions

Consideration of the research problem against the background and focal literature reviewed in this chapter has led to the five research questions that form the basis of this thesis.

- 1. How can design theories be evaluated and compared?*
- 2. What are the implications of including human values in theories of human design cognition?*
- 3. What are the implications of using post-positive perspectives for research and theory-building in the area of engineering design cognition?*
- 4. What are the theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors?*
- 5. How do designers use information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors?*

3. Theoretical position

3.1 Introduction

This research is practical rather than philosophical: its purpose is to find a solution to a problem, albeit an abstract one. Theory, theoretical perspectives, theoretical structures, paradigms, methodologies and methods are regarded as research tools rather than reified standpoints. In this thesis, research has been conceptualised as a pragmatic pursuit; as an exploratory activity rather than an attempt to identify 'truth'. This concurs with the positions of Argyris (1980) on rigorous research, Feyerabend (1975) on research methodology, Flood (1990) on systems research, Giddens (1987) on social research and Guba (1990) on paradigmic analysis and post-positivist research. This perspective fits well with those who see research as a complex of different fields and those who regard cognitive constructs in terms of their utility (see, for example, Coyne 1990c; Daley 1982; Enc and Adams 1992; Hoover, Rinderle and Finger 1991; Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Robinson 1986; Rowan and Reason 1981a, 1981b). This utilitarian perspective conflicts with the positivist perspective used in much of the literature of engineering design research and with researchers who have argued against positivism but wish to replace it with a single post-positivist paradigm (Coyne and Snodgrass 1993).

Chapter 3 has two roles in the thesis; it provides a description of the ontological, epistemological and methodological position upon which the research is based, and, in addition, it provides many of the theoretical and conceptual tools and arguments used in later analyses. In Hamlyn's (1990) terms, the theory needed to answer the research questions has been 'thinned' to a manageable level by 'thickening' up the theory relating to theoretical perspective and framework. The research problem is addressed via the research questions by standing outside the existing theories and assumptions of engineering design research as advocated by Indurkha (1992), Smith (1990), Rosen (1980) and Stegmuller (1976). From this meta-theoretical perspective, the search for answers to the research questions raised in Chapter 2 is guided by the following contextual conditions previously described in Chapters 1 and 2,

- The terminology of engineering design theory is ill-defined and with little agreement about fundamental terms or concepts because of lack of attention to epistemological and ontological concerns.
- The development of engineering design theory has been predominantly based on positivist, technicist and economic rationalist perspectives that are not well suited to addressing the human aspect of designing.
- The inclusion of social, environmental and ethical matters in theories of engineering design necessitates addressing the matter of human values because designing is a human activity and all human activities are dependent on human values, and because social, environmental and ethical factors themselves are dependent on human values.
- Critical analysis and post-positivist paradigms enable the identifying, clarifying and resolving of conceptual and terminological difficulties and offer the conceptual means of addressing issues involving human values.

3.1.1 Terminological issues

The lack of definition and agreement about the terminology of engineering design research means that any research into engineering design theory is difficult. There are conceptual and terminological difficulties associated with ontological, epistemological and theoretical aspects of engineering design research. Any attempt to resolve these difficulties using the existing terminology is compromised by that very terminology, and any attempt to redefine the terminology by reference to existing theory has similar problems because of the lack of conceptual coherence between engineering design theories themselves and the lack of attention which has been given to the ontological and epistemological foundations of these theories.

An obvious starting point is to carefully and completely define all the terminology of existing engineering design theory from the meanings attributed in the literature, and a glossary of this sort was unsuccessfully attempted before the magnitude of the terminological and theoretical problems were fully apparent (see Appendices 1, 2 and 4 and Chapters 1 and 2).

An alternative approach is to start with theory and to develop definitions based on the underlying theoretical, epistemological or ontological positions of existing theories. This would, however, be hermeneutic or semiotic research at a high level of complexity and abstraction because of the apparent reluctance of engineering design researchers to identify their theoretical perspectives and assumptions.

Neither of the above outlooks provides a satisfactory approach: the terminology problem cannot be resolved by focusing on either terminology or theory. Successfully dealing with the terminological confusion requires addressing the situation indirectly. What is needed is a means of clarifying *both* theory and terminology without depending solely on existing terminology or theory. There are three ways forward. The first is to use the meta-theoretical relationship between this research and engineering design research because this research does not *have* to use the language of engineering design research except where it refers to existing theory or terminology. This approach necessitates devising a new terminology. The second way forward is to focus on the terminology of areas that are of relevance to this research, but that have been neglected by other researchers. This approach is potentially fruitful: the criticisms raised in Chapter 2 relating to the balance of engineering design research imply that solutions to the research problem are not likely to be found in the mainstream of existing research and, in addition, the less well investigated areas have more pristine terminology due to their lack of literature. The third way forward is to utilise the terminology of well established human knowledge in other disciplines that have addressed similar problems. This way forward also offers the possibility of finding a satisfactory epistemological and ontological basis for engineering design research that is coherent with other well justified human knowledge.

3.1.2 Human values and engineering design theory

The dominance of positivism and the scientific perspective in engineering design research has restricted the way that the human aspects of designing have been included in theories describing engineering design (Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Dilnot 1982). Engineering design research is defined in Chapter 1 as being concerned with human creativity whose output is technological. Human values are a necessary aspect of engineering design theory because values are necessarily involved in explaining human creativity: even the definition of creativity

itself depends on human values (Heath 1993; Bono (in Lawson 1993)). In short, all proposals, theories, concepts, discussions and arguments of engineering design theory are conceptually placed in a value laden ecology. The inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory particularly depend on human values for the following reasons:

- Decisions about what is socially and environmentally important and what is ethically good are intimately linked to human values.
- Human values are a necessary aspect of explaining cognition.
- Human values underpin explanations of the socio-cultural aspects of designing.

3.1.3 Benefits of focusing on ontology and epistemology

Resolving the issues of terminology, theoretical perspective and human values involves changing the ontology and epistemology of engineering design research. Working from epistemology and ontology towards a clarification of theory and terminology is straightforward compared to the alternatives. It is not necessary to assume 'correctness' of the meanings of terms. This process is not sensitive to existing faults of description, argument or theorisation in the matter being studied because it is creating a parallel theoretical structure to existing theory that is grounded on established foundations. An ontological and epistemological focus provides, at an early stage, a structure against which different aspects of the existing literature can be compared and contrasted, and it allows new terminology and theory to be built on elements of knowledge and theory which are already accepted as well justified. Changing the ontology and epistemology of engineering design research permits a change of focus from the designed artefact to the activity of designing, and allows the inclusion of human valuing and other human characteristics.

This 'foundational' approach to resolving terminological and theoretical problems in engineering design and engineering design research is supported by the changes in the ontological, epistemological and methodological foundations of systems research in the last decade (Flood, 1995). Systems researchers have looked to other ontological and epistemological foundations than positivism and scientism because these had led to problems of philosophical justification, lack of theoretical integrity and poor practical applicability of theories, research

methods and practice (Flood, 1995; Ellis, 1995; Flood and Jackson, 1991; Flood, 1990; Flood and Carson, 1988)). Systems disciplines have absorbed post-positivist and constructivist outlooks, and as a result epistemological and ontological changes have been made and theories developed that reflect these changes (Hutchinson 1997). Engineering design theory and research has been implicitly and explicitly dependent on systems outlooks, models and theories, and these changes in the systems disciplines imply that a review of the theoretical and philosophical foundations of design theory and research is also indicated (Holt, Radcliffe and Schoorl 1990; Love 1995a).

Two addition points are peripheral to the present discussion, but require further clarification. Firstly, it is acknowledged that engineering design theorists and researchers have undertaken semantic or epistemological analyses, and that the development of many theories within what Dasgupta (1991) classified as the 'Information Processing', 'Algorithmic', 'Formal' and 'Artificial Intelligence' paradigms of design have depended on epistemological and semantic analysis and justification. The epistemological and semantic analyses conducted by those operating within Dasgupta's classifications, however, have focused on:

- The artefact and its definition
- The data, information or knowledge used by the designer
- The symbolic representation issues relating to representing information and processing algorithms

These foci are different from the epistemological focus on *theory* of this research.

The second point relates to the way that some researchers have conceived designing and design research in language terms (Schon 1992, 1983; Coyne 1991a; Mullins and Rinderle 1991; Rinderle 1991). The resolution of terminological problems in this research by focusing on *semantic* issues contrasts with the *syntactical* perspective of design theorists whose focus is the establishment of formal object based design languages (see, for example, Cross 1993, 1989, 1984b; Rinderle 1991; Mullins and Rinderle 1991; Dasgupta 1991; Suh 1990; Yoshikawa 1985c).

This chapter defines all aspects of the theoretical position used in this thesis including the way that theory is viewed and the particular meta-theoretical viewpoint that is used. The chapter contains six sections:

- Introduction
- Choice of theoretical perspective and framework
- Theory: its definition and validation
- Meta-theoretical analysis
- The limitations of the research position used in this thesis
- Summary

3.2 Choice of theoretical perspective and framework

Before addressing the research questions it is necessary to define the theoretical position used in this research. Before this can be done, however, the context within which this theoretical position is developed must be clarified. The literature relating to the choice of theoretical framework in engineering design research is limited, and the dominant position has favoured a positivist scientific basis for engineering design research. Some engineering design researchers have argued that social science research perspectives and methodologies are better suited to research in this area (Reich 1994a; Bowers 1991; Thomas and Carroll 1979). In the natural sciences, it has been epistemologically sufficient to elaborate on the details of research method and the theory to which it relates: the aspects of a thesis that Phillips and Pugh (1987) have referred to as the data theory and the focal theory. In the social sciences, however, researchers have been expected to discuss the epistemology of their research in more detail (Argyris 1980). Traditionally, the predominant epistemological foci have been the object of research and the theory that is used to interpret it. This emphasis on the research object and its associated theory has become too restrictive, and as positivism has declined in privilege the scope of epistemological explanation has been extended to include both the researcher and the

sociological, historical, cultural and theoretical context of the research (Guba 1990a, 1990b; Reason and Rowan 1981a, 1981b). A major influence in this change was the way that Kuhn (1962, 1982) described how 'paradigms' bound and shape the conceptual understanding and creativity of scientists and, hence, the concepts and theories that are produced. Kuhn's analyses were originally only justified with respect to the natural sciences, but the idea and the term have since permeated into other disciplines. Kuhn's concept of 'paradigm' is widely used to facilitate discussion about the form and validity of research methodology (see, for example, Cross 1996; Woodbury 1993; Colajinni, Grassi, Manzo and Naticchia 1991). It has become problematic, however, because of the many different ways that it has been used both by Kuhn and others (Stegmuller 1976a). For, example, 'paradigm' is used to mean any of the following:

- 'A 'world view' that includes any of the assumptions and bases of theory of research (Reich 1994a, 1994b).
- The public face of any theory which has been generated as a result of research (Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Cross, Naughton and Walker 1981).
- The running together of methodological perspective, methodology and method (see, for example, the publications of the 'design methods movement' (Cross 1984d) and, more particularly, the 'received view' of Suppe (Cross, Naughton and Walker 1981)).

Each of these uses of 'paradigm' are different, and does not include all aspects of theoretical perspective and structure that underpins research or theory-making. The term 'paradigm', therefore, is not used in this thesis as a key term in analysing the foundations of research.

Three terms that have a similar role to 'paradigm' and have promised a similar conceptual and terminological economy are 'metaphor', 'reification' and 'privilege'. 'Metaphor' is used to describe the way that humans represent the unknown in terms of the known. Like 'paradigm', its utility has declined as it has become clear that it has been used in a variety of contradictory ways (Indurkha 1992, Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992b). The terms 'reification' and 'privilege' – as in the 'reified frameworks' of Nideau (1991), and the 'privileged metaphors' of Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin (1992) – have a conceptually supporting role to the

more primary concepts of ‘metaphor’ and ‘paradigm’, and are limited by the semantic problems of these primary concepts. In spite of their differences, the meanings of ‘paradigm’, ‘metaphor’, ‘reification’ and ‘privilege’ have considerable overlap, and all of them point to the ways that one or more of beliefs, attitudes, experiences, theories, concepts and assumptions underpin and shape human action and cognition and its consequent effects, particularly in research.

The traditional philosophical terminology of ‘ontology’, ‘epistemology’ and ‘methodology’ provides a more established basis than ‘paradigm’, ‘metaphor’, ‘reification’ and ‘privilege’, for considering how prior circumstances affect action and cognition in individuals and research outcomes. Epistemology links ontology and methodology because epistemology is concerned with the way that reality is represented by theory that has been created as a result of research method. The combination of ontology, epistemology and research methodology gives the terminological and conceptual means to encompass all the considerations that paradigm, metaphor, reification and privilege have attempted to address. It has been argued that ontology and epistemology are inseparable because of the reciprocity between ‘the way that an individual human’s sense of what existence is’ is constructed and ‘the model of existence on which that construction is based’: that is, the answers to ‘What is existence?’ and ‘What is knowledge?’ are mutually interdependent (Guba, 1990b). This potential meta-epistemological interrelationship presents no problems in this research—just as the theoretical overlap of kinematics and dynamics in the study of moving bodies presents few difficulties below the level of relativity.

3.2.1 Theoretical perspective

The theoretical perspective that informs any research has three aspects to it:

Theoretical Perspective	
Ontological Perspective	Assumptions about reality. ‘World View’
Epistemological Perspective	Assumptions about the relationship between the ‘world’ (ontologically defined reality) and theory
Methodological Perspective	Assumptions that guide the choice of methodology including the particular way of seeing the object of research.

Table 3: Components of theoretical perspective

The theoretical perspective of engineering has a mechanistic and deterministic world view which depends on assumptions that the world can be mathematically represented and studied using a scientific methodology.

Theoretical Perspective of Engineering	
Ontological perspective	Mechanistic, deterministic
Epistemological perspective	Mathematical, logical empiricism (positivist)
Methodological perspective	Scientific

Table 4: Components of the theoretical perspective of Engineering

The mechanical, deterministic world of engineering contrasts with those social sciences whose choice of methodologies are mediated by constructivist, phenomenological, hermeneutic and other relativist ontological and epistemological perspectives. For example, the theoretical perspective of constructivism is defined by Guba (1990) as follows,

Theoretical Perspective of a constructivist Social Science	
Ontological perspective	Individually constructed and interpreted
Epistemological perspective	Critical subjectivism
Methodological perspective	Critical analysis

Table 5: Components of the theoretical perspective of a constructivist social science

The theoretical perspectives of engineering science and social science are both of relevance to research into engineering design because engineering design research is concerned with theories of designing, designers' practices and technology, that is, the study of designing necessarily has aspects of *theoria*, *praxis* and *techne* (Reich 1992). The range of research methodologies of engineering and social science that are relevant to engineering design research are pragmatically bounded by *scientism* which corresponds approximately to the theoretical perspective for engineering and the constructivism described by Guba (1990b) (Reich 1994).

3.2.2 Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework of a research project defines which elements of theoretical perspective, methodology, method and technique are seen by peers as sufficient to validate a particular research project. Thus, the theoretical framework consists of the chosen positions on

theoretical perspective plus the choices of methodology, method, and research technique as shown below.

Theoretical Framework
Ontological Perspective
Epistemological Perspective
Methodological Perspective
Methodology
Method
Research Technique

Table 6: Components of a Theoretical Framework

In engineering, the ubiquitousness of the scientific ontology, epistemology and methodology leads to their conflation. Thus, the theoretical framework for engineering research is relatively short,

Theoretical Framework of Engineering Research
Theoretical Perspective (Scientific)
Methodologies
Methods
Techniques

Table 7: Theoretical framework of Engineering Research

For some researchers, the theoretical framework is defined almost completely by a mathematical model. For example, the theoretical framework needed to validate research into a particular application of finite element analysis might be reduced to,

Theoretical Framework of Finite Element Research Project
Method (Mathematical validation of finite element analysis - supported by scientific perspective)
Research technique

Table 8: Components of the theoretical framework of a finite element research project

In contrast to Engineering, the Social Sciences have paid more attention to the details of theoretical perspective. Social Science research that allows that the world is subjectively interpreted has had to consider the implications of this perspective for research and its validity, and this relativist approach to reality has led to the necessity of justifying, in detail, the theoretical framework within which particular research has been undertaken (Argyris 1980;

Berger 1980; Flood 1990). Historically, discussion of theoretical perspective has focused mainly on the epistemological perspective, but the development of post-positivist world views and their implications for the validity of methodology have led to a more equal spread of attention between ontological, epistemological and methodological perspectives (Guba 1990a; Hamilton 1974).

3.2.3 Theoretical framework and paradigms

Before continuing further towards identifying the theoretical framework for this research it is necessary to place the terms ‘theoretical framework’ and ‘theoretical perspective’ relative to the discourse on ‘paradigms’ because much of the recent work in the area of theoretical framework has assumed Kuhn’s ‘paradigm’ as a basis for discourse (see, for example, Guba 1990b; Lincoln 1990; Schwandt 1990; Smith 1990). Although the term ‘paradigm’ has been used in differing ways, the overarching picture is that research paradigms guide how the object of research – whether actual or theoretical – is perceived and investigated and, as a result, the particular ‘paradigm of research’ dictates the type of theory which is constructed. Thus, the conscious or unconscious choice of research paradigm acts to give a perspective on reality and limit the choice of research methodology, research method, research technique and theory.

The concept of a ‘research paradigm’ that guides theory-making and how particular research is to be done comports well with the definitions of theoretical perspective and theoretical framework used here because, although the focus of the ‘paradigm’ literature is on research methodology, the explanations of its effect are grounded in ontological and epistemological concerns and research method. Thus, pragmatically, the concept of ‘paradigm’ can be deconstructed in a similar manner to theoretical framework,

Elements of the concept of ‘paradigm’
Ontological beliefs and assumptions
Epistemological assumptions and metaphors
Methodological preferences
Methodology
Methods

Table 9: Elements of the concept of ‘paradigm’

3.2.4 Review of positivist and post-positivist theoretical perspectives

Before deciding on the theoretical perspective and theoretical framework of *this* research it is appropriate to review in more detail the positivist and post-positivist perspectives and their relationship to engineering design research.

The application of the scientific method to human affairs was first proposed as a 'positivist' philosophy by Comte, and later developed by Carnap and his associates in the Vienna school into the empiricist based 'logical positivism' (Phillips, 1987). The purpose of positivism's earliest proponents was to dislodge metaphysics from philosophy, leaving philosophy based on only those aspects of existence which could be perceived directly, measured, or proven from perception or measurement (Giddens 1987; Guba 1990a; Harre 1981). The positivist outlook combined an empirical basis for interpreting phenomena with the representation of phenomena as theoretical entities, and this combination has provided the basis for the development of a comprehensive set of mathematically based physical theories in the natural and technological sciences. The positivist outlook has also defined which aspects of reality are best suited to being modelled mathematically or being represented by logically based theories. Positivism and logical positivism have had a dominant theoretical influence across the academic spectrum (Flood 1990; Giddens 1987; Shipman 1981).

The widespread appearances of positivist and logical positivist perspectives in engineering design research were not, however, derived solely from their philosophical origins. They were a consequence of the fact that research into engineering design was historically based on engineering outlooks because the initial focus of engineering design research was to improve the methods used in the design of engineering artefacts (Cross 1993, 1984b; Pahl and Beitz 1984; Matousek 1963; Jones 1963). This engineering perspective of improving methods of engineering analysis led to a focus on the mathematical analysis of engineering situations, and resulted in the same theoretical framework and scientific, mathematical methods being applied to other aspects of design research. It is because of this history of engineering design research that it was necessary to differentiate between 'engineering theory' and 'engineering design theory' in Chapters 1 and 2.

By the early 1960s, research into engineering design had begun to move more towards making theory about the human creative act of designing rather than focusing solely on developing analytic methods in the mathematical modelling of artefact behaviour (Gordon 1961; Jones 1970; Jones and Thornley 1963). The theoretical perspective and structure used for this new direction remained the same – that which was appropriate for research into artefact behaviour. Hence the positivist perspective became the default perspective of engineering design research regardless of its suitability or validity (Dilnot 1982; Love 1995a; Reich 1994a). The dominance of the positivist perspective is still evident today and its ubiquitousness across the field of engineering design research can be seen in the following:

- That designing is based on an underlying logic similar to *scientific* logic (Porter, 1988).
- That design should be seen as a technology, and that design research should *use similar paradigms as research into technology* (Cross, Naughton and Walker, 1981).
- That design is a *science* of the 'artificial' (Simon, 1969).
- That *mathematical programming* and *knowledge-based expert systems* are the major paradigms of design synthesis (Fenves and Grossman, 1992).
- That the *technically* based total design theory is suitable for clarifying the field of engineering design research (Pugh, 1990).
- That design studies should be based on the *formalization* and *mechanisation* of the creative process (Zeng and Cheng, 1991).
- That design issues should be incorporated into Artificial Intelligence systems by means of retrospective rational proof planning (Lowe 1994).
- That the use of the *scientific* paradigm in design research leads to the collection of *all* information about designing (Hubka and Eder, 1990).
- That *information-processing theory* and *behavioural psychology* are the main methods for investigating designers' activities (Lera, 1983).
- That designing is logically impossible (O'Cathain, 1982).

- That mathematical searching heuristics can replicate human abilities to solve ill-structured problems (McDermott, 1982).
- That design research is concerned only with the 'environment, the problem and the process' (Ullman, 1992).

In recent years, positivism's claim as the only theoretical perspective has been challenged on several fronts. Essentially, what is argued is that positivism, and scientism, offer a logical and efficient way of modelling reality, but the 'reality' that they model is a restricted subset of existence. The assumption that science is the most appropriate theoretical framework for engineering design research has resulted in the epistemologically under-justified application of quantitative scientific methods to qualitative issues and ignores the philosophical difficulties presented by the application of the scientific method outside the physical domain. It has not been widely appreciated in the engineering design research field that positivism presents these difficulties, and that in philosophy the positivist position has been refuted for some time; that there are intrinsic problems concerning the objectivity that underpins the theoretical models of design research derived via scientism; that there are fundamental problems concerning the theoretical status of objects when a positivist perspective is applied to design research; and that, by definition, positivist epistemologies do not address qualitative matters and issues involving human values (Coyne 1991b; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992a, 1993; Crane 1989; Daley 1982; Guba 1990b; Harre 1981; Phillips 1987; Reich 1994a, 1994b). These arguments do not negate the use of the scientific perspective in engineering design research. Rather, they change the theoretical role of science from an overarching world view – an all encompassing ontology, epistemology and methodology – to a research tool that is appropriate in some areas of human inquiry relating to situations where a mechanistic, deterministic objectivised view of reality is acceptable. The weight of argument against positivism from outside and inside the field of engineering design research lead to the conclusion that it is an inappropriate basis for the theoretical framework of this research.

Post-positivist ways of viewing the world add a wider perspective by offering greater insight and understanding into social and subjective considerations and providing an epistemological

structure that can include those considerations. In post-positivist epistemologies, knowledge and fact are relativistically defined and depend on differing individual human realities (Reich, 1994a; Guba, 1990a, 1990b; Reason and Rowan, 1981a). The main sources of post-positivist outlooks are based on addressing two issues:

- Resolving the inconsistencies in positivism, whilst maintaining that rationalism and empiricism are untouched by positivism's failures (Phillips, 1990; Cross, Naughton and Walker, 1981; Popper, 1976, 1963; Magee, 1973)
- Responding to challenges to the assumption of an objective reality that positivism depends on, and investigating the implications of assuming that reality is not an objective phenomenon (Coyne and Snodgrass, 1993; Guba, 1990b; Schwandt, 1990; Phillips, 1987; Harre, 1981)..

Resolving these issues has led to two strands of post-positivism:

- The 'neo-positivism' represented by Popper (1963) and Phillips (1987).
- The existential, constructivist, phenomenological, structuralist and post-structuralist, relativist, practicist, modern, post-modern and other post-positivist ontological and epistemological perspectives that reject positivism (Guba, 1990a).

These two strands of post-positivism have led to a terminological problem. Guba (1990b) has suggested that 'post-positivist' be applied only to those mainly Popperian perspectives that used the rationalist epistemology of science. Hence Guba's meaning of 'post-positivism' is similar to the 'neo-positivism' above. Guba's convention, at this moment in history, makes some sense and accords with the similar use of 'post' in 'post-modern' and 'post-structuralist', but it fails to draw an exact boundary between the 'post-positivist' and the alternative post-'post-positivist' perspectives. This lack of temporal and conceptual clarity is especially problematic for analysing the literature of engineering design research where a tendency to neo-positivist

perspectives is not uncommon (see, for example, Dasgupta, 1992, 1994; Hertz, 1992; Abel, 1979). In addition, Guba’s terminology is not universally followed. For example, Perry (1996) uses the term ‘phenomenological’ to refer to all non-positivist perspectives. For reasons of simplicity, clarity and brevity, therefore, the term ‘post-positivist’ is used in this thesis to refer to any or all of the replacements for positivism, and, where necessary, individual theoretical perspectives or paradigms are identified by name.

The post-positivist perspectives differ in their attitude to knowledge and truth from positivism. Positivism is based on a scientific perspective that depends on presuming that facts are objectively determinable and unchanging over time, and this necessitates a definition of the subject-object divide that defines fact in this manner (Harre, 1981). Post-positive perspectives define the subject-object divide differently, and some bridge it resulting in alternative definitions of the stability and determinability of fact that range from absolute relativism – the consequence of a hermeneutic perspective – to the ecological and biological determinist perspectives of Thines (1977) and Popper (1976) (Coyne and Snodgrass 1991).

Popper (1976) developed a post-positivist model that is useful in unravelling some aspects of the terminological confusion of engineering design research. This model divides reality into three incommensurable worlds:

- A *subjective world* of human internal feelings and cognition
- An *external world* of observed phenomena
- A *theoretical world* that contains the concepts and theories that provide the means of public and private discourse and analysis.

Popper’s 3 World model provides a useful means of separating different aspects of, for example, cognition,

Popper’s 3 Worlds	Aspects of cognition
Subjective world	Thinking about theory
Objective world	The brain in which thinking happens
Theoretical world	Theories about thinking

Table 10: Popper’s separation of different aspects of cognition

Similarly the 3 World model can separate different aspects of theory:

Popper's 3 Worlds	Aspects of Theory
Subjective world	Theory as individual cognition
Objective world	Theory written down and made public
Theoretical world	Theory <i>qua</i> theory

Table 11: Popper's separation of different aspects of theory

Popper's three fold classification of theory is useful at various points in this thesis because these different forms of theory are frequently confused in the literature of engineering design research. Different research perspectives are needed for addressing issues about physical phenomena from those used for investigating theories about internal psychological processes, or those used for analysing the validity and coherence of design theories and disciplinary structure.

Other post-positivist perspectives have moved further from the positivist tradition than Popper. The hermeneutic philosophy, which evolved out of the works of Husserl, Heidegger and Gadamer, and the deconstructivist perspective of Derrida, has left no place to stand to make any objective observations: in these perspectives all theories and concepts are relative and interpreted (Coyne, 1991b; Flood, 1990). Heidegger's (1962) existentialism emphasised the sense of being or 'dwelling' in a situation as more important than objective considerations. Berger and Luckman (1987) developed a paradigm of social constructivism in which it is argued that an individual's construction of reality is more dependent on social interaction than objective concepts. Giddens (1978) has argued that many matters that were previously considered to be epistemological are now seen as depending on social conventions and human values. Habermas' critical theory extended and elaborated Berger and Luckman's social constructivism into the realms of politics, power and hegemony (Giddens, 1987). Guba (1990) and Lincoln (1990) developed a constructivist perspective that assumes that reality is constructed on the basis of individuals' unique personal experiences and histories.

3.2.5 Theoretical framework of this research

The choice of theoretical perspective for this research is dictated by its focus on epistemology and theory. The theoretical framework of this thesis is different from the theoretical frameworks of engineering design research, engineering design theory and engineering design because of its meta-theoretical relationship to them. There is a separation between the theoretical frameworks

of this research and engineering design research because its research purpose is different from mainstream engineering design research. This research reviews and critiques the foundations of engineering design research and its purpose is to investigate and propose changes. There is an hierarchy as shown in Table 12 below.

Theoretical framework of this research
Theoretical framework of engineering design research
Theoretical framework of engineering design theory
Theoretical framework of engineering design

Table 12: Hierarchy of theoretical frameworks

Many of the research questions identified in Chapters 1 and 2 relate to how theories can be made about aspects of engineering design and engineering design theories in Popper’s ‘subjective’ and ‘external’ worlds. The research questions and their contexts involve conceptual abstractions and symbolic representations whose epistemological backgrounds may be viewed as paradigmic assumptions (Kuhn 1962; Guba 1990b; Smith 1990), metaphors (Coyne and Newton 1992; Indurkha 1992; Coyne 1991b) or reified conceptual frameworks (Nideau 1991) but whose final repose is in theory-making and theory (Rosen 1985; Stegmuller 1976). Hence, theory itself is one of the central foci in this research.

A wide variety of mainly positivist theoretical perspectives has been used in engineering design research and must be encompassed by the theoretical perspective of this research. For example:

- Abel (1979) argued for increased rationality in design – by inference using a rational perspective.
- Adelman, Gualtieri and Riedel (1994) applied a research program based on three different theoretical approaches to an evaluation of expert systems in design.
- Akin (1979) drew attention to the different sorts of investigation needed in design and argued for the use of psychological research methods.
- Dasgupta (1992) claimed that design research should result in a discipline of design theory; an empirical discipline based on a scientific methodology.

- Dasgupta (1994) attempted to build an empiricist design theory by combining a socio-historical research perspective, which he used to investigate the development of a design in progress, with a perspective drawn from cognitive science. His analysis used aspects of a critical perspective alongside issues that might more appropriately have been addressed from within an hermeneutic perspective.
- Hertz (1992) used perspectives drawn from cognitive psychology and information-processing together with empiricism to propose a model of individual creative design process.
- Holt, Radcliffe and Schoorl (1985) argued that the main perspectives in engineering design should be analysis, systems thinking and human factors.
- Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian (1992) developed a taxonomy of design research from within an information-processing perspective. In doing so they pointed to a range of other theoretical bases for research into design process.
- Lawson (1993) maintained that design refers to an enormous range of activities, and hence to a very wide range of theoretical perspectives.
- Nadler (1989) emphasised psycho-social analyses of designers' approaches to design.
- Piela, Katzenberg and McKelvey (1992) combined a participatory research perspective to CAD system users with a scientific perspective used to investigate the CAD system itself.
- Pugh (1982) claimed that design encompasses and integrates both the arts and the sciences. Implicit in his suggestion is the argument that design research needs to contain all research perspectives.
- Reich (1995, 1994a, 1994b) utilised a critical methodology in his research into general design theory and design research methodology.
- Schon (1992) argued that to understand the information-processing tasks in designing it is necessary to use a phenomenological research perspective.

- Steinberg (1994) insisted on a scientific perspective on design research.
- Talbot (1981) noted a wide spectrum of research methodologies evident in the Design: Science: Method conference.

The above range of different ontological, epistemological and methodological perspectives suggests that it is necessary to use a theoretical perspective for engineering design research that is capable of including all these viewpoints. Each theoretical perspective, however, addresses different aspects of a research situation and leads to different kinds of outcome (Guba, 1990b, Smith, 1990). For example, a phenomenological methodology would treat engineering design as a phenomenon that is experienced; an hermeneutic methodology would focus on the meanings involved in designing and the theory-making about it, applying Habermas' Critical Theory would lead to a focus on hegemonic, social and political considerations.

One possibility of satisfying the above constraints on the choice of theoretical framework is to choose on the basis of epistemological utility. That is, instead of theoretical frameworks or perspectives being chosen or compared solely on their claims to truth, they are viewed as tools representing ontological and epistemological traditions and chosen as appropriate to particular tasks (Feyerabend, 1975). This leads to the possibility that several theoretical perspectives might be used at the same time on the same topic or within the same research program – a plurality rather than a singularity of perspectives – chosen on the basis of their suitability with due respect to issues of validity (Reason and Rowan 1981b).

The use of multiple theoretical perspectives has been suggested by some design researchers involved in meta-theoretical investigations (Cross, Cross and Glynn 1986; Franz 1994; Schon 1992). This multi-perspective approach is supported by Guba (1990) in research into alternative paradigms; Flood (1995, 1990) in the field of systems theory; Lawton (1994) on research into architectural design; and Reich (1994a) in research into artificial intelligence and engineering design. The most obvious difficulty with using multiple perspectives is in bringing together research data from different theoretical positions and methodologies. These difficulties arise in trying to coalesce information from *any* two research investigations, even those using similar perspectives, because all research and data are incomplete and under-justified, and provide the

basis for further developments (Argyris 1980; Kuhn 1962; Phillips 1987; Popper 1959, Reich 1994a). It is only if absolute truth is taken as the touchstone for research quality that these issues become potentially irresolvable.

The most important issues for the choice of theoretical perspective and framework of research concern how appropriately they address the research questions. The main criteria are:

- The 'world view' must be broad enough to include the human aspects of designing alongside the spread of existing perspectives of engineering design research that range from scientific determinism to romantic assumptions about 'human genius'.
- It must provide the conceptual and analytical means of reviewing and critiquing epistemological, ontological and theoretical issues in engineering design research.
- It must provide the means of including subjective human experiencing and human values into engineering design theory.

It is clear that a positivist or scientific perspective is insufficient from the arguments presented earlier. Post-positivist perspectives can satisfy one or more of the above criteria and would be capable of addressing the research questions, but some are less appropriate than others because their primary focus is less well matched to the research circumstance. For example, the social constructivism of Berger and Luckman (1987) addresses the research issues through the social context of the engineering designer rather than focusing on the designer.

The most pervasive aspect of the research problem and research questions concerns how human values influence how designers view the world and construct designs in their consciousness.

The most appropriate ontological and epistemological perspective for addressing these issues is the constructivism of Guba (1990b) and Lincoln (1990) because the constructive perspective focuses on how an individual interprets and constructs their own internal worlds.

Constructivism uses any epistemological and methodological perspectives that help address its central concerns and therefore can encompass the scientific perspectives of existing engineering design research. In addition, it can satisfy the concerns of some researchers that *any* theory-making and theory depends fundamentally on human values (Guba, 1990b; Rosen, 1985;

Stegmuller, 1976). Using a constructivist basis also assists with addressing the problems of terminological confusion and theoretical under-justification in engineering design. The constructivist position is accompanied by an appreciation of the need to address semantic difficulties because of its assumption that theory and abstraction are based on knowledge that is relative and interpreted, and consequently it contains the necessary analytical basis for dealing with terminological and conceptual confusion (Guba 1990a). In addition, it provides a means of addressing the lack of ontological and epistemological justification discussed in Chapter 2 because of its close relationship with the critical perspectives and methodologies (Reich 1994; Franz 1994; Guba 1990b). For these reasons, constructivism is chosen as the ontological and epistemological perspectives of this research. Both ontology and epistemology must be the same because the use of a constructivist ontological perspective implies that knowledge and theory are also constructed and, hence, the epistemology of that knowledge must also be constructivist (Guba 1990b).

The remaining element of theoretical perspective to be decided upon is the methodological perspective. The position taken here is that all theory is relative: that theory and 'truth' may coexist but the search for a 'true' theory must be fruitless. It is still necessary, however, to be able to differentiate between 'good' theory and 'poor' theory and to compare and contrast theories. That is, it is necessary to address matters of 'meaning' and 'correctness' between and across theories. A critical methodological perspective is regarded as the best choice for this type of research because critical analysis is the most appropriate methodology for analysing theoretical issues particularly those concerning research methodologies (Reich, 1994; Franz, 1994; Flood, 1990; Rowan, 1981a).

Thus the theoretical perspective of this research is as follows,

Theoretical Perspective of this Research	
Ontological perspective	Constructivist
Epistemological perspective	Constructivist
Methodological perspective	Critical

Table 13: Theoretical perspective of this research

These choices derive from analysing the purpose and context of this research. They also accord, however, with the arguments of other researchers involved in developing a satisfactory epistemological and methodological basis for design research (Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Dilnot 1982; Franz 1994; Reich 1994a, 1994b, 1995).

The above choice of ontological, epistemological and methodological perspectives defines the choice of the practical elements of the theoretical framework used in this research. A critical methodological perspective implies that the choice of methodology, method and techniques are also critical and involve variants of critical analysis. Hence, the theoretical framework of this research is,

Theoretical Framework of this Research	
Ontological perspective	Constructivist
Epistemological perspective	Constructivist
Methodological perspective	Critical
Methodology	Critical
Methods	Critical
Techniques	Variants of critical analysis

Table 14: Theoretical framework of this research

3.3 Theory: its definition and validation

Defining the theoretical framework of this research is the first step in answering the research questions. The constructivist perspective has underlying assumptions that lead directly to a focus on the ontology and epistemology of engineering design theory. From a constructivist position, knowledge is relative and constructed: human knowledge and action is seen as being constructed within a social and cultural framework where differences in social or cultural context or individual differences in cognition mean that knowledge is relatively situated.

Consequently, theories and concepts have a status that depends on the privilege that is given to them rather than them being 'true' or 'absolute', and this means that a full understanding of any theory or concept depends on knowledge and understanding of its epistemological and ontological foundations. It is for this reason that the constructivist perspective in this research gives rise to an emphasis on the choice of ontological and epistemological assumptions about theory and its validation. The research problem involves bringing social, environmental and

ethical factors into engineering design theory, and in this section those aspects of theory that are necessary to that task are explored and the position of this research on theory is defined.

The discourse of theories in engineering design research is similar to other disciplines. The tools of discussion are the meanings of words and symbols, and the arrangements used to construct relationships between them. Concepts, theories and arguments are constructed and communicated using words and syntax and are tested by asking:

- Whether they model the phenomena adequately
- What they are derived from
- Whether the derivation is correctly based on other theories
- How well they fit with data

Kuhn and others have argued that the validity of a theory depends on how that theory fits within a wider network of well established theory and knowledge (Berger and Luckmann 1987; Kuhn 1976; Rosen 1980; Stegmuller 1976). From this epistemological perspective, concepts, theories and arguments depend for their meaning on everything that is related to them. For example, theories of machine dynamics that describe kinematic and dynamic behaviour of elements of machinery also relate to other less focal issues such as the use of Euclidean geometry, assumptions about the range of rigidity of materials used in practical machines, particular ways of seeing and representing elements in two and three dimensions, assumptions about what is a machine element and what is not, what kind of technologies are available, and, more distantly, the socio-cultural situation that gave rise to the machines or theories. These additional non-focal implications which have an association with a theoretical entity also need to be inspected because the validity of a concept, theory and argument may depend as much on these outside considerations as on the careful construction of intended primary representations, relationships and meanings. In short, a concept or theory must not only be verifiable in terms of its immediate intention, it must also comport well with other privileged human knowledge.

In theories about the human activity of designing, the reality of the human designer is represented in a reduced manner, and such theories are tested by asking:

- Whether anything has been left out which is necessarily part of what the theory seeks to represent?
- Whether anything has been left out which might contradict the theory?
- Whether the bounds and contexts of theories are clearly included in their description?

A theory that does not have a satisfactory answer to one or more of these questions can then only be validated by reviewing all of its aspects – its construction, the theoretical elements on which it is based and all other peripheral matters to which the theory relates. They all must be considered part of the theoretical whole and must reasonably be expected to withstand critical theoretical, semantic and epistemological scrutiny (Hamlyn 1990; Kuhn 1976).

3.3.1 Analysis and intuition

Most theories of engineering design include an element relating to the creation or invention of new design solutions in their model of design process without any epistemologically complete explanation of how it is achieved. This is a substantial theoretical weakness of existing engineering design theory because it is this aspect of the design process that fundamentally differentiates designing from other activities. Rosen (1980) argued that intuition is the primary means for conceiving concepts and developing theory, and this intuition lies beyond analysis because of the role of the transcendental ego in human functioning. Here, the term ‘analysis’ is used by Rosen in the philosophical sense of ‘taking apart using a critical perspective’, rather than the engineering sense of ‘using a mathematical model’. For Rosen, the creative act cannot be explained using analytical and rational means and this implies that *any* attempt to formulate a description of the creative process by analytical means is bound to fail. More importantly for engineering design research, it points to difficulties in differentiating designing from other less creative activities. Rosen resolves these issues somewhat by arguing that synthesis has a more primary role in theory-making than analysis because ‘every analysis depends on a prior synthesis, that is, ‘if there had not first been a putting together (whether by nature or the analyst) there could be no taking apart’. From Rosen’s position, the social act of theorising is grounded in analysis, but that analysis is always based on synthesis. Although Rosen’s language is of philosophy, it applies also to engineering and engineering design in that after an

analysis has been undertaken something new exists: the taking apart of analysis results in a new creation in knowledge. In engineering, a mathematical model is used to analyse potential performance and this results in new technical information. In designing, the problem specification and possible partial solutions are conceptually dismantled to assess their functionality and this provides information leading towards a new solution. In philosophy, ideas and theories are taken apart to check their validity and this leads towards new ideas. In each case, something new which lies in Popper's third world of theory is created. That is, whilst the analysis must depend on a previous synthesis, the act of analysis itself leads to a synthesis of something new and this can exist as understanding in the mind of the one whose intuition creates the synthesis, or in the objective world embodied as theory. Rosen's position on the role of intuition is similar to that which underpins most post-positivist perspectives or alternative research paradigms whether stated explicitly or not (see, for example, Bastick 1982; Coyne 1997; Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992; Guba 1990a; Heath 1993; Heidegger 1963; Kuhn 1962; Magee 1973; Popper 1959, 1976; Stegmüller 1976; Takala 1993; Tovey 1997).

3.3.2 Metaphor and engineering design theory.

The concept of metaphor offers an alternative way of theorising about the creative aspects of engineering design in a manner that is more circumspect than Rosen's exploration of the limits of analysis (see, for example, Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1993). This circumspection presents some pitfalls, however, because of the way that metaphor is neither an exact nor complete representation and yet may be a coherent and functional representational system. In addition, theories are culturally and historically placed because different cultural bases with different values and assumptions lead to different theoretical metaphors (Carpenter 1989; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1993). Both these considerations present problems for predicting from metaphor or extending theory using metaphor. Indurkha (1992) clarified issues in this area in two ways by deconstructing and drawing out the different theoretical positions held by those researching metaphor. He drew attention to the distinction between *meaning* and *correctness*, and observed that metaphor is frequently and unhelpfully confused with predictive analogy: a point that applies particularly to engineering design

research because of researchers' preference for deterministic solutions. Indurkha's work provides the basis for researchers to differentiate between research into the metaphorical aspects of design thoughts and designers' use of predictive analogy, and points towards a solution to some of the underlying epistemological and ontological difficulties relating to a metaphorical view of design practice. Indurkha's analyses are relevant to this research in that they emphasise a need for caution in the use of metaphor for clarifying or building theory, especially where ontological and epistemological considerations are being reviewed.

3.3.3 Qualitative and quantitative aspects of theory

Rosen's (1980) analyses, Indurkha's (1992) metaphors and the theories of engineering design researchers all describe, formulate or manipulate knowledge. The positivist perspective that dominates engineering design research depends on knowledge being quantifiable, but the perspective used in this research and defined earlier in this chapter allows and assumes that knowledge can also be qualitative. For this research, the qualitative aspect of knowledge has more importance than the quantitative aspect because designers' creation, comparison and validation of internalised pseudo-realities is essentially a matter of human values.

Knowledge has both quantitative and qualitative aspects and it is tempting to assume that the difference between qualitative and quantitative knowledge is that knowledge is quantitative when it can be measured or expressed as a measurement and qualitative when it is perceived through the senses. Hamlyn (1990) and others have pointed to this being an oversimplification that depends on the limitations of positivism, information-processing perspectives and a central processor based model of cognition (see, for example, Guba 1990a; Reason and Rowan 1981a; Rosen 1982).

Classifying knowledge as quantitative or qualitative is not necessarily straightforward. For example; the knowledge gained by experiencing the loud noise from a sports car is qualitative, but the knowledge of whether the vehicle that the loud noise came from was a sports car or a bus, or whether there was (or was not) a sports car or a bus in the same vicinity is a quantitative matter. In the above case, the knowledge as experienced is qualitative, but the experientially based knowledge about 'identity' and 'presence' are quantitative. The identity knowledge

relates to either a sports car or a bus and the information about its presence is that the sports car or bus was either there or it was not there. Put simply, the knowledge contains information about the quantity of buses or sports cars which were present (or not). Identity and presence are aspects of designed objects that are often assumed to be qualitative rather than quantitative, especially when the quantitative aspects are binary, i.e., on or off, 'there' or 'not there', 'before' or 'behind', or, 'to the left' or 'to the right' (see, for example, Wong and Sriram 1993).

Another example that illustrates the difficulty in separating the quantitative aspects of knowledge from the qualitative is the following: Dump trucks are designed in a range of sizes from those used on small urban building sites to those used in mining and other resource handling. Typical payloads range from 500 kg to 50 tonnes. A designer being asked to design a dumper truck to carry 300 tonnes would likely view the request in a different light from that of one for 30 tonnes. Although the information '300 tonnes' is obviously quantitative, it contains qualitative knowledge, for example, about the likely difficulty of the project. Similarly, a persons hearing that the day's temperature forecast is 25⁰C is likely to respond differently to one hearing a forecast of 50⁰C, indicating that the quantitative information brings with it a qualitative aspect.

In contrast to Engineering, much of the knowledge associated with the Arts and the Social Sciences is qualitative. This qualitative knowledge is, however, stored and expressed symbolically in words and other visual images, along with sound and, in the case of some sculpture, touch.

At this stage, it is sufficient to establish that:

- Overtly quantitative information may have qualitative aspects and vice versa.
- Knowledge is neither exclusively quantitative nor qualitative and often contains both simultaneously.

3.3.4 Problems of validation of engineering design theory.

The adoption of a post-positivist theoretical framework in this thesis means that the validation processes of positivism are no longer appropriate. The means of testing theory that are

sufficient for engineering purposes are not sufficient for wider epistemological justification because they do not include or point to either a complete description of what a theory is, or a means of establishing the validity of theories beyond the framework within which they are coined. This limitation of positivism is one reason why engineering design research has had problems in validating its theories. Other problems of validation in engineering design research are due to the complexity of the phenomena implicated in design, the problems of data collection, difficulties of comparison of theories and data, and the application of inappropriate research paradigms (see, Chapters 1 and 2, Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Cross 1990; Franz 1994; Reason and Rowan 1981b; Reich 1992, 1994a). Research into problem-solving behaviour and creative action are considered to be some of the more difficult areas of cognitive psychology (Thomas and Carroll 1979) and it may be intrinsically impossible if either Popper's (1976) or Davies and Talbot's (1987) accounts of such matters are correct. There is little that can be considered hard data that is universally applicable, and there has been insufficient attention given to identifying the background issues that affect the collection of valid and useful data about designers' internal cognition and the theories based on them (Davies 1995; Ehrlenspiel and Dylla 1989; Lloyd, Lawson and Scott 1995; Waldron and Waldron 1988). Making cogent theory about the internalised activity of designing is working in the realms of circumstantial evidence because external behaviour is only symptomatic of internal thought processes, and as such is not definitive (Phillips, 1987). Comparing theories and data of engineering design research presents potentially insurmountable temporal problems due to the socio-cultural context of designing where practical comparisons of design theories and data would need the initial social, cultural, economic and technical factors to be the same for each experiment, and collecting the results would entail longitudinal studies of socio-economic change over years or decades (Wallace and Burgess 1995).

3.3.5 Validating engineering design theory.

The constructivist perspective on validating engineering design theory used in this thesis follows Kuhn (1962) and other relativist epistemologists in that it looks to the relationship between theories rather than attempting to validate theory directly in terms of observations. Hence, it avoids many of the difficulties described in the previous subsection (see, for example,

Flood 1990; Guba 1990b; Harré 1981; Lincoln 1990; Popper 1976; Reason and Rowan 1981b; Rosen 1980; Smith 1990; Stegmüller 1976). The way the constructivist, relativist validation of theory is interpreted in this thesis is as follows.

All theories start as speculations and validation is a two step process: firstly, deciding whether the speculation is internally coherent, and secondly assessing whether it is sufficiently well supported by external considerations. Validating the initial speculation has three aspects to it:

- **Internal consistency** – Is the description of the speculation true to the speculation itself and does it coherently describe what is speculated?
- **Accuracy** – Does the speculation fit the data it was derived from?
- **Bounds** – Does the speculation define what is included in it and what is not?

At this point the speculation exists as a semantic construct that fits a set of data and has defined boundaries. The difference between the speculation and a valid theory is in terms of public confidence and its usability. To illustrate this difference, consider the speculation that the moon is the head of a man made of green cheese. The speculation meets the above criteria: the description accurately describes the speculation, it fits a set of data and its scope is well defined. As a theory, however, it is contradicted by other data, moon rock samples, for example, and, more importantly, it does not fit with a variety of other theories in which society has more confidence. In addition, its utility is low because it does not provide a useful model of the situation for those who might use such a model, such as astronomers and space scientists.

The validation of a speculation as a respectable theory depends on:

- Coherence with other data
- Coherence with existing theory
- Elegance and simplicity
- Relevance to users
- Utility

Data Coherence – The ‘green cheese’ speculation is validated by the data on which it is based, seeing the moon through the naked eye, but it does not fit a wider range of data, for example, the appearance and texture of actual moon rock.

Coherence with other Theory – The ‘green cheese’ speculation does not comport well with other theories about astronomical bodies in which there is a considerable amount of confidence: theories about gravity and planetary motion imply the moon has a density different from cheese.

Elegance and Simplicity – Theories represent phenomena in different ways and some theories have an elegance and simplicity which makes them preferable. If it is speculated that the moon is made of green cheese then its incorrect density must be compensated for somehow in theories of planetary motion. Other theories about the constituency of the moon lead to less complex outcomes and hence are more preferable.

Relevance – Theories must be relevant to those working with the circumstances that the theories model. For those sailors using the moon for navigation, it matters little what the moon is made of. It is more relevant to know its position and that its behaviour is predictable. The speculation that the moon is made of green cheese is not relevant in theoretical terms in navigation.

Utility – Usefulness is what lies behind relevance in terms of the relative validity of a theory. The speculation that the moon is made of green cheese must also be useful to be a valid theory. It is not obvious how such a theory would be practically or theoretically useful except in imaginative storytelling or analysing the structure and dynamic of theory. This need for utility in theory is also found in the preference of sea navigators for earth-centred theories as a basis for navigation tables, regardless of the actualities of the earth rotating about the sun.

To recap, engineering design theory is validated by scrutinising the way it describes the activities of designing and how well it fits with information and theory from a range of sources both in and outside the field of engineering design research. That is, engineering design theories must be coherent with well justified theories from other disciplines as well as immediate

subjective and objective experience and data. If there exist contradictions between an engineering design theory and other sources of knowledge then the validity of the engineering design theory must be doubted. This dependence on external knowledge for validity is reflexive, however, because other knowledge and theory may also depend on engineering design theory and may also be refuted by it.

3.3.6 Summary

In this research it is assumed that theories have the following characteristics,

- Theories provide a common basis for discourse about a situation.
- Theories are abstract mental constructs which model particular aspects of existence.
- Theories are abstract structures whose elements and relationships are discrete concepts or theories themselves.
- Theories are used to predict the future before it is actualised, and can be applied to quantitative and qualitative situations.
- All theories and the concepts which they encompass depend upon assumptions and human values.
- Theories are based on knowledge which is both quantitative and qualitative.
- Theories are metaphors which are based on available knowledge and are culturally and historically placed.
- The value of a theory and its associated concepts lies in modelling a situation from a particular point of view as well as in the theory's accuracy. For example, the biochemical description of a flower and the theoretical model of its energy exchanges are different, and which one is used depends upon which is more pertinent rather than which is more accurate.
- Theories condense and coalesce knowledge: they are reductionist because they give conceptual and semantic privilege to those aspects of a situation which are considered more important or relevant (Coyne 1991; Coyne and Newton 1992; Stegmüller 1976). In

this, the privilege given to particular human values and assumptions play an *a priori* role.

- Making theory depends primarily on intuition and synthesis: analysis has a secondary role.

Validating theory depends upon:

- The internal consistency and coherency of the initial speculation
- Coherence with other data
- Coherence with existing theory
- Elegance and simplicity
- Relevance to users
- Utility

3.4 Meta-theoretical analyses

3.4.1 Introduction

So far in this chapter, the theoretical perspective and framework used in this thesis have been chosen and the way that theory is viewed has been defined. What remains is to develop the side of this theoretical framework that enables its use in addressing the research questions, and to discuss the limitations of the combination of research perspectives and assumptions used here. This section describes a way of deconstructing engineering design theories and concepts into interrelated theoretical elements. The difference between this deconstruction and those described earlier in the chapter is that the focus is on making sense of the existing theories, concepts and terminology of engineering design research rather than the theoretical positions or frameworks within which research is undertaken. That is, the focus is on clarifying theory rather than determining the choice of theoretical framework and the outlook on theoretical issues. Before an appropriate meta-theoretical research method can be developed, the detail of the terminological and conceptual problems of engineering design research are reviewed to provide a background context to that development.

3.4.2 Reviewing the detail of terminological and conceptual problems in engineering design research

The lack of terminological and conceptual precision creates semantic difficulties for critically analysing the concepts and theories of engineering design research. In some cases, researchers have defined a concept to have a particular meaning and then used it later in the same text with a different meaning. In other cases, researchers have confused metaphoric meaning and literal meaning. In still other cases, the same word has been used to denote different concepts, processes or activities. These problems are compounded by confusion in the literature about the theoretical relationships between different aspects of even the most basic concepts and theories because the same words and similar concepts are used in theoretically different circumstances. Examples 1, 2 and 3 below illustrate common problems of lack of terminology, confusion and conflation of concepts, and under-definition due to combining ill-defined terms and phrases.

Example 1: Lack of terminology

The term *synthesis* is one of the basic terms of the literature of engineering design research and is used to mean 'the creation of something new'. Its dictionary definition is 'the assembling of separate or subordinate parts into a new form' (*Webster Comprehensive Dictionary* 1986). Much of what is often called synthesis in engineering design research is not, however, of this form of 'building with conceptual bricks'. For example, designing that makes small parametric changes that result in trading different functional gains and losses. There does not appear to be any suitable word in English to describe this qualitative aspect of creativity, and hence the term synthesis has been used by engineering design researchers for both purposes. This presents two problems: firstly, the lack of terminology encourages all creativity to be seen as mechanistic and deterministic assembly of discrete elements; and secondly, for that literature which includes alternative creative processes, the correct meaning of synthesis has to be inferred from its context.

Example 2: Confusion and conflation of the concept of 'design thought'.

The concept of a 'design thought' is one of the most fundamental concepts of engineering design research. At first glance, the term 'design thought' appears to have a singular

meaning as the 'thought content about a design cognised by a designer in some generic manner'. There are several subtle variations on this meaning, however, that are superficially similar but are epistemologically different, and which lead arguments containing the term 'design thought' in radically different directions. Some examples are:

- The content of a 'design thought' may be a clear, final formulation ready to be drawn or otherwise communicated.
- A 'design thought' may be essentially a partial cognitive construction, with the final formulation of the 'design' occurring outside the mind because the visualisation processes of the mind can address only a very restricted number of factors.
- A 'design thought' may be the processing which prefigures the raising of a complete or partial conceptualisation of a design solution, seen photograph-like in the mind, rather than by some other means of cognitively internalised representation

The above meanings are not a complete set of possibilities, but show that the variations in meaning of a phrase such as 'design thinking is a cognitive process' is inadequately specific for precise analysis or comparative critique.

Example 3: Combining ill-defined terms and phrases.

The following sentence, is typical of the literature of engineering design theory.

The design of the shaft depended on the decision-making processes used by the designer.

Like 'design thought', at first glance, it appears singular in meaning, yet the critical perspective leads to questions that expose its lack of definition:

- Does 'the design of the shaft' mean the *activity of designing* the shaft?
- Does it refer to an *engineering drawing* of the shaft (or some other symbolic communication)?
- Does it refer to an *actual* shaft?

- Does 'decision-making processes' refer to *decisions based on basic models* of shaft behaviour for example, models of force, stress or dynamics?
- Does it mean that the design is *defined by the results of higher order methods* which use the output of, for example stress behaviour, to optimise the shaft geometry?
- Is it referring to the designer's *internal cognitive decision-making processes*?
- Does 'decision-making processes' mean a *process based on the wider internal perspective (or world view) of the designer* which includes personal habits, values, beliefs about the world, the effects of the designer's environment, or other internal influences?

The above list of questions is illustrative only, and does not point to all possible meanings of the phrases 'design of the shaft' and 'decision-making processes'. The combination of potential meanings of the two phrases gives a large number of meanings for the initial sentence. This results in any discussion using that sentence being poorly defined because of the many meanings that can be attributed to it. When the context is loosely defined in a similar manner, there is little that can form a basis for drawing out the exact meanings from the text.

This semantic under-determination of the terms, concepts and theories in engineering design research brings confusion into any discussion about designing. It limits the analysis of individual research, and restricts the application of the results of particular projects elsewhere in the field. These problems of semantic multiplicity and flexibility lead back to problems at epistemological and ontological levels of theorisation. The confusion is caused by a lack of clarity about relationships between terminology and concepts and the relationships between concepts themselves. To identify these relationships and make them coherent it is necessary to be able to identify, separate and make public the different nuances of meaning and concept by some method that focuses on the classification of the theories, concepts and terms of engineering design research as related theoretical elements. That is, it is necessary to take a

meta-theoretical stance and to develop a theoretical structure within which different concepts and theories can be placed.

3.4.3 Meta-theoretical analysis

From a constructivist perspective, all terminology, concepts and theories are human cognitive constructs. They are *abstractions* in the sense that particular aspects of reality are abstracted and symbolically represented in the realm of theory. These theoretical abstractions include human assumptions and human values where these are conceptualised and brought into the public realm in some manner. In terms of Popper's (1976) three worlds model, abstractions, terminology, concepts and theories are all 'World 3' theoretical entities.

The academic world is divided in its interest in abstractions, although using and structuring abstractions is fundamental to most disciplines and goes back at least to the earliest Greek philosophers (Ong 1982; Reason and Rowan 1981a). This difference of interest is echoed by Snow's (1964) description of academia as two cultures of Arts and the Natural Sciences. The difference of interest in abstractions between the two cultures is reflected in the amount of attention paid by each to issues of ontology and epistemology in research. Subjects whose theoretical foundations are not amenable to Cartesian validation have had to look closely at the principles underlying the development and justification of concepts and theories, and this is especially true of the recently developed research methodologies in Anthropology, Ethnography, Education and Sociology such as the Grounded Theory of Glaser and Strauss (1973), and the Action Science of Agyris (1980) (Berger 1980; Guba 1990; Illich 1978; Mohr 1988; Shipman 1983). In contrast, ontological and epistemological exploration in research and theory-making is rare in disciplines that remain attached to positivism and scientism (Giddens, 1987; Guba, 1990a).

In disciplines where researchers have paid attention to ontological and epistemological matters, the focus has mainly been on the implications of ontology and epistemology for research methodology rather than other aspects of research and theorisation (Guba, 1990a; Reich 1994). An alternative to this purely methodological focus is the meta-theoretical perspective where concepts and theory are regarded as theoretical abstractions and structures (see, for example,

Rosen 1980; Stegmuller 1976; and Popper 1976). This meta-theoretical perspective is more appropriate for improving the consistency and coherence of theory and theory-making than focusing only on research methodology because it addresses the theoretical problems directly rather than through methodologies or 'paradigms'. A meta-theoretical approach to analysing theory and concepts assumes that they fit into an hierarchical structure because theories and concepts exist as descriptions of relationships between other theoretical elements. This hierarchical structure does not presume that the theories of engineering design can be developed into a logically related super-theory in the manner of, for example, geometry. The hierarchical theoretical structure that is conceived of here is similar to that of the social sciences where theories at the large, small and middle scales do not necessarily follow logically from each other, and where the most that can be said is that theories at different levels relate to and depend on other theories, concepts and assumptions at other levels (Giddens 1987). That is, the theories and concepts of engineering design form a theoretical chain which is at one end grounded in the concreteness of reality and at the other end bounded by the assumptions and beliefs that humans make about existence and reality. At the lowest level of abstraction is the initial conversion of our sensual perception of reality into concepts by naming phenomena: the first level of abstract cerebral processing. The highest meta-level of abstraction relates to human ontological or religious beliefs about existence. Between these two bounds – the conceptualisation of direct perceptions of 'reality' and beliefs about 'what is fundamental about existence' – are the layers of theoretical and everyday abstractions which are the stock in trade of communication and reflection in such diverse occupations as journalism, art, science, technology and academe. Thus, theories and concepts lie at different levels in a meta-theoretical hierarchy.

Theories relate to other theoretical elements both in an hierarchical sequence of abstraction and also in parallel at similar levels of abstraction. It is the hierarchical relationships that provide a direct means of testing the validity and correctness of theoretical development. The sideways relationships offer a means of validating theory in terms of existing theory about similar issues. This combined hierarchical and lateral approach to the validation of theory comports well with the weight of academic opinion that all theory is unprovable in isolation but depends for its

validity upon a wider theoretical structure or theoretical ecology where each theory or concept fits within a web of theoretical elements which it both supports and is supported by (see, for example, Guba 1990b; Murray 1986; Phillips 1987; Popper 1976; Rosen 1980; Smith 1990; Reason and Rowan 1981b; Stegmüller 1976). For mathematically expressed theories, the resolution of the elements of equations into hierarchical theoretical structures is a trivial problem. For theories that are not of that form, however, the classification of theoretical elements into the appropriate levels of abstraction is not necessarily self evident and some form of meta-theoretical abstraction taxonomy is needed to decompose design theories and concepts into their relevant contributions at different levels of abstraction.

The use of a meta-theoretical hierarchical taxonomy for analysing theoretical relationships is demonstrated here by its application to a meta-theoretical analysis of the engineering concepts of *stress*, *force* and *area*. These are human constructed theoretical concepts that do not exist themselves as physical phenomena: that is, they are terms that represent phenomena abstracted and reduced in a particular manner. In the terms of Newtonian engineering, *stress* is defined as the *force* transmitted per unit *area*. That is, *stress* is at a higher meta-theoretical level than *force* and *area* because it builds on them and describes a more abstract relationship. The lower level abstractions *force* and *area*, in their turn, however, depend for their meanings on conceptualisation of observations of the *movement* of physical objects: force is perceived by its effect on shape and position, and *area* is related to perception of *distance* (Hogben 1951). As Newton and Euclid have observed in their own ways, *stress* is meta-theoretical to *force* and *area* which in their turn are meta-theoretical to *movement*.

Higher level abstractions also play their part in the definition of *stress* in the way that they bound the possibilities for how *stress*, *force* and *area* are conceived and their relationships validated. These higher level abstractions include:

- The assumption that the world can be mathematically modelled.
- Beliefs about the constancy of the world and our perceptions of it (Levin 1993)
- A belief system which allows us to make such theoretical models without fear of divine retribution.

Thus, the validity and justification of every theory or concept in engineering design research is dependent upon its meta-theoretical coherence with theories and concepts at higher and lower levels of abstraction.

To recap: theories and concepts describe the relationships between other theories and concepts, and simultaneously depend on other, more abstract theoretical constructions for their validity and coherence. Consequently all theories and concepts are abstractions that exist in a meta-theoretical hierarchy of theories and concepts all of which exist in Popper's World 3. At one end of this hierarchy is the symbolic representation of the 'concrete' world as experienced through our senses. At the other end of the hierarchy, the most abstract level, is the ontological world of assumptions about reality, personal values and value systems. Between them lies the theoretical structure which gives conceptual and semantic coherence and validation to human theorising. The critical perspective of this research requires a greater amount of semantic and conceptual definition than that typical of the literature of engineering design research, particularly with respect to ontological and epistemological issues, and this necessitates some practical means of meta-theoretically classifying the hierarchical relationships between different engineering design theories and concepts.

3.4.4 Meta-theoretical hierarchy as a research method for separating elements of engineering design theory, concepts and terminology to avoid semantic and conceptual confusion

The meta-theoretical viewpoint offers a methodological perspective on the relationships between theories and concepts and their validation, but it is not, however, a methodology or method in itself. What is needed in this research is a method that provides the means of meta-theoretical analysis that aids with resolving the semantic and conceptual problems of engineering design research.

Some of these problems can be eliminated prior to the development of a meta-theoretical method by defining them as problems of engineering research rather than problems of engineering design research. This is because the term 'engineering design theory' has been widely used in the literature to denote all and any theoretical proposals in the field of engineering design. Using the terminology of Chapter 1, these 'engineering design theories and

concepts' separate into 'engineering design theories and concepts' and 'engineering theories and concepts', in the manner suggested by Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian (1992). Hence, many of the semantic and conceptual difficulties of the literature are excluded from this research.

This initial separation is helpful but it is insufficient and further classification is necessary to separate, for example, the particular aspects of a theory or concept that relate to cognition from, say, those aspects relating to object behaviour or design. In this classification, Reich's (1994a) layered model of methodology provides a potential structure for classifying different theories, concepts and terminology and their relationships on epistemological lines (see Table 15).

Layers of research methodology
World views
Research heuristics
Specific issues

Table 15: Reich's (1994a) layers of research methodology

Reich's layered model is aimed at defining research methodology, however, rather than resolving semantic and conceptual problems, and, although providing a template for developing a hierarchical taxonomy of theory, it is not sufficient for the purposes of this research as it stands. To clarify the situation further it is also necessary to separate the theories, concepts and terms of engineering design research into the different *aspects of the theoretical* that are defined by Popper's (1976) three worlds (see Table 16).

Aspects of the Theoretical
Theory as individual cognition (subjective world)
Theory written down (objective world)
Theory as theory (theoretical world)

Table 16: Aspects of the theoretical according to Popper's three worlds model.

In addition, it is also necessary to include in the meta-theoretical hierarchy the different *types* of engineering design theory, some of which are illustrated in Table 17 below.

Types of theory
Scientific

Psychological
Social
Mathematical
Information processing

Table 17: Types of engineering design theories

The above considerations are brought together in the following initial development of Reich’s (1994a) epistemologically layered model (see Table 18).

Layers of engineering design theory
Philosophical issues
General theories of design
Theories about design cognition
Theories about object behaviour

Table 18: Initial layered taxonomy of engineering design theory

Before developing Reich’s layered model further, it is appropriate to establish the meta-theoretical relationship between different aspects of engineering design research. In engineering design research, the meta-theoretical hierarchy ranges across the theoretical considerations of engineering design epistemologists, engineering design researchers and engineering designers, and can be represented in an abstraction hierarchy as shown in Table 19.

The meta-theoretical relationships between different aspects of research into engineering design
Theories and concepts of this research
Theories and concepts of engineering design research
Theories and concepts of engineering design

Table 19: Meta-theoretical hierarchy of engineering design research

The rows in the above table also can have meta-theoretical hierarchies that nestle like Chinese boxes in a similar manner to the ‘holonic’ view of theoretical relationships found in systems research (Hollick 1998; Hutchinson 1997). Each level contains the theories and concepts of all levels below it, and the higher order abstractions provide the theoretical foundations for lower levels.

Combining Table 18 and Table 19 leads to the more comprehensive hierarchy of Table 20.

Meta-theoretical hierarchical levels	Purpose
Ontological assumptions	Provide a basis for epistemologies

Research epistemologies	Provide a basis for research
Engineering design research	Provides a basis for theory
Engineering design theories	Guide designing
Engineering design domains	Create artefact definitions

Table 20: Intermediate development of a meta-theoretical hierarchy of engineering design theory.

There are two main problems with Table 20 due to the categories being too coarse for detailed critical analysis of engineering design theory. Firstly, the level labelled 'design research' is better allocated to the overarching general theories of design that guide particular theories. The relevant issues of engineering design research relate to ontology and epistemology and are effectively included in the previous two levels. Methodological matters relate to the gathering of information and as such are exempted from the hierarchy. Secondly, more detailed categorisation is needed in the lower levels because the majority of the literature lies in the bottom two categories.

Popper's (1976) model of different aspects of theory shown earlier in Table 16 points to the need to include an additional lower level in order that the human ability to objectivise internal subjective realities is included. This level is crucially important for two reasons. Firstly, it enables the inclusion of those theoretically primitive aspects of human action relating to identifying objects and circumstances and creating initial concepts. Secondly, it enables this research, and the meta-theoretical hierarchy, to include those aspects of theory-making and research that relate to the development of new theory. This is because anything that has been given a name or conceived as an entity – regardless of whether it is achieved in the subjective or objective worlds – can be theorised about.

The application of Popper's three worlds model in this manner points to a clarification of the relationship between his three worlds. Popper's 'subjective' and 'external' worlds are bridged via the 'theoretical' world through language addressed internally because it is irrelevant in theoretical terms whether the individual concerned writes theory in the external world, vocalises it silently to themselves or conceptualises it in their 'minds eye' (Ferguson, 1992b; Hamlyn, 1990; Rosen, 1990). Additionally, theoretical labelling, and hence theorisation, extends over all of Popper's worlds because theoretical abstractions can be theorised about by giving

them meta-labels. For example, different logic chip architectures are given names and dealt with as abstractions in a similar manner to physical and subjective phenomena. This implies that, in terms of research, all aspects of Popper's three worlds become World 3 theoretical entities. This is as it should be if meta-theoretical analysis is to be applicable to any concept or theory, and particularly where the focus is on theory-making qua theory-making rather than on the entity being theorised about.

All of these considerations are accommodated in the final version of the meta-theoretical hierarchy shown in Table 21 below.

Level	Classification	Description
1	Ontology of design	The ontological basis for design theory and the activity of designing. It is at this level that the human values and fundamental assumptions of researchers, designers and others implicated in designing are included in critiques of theory.
2	Epistemology of design theory	The critical study of the nature, grounds, limits and criteria for validity of design knowledge.
3	General design theories	Theories which seek to describe the whole activity of designing and its relationship to both the designed objects and the environment.
4	Theories about the internal processes of designers and collaboration	Theories about the reasoning and cognising of individual designers, of negotiated design in collaborative design teams, and of socio-cultural effects on designers' output.
5	Theories about the structure of design process	Theories about the underlying structure of design process based on domain, culture, artefact type and other similar attributes and circumstances.
6	Design methods	Theories about and proposals for design methods and techniques.
7	Theories about mechanisms of choice	Theories about the ways that choices are made between different elements, designed objects, processes, systems or other types of possibility.
8	Theories about the behaviour of elements	Theories about the behaviour of elements which may be incorporated into designed objects, processes and systems, e.g. 'the camshaft rotates at 600 rads/sec'.
9	Initial conception and labeling of reality	This is the level at which humans descriptions of objects, processes and systems are coined, e.g. 'a vacuum cleaner', 'a car body', 'a groyne', 'a database', 'sitting' at a 'desk', 'hearing' 'noise', 'smelling' 'fumes' from an 'exhaust' and 'watching' 'sunsets'.

Table 21: Meta-theoretical hierarchy of concepts and theories in engineering design research

The above meta-theoretical hierarchy provides:

- A taxonomy for classifying theoretical aspects of this research and engineering design research in general.
- A hierarchy for clarifying the meta-theoretical relationships between theories and concepts found in the literature of engineering design research.

It is emphasised that although this taxonomy was developed as a basis for categorising different theoretical abstractions about designing, the focus is not on the *content* of the abstractions or theories. This is an hierarchical taxonomy of theories and concepts as *abstract theoretical elements* whose important relationships are those of theoretical and conceptual definition and necessary assumption. For example, the theories and concepts of level 5 presume particular metaphors

and theories of level 4. The theories of level 4, however, do not depend upon the theories and concepts of level 5. The contents of the theories and metaphors are not relevant to the structural relationship between the levels.

The expanded hierarchy makes it possible to distinguish different aspects of engineering design theory so, for example, theories relating to mechanisms of choice in level 7 are concerned with the selection of particular design elements whose behaviours are described in the theories and concepts of level 8 and which are based on empirical experience raised as concepts in level 9. Theories about mechanisms of choice also depend, consciously or unconsciously, on various privileged assumptions at higher orders of abstraction contained in levels 1 to 6. For example, assumptions, or presumptions, about design method and process, or even more abstractly, about what designing is, or more abstractly still about what the world is.

Research and theory generation at each meta-theoretical level is highly interdependent with that done at other levels although different disciplines or fields of engineering design have a different balance of activity at each level. For example, theories proposed in the fields of engineering design research relating to Mechanical Engineering and Artificial Intelligence occupy predominantly different niches and have a different distribution in the above hierarchy. In each field, however, all of the meta-theoretical levels exist and hierarchical relationships exist between theories and concepts at those levels, whether or not they are recognised.

The advantages of using the meta-theoretical hierarchy of Table 21 as the basis of critical analysis of engineering design theories and concepts are:

- Each theoretical element – as an abstraction – can be evaluated in terms of its connection to well-justified abstractions at other levels.
- Where a new concept is proposed at any level, the need for appropriate terminology can be identified to distinguish the new concept from similar concepts at the same or different levels of abstraction.
- Where new theories and concepts are proposed at any level, the necessary associated abstractions should be able to be identified for all other levels.

- The meta-theoretical hierarchy provides a means of testing whether general theories of design are complete and contain a coherent set of well justified abstractions at all levels.

The dominant theoretical cultures of engineering design research potentially give rise to a misunderstanding of what is argued here because of their emphasis on physical objects and phenomena. If the level headings of Table 21 are viewed from an engineering perspective:

- Levels 1–3 relate to philosophical matters
- Levels 3–6 relate to design process
- Levels 8 and 9 relate to objects

On this basis, the theory categories relating to design process (levels 3 to 6) and the theory categories relating to objects (levels 8 and 9) appear to form two parallel but co-ordinated streams, apparently dissolving the meta-theoretical hierarchy. This alternative application of the meta-theoretical headings may be of some use in the identification of the foci of research effort about engineering design, but is incorrect in terms of analysing the meta-theoretical relationships between different theories and concepts – the theoretical perspective used here. Using a critical meta-theoretical viewpoint, the theories relating to design process apply to other less abstract elements or entities and their behaviour (levels 8 and 9) and therefore, in terms of abstraction, there is an hierarchy not two parallel streams. It is irrelevant that some of these level 8 and 9 entities or elements, particularly non-physical ones, may be difficult to conceive and theorise about, and in engineering terms, are ‘very abstract’. It is matters of theory structure and dynamic which are being addressed here rather than cognitive difficulty or technical relevance.

3.4.5 Examples of critical analysis using the meta-theoretical hierarchy

The following two examples illustrate how the meta-theoretical hierarchy can be used to compare, critically analyse, and draw out the assumptions and theoretical relationships of two metaphors of design; ‘design as information processing’ and ‘design as a creative process’.

This perspective on engineering design is the dominant paradigm of engineering design research and is represented by the work of Suh (1989), Tomiyama (1994), Tomiyama and Yoshikawa (1985) and Yoshikawa (1981). The information-processing metaphor of engineering design is based on positivism and science, and in this metaphor phenomena are described as information in ways that are amenable to manipulation by computer. Some of the main theoretical characteristics of the 'design as information processing' metaphor of design are laid out in Table 22.

Level	Classification	Theoretical characteristics
1	Ontology of Design	The universe is presumed to be consistent. 'Design as information processing' assumes that information is 'value neutral' and that it is possible to codify reality in information in such a way that reality has the same meaning for any person using that information. Cultural factors and human values related to designing are quantified.
2	Epistemology of Design Theory	Design information, methods and theories are satisfactory if they transform and transfer information in the manner intended.
3	General Design Theories	Using an atomistic and deterministic framework it is assumed that design can be automated, and that the human designer is only necessary to oversee that process.
4	Theories about the Internal Processes of Designers and Collaboration	It is assumed that human expertise can be mathematically modelled. The designer is assumed to rationally select and bring together particular information to produce a satisfactory design solution by satisfying a set of constraints. Interaction between design team members is seen only in terms of the communication of information.
5	Theories about the Structure of Design Process	The design of an artefact is seen as an information selection and management process in which, The world can be codified in a form suitable for information processing. The correct information can be supplied to the designer. The designer uses an information-processing algorithm to 'design'. A description of the designed artefact can be provided for manufacture. The manufacture of the artefact can be achieved from the supplied information without ad-hoc interpretation.
6	Design Methods	Designing is the codification, selection and management of information. The characteristic design method is the use of information-selecting algorithms.
7	Theories about Mechanisms of Choice	The choice of decision-making methods and evaluatory techniques is dependent upon their communication, efficiency, data integrity and data validation. The relevant fields of study which relate to the reasoning behind design choice include: communication theory, artificial intelligence, cognitive psychology of decision-making, systems analysis and information processing.
8	Theories about the Behaviour of Elements	The behaviour of elements of the designed artefacts are described in terms which allow for convenient information processing. For example, the use of mathematically based models rather than physical scale models.
9	Initial Conception and Labelling of Reality	Descriptions of information sources such as books, computer files, expert knowledge. Descriptions of information types such as 'fluid viscosities', 'Pantone codes', 'customer needs' and 'product specifications'. Descriptions of information flow processes such as 'telephoning', 'DFX file transfer', 'interaction with stakeholders', 'human-machine interactions', 'design team collaboration'. Conceptualised feelings of 'being overwhelmed by too much information' or 'wondering where to find appropriate information'.

Table 22: Meta-theoretical hierarchy of information-processing metaphor of engineering design

Example 5: Design as a creative process

Human creativity is a metaphor of design that emphasises the role of the internal intuitive creative processes of the human designer. It was the prevalent model of technical design for many years but recently has become unfashionable (Coyne and Snodgrass, 1992a, 1991; Gault 1997; Glegg 1971). At root, it relies on psychological and philosophical theories of creativity and intuition, although research in these areas is not extensive (Amabile 1983). Some of the main theoretical characteristics of the creative metaphor of engineering design are listed below in Table 23.

Level	Classification	Theoretical characteristics
1	Ontology of Design	The creative metaphor of engineering design defines creativity as an activity that cannot be reduced to a set of algorithmic steps and, hence, from this perspective engineering design cannot be automated. The creative metaphor includes the qualitative aspects of human values, attitudes and assumptions.
2	Epistemology of Design Theory	The validity or coherence of design methods and theories depends on the intrinsic creative ability and judgement of the designer or design theorist. Domain-based human critics provide external post-facto comment on the works of designers.
3	General Design Theories	Design is seen as a creative activity and other aspects of design process are subordinate to this.
4	Theories about the Internal Processes of Designers and Collaboration	There are three theoretical outlooks relating to internal creative processes of designers and collaboration between designers: each assumes that human creativity is a mysterious process. Designing is a product of human genius and that is as much as can be said. It is possible to research creativity via some means of phenomenological analysis. Creativity can be explained in terms of biological and psychological processes. Descriptions of individual designers' creative processes refer to intuition, experience, feelings and style and domain traditions. Collaboration between designers is seen as a process of trying to communicate nuances of feeling.
5	Theories about the Structure of Design Process	Creativity based models of design process are similar to technically-based design models, for example, the systems based analysis-synthesis-evaluation model, with evaluation feeding information back into the other elements. Some Romantic models of designing omit the evaluation feedback loop on the basis that the individual genius of the designer is the measure of the quality of the design. The human 'creative' aspect of the design process is 'intuitive' and mysterious, and the most dominant aspect of the design process and all other process elements have a supporting role to creativity.
6	Design Methods	A range of methods has been developed to facilitate the designer's use of the right hemisphere of the brain and temporarily discourage analytical thinking and use of the left hemisphere of the brain, for example, the associative and analogical techniques of Synectics, Mind Maps and Brainstorming (see, for

		example, Buzan 1989; Gordon 1961; Hampden-Turner 1981; Lumsdaine and Lumsdaine 1995; Springer and Deutsch 1993). Some methods provide guidance in specific domains for visual creativity and manipulation of concepts, and include concepts of visual balance, the flow of form, repetitive elements and geometrical transformations. All creative design methods assume a sufficient base of experience residing within the designer(s).
7	Theories about Mechanisms of Choice	The dominant mechanism of decision-making and evaluation is the use of 'feelings'. The evaluation and validation of matters of choice are justified by casuistic means and because they depend upon human values, they too lie in the domain of 'feelings'.
8	Theories about the Behaviour of Elements	The main focus is on the interrelationships between elements and the properties of elements are commonly defined in terms of other elements or external influences. For example, 'the gearbox is well matched to the engine'. 'the brackets are stiff enough for the locking mechanism'.
9	Initial Conception and Labelling of Reality	Objects are described adjectivally rather than by using simple noun descriptions, for example, an 'elegant' solution, a 'strong' red, a 'pretentious' vestibule, a 'convoluted' melody. The activity of designing is conceived in terms relating to observations through the senses—mainly sight—together with internal body sensations and kinæsthetics, all conceptualised as 'feelings'.

Table 23: Meta-theoretical hierarchy of the creative metaphor of engineering design

The above deconstructions are not complete, and are intended only to illustrate the use of the meta-theoretical hierarchy. Although the deconstructions are incomplete and sketchy, critical analysis of the theoretical characteristics of the two metaphors shows substantial theoretical differences between them throughout the hierarchy and defines the levels of abstraction at which particular differences occur. The meta-theoretical hierarchy shows the theoretical or conceptual range of each metaphor and publicly lays bare the underlying facets of any general theory of engineering design based on that metaphor. The meta-theoretical hierarchy provides the means to ask not only 'What is meant by this concept?', but also to ask; 'What other abstractions is it related to and how?', 'How coherent is it with other concepts and abstractions?', 'What implications has it for other abstractions at lower levels?' and 'What assumptions does it depend on?'. Thus, when a new metaphor, theory, concept or other abstraction is proposed, it can be analysed not only in terms of its own content but also in terms of its conceptual placement and relationships.

The usefulness of this aspect of the meta-theoretical hierarchy is shown in the way that meta-theoretical analysis can address issues of metaphoric redefinition where proponents of theories or metaphors of engineering design attempt to extend the scope of a metaphor or theory by

broadening the meaning of its title. For example, the scope of the metaphor of ‘information processing’ might be uncritically extended by emphasising that everything can be expressed as information, and, similarly, the metaphor of ‘creativity’ might be extended by the claim that *every* perception, action or thought is new and hence created. Extending the meaning ascribed to the title of the metaphor without publicly changing the content of the meta-theoretical structure is theoretical double-speak and leads to confusion both in conceptualisation and the validation of concepts and conceptual structure. The above method of critical analysis of engineering design theory using the meta-theoretical hierarchy shows the actual theoretical structure being ascribed to a metaphor regardless of changes of title and consequently provides a more secure basis for analysis, comparison or critique.

3.4.6 Role of meta-level theoretical analysis in this research

Earlier in this chapter, the concept of a theoretical framework for research was described in terms of the structure of Table 24.

Theoretical Structure
Ontological Perspective
Epistemological Perspective
Methodological Perspective
Methodology
Method
Research Technique

Table 24: Theoretical framework of research

The use of the meta-theoretical hierarchy in this research aligns with the lower three levels of the Table 24 because it is a research technique and method as illustrated in the previous sections and, additionally, it is a methodology because it offers a structure that can be used as the basis for a variety of research methods. The higher three levels of Table 24 also describe aspects of the role of the meta-theoretical hierarchy in this research because of the similarity between designing and research (see, for example, Argyris 1980; Bucciarelli 1984; Cross 1993; Colajinni, Grassi, Manzo and Naticchia 1991; Guba 1990b; Newbury 1996; Popper 1976; Robinson 1986; Roozenburg 1992; Rosen 1980; Schon 1984; Smith 1990; Stegmuller 1976). Arguments for this similarity include:

- Designing is a research process and therefore it shares the same ontological, epistemological and methodological basis as research.
- Research and theory are designed and this implies that they are underpinned by the ontological, epistemological and methodological basis of designing.
- Designing is similar to scientific research. This is implied by those who aim to develop a design science or science of design.

This suggests that the above meta-level theoretical hierarchy which was developed for the critical analysis of the theory that is the *product* of engineering design research also applies to engineering design research itself. This is further supported, from an empirical perspective, by the fact that the conceptualisation of phenomena classified in level 9 in the meta-theoretical hierarchy is one of the most fundamental human research techniques. Hence, in this thesis, the role of meta-theoretical analysis goes beyond methodology, method and technique. It is a fundamental part of the theoretical perspective that is used in this thesis because it is the model that underpins how relationships between theories and theoretical elements are conceived and analysed.

3.5 Limitations of the theoretical position underpinning this research

The theoretical position of this research consists of the theoretical perspectives, theoretical framework, assumptions about theory, and means of meta-theoretical critical analysis of theory, concepts and terminology. This theoretical position is suited to analysing a wider range of problems of engineering design research than it is used for here, but it has limitations because it is not intended to provide all the necessary means to fill out particular details of new engineering design theory.

Firstly, some researchers have argued that design is a social or psychological phenomenon and that it is the research paradigms of these disciplines that should be used for analysing and developing engineering design theory (see, for example, Cross and Cross 1995; Dilnot 1982; Heath 1993; Takala 1993; Thomas and Carroll 1979; Visser 1991, 1996). The theoretical position

used here is limited to providing support for clarifying the ontological, epistemological and methodological aspects of such social or psychological analyses.

Secondly, the constructivist perspective used in this research limits the privilege given to objective data because it emphasises that knowledge, objective or otherwise, is relativistically modified in the interpreted construction of human realities. This means that there is an asymmetric relationship between the products of this research and mainstream positivist engineering design research. The products of positivist engineering design research can be validly interpreted via the perspective used here but not vice versa.

Finally, the theoretical position of this thesis is of limited utility in the undertaking of engineering design research from hermeneutic, phenomenological or post-rationalist perspectives because it is fundamentally grounded in rationalism and empiricism. Coyne and Snodgrass (1992a) argue that this is a problem for all design research that includes subjective considerations because it is the language of objectivism that is used to deconstruct rationalist and objectivist views of reality. This problem is reflected in the way that the meta-theoretical hierarchy developed in this chapter for the analysis of engineering design theory does not include issues of creativity and intuition as a level in the hierarchy. This apparent exclusion is because, according to Rosen's (1982) arguments, both creativity and intuition lie beyond analysis and hence are inappropriate classifications for elements of engineering design theory. Instead, theories of creativity and intuition are deconstructed into their contributions at the appropriate meta-theoretical levels in terms of their epistemological characteristics.

3.6 Summary of Chapter 3

In this chapter, the theoretical perspective used in this thesis has been developed, and this included the following elements:

1. The development of a theoretical framework that provides a structure for the different epistemological aspects of theoretical perspective and research method.
2. The particular choices of the different aspects of the theoretical framework that are used in this research.

3. The ontological and epistemological assumptions about the characteristics of theory and its validation.
4. The development of a meta-theoretical hierarchy of engineering design theory for classifying different theoretical aspects of the literature of engineering design research.

The individual characteristics of the elements above are summarised below in Tables 25, 26 and 27, and Lists 1 and 2.

Theoretical Framework
Ontological Perspective
Epistemological Perspective
Methodological Perspective
Methodology
Method
Research Technique

Table 25: Theoretical framework that relates different aspects of theoretical perspective and research method.

Theoretical Framework of this Research	
Ontological perspective	Constructivist
Epistemological perspective	Constructivist
Methodological perspective	Critical
Methodology	Critical
Methods	Critical
Techniques	Variants of critical analysis

Table 26: The characteristics of the theoretical framework of this thesis

List 1: Characteristics of theories

In this thesis, theories have the following characteristics

- Theories provide a common basis for discourse about a situation.
- Theories are abstract mental constructs which model particular aspects of existence.
- Theories are abstract structures whose elements and relationships are themselves discrete concepts or theories.
- Theories are used to predict the future before it is actualised and can be applied to quantitative and qualitative situations.

- All theories and the concepts which they encompass depend upon assumptions and human values.
- Theories are based on knowledge which is both quantitative and qualitative.
- Theories are metaphors which are based on available knowledge and are culturally and historically placed.
- The value in a theory and its associated concepts lie in modelling a situation from a particular point of view as well as the theory's accuracy. For example, the biochemical description of a flower and the theoretical model of its energy exchanges are different and which one is used depends upon which is more pertinent rather than which is more accurate.
- Theories condense and coalesce knowledge: they are reductionist because they give conceptual and semantic privilege to those aspects of a situation which are considered more important or relevant (Coyne 1991; Coyne and Newton 1992; Stegmüller 1976). In this the privilege given to particular human values and assumptions play an *a priori* role.
- Making theory depends primarily on intuition and synthesis: analysis has a secondary role.

List 2: Validating theory

In this thesis, the position taken on the validation of theory is that it depends upon,

- The internal consistency and coherency of the initial speculation
- Coherence with other data
- Coherence with existing theory
- Elegance and simplicity
- Relevance to users

- Utility

Level	Classification	Description
1	Ontology of design	The ontological basis for design theory and the activity of designing. It is at this level that the human values and fundamental assumptions of researchers, designers and others implicated in designing are included in critiques of theory.
2	Epistemology of design theory	The critical study of the nature, grounds, limits and criteria for validity of design knowledge.
3	General design theories	Theories which seek to describe the whole activity of designing and its relationship to both the designed objects and the environment.
4	Theories about the internal processes of designers and collaboration	Theories about the reasoning of individual designers, or of negotiated design in collaborative design teams, or of cultural (?) effects on designers output.
5	Theories about the structure of design process	Theories about the underlying structure of design process based on domain, culture, artefact type and other similar attributes and circumstances.
6	Design methods	Theories about and proposals for design methods and techniques.
7	Theories about mechanisms of choice	Theories about the ways that choices are made between different elements, designed objects, processes, systems or other types of possibility.
8	Theories about the behaviour of elements	Theories about the behaviour of elements which may be incorporated into designed objects, processes and systems, e.g. 'the camshaft rotates at 600 rads/sec'.
9	Initial conception and labelling of reality	This is the level at which humans descriptions of objects, processes and systems are coined, e.g. 'a vacuum cleaner', 'a car body', 'a groyne', 'a database', 'siting' at a 'desk', 'hearing' 'noise', 'smelling' 'fumes' from an 'exhaust' and 'watching' 'sunsets'.

Table 27: Meta-theoretical hierarchy of concepts and theories in engineering design research

All of the above developments are used in Chapters 4 and 5 in addressing the research questions and reviewing the implications of those answers for the resolution of the research problem and its context.

4. Research findings

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the theoretical perspective and methodology of Chapter 3 are used to address the research questions that were identified in Chapter 2. The role of this chapter is limited to presenting and discussing the findings and analyses that pertain directly to answering the research questions. The subsequent discussion of the findings with respect to the research problem and the literature of engineering design research is left to Chapter 5. In Chapter 5, the implications of the outcomes of Chapter 4 to the research *problem* and to its parent disciplines are discussed: conclusions are drawn from the individual results of the research and the implications of those conclusions are examined. This separation between the answering of the research questions and the discussion of the wider implications of those answers follows the PhD structure proposed by Perry (1996).

This chapter consists of three sections:

1. Introduction
2. Results of applying the theoretical position of Chapter 3 to the research questions
3. Summary of findings

The second section is divided into subsections that address each of the five research questions raised in Chapter 2:

1. *How can engineering design theories be evaluated and compared?*
2. *What are the implications of including human values in theories of human design cognition?*
3. *What are the implications of using post-positive perspectives for research and theory-building in the area of engineering design cognition?*
4. *What are the theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors?*

5. *How do designers use information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors?.*

Each subsection concludes with a conceptual diagram of the findings of that section. These findings are summarised in the final section of this chapter ready for the analyses and discussions of Chapter 5 where the implications of the findings for the research problem and its wider context in engineering design research are considered.

4.2 Results of the application of the theoretical position of Chapter 3 to the research questions.

In this section, the theoretical position of this research, defined in Chapter 3 and consisting of the theoretical framework, the assumed characteristics of theory, and the meta-theoretical hierarchy are applied to the task of answering each research question in turn.

4.2.1 Research question 1

How can engineering design theories be evaluated and compared?

The theoretical and conceptual confusion that is endemic in engineering design research limits the benefits that can be gained by building on existing theory. Adequate means are needed for comparing the detail of competing theories and concepts and for evaluating and validating new theory. For example, the two competing concepts, of 'design as analysis' and 'design as creation' are paradigmatically different but it may be necessary to choose one or the other for a particular situation. Similarly, a new concept such as 'Total Design' (Pugh 1991) needs an appropriate means of epistemological evaluation because its definition as an activity that encompasses product, process, people and organisation appears to be a conceptual mismatch of the same kind as that described by Langrish (1988) relating to design and technology transfer. What is needed is the theoretical and epistemological detail of each concept so that an informed choice may be made, and this requires a means of deconstructing concepts so that their elements and the relationships between them can be evaluated and validated.

The first research question has four aspects to it (Stegmüller 1976; Walton 1996):

1. Defining the characteristics of theory and concept and the validation of theories and concepts.
2. Establishing some means of deconstructing theories and concepts into meaningful and public categories that clarify issues relating to the structure and dynamics of theories and theory-making.
3. Deciding on a theoretical explanation of the closure of the various processes involved in evaluation and comparison.
4. Definition of the boundaries of engineering design research

The first aspect of the research question has been addressed in Chapter 3 where theory, its characteristics and its validation were discussed in detail. The second aspect of the research question was also addressed in Chapter 3 via meta-theoretical analysis and the method of deconstructing engineering design theory using the meta-theoretical hierarchy.

What remains is to use the theoretical position that was defined in Chapter 3 to address the problem of closure. The theoretical explanation of closure presents difficulties in analysis because it is essentially meta-theoretical and, hence, is explained more in terms of what it is not. This is because 'what closure is not' is what lies under the same theoretical realm as what is being discussed. Rosen (1982) addressed the closure problem indirectly, and in two stages, whilst exploring the boundaries of the analytical realm. Firstly, Rosen argued that intuition has an essential role in theory and theory-making via the cognitive activity involved in analysis and then he pointed towards the role of intuition in clarifying and defining closure:

Analysis is a mode of cognition, and is therefore regulated by the judgement, intuition, or sensibility of the analyst. Knowing how to carry out a sequence of analytic operations is not the same as knowing the appropriate domain of application, nor is it the same as knowing how to start and when to stop the sequence.

From this position, Rosen argued that, in the limit, closure and all that depends upon it in the analytical and theoretical realms cannot be based upon theoretical constructs or analyses, but instead must be based on some transcendental aspect of human functioning such as intuition.

Analysis is the admittedly indispensable road to our destination, but it is no more the destination than it is the intention to begin the voyage. One could perhaps say that the destination is an articulated structure. But we know that we have reached the destination only when we recognise a given articulation as the explanation of that structure. We cannot see that an analysis explains a structure by performing an additional step in the analysis. At some point we must see that we are finished. And to see an analysis is not to analyse. It is rather to see an articulated structure as a unity, whole, or synthesis. Furthermore, to see the unity or wholeness of the structure is not to see it as a sum of parts. We can always add another element to a sum, or another number to a sum of numbers. There has to be some reason for our not adding another number to a given sum, and this reason is our intuition or perception that we now have enough. The judgement that an analytical exercise is appropriate is not the same as the arithmetical or quasi-arithmetical measuring of the steps in that exercise.

Although in his writing Rosen is mainly referring to the validation of philosophical theory about analysis, his arguments extend, as he clearly intends them to, to all aspects of theory-making and conceptualisation because it is the justification of analysis in Philosophy that underpins its use in other disciplines such as engineering design research. Rosen's arguments define the key role that intuition plays not only in closure, but also in deciding what theories and concepts are and the best ways of validating, evaluating or comparing theories and concepts. In short, Rosen is pointing to the role of human intuition, based on individual human values, as the key element of justification. That is, Rosen is arguing that, in epistemological terms, the issues of whether theories and concepts are satisfactory, and whether and how theories and concepts are satisfactorily evaluated and compared, depends primarily on human values rather than objective aspects of theories and concepts themselves.

Finally, the evaluation and comparison of engineering design theories and concepts also depends on the boundaries of the discipline of engineering design research for the reasons raised in Chapter 1. Defining particular theoretical mechanisms for the evaluation and comparison of engineering design theories depends on what sort of theoretical entities engineering design theories are, because the most appropriate means of evaluating and

comparing theories about objects (say) are different from those that are most appropriate for evaluating and comparing theories about human cognition, intuition and creativity. That is, the answer to the research question also depends on the definition of the term 'engineering design theory' and in turn on the definition of 'engineering design research'. Neither of these terms is either absolute or fixed and, consequently, the meanings chosen for them depend on human values and intuition as to what is most theoretically elegant.

Bringing all of the above considerations together, the answer to the question 'How can engineering design theories be evaluated and compared?' is composed of four elements each of which is dependent on intuition and human values. These four elements are shown in the conceptual structure of Figure 9.

4.2.2 Research question 2

What are the implications of including human values in theories of human design cognition?

Identifying the implications of including human values in theories of human design cognition depends on the theoretical perspective and scope of the research. Consequently, the implications that are identified here are grounded in the definitions of Chapter 1, the discussions of the background literature found in Chapter 2, and the details of the post-positivist theoretical position developed in Chapter 3. Human value is one of the main foci of the post-positivist paradigms that emphasise that individuals perceive and remember the world differently (Eno 1996; Guba 1990a; Phillips 1987, 1990; Schwandt 1990; Reich 1994a, 1994b). From a post-positivist position, engineering design research needs to address issues of human value because human values underpin the creation of all artefacts (Eno 1996). At the theoretical level of this thesis, the five main findings of addressing the second research question are:

- Ethics are important aspects of theories about engineering design.
- A richer picture of the ways that designers use design knowledge is possible via the theoretical concept of design worlds.
- It is possible to include issues of human purpose, ethics, and feelings in engineering design theory.
- It is possible to include the qualitative aspects of designing in engineering design theory.
- Epistemological difficulties relating to theories about automatic or mechanistic design become evident.

The philosophical discipline of ethics is the study of matters of right and wrong, good and bad.

Ethics is involved in situations by statements such as:

We ought to...

We should...

The correct way to do this is...

That... is wrong.

Epistemologically speaking, any use of human values results in decisions of right and wrong or good and bad, and hence a test as to whether ethics is an aspect of a situation is whether the choices or actions depend on human held values. This leads to the conclusion that, because of the underlying values and assumptions used by humans to choose or act, the conscious and unconscious processes of human activity always have an ethical dimension. Hence, the role of ethics spans from the practical and praxical, through the epistemological to the ontological.

It is only those aspects of ethics that relate to designing engineering artefacts that are relevant here. For engineering design, the scope of ethics includes:

- The use of a technical artefact
- The specification of the artefact
- The decisions on which the specification depended
- The decision-making processes which were chosen
- The agency(ies) involved in the processes (both human and non human)
- The assumptions and human (or other) values on which choices were made (whether about the specification or the decision-making processes).
- Those matters which affect which assumptions and values (human or otherwise) are used.

Ethical issues are found in engineering design in many situations that are apparently factual and value free. It is epistemologically difficult to make a case for engineering design being a value free, factual island of logical positivism immune from the ethical considerations which are part and parcel of all other human activities because the use of technology, the making of technology, the conceptualisation of technology and the matters which lead to such occurrences all have an unavoidable dependence on the values which humans hold (see, for example, Beder

1993; Pacey 1983; Westrum 1991; Willoughby 1991). For example, an engineering designer may calculate the loads on a beam and claim that,

*This size beam **should** be strong enough.*

In making the statement 'This size beam should be strong enough', the designer is also introducing a consideration of confidence about the strength or safety of the beam that depends on human values. The designer is making judgements about the loads that the beam is likely to be subjected to in normal service, about the adequacy of the mathematical or other theoretical models of the beam's behaviour, and about the safety factors that are appropriate. Each of these judgements depends the values that the designer holds.

Ethics is implicated in theories of engineering design cognition, however, whether engineering design is viewed as value free or value laden. If designing engineering artefacts includes consideration of their human consequences then ethics is involved because these considerations involve human values. If, however, engineering design is undertaken without considering anything other than the technical consequences, it implies that consciously or unconsciously, a decision based on human values has been made to do so. This brings the action under the remit of ethics. Either way, theories of engineering design cognition have an unavoidable ethical aspect.

One reason that engineering design is sometimes assumed to be value free is due to its use of mathematics. Mathematical modelling of physical situations has been successfully used on so many occasions that it has acquired the reputation for meeting the criteria of truth in many situations, and comments such as 'If in doubt, calculate', or 'It may look right, but what do the calculations show' indicate that mathematics is often given greater truth-telling status than sense data. The engineering analysis of a proposed artefact or system by mathematical means appears to be value free because it is concerned only with the application of symbols which have defined properties and relationships. The absolutism and determinism of mathematically symbolised concepts along with the internal consistency of their syntax and semantics gives this apparent freedom from issues of human value. Engineering designers, however, *use* mathematical methods to model real situations, artefacts and systems for the purposes of design. This difference of intention is significant. Engineers choose which models are used,

which parameters are included, which aspects of reality are taken into account, and which results are predicted. Each of these choices depends on human values. In summary, ethics is implicated in engineering design via human values regardless of the apparently value free nature of the mathematical basis of engineering analysis.

For the above reasons, ethics is also implicated in 'design worlds'. These 'design worlds' are designers' mental representations of real world situations and are used by designers to conceive and 'try out' new designs or parts of designs (Schon 1992; Schon and Wiggins 1992). Designers create and experience these internal temporary worlds to represent reality as it might be in the future and consequently, theories about this representation and experiencing of potential futures are a significant aspect of research into design cognition. Theories about the representation and experiencing of internalised design worlds involve human values because these values influence how internal realities are perceived and constructed and, in addition, human values guide designers' decisions about which aspects of a design are better or worse, which avenues are best to explore and when to stop designing (Hamlyn 1990; Petroski 1992; Oxman 1996; Rosen 1980; Soufi and Edmonds 1996). The application of techniques of information analysis to these aspects of design cognition was discussed in detail in Chapter 2 where the problems of their positivist foundations were raised especially the need for human values to be objectively fixed and quantitatively expressed and the difficulties of resolving the representation problem (Coyne 1991b; Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Hamlyn 1990, Newell 1982, 1990; Simon 1982).

A design world is a designer's temporary internalised vision of the circumstances surrounding how the future 'ought' to be if the real world goes according to the plans conceived of in that design world. Consequently, design worlds can have any 'rules' or value systems applied to them because they are mental constructs limited only by the creative conceptualising power of individual designers. The conscious and unconscious use of human values by a designer, and the sense of 'ought' that is a part of the phenomenon of design worlds, leads to the need for ethical considerations to be addressed in theorising about design cognition. The inclusion of human values in theories of human design cognition offers the means of addressing these

ethical aspects of designing in an epistemologically more complete manner than is possible otherwise.

The intuition that underpins the creation and management of an individual designer's temporary design worlds is an ephemeral phenomenon. It is clear, however, that intuition, whatever its form or formlessness, must have something to work on and this 'material for intuition to work on' comes from all three of Popper's epistemological worlds (Phillips 1987). It comes from the world as experienced by the senses of sight and touch etc., the world of theories, and the internal subjective world of the person that is intuiting. In terms of the subjective world, Rosen's (1980) analysis extends further than either that of Popper (1976) or of Phillips (1987). Rosen distinguished between the remote and unintellectualised re-experiencing of an original experience of an object, and the experiencing and re-experiencing of an internalised conceptualisation of a real or theoretical object via that conceptualisation and the intellect. That is, Rosen distinguished between memories of the real world that are accompanied by the same bodily responses (including affective, kinæsthetic and hormonal responses) as the original circumstance, and the remembrance of a conceptualised collection of properties that represent some aspects of the original experience. For example, Rosen distinguished between re-experiencing a memory of a flower, and the experience of watching a conceptualised memory of the experience of perceiving the same flower. Rosen's arguments concerning the limitations of analysis apply to both direct and conceptualised memories via limitations of analysis in both constructing memory and experiencing. Hence, it is necessary to include human internalised influences in any explanation of the use of memory and experiencing and this depends on human values. These issues are of significance for engineering design research and for addressing this research question because memory and experiencing, whether of the real world or of theoretical objects, are an aspect of human creative cognition, and Rosen's analyses point to the role of human values in those aspects of human creative cognition that lie beyond the analytical.

A substantial proportion of the literature of engineering design research supports a human-centred view of design and design cognition (see, for example, Coyne 1991b; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992a, 1992b; Cross 1989; Dasgupta 1991; Duggan 1970; Franz 1994; French 1988;

Guba 1990a, Jones 1970; Phillips 1987, 1990; Pugh 1990; Rapoport 1969; Rosen 1980; Wray 1992). In terms of design theory, a human-centred view of design implies that due consideration needs to be taken of human goals and human responses, and this implicates matters of intention, purpose, feelings and ethics. An emphasis on ethical and aesthetic concerns is a natural consequence of a constructivist perspective on human design cognition that is grounded in human values regardless of the biological, psychological or theoretical models of action and cognition that are used (Guba 1990a; Lincoln 1990; Singer 1995). The emphasis on ethics and aesthetics in association with human values provides a basis for the inclusion of intentionality and feelings into theories of human designing. Without human values, the aims and objectives of designing must be expressed indirectly in mechanistic or other terms, but with human values, the decision-making and optimising aspects of designing can relate directly to human purpose (Alexander 1980; Rapoport 1969). The inclusion of human values also enables the alignment of theories of design cognition with theories of intuition that enable the inclusion of feelings and emotions into explanations of designing (see, for example, Bastick 1982; Rosen 1980; Sternberg 1990). This inclusion of feelings is long overdue because, although there is extensive anecdotal references to the role of feeling in the literature of engineering design, there is as yet no epistemologically satisfactory means of including feelings or related human issues (see, for example, Appendix 5; Akin and Akin 1996; Bastick 1982; Cross 1989, 1990; Davies 1985 (in Cross 1989); Davies and Talbot 1987; Galle and Kovács 1996; Glegg 1971; Kolodner and Wills 1996; Lawson 1990, 1993, 1994; Liu 1996; Simmonds (in Lera) 1983). In addition, bringing human values into theories of human design cognition offers the means of undertaking the ethical changes to engineering design theory that Jonas (1982) argued are necessary because traditional ontological and ethical assumptions relating to human values no longer hold.

Finally, two other issues arise from combinations of the above. Firstly, the inclusion of human values as a basis for addressing many human aspects of design cognition points to the need for a change of focus in engineering design research from quantitative to qualitative concerns because human value is the essential difference between qualitative and quantitative matters. Secondly, the inclusion of human values into the theory concerning 'design worlds' and associated theories of design cognition allows an epistemological problem relating to theories

about automatic designing to emerge. The problem is that of making sure that the correct values and value systems are used in the design world in question and that other additional values and value systems are not included by accident, presumption or ubiquitousness. In both cases, the integrity of the automatic means of design choice and design optimisation would be compromised by being based on incorrect values, and this would lead to the development of inappropriate design solutions.

In conclusion, the inclusion of human values in theories of human design cognition has wide reaching implications for engineering design research and the development of engineering design theory. The implications that have been identified here are represented in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10: Research question 2 - Implications of including human values in theories of human design cognition.

4.2.3 Research question 3

What are the implications of using post-positive perspectives for research and theory-building in the area of engineering design cognition?

The previous section described the implications of including human values in theories of design cognition and overlaps this section because including human values implies the application of a post-positivist outlook. A detailed description of the implications of a post-positivist perspective to all aspects of research into engineering design cognition is beyond the scope of this research because it would involve the majority of existing research that has been based on positivism. In this section, the scope of the research question is restricted to the five post-positivist implications that have emerged from the definitions, theoretical position and preceding analyses of this research:

- Clarification of the differences between information and knowledge.
- Epistemological primacy of feelings over rationality in theories of engineering design cognition.
- Demise of the 'black box' positivist model of engineering design cognition.
- Limitations on engineering designers' perceptions and creativity due to ontological assumptions and values.
- Epistemological difficulties relating to the justification of protocol analysis as a research method for investigating human design cognition.

Hamlyn (1990) and others have used subjective and objective considerations to distinguish between information and knowledge (Coyne 1991b; Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1992b; Rosen 1980). From their perspective, information is the public face of knowledge; that is, information is human knowledge reduced by the conscious and subconscious, internal and external, methods of conceptualisation and communication. This reduction of knowledge to information is due to several processes. Take, for example, the observation of a flower by an individual. When the individual perceives a flower this is first an experience: a sensual perception only. The second step, is the perception of this experience in the individual's consciousness, and this

depends on a memory of the experience. So far, the process has not involved the individual making concepts or conceptualising because the memory is of the experience as is. To enable the individual to reflect on the memory and discuss it, the memory of the flower is reduced to the mental pictures or concepts that are particular to the individual. At this point, conceptualisation and the reduction of the experience into information has commenced. For the individual to discuss the experience of the flower it is then necessary to convert the individual's personal conceptual representation of the experience into public concepts and symbols, for example, a 'red rose'. Further reduction and abstraction is then possible in the public realm via, for example, the classificatory systems and theories of ecology or biology. Thus, information and knowledge are distinct: 'red rose' is the information and the experiencing of the flower is knowledge. Thus, knowledge is more than information, and informatic perspectives on knowledge limit what may be inferred about the content and use of that knowledge. The use of a post-positivist perspective on engineering design cognition offers the means of exploring aspects of designers' use of knowledge that depend on clarification of the differences between information and knowledge.

The above reduction of the knowledge of the flower to information has four stages,

1. The experience.
2. The unconceptualised memory of the experience.
3. The conceptualised memory of the experience.
4. The description of the conceptualised memory in language or public symbols.

The information about of the flower is the knowledge of the flower reduced according to the particular ways that that individual memorised the experience, conceptualised it and converted it into public concepts via language. Epistemologically, issues of feelings are relevant mainly to the first two stages, with rationality applying only to the last two stages. The above description of the way that information is derived from knowledge points, therefore, to 'feelings' being epistemologically more foundational than rationality in matters of cognition. This is also supported by the way that feelings are fundamentally implicated in an individual's choice of

how the memory is conceptualised and that conceptualisation is described (see, for example, Bastick 1982; Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Davies and Talbot 1987; Rosen 1980; Schön 1984; Stegmüller 1976). This relative importance of feelings suggests that the development of satisfactory epistemological foundations for research into engineering design cognition requires additional research in the area of the structural dynamic of feelings compared to the rational issues that have been the central focus of the existing literature of engineering design cognition.

The use of a constructivist perspective to include human values and feelings in theories of engineering design cognition enables the investigation of those issues that have been hidden inside the 'black box' of design creativity which has underpinned most theories of engineering design creativity and process (Dasgupta 1991; Jones 1970). Jones used the concept of a 'black box' of design cognition to refer to those aspects of designing that cannot be adequately explained within a particular theoretical framework. For example, in classical systems or informatic terms, the part of design process where a new design is invented or conceived is a 'black box' because positivism has no adequate explanation of invention. This 'black box' nature of the inventive aspects of design process has been hidden within the metaphor of 'searching through solution space' in the recent literature of engineering design research (see, for example, Brown and Hwang 1993; Coyne 1991a; Coyne and Newton 1990; Dasgupta 1991; Gero 1991b; Lowe 1994; McDermott 1982; Steinberg 1994). The concept of 'searching through solution space' offers many benefits in terms of defining the solutions to design problems that are Well-defined and well-structured, but presents several problems when it is extended into the realms of human intuition and creativity. Firstly, at a macro scale, the concept of searching does not attempt to explain inventive behaviour or insight that is not searching. Secondly, at the middle scale, it simply moves the problem into the area of the mechanics of information transformation, leaving unexplained the role of intuition in deciding what to search, why and how, and when to stop. A further middle scale difficulty is that it is not well proven in the literature that designers actually work this way except when using formal design methods based on searching. Also, evidence that the internal process of designing is one of search would necessarily unjustifiably presume isomorphism of internal and external realities as argued by Phillips (1987) in relation to Piaget's models of cognition. Finally, at the micro scale, the searching model of design

cognition makes little theoretical connection with the issues of feelings, individual values and individual assumptions that designers maintain are an essential aspect of designing. In summary, the application of post-positivist perspectives offers new ways forward for investigating those areas of human design cognition that previously lay within Jones' 'black box' and the positivist definitions of design thinking (e.g. Akin 1992). The application of post-positivist perspectives changes the focus of research into engineering design cognition from the conscious and publicly observable aspects to the subconscious aspects by emphasising the phenomena of human designing and the way that humans interpret and construct knowledge.

Besides the above implications relating to the 'black box' theoretical aspects of design thinking, the application of post-positivist perspectives has direct implications for the foundations of theories of engineering design cognition due to its focus on the assumptions and values that underpin an individual's interpretation of reality and their construction of their own 'world view'. Hermeneutic and phenomenological perspectives on design cognition suggest that the perception, experience and action of the engineering designer is based on experiencing and an individual designer's experiential history (Coyne 1991b; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992, 1993; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992; Indurkha 1992; Nideau 1991). In this sense, the constructivist position on engineering designing echoes descriptions of how the research and theory-making of natural scientists is influenced by their ontological assumptions and values (Coyne 1991b; Kuhn 1962; Nideau 1991; Stegmüller 1976). Practical evidence of this influence of past experience on human designing comes from Liu's (1995) discovery that experienced designers can modify their ability to recognise shapes by using their experience to change what Liu conceived as a *threshold of recognising activation* in order to perceive emergent underlying shapes and patterns. Taken together, the above considerations point to the conclusion that the output of designers is guided and limited by their world views, their values, their experiences and their knowledge.

Finally, are the implications of a post-positivist perspective for the epistemological validation of protocol analysis. Protocol analysis is currently the preferred means in the engineering design research literature of exploring the mechanisms of design cognition (see, for example, Akin and Lin 1995; *Design Studies*, 'Special Issue: Analysing Design Activity' 1995; Dorst 1995; Ennis and

Gyezly 1991; Galle and Kovács 1996; Tang and Leifer 1991). Protocol analysis is based on using the recorded external observations of one or more human designer to make proposals about how designers' internal cognition functions. The designer(s) being tested may also be asked to explain their actions either during designing or afterwards. The information that has been recorded is then analysed and abstracted via protocols to explore, amongst other things the representation of objects, the generation of designs, designers' knowledge bases, design problems and design thinking (Akin and Lin 1995). It is the epistemological validation relating to design thinking that is being addressed here.

There are several problematic aspects of the epistemological validation models of design thinking based on protocol analysis. Firstly is the effect on a designer's thinking of verbalising about that thinking whilst designing (Davies 1995). Concurrent verbalisation can affect designed output either way. It may reduce the quality of a designer's output because thinking about and talking about designing has to be undertaken by the designer in parallel to the designing itself and this may reduce the cognitive resources available for designing.

Alternatively, the designer's verbalisation may improve their designed output because it necessitates the designer watching how they are designing: in effect, the verbalisation has become a design method. Davies' findings are that designers design differently when asked to verbalise about their design tasks. From a constructivist perspective, this change in design behaviour would be expected because the need to verbalise would require changes in how the designer interpreted and constructed the internal design worlds that would support the separate tasks of designing and verbalising.

The second problem for the validation of protocol analysis concerns the way that designers describe their internal experiences. From a constructivist perspective, it is unlikely that the verbal protocols would provide an accurate and unique description of the designer's thinking because of the multiplicity of ways that the designer's knowledge of their thinking can be reduced into verbal information about it, and because that process depends on individual human values and assumptions (see discussion earlier in this chapter relating to differences between knowledge and information). The details of this second epistemological difficulty are also supported by the findings of Davies' (1995) research.

The third difficulty, is the epistemological argument that the method of protocol analysis cannot be validly used to identify actual human methods of cognition even if the verbalisation and other requirements of gathering protocol information did not influence designing, and the designer's description of their cognition was accurate. The argument is presented by Phillips (1987) as follows. Phillips draws attention to the similarities between trying to pin down what is happening inside an individual by observing behaviour, and trying to derive the internal processes and construction of a calculator by observing its ability to add $2 + 2$ to make 4. In the case of the calculator, the range of possible internal configurations and processes which could be used to emulate the required mathematical functions is only lightly constrained by this functional requirement to add 2 to 2, and any theory as to the exact internal nature of the calculator would be underdetermined. In terms of an individual, external observation does not define internal functioning. Drawing a parallel: protocol analysis might lead to a description of 'a' means whereby some aspects of the internal activities of a human can be represented, but to propose that this is 'the' means that humans function is to claim too much. This difficulty of proving congruency or isomorphism of internal subjective realities with theory, or expressed symbolism or externally observed reality is a problem for any attempt to research cognition via observation (Guba 1990b; Philips 1987; Popper 1976).

To summarise, attempting to establish a well justified relationship between the words or symbols used by an individual designer and the individual's internal reality presents epistemological difficulties. These difficulties are exposed by the basic premises of the various forms of constructivism and by the post-positivist analyses of Guba (1990a) and others (see, for example, Davies and Talbot 1987; Magee 1973; Margolis 1989; Phillips 1987; Popper 1976). The application of a constructivist perspective to protocol analysis leads to the conclusion that the validation of protocol analysis presents epistemological difficulties.

The constructivist position taken in this thesis implies not only that knowledge *may be interpreted*, but that it *will always be interpreted* due to the uniqueness of individual world views (Coyne 1991b, Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Guba 1990; Reich 1994a, 1994b). This construction of reality by individuals, whether the construction is socially dependent as Berger and Luckmann (1987) argued, or otherwise, goes against facts being defined 'absolutely' and leads to 'truth'

being an interpreted matter. This does not mean that scientific methods are unusable, or that there can be no agreement between researchers: it means that, from a constructivist perspective, engineering design theories must be compatible with individualised knowledge interpretation and construction, particularly with regard to cognition. The implications of applying post-positivist perspectives for research into human engineering design cognition that have been discussed above and represented in Figure 11 below reflect this situation.

Figure 11: Research question 3 - Implications of using post-positive perspectives for design research and theory-building in the area of engineering design cognition.

4.2.4 Research question 4

What are the theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors?

In this section, the focus is on the theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors because it is these characteristics that inform the development of engineering design theory rather than their knowledge content, the means of persuasion used to try to encourage ethical action, or the different stances which underpin epistemological, theoretical and practical

judgement. The discussions in this thesis have so far focused mainly on the social, environmental and ethical *consequences* of technology, but the concept of social, environmental and ethical factors also includes the ways that designers take into account social, environmental and ethical impacts *on* their designs, for example due to corrosion or misuse. Both aspects involve a relationship between the artefact and human concerns. The findings relating to the theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors that emerge from addressing research question 4 in this section are:

- Social, environmental and ethical factors are a form of knowledge.
- Knowledge about the social, environmental and ethical aspects of technology is more than 'information'.
- Social, environmental and ethical factors are derived from an individual designer's experience or the recorded experience of others.
- The knowledge that comprises social, environmental and ethical factors is always interpreted.

The terms 'social', 'environmental' and 'ethical' refer to knowledge about different aspects of reality, and it is the ways that engineering designers are influenced by these types of knowledge that provide the basis for defining the characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors. Engineering designers are guided by knowledge and information about the social, environmental and ethical aspects of technology from a variety of sources that include laws, national and international standards, codes of practice and ethics, policy guidelines, institutional tradition, organisational directives, cultural pressures and personal experience (Court 1995). From a constructivist perspective, the interpretive underpinning of all human conceptualisation and action means that the ways that an engineering designer uses, or is influenced by, the knowledge and information about social, environmental and ethical aspects of technology must depend on the human values and assumptions held by that designer regardless of whether the knowledge or information is quantitatively expressed or apparently value free. Within this theoretical framework, the main issues that are evident in defining the

theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors with respect to engineering design theory are:

- The ways that social, environmental and ethical factors are aspects of knowledge.
- The sources and forms of the knowledge and information that comprise social, environmental and ethical factors.
- How engineering designers use or are influenced by social, environmental and ethical factors.

This is a similar range of issues to that identified by Court (1995) in his research into the characteristics of engineering design information. Court's research was undertaken from a positivist perspective, and his focus on information, rather than knowledge, was appropriate to that theoretical viewpoint. The theoretical perspective of this research is post-positivist, however, and its constructivist basis means that knowledge is its main focus and information is viewed as the reduced, abstracted and publicly defined aspect of knowledge. This difference of focus means that the ways that designers use and are influenced by social, environmental and ethical factors must be addressed, because this is the area where the differences between knowledge and information are most evident. This aspect is addressed in more detail in the next section where it is the subject of research question 5. This need for additional research into designers' use of personal knowledge rather than information is supported by Court, particularly with respect to designers' experiences and designers' internal activities.

Before continuing further, it is necessary to point to a number of aspects of the role of social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering designing. Firstly, knowledge of the social, environmental and ethical aspects of technology is what guides engineering designers in the creation and choice of concept and technological detail (Papanek 1984). Secondly, this knowledge is interpreted individually by the engineering designer so that it can be used in other circumstances. Thirdly, knowledge of the social, environmental and ethical aspects of technology results in changes to the internal functioning of the designer because it influences the designer to create something different than otherwise. Finally, the changes to the internal functioning of the designer mean that it is epistemologically insufficient to view social,

environmental and ethical factors as information that is external to the internalised human activity of designing. These aspects of the role of social, environmental and ethical factors underlie the analyses that follow.

Engineering designers gain knowledge about the social, environmental and ethical aspects of technology from two sources:

1. Their personal interpretation of pictures, reports, analyses, diagrams, stories and other representations that describe technology and its relationship to social, environmental and ethical considerations in particular circumstances.
2. Their own phenomenological experience.

These categories overlap because in both the knowledge is received via the designer's senses, and in both the knowledge can be represented in symbolic form. For example, an engineering designer may be personally present when an engine is tested but the information the designer perceives is via test equipment or computer readouts. Regardless of whether the source is pure information or empirical data, the knowledge is gained by interpreting and internalising that information; transforming information into knowledge via the designer's own human values and assumptions. The differences between the social, environmental and ethical aspects of the underlying knowledge that relate to a particular design situation are differences of knowledge content rather than differences in how the designer's cognition includes these issues. This means that, epistemologically, the differences between, for example, the knowledge content of social factors from environmental factors are essentially irrelevant to defining their theoretical characteristics. The individual theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors are defined by the nature of their creation and eventual use by human designers and this is addressed in more detail in the next section. The characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors that have emerged as a consequence of research question 4, but excluding those that are addressed in relation to research question 5, are illustrated in the conceptual diagram of Figure 12 below.

Figure 12: Research question 4 - Theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors.

4.2.5 Research question 5

How do designers use information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors?.

The previous section raised the importance of taking into account how engineering designers use information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors because this has a bearing on the epistemological detail of how these factors are included in engineering design theory. In this section, the use of social, environmental and ethical factors by engineering designers is explored, and this exploration brings out some additional aspects of their role which are beyond those revealed in the previous section. The main issues to emerge are:

- The importance of post-positivist perspectives for providing an adequate framework for analysing the qualitative aspects of engineering designers' use of social, environmental and ethical factors.
- The importance of addressing unconscious cognition in theories of engineering design.

- The importance of interpretation for including social, environmental and ethical factors into engineering design theory.
- The role of human values for engineering designers forecasting the consequences of particular artefacts or technologies.
- The importance of including perception in explanations of the use of social, environmental and ethical factors by engineering designers.
- The role of ethics in how engineering designers use social, environmental and ethical factors.
- The epistemological primacy of ethics and ethical factors over social and environmental factors.

The background to addressing research question 5 is the changes over time in the ways that engineering designers use and have used the information and knowledge of social, environmental and ethical factors. Engineering design in the early stages of the industrial revolution was a process in which the means of designing each artefact was carried in the minds of craftsmen steeped in tradition. The cumulative store of design knowledge and information about that artefact and its evolution through the trialling of many variations was contained in the artefact and the craft-person's memories from apprenticeship and practising the craft (Alexander 1964; Jones 1970; Rapoport 1969). From historical design analyses, it appears that, when engineering design was a craft process, social, environmental and ethical factors were addressed unself-consciously by the craftperson and were integral to the activity of designing and making an artefact (Alexander 1964; Rapoport 1969; Sumpter 1997).

In the last century, engineering designing has become more conscious and its processes have become more public which has led to a move towards the quantification of design information. Until recently, social, environmental and ethical factors were separated into those which were beneficial and those which were problematic. The beneficial effects were seen as what the product is intended to do and the problematic effects were the constraints on designers' creativity. To put it into contemporary design jargon: the design focus was to maximise

performance for some functions within a solution set search space bounded by minimum requirement criteria for other attributes. The designer's role was to maximise the beneficial effects whilst constraining the problematic effects so as to satisfy particular criteria. This perspective on beneficial and problematic effects of technology underpins many of the social, environmental and ethical prescriptions of professional engineering institutions. For example, the Engineering Council of the UK gives the following professional advice on environmental matters to engineering designers (Engineering Council 1993).

Utilise the best available technology and techniques not entailing excessive cost.

Maintain a balanced, disciplined and comprehensive approach to environmental issues.

Seek to balance costs with the net benefits to the environment and to human society, to achieve the best possible environmental option.

Be open-minded, seeking to comply fully with the law and regulatory framework but recognising that you may need to go beyond compliance with the minimum standards which they represent.

Each of the above guidelines is based on assuming that engineering designers will attempt to produce the most benefits whilst satisfying safety and other standards. The inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors in this benefit/problem framework entails a qualitative aspect to engineering design theory. Choosing how much to 'go beyond compliance', or deciding what is 'excessive cost', or 'maintaining a balanced approach', or 'balancing costs and net benefits', and choosing which technology is 'best' (and for what reasons) are all matters of human judgement and are based on human values. Hence, they are all dependent on things internal to engineering designers and design decision makers as human beings.

Recently, the social, environmental and ethical aspects of engineering design have become more quantified. Some design theorists have noted the asymmetry between how the beneficial and problematic aspects of technology have been addressed and suggested that for any engineering design all performance criteria should be specified in a manner which is objectively determinable (see, for example, Adie 1994; Chandrasekaran 1990; Glegg 1971; Gregory 1966a; Lowe 1994; Pugh 1985, 1991). This move towards the specification of comparative performance

in quantitative terms also has been supported by moves to automate routine design activities via computer and the sundry computer aided aspects of designing. In addition, moves towards improved accountability and contractual clarity between different organisations involved in engineering design have also resulted in the quantitative specification of design performance. For example, Glegg (1971) noted that it is no longer sufficient to say that a new design of gearbox must be significantly quieter than a previous model, it is necessary to specify quantitatively how quiet the new model must be. This quantisation of specification, first based on the use of mathematical models and later used as a basis for contractual satisfaction, has resulted in the widespread assumption that only factors which are reducible to a numerical status may be included in engineering designs, engineering design processes, engineering design theory and engineering design research. Consequently, within this dominant quantitative perspective, the social, environmental and ethical aspects of technology are viewed as quantitatively expressed information.

In this informatic climate of engineering design research, Court, Culley and McMahon (1993) and Culley, McMahon and Court (1995) explored how designers in practice interact with information, particularly in the conceptual and embodiment stages of designing. Building on this research Court (1995) concluded that engineering designers' access information via personal means regardless of the design task, and that this personal aspect of the ways designers interface with information needed further attention. The positivist perspective of Court's research precludes the inclusion of the human aspects of designing in his informatic model because this requires a means of including human values and the ways that humans interpret and construct their individual realities. The post-positivist perspective of this research, however, provides the epistemological basis for these personal aspects of the ways that engineering designers access and use design information and knowledge to be explored.

The critical constructivist perspective of Chapter 3 and the analyses of Chapter 2 point to designers being influenced by knowledge and information about the social, environmental and ethical consequences of technology via both conscious and unconscious processes. Both Alexander (1964) and Jones (1970) noted that the unconscious designing of the traditional craft-person can produce astonishingly well balanced results that allow each part of a design to be

shaped by many factors, for none of which the craft-person would be able to provide reasons. Alexander (1964) argued that traditional design methods were a product of an unself-conscious culture, and that modern processes of engineering design were self-conscious and based on a self-conscious culture. Alexander observed that the traditional processes seemed to produce more satisfactory results and, comparing self-conscious and unconscious design processes, asked,

Why are forms made in the self-conscious culture not so well fitting or so clearly made as those in an unconscious culture? In one case the form making process is a good one, and in the other bad.

Alexander proposed that unconscious designing has a structure which makes it homeostatic, and that self-conscious design processes disrupt homeostasis to an extent that the production of forms which fail to fit their contexts is not only possible, but likely. Alexander suggested that the division of design cultures into self-conscious and unconscious was a consequence of the differences in education and training of designers and craftpersons. In self-conscious cultures form-making is taught academically by means of explicit rules and general 'principles' whereas in unselfconscious cultures teaching relies on the gradual exposure of the novice to the craft and learning occurs by imitation and correction. Alexander's explanation adds detail to the cognitive explanation discussed in Chapter 3 that human designing depends on non-analytical intuitive processes, and hence on unconscious cognition. If Alexander's arguments are proven then not only is the study of unconscious cognition important for explaining the activity of designing as is argued in Chapters 2 and 3, but also it is important as an essential aspect of producing better design output.

Alexander (1964) and Jones (1970) were describing the differences between information-based and knowledge-based design cultures. In the self-conscious design culture, designers are trained to use information only. Craft based unconscious designers, however, have the design information consolidated with human values as design knowledge. This distinction is important in answering the question of how designers use information or knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors. Identifying the social, environmental and ethical

aspects of technology is a study in hindsight, i.e., an historical study. The relevance, to the designer, of the social, environmental and ethical implications of technology is in how that information or knowledge may be used to aid the conceptualisation of future artefacts, that is, the designer has a purposeful interest in the social and environment aspects of technology. This intentionality immediately brings in issues of human value because the designer uses these values to decide which issues are important or relevant.

It is widely accepted that engineering designers interpret information and knowledge as a necessary part of their work. For example, Furman (1981) reported that designers' work includes the interpretation of customer requirements, the visualisation of design solutions and the interpretation of feedback from tests and field trials (see also Appendix 5). In general terms, engineering designers interpret knowledge and information to extend its use beyond the circumstances from which it was gathered, but the epistemological detail of engineering designers' interpretation of information and knowledge requires further expansion particularly with respect to the changes consequent on any processes of gathering and use of information and knowledge. If the knowledge *about* a situation was not reduced, abstracted or changed in some way it would *be* the situation, not something different from it. Similarly, if a designer's knowledge of a situation was total, and not adapted or interpreted, it would be the *consciousness* or *experience* of that situation. Designers' usage of information and knowledge is usually different from either of these absolute circumstances and therefore it is necessary to assume that some interpretive change happens both in its acquisition and its use, and that interpretation is an important characteristic of designers' use of social, environmental and ethical factors.

This role of interpretation underpins the ways that engineering designers create conceptualisations which, when actualised, must entail certain consequences and not others. Whilst designing, these consequences are addressed (or not) in an abstract manner by the designer forecasting what will happen. Social and environmental impact assessment methodologies depend on assumptions that the relationships between technology and the environment are determinist in nature; that is, that there are clearly defined and mathematically modelable relationships between causes and effects. A critical constructivist perspective on these issues brings to light inconsistencies in the above assumptions. Firstly, forecasting is more

than being able to provide an explanation of the relationship between a cause and a consequence. It is commonplace to set student engineers 'problems' which require the application of mathematical modelling techniques to accurately forecast a future condition. Forecasting in this manner, however, depends upon the problem lying in a conceptually closed and bounded situation, i.e., one in which it is at least theoretically possible to deterministically relate all outcomes with all possible inputs. The relationship between technology use and its social and environmental consequences is not conceptually closed and bounded with present levels of human understanding. Relationships between particular technological implementations and their social and environmental consequences may not be intrinsically *unknowable*, but the possibility that the details of the relationship may be known in the future does not change the situation for those designers working in the present for whom the situation is *at present* incompletely known.

Designers' use of forecasting depends on human values in a variety of ways. Firstly, if some knowledge about the non-technical consequences of including particular technical schema or detail into an artefact are to be included then the designer must have some inkling that there may be non-technical consequences implicit to a particular technical decision which are of significant magnitude. That is, a magnitude, based on the designer's values and assumptions, at which some further activity is deemed necessary, whether that activity is the relatively subliminal one of remembering additional details, or perhaps the commitment of resources to knowledge acquisition by some other means. Secondly, it must be possible for the designer to identify what knowledge might be appropriately interpreted to aid with the forecasting of potential consequences. Thirdly, for any forecasting of likely non-technical consequences of technology detail to be useful, it is necessary that the forecasts associated with detail may be combined into something larger, because technology as used consists of an aggregation of technological detail. Each of these three aspects of the proper forecasting of the non-technical consequences of technology use depends on choices based on human values, and thus human values form an essential aspect of forecasting the social, environmental and ethical consequences of technology or technological details.

Human values and the underlying assumptions that human engineering designers make are one side of the process of cognition. At the other end of the spectrum in terms of the meta-theoretical hierarchy of engineering design theory is the direct perception of reality, and some researchers have argued that addressing this perceptual aspect of design cognition is an essential aspect of understanding processes of cognition (Goldschmidt 1994; Hamlyn 1990; Lazear 1990; Smets and Overbeeke 1994). There are two sides to issues of perception in design cognition; external perception and internal perception. Issues of external perception relate to the use of the senses, for example, the sight of a real object. The internal aspect of perception relates to how the information about the world outside an engineering designer causes neurological changes via sense mechanisms that result in human knowledge. Both external and internal aspects of perception also involve issues related to the meanings attributed to what is perceived (Norman 1992).

The boundary between external and internal aspects of perception is not well agreed. Liu (1995) investigated the way that designers recognised the emergence of partially defined shapes, and concluded that the perception of objects was dependent on training and skill. Similar connections between the external attribute of 'seeing' and the internal attribute of 'identifying' are supported by research into brain hemisphere function (see, for example, Cross, Cross and Glynn 1986; Springer and Deutsch 1993; Ward 1984). Smets and Overbeeke (1995) illustrate this connection in their research involving perception that crosses sensory modalities where they concluded that it was possible for industrial designers to express the taste of a dessert through the appearance of its packaging. For taste to be identified by sight implies that both are dependent on some internalised connection, and Eno's (1996) discussion of the role of cultural style suggests that that may be part of the explanation. Both brain hemisphere research and Smets and Overbeeke's (1995) research on sensory modalities implies that what is seen is a function of what is known already, and hence there is a connection between the internal and external aspects of perception. Addressing the same issues in practical terms, Goldschmidt (1994) and Tovey (1992a, 1992b, 1997) have argued that designers use a visual means of thinking. Goldschmidt argues that perception is part of a way of visual thinking that includes visually rational reasoning. Tovey argues that industrial and automotive designers perceive

objects and shapes within a shared culture of meaning and that this is reflected in their language and communication. Both perspectives go against the dominant linguistically-based paradigm of rational thought. Weaknesses in the linguistic and rational model of cognition are exposed by Hamlyn's analyses of the role of perception in which he argues that models of cognition that are based on a central processor with mechanistically defined inputs and outputs are untenable due to the difficulties of explaining how meaning and identification is attributed to undifferentiated sensory perceptions.

Gibson's ecological theory is proposed by Smets and Overbeeke (1994) as a practical means of bridging the theoretical difficulties between internal and external aspects of perception in design research. Gibson's theory assumes that humans perceive the world because they interact with it rather than simply because they view it, or perceive it through another sense, and change the sensory inputs into object data. This ecological outlook, in theory, potentially offers the means of including the generation of human values from experience into design theory by tying human values to human interaction with external reality. The ecological theory does not, however, provide an explanation of the way that emotions and values are created nor explain how emotions and values are associated with cerebral constructs such as the new designs that designers create in their internalised design worlds.

Regardless of the present difficulties in devising adequate theoretical means to explicate perception and the detail of its role in cognition, it is apparent that the rational central processing model of design cognition is limited in the way that it can address some of the fundamental issues in human designing. Perception is part of how engineering designers use information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors whether via internal perception, external perception or some mixture of both. Consequently, in this research, it is concluded that perception has a role to play in the way that engineering designers use social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory.

Finally, building on the analyses relating to research question 2, is the role of ethics in how engineering designers include information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors. Ethics is important in the study of how an engineering designer's perspective(s)

affects their use of knowledge about the non-technical consequences of technology because engineering designers hold personal values that underpin their conscious and unconscious activities. In some situations, some of the human values that influence designing can be objectivised and subjected to public ethical appraisal. For example, the particular values relating to decisions about the maximum loads a lift should safely carry. In other cases, however, the human values that shape the design and evaluation of engineering artefacts are hidden even from the designers themselves because they are the assumptions that underpin that individual's sense of reality (Eno 1996).

Ethics is implicated in the use of social, environmental and ethical factors, and hence in theories of engineering design, in two ways. Firstly, ethics is implicated in design decision-making because all decisions depend on human values in the formulation of the scope and framework of the epistemologically defined circumstance within which the decision is made, and in the actual preferences that are made between competing options for the eventual decision. Secondly, ethics is implicated in the unconscious creative aspects of designing because the balance of internal influences that result in one design being conceived rather than another relate to the human values that a designer holds. These values shape and influence the definition of the design problem, particularly in terms of the subtle ill-defined aspects of the design problem definition and the likely means of resolving it, and, in addition, the values will have influenced the designer's acquisition of experience, the memories of experiences, and the ways that that experience emerges as design solutions (Coyne and Snodgrass 1992a). This dependence of engineering designing on human values means that ethics, the study of how human action is influenced by human values, is a necessary aspect of how designers use knowledge and information about social, environmental and ethical factors.

Finally, the role of ethics in the ways that engineering designers design has implications for defining the characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors because the choice and use of particular social and environmental factors, whether undertaken consciously or unconsciously, is an ethical matter. This means that ethics and ethical factors have an epistemological primacy over social and environmental factors.

To recap, the study of how engineering designers' use of social, environmental and ethical factors brings out some additional aspects of social, environmental and ethical factors which are in addition to those raised in previous sections of this chapter. The main issues to emerge are illustrated in Figure 13 below.

Figure 13: Research question 5 - Engineering designers' use of information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors.

4.3 Summary of Findings

In this chapter, the outcomes of addressing the five research questions using the theoretical perspective, framework and methods developed in Chapter 3 have been presented in Figures 9 to 13 and these are summarised below. The discussion of the findings in terms of resolving the

research problem and in terms of their implications in the wider literature is left to the following chapter to facilitate a smooth flow of argument and to avoid unnecessary repetition.

The outcomes of research question 1 concerning the evaluation and comparison of theories and concepts of engineering design research were twofold. Firstly, the need for greater clarity about the epistemological positions and definitions that underpin evaluation, comparison, analysis and validation of engineering design theories and concepts, and secondly, the need to include issues of intuition and human values.

In research question 2, the inclusion of human values into theories of human design cognition led to several findings that condense into two main issues. Firstly, that ethics is an important aspect of theorising about human design cognition. Secondly, that the inclusion of human values into theories of human design cognition via the 'design worlds' or similar metaphors leads to a focus on the qualitative aspects of engineering design, and points to inconsistencies in the epistemological foundations of theories that are aimed at automating designing.

The exploration of the implications of applying post-positivist perspectives to research into engineering design cognition in research question 3 points to the need for a change of focus from 'rationality and information' to 'designers' feelings and knowledge', especially with respect to the way that designers' output is bounded by their ontological assumptions. In addition, the application of post-positivist research perspectives leads to the theoretical demise of the 'black box' models of human design cognition and points to difficulties with the epistemological justification and validation of protocol analysis as a research tool for exploring design cognition.

The investigation of the characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors in research question 4 leads to an emphasis on social, environmental and ethical factors as a form of interpreted knowledge, derived from the experiences of individual designers and others, that cannot be adequately theoretically represented in terms of 'facts' or information.

The analyses relating to research question 5, concerning designers' use of information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors, brings together many of the findings of research questions 1 to 4. The outcomes of these analyses point to the role of human values in

how designers model the future and the necessity of using post-positivist perspectives for analysing the interpretive, qualitative and unconscious aspects of designers' cognition, including social, environmental and ethical factors. Issues of perception emerge as an important aspect of designers' use of social, environmental and ethical factors, and the importance of the role of ethics is raised again, this time with regard to designers' use of knowledge. This latter issue points to ethics and ethical factors being epistemologically more fundamental than other design factors.

5. Conclusions and implications

5.1 Introduction

Before looking at the research findings in their wider context, it is beneficial to recapitulate the structure of this research and the development of the thesis, so far. In Chapter 1, the research problem was presented and the justification for undertaking the research was outlined. In addition, in Chapter 1, the terminology used for this thesis was described and the methodology and structure of the research was reviewed. In Chapter 2, the centrality of the research problem to the field of engineering design was identified and the literature that provided the theoretical context to the research problem was reviewed. This review of the literature exposed widespread epistemological, conceptual and terminological inconsistencies in engineering design research that were in many cases due to the application of inappropriate research perspectives, methods and concepts. These problems with epistemological, conceptual and terminological inconsistencies meant that it was important for this research to address issues of theoretical perspective and framework in more detail and at a greater depth than would otherwise be expected. Five research questions emerged in Chapter 2, each of which represented an issue that needed to be resolved before the research problem could be adequately addressed. These questions all presumed the application of a post-positivist research perspective and therefore much of the analysis that led to their being answered was raised in Chapter 3 where issues of theoretical perspective and framework were addressed and the critical constructivist framework for this research was developed. This framework included the development of the epistemological definition of theory and its validation that was used as the basis for addressing the research questions in Chapter 4. In addition, in Chapter 3, a means of critical meta-theoretical analysis was developed which led to the definition of a meta-theoretical hierarchy. Together, these meta-theoretical tools aid with the clarification and validation of existing engineering design theory and provide a more coherent conceptual basis for the development of new engineering design theory. In Chapter 4, the outcomes of applying the research perspectives and theoretical tools developed in Chapter 3 to the research questions were reported along with their associated discussions.

In this chapter, the findings of Chapter 4 are discussed in terms of the research problem and their implications across wider theoretical and practical contexts. The findings that have emerged from the individual research questions are brought together to develop a means of incorporating social, environmental and ethical factors into engineering design theory in a manner that is epistemologically more satisfactory than previously described and implied in the literature. The way that the research problem has been addressed in this research raises suggestions for changes to the disciplines of engineering design research and design, and points towards a means of unifying design theories. Finally, in this chapter, the distinct contributions to knowledge that have arisen out of this research are identified along with the limitations of the research and proposals for future research. To summarise, the picture of the research problem described in Chapter 1 had missing pieces that were identified in Chapter 2; these pieces were found in Chapter 4 as a result of the efforts of Chapter 3; and in Chapter 5 the appearance of the completed picture is discussed.

Chapter 5, consists of ten sections:

- Introduction
- Research findings and the research problem
- Resolution of the research problem
- Implications for engineering design theory
- Implications for engineering design research as a discipline
- Implications for the discipline of design
- Implications for design education
- Implications for the unification of engineering design theories
- Limitations
- Contributions to knowledge
- Further research

5.2 Research findings and the research problem

In this section, the focus is the way that the research findings of Chapter 4 help resolve the research problem. The contributions to resolving the research problem of the findings of each research question are discussed in turn.

5.2.1 Resolving the research problem: contributions of the findings from research question 1

The first research question, ‘How can engineering design theories be evaluated and compared?’, was raised because the review of literature in Chapter 2 indicated that the means of evaluation and comparison implicit in the literature of engineering design research were more suited to theories about objects and physical phenomena than to theories about human designing. Research question 1 was addressed from the critical constructivist position that was chosen in Chapter 3 as being most appropriate for research into human design cognition, and the findings were expressed in Chapter 4 in Figure 9 reproduced below as Figure 14.

Figure 14: Research question 1 - Evaluation and comparison of engineering design theories (Chapter 4, Figure 9).

The findings of research question 1 are important to the resolution of the research problem in several ways. Firstly, they point to the importance and need for the development of appropriate epistemological positions on theory, concepts, and closure and, in addition, they point to the need for suitable means of deconstructing and validating theories and concepts and the relationships between them. Secondly, disciplinary issues are raised in that the concepts of 'engineering design' and 'engineering design research' must be defined in a manner that is appropriate to the study of the human processes involved in the designing of engineering artefacts rather than the physical behaviour of those artefacts or the representation of the artefacts and design problem in informatic terms. Thirdly, the findings indicate the ubiquitous role of intuition and human values in all aspects of evaluating and comparing engineering design theories.

In summary, the findings of this research question suggest that the inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory depends on:

- Appropriate methods of deconstructing, evaluating, comparing and validating engineering design theories that includes intuition and human values as necessary.
- A position on the closure of analytical argument that has intuition and human values as primary epistemological considerations.
- The choice of appropriate definitions for 'engineering design' and 'engineering design research' that allow that designing is an essentially human activity.

5.2.2 Resolving the research problem: contributions of the findings from research question 2

The findings of research question 2, 'What are the implications of including human values in theories of human design cognition?', elaborates on the role of human value that forms an important aspect of the findings of research question 1. In this second research question, the emphasis is on human design cognition, a fundamental aspect of human designing. Again the research question was addressed from the critical constructivist position that includes the

assumptions about theory, its validation and deconstruction that were developed in Chapter 3. The research findings of Chapter 4 were summarised in Figure 10 which is reproduced below as Figure 15.

Figure 15: Research question 2 - Implications of including human values in theories of human design (Chapter 4, Figure 10).

The findings of research question 2 raise several additional issues that relate to the resolution of the research problem. Firstly, including human values through the metaphor of ‘design worlds’ enables a more comprehensive picture of design knowledge and its use by designers and this assists in the differentiation of design knowledge from design information. Secondly, the inclusion of human values emphasises the qualitative aspects of engineering design and provides the basis for matters of human purpose, feelings and ethics to be included in engineering design theories. Thirdly, ethics becomes an important part of theories of engineering design cognition because any activity involving human values has an ethical aspect. Fourth, the inclusion of human values raises epistemological difficulties relating to

theories of automated designing in that these types of theories imply an independence from the essentially human aspects of design creativity and cognition that defines designing as different from other activities. Consequently, the inclusion of human values into theories of human design cognition via the theoretical perspective used in this thesis implies that theories of automated design are better viewed as engineering theories or informatic theories. In summary, the findings of this second research question suggest that the inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory depends on,

- The inclusion of human purpose, feelings and especially, ethics into theories of engineering design cognition.
- A focus on the qualitative aspects of engineering design.
- The relocation of theories of automatic designing into other, more appropriate, disciplines.

5.2.3 Resolving the research problem: contributions of the findings from research question 3

The findings of research question 3, 'What are the implications of using post-positivist perspectives for research and theory-building in the area of engineering design cognition?' build directly on the arguments raised in Chapters 2 and 3 that the positivist perspective that dominates the existing literature and research into engineering design is inappropriate for research into human designing. Research question 3 is used to explore how research and theory-building in engineering design cognition would be different if undertaken from a post-positivist perspective. The research question was addressed using the critical constructivist perspective of Chapter 3 and the findings expressed in the conceptual figure reproduced below in Figure 16 (found earlier as Figure 11).

Figure 16: Research question 3 - Implications of using post-positive perspectives for design research and theory-building in the area of engineering design cognition (Chapter 4, Figure 11).

The findings of research question 3 are that changes are necessary to engineering design theory as a result of changing from the dominant positivist outlook to one of the post-positivist perspectives that enables the inclusion of the human aspects of designing that are implicit in the integration of social, environmental and ethical factors into engineering design theory. The main implication of applying a post-positivist perspective is to move engineering design theory away from its contemporary foci of information and rationality. The application of post-positivist perspectives also further clarifies the need to differentiate between knowledge and information, and points to the demise of the informatically based 'black box' metaphor for facilitating the inclusion of aspects of human design cognition that were epistemologically unable to be addressed via positivism. At an epistemological level, the findings raise two issues that need to be adequately included in the foundations of engineering design theory. Firstly, the primacy of feelings over rationality that is a consequence of the physical expression of human

values in the consideration of rational matters, and, secondly, the way that designers' creativity and perception are dependent on their ontological bases because the ways that individuals interpret reality are based on their belief and value systems. Finally, the application of post-positivist perspectives challenges the validity of protocol analysis as a research method for investigating the cognition of human designers on the grounds that the method assumes that it is possible to accurately infer internal human cognitive mechanisms and processes from observation of external behaviour, and that the means of acquisition do not materially influence the acquired data. These issues imply that protocol analysis and the data that emerge from it does not make a satisfactory contribution to resolving the research problem addressed in this thesis.

In summary, the findings of this research question suggest that the inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory depends on,

- Differentiation between knowledge and information
- The epistemological primacy of feelings over rationality
- Representation of the dependence of designers' creativity and perception on their individual ontological bases
- Clarification of the limitations of protocol analysis as a basis for developing, supporting and validating theories relating to human design cognition

5.2.4 Resolving the research problem: contributions of the findings from research question 4

The purpose of research question 4, 'What are the theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors?' is to identify what sort of theoretical entities social, environmental and ethical factors are, so that an epistemologically appropriate framework of engineering design theory can be chosen to incorporate them. The research question was addressed using the critical constructivist perspective chosen in Chapter 3, and this indicated that a complete picture of the theoretical characteristics could not be achieved without considering how designers *use* social, environmental and ethical factors. This is because developing a complete picture of the theoretical characteristics depends on developing a

theoretical representation of how designers' convert external information to internal knowledge and how this knowledge influences creativity. These issues are addressed by research question 5, and hence it is only those issues that are not addressed in regard to research question 5 that are the subject of Figure 17 below (a copy of Figure 12).

Figure 17: Research question 4 - Theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors (Chapter 4, Figure 12).

The dominant theoretical characteristic of social, environmental and ethical factors that emerges in the findings of research question 4 is that they are a form of knowledge. Social, environmental and ethical factors are knowledge that is gained as a result of designers interpreting their own experiences or the recorded experiences of others and hence, in line with the findings of the previous research questions, the knowledge that comprises social, environmental and ethical factors is epistemologically more than information. Therefore, the findings of this research question imply that the inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory depends on:

- The theoretical representation of social, environmental and ethical factors as knowledge that includes considerations of human value.

- The theoretical representation of design knowledge taking full account of its origination in the experience of designers and the recorded experiences of others expressed as information via the interpretation of individual designers.
- The representation of information as an epistemologically reduced subset of knowledge.

5.2.5 Resolving the research problem: contributions of the findings from research question 5

The findings of research question 5, 'How do designers use information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors?' adds to the findings of research question 4 in that it brings out the additional theoretical characteristics of social, environmental and ethical factors that depend upon the theoretical representation of how designers use them. The findings related to this research question bring together many of the considerations of the previous findings because researching designers' use of knowledge emphasises the human aspects of designing, and the application of a post-positivist perspective leads to the emergence of those significant issues of engineering design that can not be addressed via positivism. Figure 18 below summarises the findings related to research question 5 (previously found as Figure 13).

Figure 18: Research question 5 - Engineering designers' use of information and knowledge about social, environmental and ethical factors (Chapter 4, Figure 13).

In this question, research question 5, the findings relate mainly to the internalised interpreted and valued aspects of design cognition because the focus is on how designers' use of social, environmental and ethical factors can be characterised in engineering design theory. The findings of this research question suggest that the inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory depends on:

- Using post-positivist research perspectives.
- Including the unconscious aspects of engineering design cognition.

- The inclusion of the ways that designers interpret knowledge and information relating to social, environmental and ethical factors.
- The inclusion of issues relating to human values in models of how designers forecast the future whilst designing.
- The inclusion of issues of human perception in explanations of how designers use social, environmental and ethical factors.
- The importance of ethics in explanations of how designers use social, environmental and ethical factors.
- The epistemological necessity of addressing matters of ethics and ethical factors prior to social and environmental factors when theorising about or researching engineering designers use of social, environmental and ethical factors.

This section completes the scope of the research investigation into the five particular aspects of resolving the research problem that were represented by the research questions. What remains is to assemble these findings together into a single coherent theoretical proposal and this issue is addressed in the next section.

5.3 Resolution of the research problem

The research problem that forms the basis of this thesis is 'Can social, environmental and ethical matters be better included in theories about designing engineering artefacts by applying a post-positivist perspective?'. The findings indicate that this is possible, not least because several fundamental issues relating to designing that cannot be addressed under the dominant positivist perspective can be included through the use of post-positivist perspectives, particularly those epistemological issues related to the inclusion of human values and how prior knowledge, rather than information, impinges on human creativity. The post-positivist approach to research in engineering design adds to the existing body of scientific research in the sense that it provides additional epistemological and theoretical means to address those human aspects of designing which cannot be addressed in an epistemologically satisfactory manner by

the positivistic application of the scientific approach to research whilst allowing that scientific research perspectives are appropriate to the behaviour of objects.

In summary, the research problem is resolved by re-envisioning research into engineering design and the main characteristics of this new approach are that:

- Engineering designing is an essentially human activity and that this human aspect is central to the development of epistemologically satisfactory engineering design theory.
- Intuition and human values are epistemologically essential aspects of explanations of engineering designing, particularly with regard to the roles of human purpose, creativity, feelings, forecasting, analysis and evaluation.
- Knowledge and information are differentiated between on the grounds that knowledge is information internalised by the designer with all that that implies concerning conscious and unconscious perception, interpretation and construction of the internal and external realities of individual designers.
- In epistemological terms, human feelings have a theoretical primacy over rationality.
- Ethics is an epistemologically essential aspect of engineering design cognition and engineering design theory.
- Post-positivist research perspectives, especially constructivism and critical analysis, are needed to address the above research issues.
- Scientific research into objects, physical phenomena and information is subsumed within the post-positivist approach.

This new approach resolves the research problem in several ways. Firstly, by bringing human values and assumptions into the theoretical arena it allows the qualitative aspects of social, environmental and ethical factors to be included in engineering design theory, and thus resolves the problems due to attempts to inappropriately quantify these issues. Secondly, by focusing on the activity of designing rather than the designed object it provides the means of including human values and assumptions into engineering design theory via intuition,

perception, interpretation and the construction of worldviews and design worlds. Thirdly, by insisting on the centrality of human action in engineering design theory, this new approach brings out the importance of ethics in all theoretical explanations of designing and the use of design knowledge. These factors, based on a post-positivist perspective of engineering design research, combine to outline a way of including social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory that significantly improves on what is possible under positivism and science.

5.4 Implications for engineering design theory

The centrality of social, environmental and ethical factors for engineering design theory argued in Chapter 2, and the fundamental issues raised as a consequence of the findings to the research questions, discussed in this chapter and Chapter 4, imply that a new structure of engineering design theory is needed. If this new post-positivist structure of engineering design theory is able to include those human issues that have been neglected by positivist approaches, without loss of the benefits of existing positivist theory relating to designed objects, then it is clearly an improvement. Three questions need to be satisfactorily addressed if the new theoretical structure is to be epistemologically coherent, justifiable and relate well to well-justified knowledge in other areas of research:

- How do the above findings contribute to the new theoretical structure?
- What other theoretical elements are needed in the new structure?
- How do the theories and concepts of this new structure of engineering design theory relate to each other?

The meta-theoretical perspective and meta-theoretical hierarchy developed in Chapter 3 provides one means of addressing these issues. The main steps in the process of developing a structure for engineering design theory using the meta-theoretical hierarchy are:?

1. Identify on which meta-theoretical levels to place the different contributions from the research findings.

2. Identify the meta-theoretical levels to which other engineering design knowledge relates.
3. Inspect the meta-theoretical structure for coherency and weakness, and make changes by removing and moving existing theoretical elements, or by identifying areas where new theory needs to be developed or included.

Table 28 below is the outcome of the first stage of building a new structure for engineering design theory. The table lists the appropriate levels of the meta-theoretical hierarchy for the different points that have emerged from addressing the research questions.

The inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors into engineering design theory: points emerging from research findings	Meta-theoretical levels
Intuition and human values are an epistemologically necessary aspect of deconstructing, evaluating, comparing and validating engineering design theory.	1: (Ontology)
Intuition and human values are an epistemologically essential aspect of analysis and the closure of analytic argument.	1: (Ontology)
Designing is an essentially human activity and epistemologically sensible definitions of the terms 'engineering design' and 'engineering design research' reflect this centrality of human action.	1: (Ontology)
Post-positivist perspectives are a necessary aspect of the satisfactory inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors into engineering design theory.	1, 2: (Ontology, epistemology)
Intuition and human values are epistemologically essential aspects of differentiating between knowledge and information.	2: (Epistemology)
Social, environmental and ethical factors are forms of knowledge that include human values.	2: (Epistemology)
Design knowledge originates in the experiences of individual engineering designers and the experiences of others expressed as information.	2: (Epistemology)
Information is an epistemologically reduced subset of knowledge.	2: (Epistemology)
Human purpose, feelings and ethics are an epistemologically essential aspect of engineering design cognition.	2, 4: (Epistemology, internal processes of designers and collaboration)
The qualitative aspects of engineering design are an epistemologically essential aspect of engineering design theory.	1: (Ontology)
The individual ontological assumptions and values of engineering designers is an epistemologically essential aspect of explaining creativity and perception in designing.	1, 2, 4: (Ontology, epistemology, internal processes of designers and collaboration)
The unconscious aspects of human functioning are an epistemologically essential part of theories of engineering design cognition.	2, 4: (Epistemology, internal processes of designers and collaboration)
Interpretation is an epistemologically essential aspect of how engineering designers utilise knowledge and information relating to social, environmental and ethical factors.	4: (Internal processes of designers and collaboration)
Human values and intuition are an epistemologically essential aspect of	4: (Internal processes of designers

explanations of forecasting.	and collaboration)
Human perception is an epistemologically essential aspect of explanations of how engineering designers use social, environmental and ethical factors.	4: (Internal processes of designers and collaboration)
Human feelings have an epistemological primacy over rationality.	2: (Epistemology)
The study of Ethics is epistemologically essential to explanations of how engineering designers use social, environmental and ethical factors.	4: (Internal processes of designers and collaboration)
The study of Ethics is an epistemologically essential aspect of engineering design theory.	2: (Epistemology)
Ethics and ethical factors have an epistemological primacy over social and environmental factors.	2, 4: (Epistemology, internal processes of designers and collaboration)

Table 28: Research findings and meta-theoretical levels of engineering design theory

The meta-theoretical levels of Table 28 define the initial meta-theoretical structure of engineering design theory found in the following Table 29.

Level	Classification	Description
1	Ontology of design	Designing is a human activity and definitions of 'engineering design' and 'engineering design research' follow from this. Engineering design cognition is particular to individual designers who have their own individually constructed internal realities that are based on their interpretation of their individual experiences. Designing is a qualitatively based activity in which the designer is only partially conscious.
2	Epistemology of design theory	Positivist perspectives cannot adequately address the range of issues that are spanned by engineering design research, and hence post-positivist perspectives, especially constructivist, are needed. Intuition and human values are epistemologically implicated in deconstructing, evaluating, comparing and validating engineering design theory. Ontological assumptions and values influence creativity and perception. Human purpose, feelings and ethics are epistemologically essential to theories of engineering design cognition. Ethics is epistemologically essential to engineering design theory. Human feelings have epistemological primacy over rationality. Intuition and human values are epistemologically implicated in differentiating between knowledge and information. Knowledge is information that is interpreted by an engineering designer via their existing ontological values and assumptions and can be used in intuition. Design knowledge originates in the experiences of individual engineering designers and the experiences of others expressed as information. Hence, epistemologically, information is a subset of knowledge. Social, environmental and ethical factors are forms of knowledge. Ethics and ethical factors have epistemological primacy over social and environmental factors.
3	General design theories	
4	Theories about the internal processes of designers and collaboration	Intuition and human values are involved in closure and in deconstructing, analysing, evaluating, comparing and validating theory. Human purpose, feelings and ethics are an epistemologically essential aspect of engineering design cognition. Design knowledge originates in the experiences of individual engineering designers and the experiences of others expressed as information. The internal processes of designing are qualitative and only partially conscious. The ontological assumptions and values of individual designers underpin their creativity and perception. Intuition and human values are aspects of explanations of forecasting. Interpretation, perception and

		ethics are epistemologically essential aspects of explanations of how engineering designers utilise knowledge and information relating to social, environmental and ethical factors.
5	Theories about the structure of design process	
6	Design methods	
7	Theories about mechanisms of choice	Intuition and human values are involved in closure and in deconstructing, analysing, evaluating, comparing and validating theory. Human purpose, feelings and ethics are an epistemologically essential aspect of engineering design cognition. The internal processes of designing are qualitative and only partially conscious. Interpretation, perception and ethics are epistemologically essential aspects of explanations of how engineering designers utilise knowledge and information relating to social, environmental and ethical factors.

8	Theories about the behaviour of elements	
9	Initial conception and labelling of reality	Intuition and human values are an epistemologically necessary aspect of deconstructing, evaluating, comparing and validating engineering design theory. Intuition and human values are epistemologically essential aspects of differentiating between knowledge and information. The individual ontological assumptions and values of engineering designers is an epistemologically essential aspect of explaining creativity and perception in designing. Perceiving and conceiving are qualitative activities.

Table 29: Partial meta-theoretical structure of post-positivist engineering design theory that includes the research findings.

This completes the first step in the process of building a new meta-theoretical structure for a post-positivist engineering design theory. It is clear that the main elements of what has emerged in the research findings do not provide a complete and comprehensive meta-theoretical structure because the research was focused mainly on those areas that were identified as being poorly addressed by existing research or problematic in some other way.

The second step in the process of building a new meta-theoretical structure for post-positivist engineering design theory is to identify at which levels elements of existing positivist engineering design theory contribute to the overall theoretical structure. The main characteristics of existing engineering design theory are its basis in science and its focus on the designed object and information processing (see Chapters 2 and 3). These contributions from existing engineering design theory are represented in Table 30.

Level	Classification	Description
1	Ontology of design	
2	Epistemology of design theory	
3	General design theories	
4	Theories about the internal processes of designers and collaboration	
5	Theories about the structure of design process	Theories about information management and processing. Management theories relating to group dynamics. Systems theories of management.
6	Design methods	Methods of collecting and managing information that may be of use to an engineering designer. Computer assistance for information management and transformation for designers.
7	Theories about mechanisms of choice	
8	Theories about the behaviour of elements	Engineering theories. Informatic theories. Scientific theories. Optimisation methods for costs, theoretical and physical variables.
9	Initial conception and labelling of reality	

Table 30: Partial meta-theoretical structure of post-positivist engineering design theory that includes existing engineering design theory.

The above two partial meta-theoretical structures of Table 29 and Table 30, representing the contributions from the findings of this research and existing engineering design theory, are brought together below in Table 31.

Level	Classification	Description
1	Ontology of design	Designing is a human activity and definitions of 'engineering design' and 'engineering design research' follow from this. Engineering design cognition is particular to individual designers who have their own individually constructed internal realities that are based on their interpretation of their individual experiences. Designing is a qualitatively based activity in which the designer is only partially conscious.
2	Epistemology of design theory	Positivist perspectives cannot adequately address the range of issues that are spanned by engineering design research and hence, post-positivist perspectives, especially constructivist, are needed. Intuition and human values are epistemologically implicated in deconstructing, evaluating, comparing and validating engineering design theory. Ontological assumptions and values influence creativity and perception. Human purpose, feelings and ethics are epistemologically essential to theories of engineering design cognition. Ethics is epistemologically essential to engineering design theory. Human feelings have epistemological primacy over rationality. Intuition and human values are epistemologically implicated in differentiating between knowledge and information. Knowledge is information that is interpreted by an engineering designer via their existing ontological values and assumptions and can be used in intuition. Design knowledge originates in the experiences of individual engineering designers and the experiences of others expressed as information. Hence, epistemologically, information is a subset of knowledge. Social, environmental and ethical factors are forms of knowledge. Ethics and ethical factors have epistemological primacy over social and environmental factors.
3	General design theories	
4	Theories about the internal processes of designers and collaboration	Intuition and human values are involved in closure and in deconstructing, analysing, evaluating, comparing and validating theory. Human purpose, feelings and ethics are an epistemologically essential aspect of engineering design cognition. Design knowledge originates in the experiences of individual engineering designers and the experiences of others expressed as information. The internal processes of designing are qualitative and only partially conscious. The ontological assumptions and values of individual designers underpin their creativity and perception. Intuition and human values are aspects of explanations of forecasting. Interpretation, perception and ethics are epistemologically essential aspects of explanations of how engineering designers utilise knowledge and information relating to social, environmental and ethical factors.
5	Theories about the structure of design process	Theories about information management and processing. Management theories relating to group dynamics. Systems theories of management.
6	Design methods	Methods of collecting and managing information that may be of use to an engineering designer. Computer assistance for information management and transformation for designers.

7	Theories about mechanisms of choice	Intuition and human values are involved in closure and in deconstructing, analysing, evaluating, comparing and validating theory. Human purpose, feelings and ethics are an epistemologically essential aspect of engineering design cognition. The internal processes of designing are qualitative and only partially conscious. Interpretation, perception and ethics are epistemologically essential aspects of explanations of how engineering designers utilise knowledge and information relating to social, environmental and ethical factors.
8	Theories about the behaviour of elements	Engineering theories. Informatic theories. Scientific theories. Optimisation methods for costs, theoretical and physical variables.
9	Initial conception and labelling of reality	Intuition and human values are an epistemologically necessary aspect of deconstructing, evaluating, comparing and validating engineering design theory. Intuition and human values are epistemologically essential aspects of differentiating between knowledge and information. The individual ontological assumptions and values of engineering designers is an epistemologically essential aspect of explaining creativity and perception in designing. Perceiving and conceiving are qualitative activities.

Table 31: Meta-theoretical structure of post-positivist engineering design theory that includes the research findings along with existing engineering design theory.

The third and final stage in developing a new post-positivist structure for engineering design theory is to inspect the meta-theoretical structure of Table 31 for coherency and weakness. The post-positivist research findings and existing theory complement each other in that they relate to different levels of the meta-theoretical structure. Level 3 remains empty at this stage because a satisfactory general theory of engineering design has not yet emerged from either the research findings or existing engineering design theory. Similarly, the range of theories of engineering design process defined in level 5 is incomplete because few theories of design process have emerged relating to the detail of engineering design processes involving designers whose world views are interpreted and constructed.

The outcome of applying the above meta-theoretical analyses is the development of a more coherent and comprehensive structure for engineering design theory. The new meta-theoretical structure of engineering design theory in Table 31 includes both that designing is an essentially human activity and that engineering designing is concerned with physical objects, physical phenomena and information about them.

5.5 Implications for engineering design research as a discipline

The research findings and the associated issues leading up to them also have implications for the structure of the discipline of engineering design research. The existing disciplinary structure is problematic, and the analyses of this research point to possible improvements to that structure. The main drawbacks with the existing structure of the discipline of engineering design research that were identified in Chapters 1, 2 and 3 are:

- Problems with definitions of 'engineering design' and 'engineering design research'
- The existing disciplinary structure is ephemeral, inconsistent and lacks coherency
- Lack of a proprietary bibliographic classification structure that reflects a satisfactory disciplinary structure
- Lack of balance in the disciplinary structure due to its historic biases towards the designed object and information processing
- The structure does not offer the contextual support that would otherwise aid conceptual and terminological definition and clarity
- Engineering design research has a lack of disciplinary identity

The overall picture is of accidental and ad-hoc development by researchers whose primary theoretical allegiances were elsewhere (Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Sargent 1994). In this sense, Millers' (1996) argument that design is a meta-discipline because much of its terminology and methodology has been appropriated from other disciplines makes some sense. Similarly, there is sense in Sargent's (1994) argument that theories of engineering design are incommensurate because they are dependent on the particular information and perspectives of different technical subdisciplines of engineering.

Both Miller's and Sargent's arguments are tautological because they depend on assuming that the existing ad-hoc disciplinary structure is the most appropriate. A further weakness is that, ontologically and epistemologically, these arguments assume positivism as the dominant basis of engineering design research in the ways described in Chapters 2 and 3. The perspective presented in this thesis goes to the root of these issues by arguing that the human activity of

designing should be the central focus of engineering design and the foundation of engineering design research as a discipline. This challenges the assumptions of both Miller and Sargent and opens the way for the development of a new and more coherent structure for engineering design research.

The initial arguments that provide a basis for an epistemologically more coherent disciplinary structure for engineering design research were asserted in Chapter 2 where the centrality of social, environmental and ethical factors is represented in the diagrams reproduced below as Figure 19 and Figure 20.

Figure 19: Centrality of area of research interest in relation to three parent research disciplines (Chapter 2, Figure 2)

Figure 20: Centrality of research problem in relation to related disciplines (Chapter 2, Figure 3).

These arguments for the theoretical centrality of the human aspects of designing are grounded in the assumption that designing is essentially an activity or process that happens in human societies where humans create new artefacts and other useful, practical and theoretical structures. That is, engineering design is socially, environmentally and ethically situated (Coyne, Rosenman, Radford, Balachandran and Gero 1990; Dilnot 1982; Gasparski 1979; Konda,, Monarch, Sargent, Subrahmanian 1992; Simon 1981). In this sense, research into designing engineering artefacts is a subdiscipline of research into designing per se and, in consequence, the focus on the designing aspect of engineering design means that the technical aspects of engineering design are peripheral concerns. This conclusion fits well with the existing situation relating to other more established disciplines because the technical aspects of designing engineering artefacts are more justifiably a part of the disciplines of engineering or science.

Other factors that support a human-centred basis for the disciplinary structure of engineering design research originate in the epistemological analyses of Chapter 3. An outline of one relevant argument is:

1. The most central issue in research into engineering design is the investigation of how engineering designers create new engineering solutions.
2. The investigation of how engineering designers create new engineering solutions depends on understanding how designers *use* engineering information.
3. The particular content of that engineering information or its relationships with other engineering information is peripheral to the study of engineering design.
4. Research into engineering design depends on understanding how the information that a designer has 'taken in' influences what the designer creates. That is, research into engineering design depends on understanding the use of prior knowledge.
5. The store of prior knowledge and the ways that that knowledge is weighted and valued are different for individual designers.
6. The theoretical and investigative basis of research into engineering design must be capable of addressing the ways that designers realities are individually constructed and dependent on individual's values.
7. Therefore, the study of the individual, interpreted and constructed realities of engineering designers forms the core of the structure of the discipline of engineering design research.

The above proposal that human aspects of designing are central to the discipline of engineering design is supported by the contextual theoretical analyses of Chapter 2 and aligns well with the analyses of other researchers who have investigated the epistemological aspects of research into engineering design (Coyne 1990a, 1990c, 1991; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1992a, 1992b, 1993; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992; Cross, Cross and Glynn 1986; Dilnot 1982; Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Reich 1992, 1994, 1995). The

most striking implication of this position is the way that focusing on how design knowledge is *used* minimises the role of the engineering and scientific *content* of engineering design information, and consequently implies that research involving engineering information content and theory is more appropriately located in other disciplines. This fits well with the definitions advanced in Chapter 1 relating to the terms ‘engineering’, ‘engineering design’, ‘engineering design research’ and ‘design’ that were intended to provide a structural means of easing the terminological and conceptual confusion of engineering design research.

The discipline of engineering design research also needs to structurally reflect the theoretical relationships between areas of research and theories that are at lower and higher levels of abstraction. The meta-theoretical perspective developed in Chapter 3 provides a means of formalising the structure of theoretical relationships of engineering design research in this way via the meta-theoretical hierarchy which offers a practical example of such a framework.

Both of the above developments contribute towards the definition of a structure for the discipline of engineering design research that is internally and externally more coherent than the present disciplinary arrangement. It is internally more coherent in the sense that its structure follows the imperatives of its epistemology, and externally more coherent in the sense that it comports better with well justified research in other disciplines, and with the structure and bounds of those disciplines.

To summarise, the picture that emerges is of a discipline of engineering design research that:

- Is human-centred and necessarily based on post-positivist perspectives such as constructivism.
- Involves engineering information content and associated theories in a much reduced role.
- Has a structure based on the meta-theoretical relationship between theories of engineering design research at different levels of abstraction.
- Has more straightforward relationships between the purpose of the discipline, its ontology, its epistemology, its research perspectives and its theories.

- Has external bounds that align with other historically better established disciplines.

5.6 Implications for the discipline of design

The discipline of design is similar to the discipline of engineering design research in presenting problems relating to disciplinary titles and structure. For example, in *Design Studies*, the title 'discipline of design' is used to refer both to anything related to design and also, more specifically, to research into design. The lack of terminological and structural definition leads to similar problems as are found in engineering design research because the disciplinary and sub-disciplinary titles relating to design and to design research do not provide adequate contextual separation between 'research into design', 'the study necessary to become a designer', 'research relating to information used by designers' and 'research into designed objects'.

Much of this problem of disciplinary conflation and confusion has its origins in the founding of research groups interested in design during the 1960s and 1970s. In the early days of design research, the boundaries of the concept of design were extended widely and this resulted in the terminology defining very little (O'Doherty 1963). *Design Studies* was first published in 1979 and intended to 'establish the theoretical bases for *treating design as a coherent discipline of study in its own right*' [emphasis added]. This implies that the Design Research Society, the publishers of *Design Studies*, assumed that design was not recognised as a discipline at that time (Editorial, *Design Studies*, 1979, vol. 1, no. 1). This assumption, however, appears to be contradicted by a variety of other evidence, for example, Bruce Archer, the first contributor to *Design Studies*, was at that time Professor of Design Research, Head of the Department of Design Research and Head of the Design Education Unit at the Royal College of Art in London (Archer 1979). The existence of a discipline of design prior to 1979 is also evidenced by the number of design-related papers, collections of papers and books that were written during the 1950s, 1960s and 1970s (Cross 1993; Jones 1966, 1970; Jones and Thornley 1964a). This confusion about whether a discipline of design exists or not and how it should be structured has carried through to the present, and resulted in a disciplinary structure that is confused and disputed especially in relation to its ontological and epistemological foundations (see Appendices 3 and 4; Archer 1979, 1984; Cross 1993; Dasgupta 1991; Eder 1995; Harris 1983; Pugh 1992; Suh 1990).

Resolving the problems of the disciplinary terminology and structure of design involves addressing similar issues to those considered in the previous section relating to the discipline of engineering design research. The findings of this research, the research perspective and the associated analytical tools that have been developed in this thesis justifiably also apply to the discipline of design because they are substantially domain independent in that they relate to theories about the human activity of designing rather than the domain dependent content of design information. Consequently, the implications of the analyses of this research for the discipline of design are similar to those identified for the discipline of engineering design research, and the outline of a more coherent discipline of design that emerges is of a discipline that:

- Is human centred and necessarily based on post-positivist perspectives such as constructivism.
- Involves information content and associated theories in a much reduced role.
- Has a structure based on the meta-theoretical relationship between theories of design at different levels of abstraction.
- Has more straightforward relationships between the purpose of the discipline, its ontology and epistemology, its research perspectives and its theories.
- Has external bounds that fit better with other more established disciplines.

5.7 Implications for design education

The word 'discipline' originates etymologically from *discere* - 'to teach' via *discipulus*, 'a disciple' and *disciplina* - 'instruction'. In more modern terms, discipline is 'the studies collectively embraced in a course of learning' (*Webster's Comprehensive Dictionary* 1986). In the terminology of design, research into design necessarily has an educational aspect because 'design practice' is informed by 'design research' and 'design theory' through education grounded in the 'discipline(s) of design'. The analyses of this research extend the role of education in design because of the way that the findings point to learning and education being epistemologically foundational in the human activity of designing. This epistemological extension of the role of

education in design theory is because designers function from experience, that is, it is designer's experiences as individuals that underpin their creativity, intuition, evaluation and analysis via their assumptions, human values and feelings.

In terms of Bastick's (1982) model of intuition, an individual designer's creative acts and decision-making are dependent on their body memory because the embedding of empirical knowledge in the body and brain is necessary for the functioning of the mechanisms of feeling on which intuition and judgement depend. In this sense, the role of design education extends beyond providing design information because what is necessary is for individual designers to acquire physiologically appropriate sets of experiences that will guide their creativity and their use of that design information. Therefore, what is needed is experientially based design education that not only provides the experiences of designing but also supports the student designer's acquisition of experiences that relate particular design details to their social, environmental and ethical consequences.

5.8 Implications for the unification of design theories

Historically, the theories that have emerged as a result of research into design and engineering design have been disparate and substantially unrelated except, in the main, through their positivist foundations (see Chapter 2). This means that it is, and has been, difficult to build theory on theory and research on research or to bring together the theoretical contributions of individual research projects. Resolving this situation involves some measure of unification across the fields of design research, and currently there are three perspectives in the field on this proposal:

1. The unification of design theories is a good idea (see, for example, Dixon 1987; Gregory 1981b; Joseph 1996; Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Nadler 1989; Reich 1995; Talukdar, Rehg and Elfes 1988; Ullman 1992).
2. Design theory is already unified (see, for example, Dixon 1987; Hertz 1992; Hubka and Eder 1988; Pugh 1991; Suh 1990; Yoshikawa 1981).

3. Design theories can never be unified (Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Sargent 1994).

This research contributes to this debate in two ways. Firstly, the analyses of Chapter 2 lead to the conclusion that the unification of design theory has not yet been satisfactorily achieved because existing unified or 'general' theories of design have proven to be unduly dependent on positivism or incomplete in some other manner. Secondly, this research implies that the unification of design theory is possible, in spite of Sargent's argument that design theories are incommensurate. The findings reported in Chapter 4 suggest that the deterministic informatic perspective on which Sargent's argument depends is an insufficient basis for the definition of design, and consequently for prognosis of the possibilities or otherwise of unifying design theory.

The unification of design theory depends on having a primary conceptual basis around which existing and new theory can be arranged by some means of classification. That is, the underlying mechanism for any unification of design theory must have two main attributes:

1. That the unifying concept must be epistemologically fundamental to theories about design.
2. That an adequate means is used for classifying design theories and concepts and the relationships between them.

This research offers both a unifying epistemologically fundamental concept, and a structured means of classifying design theories and concepts and the relationships between them. The analyses and findings of this thesis suggest that the centrality of human activity in the academic study of design offers a suitable unifying concept because what is described as design (in whatever form) always implicates humans, and this, together with the understanding that any theories, theorising or theory interpretation only have meaning in a human context, is an epistemologically well founded basis for the unification of all aspects of the theories and disciplines of design.

The domain independent meta-theoretical perspective and meta-theoretical hierarchical taxonomy developed in Chapter 3 offer the appropriate means of satisfying the second attribute of a means of unifying design theories. The meta-theoretical means of deconstructing and reconstructing design theory, initially developed to provide the better inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors into engineering design theory, has the secondary consequences of grounding design theory in design practice and drawing design theories into coherent theoretical and disciplinary structures. These latter characteristics mean that the meta-theoretical perspective is not only appropriate for the classification of design theories and techniques relating to the activity of designing and information about the designed objects, it also has sufficient epistemological scope to include issues of design education and management.

5.9 Limitations

The ways that this research is intentionally delimited were described in Chapter 1 in section 1.7. The abstraction and philosophical analysis which has been used has been limited to what was considered necessary and sufficient to address the research questions. Many interesting and potentially relevant avenues have been left for another time or for other researchers to pursue. The choice of material to be analysed and the analyses used were deliberately constrained in an attempt to draw out only those aspects which appeared directly relevant to finding a solution to the research questions and resolving the research problem. The post-positivist research perspectives and analytical tools chosen and developed in Chapter 3 use rationalist means and are essentially empirical because they were identified as being the most appropriate means of addressing the research problem (see Chapters 2 and 3). In this sense, this style of research is Popperian, and has the advantage of building on rationalism to provide the necessary language, techniques and concepts to refute inappropriate aspects of existing engineering design theories, and to develop new coherent and well justified theory which permits the inclusion of social, environmental and ethical factors previously excluded by the epistemological limitations of positivism or science.

There are two main limitations to emerge from the epistemological choices that were made in Chapter 3. The first limitation is that the validity of this research cannot be proven except in terms of the correctness of its analyses due to the way that it addresses the research problem by exploring the use of a post-positivist perspective in clarifying and simplifying structural issues in engineering design theory. The most that can be said is that it can be relatively valued and compared to other epistemological approaches in terms of its coherence, elegance, semantic consistency, completeness, and uniqueness against a backdrop of ontological and epistemological clarity and consistency. The second limitation is that, at its epistemological limits, the research perspective used in this thesis does not have the scope of the phenomenological and hermeneutic perspectives that other researchers suggest are better for addressing the detail of the aesthetics of the activity of designing as a subjectively perceived phenomenon, and analysing the human aspects of the ways that theories, information and knowledge are interpreted (Coyne 1990a, 1990c, 1991b; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1991, 1992a, 1992b, 1993, Franz 1994; Reich 1994a).

A bridge exists, however, between the rational empiricist basis of this PhD and phenomenologically and hermeneutically based research due to the inclusion in this research of the feelings, emotions and values of the designer and their effects on the designer's cognition that is the subject of research question 2. By this means, the results of research into the phenomena of designing, as subjectively observed by designers themselves, can be linked with theories about designing based on rational and empirically grounded premises.

5.10 Contributions to knowledge

This research and thesis has resulted in contributions to knowledge in the areas of engineering design research and design research, especially relating to clarifying their epistemological foundations. The main contributions are:

1. Development of a post-positivist research position that enables the inclusion of human aspects of designing that could not be adequately addressed under the dominant positivist perspectives of engineering design research, yet does not exclude well justified positivist or scientific research findings.

2. Significant additional clarification of the epistemological and ontological foundations of engineering design theory.
3. Development of a coherent set of definitions that better differentiate between primary concepts of engineering design research, engineering design theory and design research.
4. Development of a new meta-theoretical perspective based on constructivism and critical analysis that enables several problems of engineering design theory relating to the roles of human valuing and the relative nature of human understanding and cognition, to be analysed.
5. Development of a new meta-theoretical hierarchical structure that enables the classification of elements of engineering design theory according to their level of abstraction. This structure aids the analysis and validation of engineering design theory, and helps define the relationships between different theories and metaphors of design.
6. Useful clarification of the role of the disciplinary structure of engineering design research in the formulation of engineering design theory.
7. Proposals for a disciplinary structure for engineering design research, based on the meta-theoretical relationship between theories of design at different levels of abstraction, whose external bounds align with other more established disciplines. This proposed disciplinary structure results in more straightforward relationships between the purpose of the discipline, its ontology and epistemology, its research perspectives, and its theories.
8. Development of the core of a human-centred basis for engineering design theory that resolves many of the problems with including social, environmental and ethical factors in engineering design theory.
9. Development of a coherent framework of engineering design theory with the following benefits and characteristics:
 - It provides a more coherent and justifiable description of the activity of designing.

- It establishes a philosophically more rigorous basis for the development of design theories, methods, techniques and aids.
- It can incorporate the justifiable knowledge embedded in previous engineering design theory.
- It provides a theoretical basis for the development of design practices and design methods in which social, environmental and ethical factors can be included in creative design activities.
- It is based on post-positivist theories of knowledge.
- Its ontological basis is that of designing as an intrinsically human activity like thinking or feeling.
- It provides a well bounded version of design theory in which most of the activities previously considered to be part of design are relocated back to their original fields of study.
- It places the intelligence of design in humans rather than in external processes or objects.
- It is validated as theory by its coherence with other well-justified theory.
- It is based on the premise that the human internalised management of information is qualitative.
- It assumes the intrinsic inseparability of human values, assumptions, and biases from the activity of designing.
- It provides an epistemologically better justified theoretical means of approaching the design of technology for different societies and cultures because it includes and allows different human values relating to social, environmental and ethical factors into engineering design theory.
- It allows designing to be viewed as both an essentially unobjectifiable internal process, and an observable, objectified external activity.

5.11 Further research

There are several avenues for further research that have emerged from this research. Firstly, is the need for additional research into improvements to the coherency of, and between, design theories, concepts and terminology, especially with respect to epistemological and disciplinary issues.

Secondly, the biological aspects of design cognition are not yet well represented in the literature. Biologically based research into design cognition presents its own epistemological and meta-theoretical issues. For example, if biological or psychoneurophysiological mechanisms are found that define the outcomes of particular aspects of human cognition, then the definitions of creativity that underpin definitions of designing would need to be refined to exclude or incorporate these mechanisms. This is a crucial point in defining the boundaries of design research because it is the purely creative aspects of design that differentiate designing from many other activities.

Thirdly, the literature reviewed in Chapter 2 indicates that psychological research into design is underrepresented in the engineering design research literature. This is surprising because it would be expected that there are many connections to be made between research relating to designers' use of individual internalised 'design worlds', and post-positivist psychological theories relating to creativity, consciousness and altered states of consciousness.

In summary, the three main areas of further research that emerge are:

1. Research that improves the coherency of, and between, design theories, concepts and terminology, especially with respect to epistemological and disciplinary issues.
2. Research into the biological or psychoneurophysiological mechanisms that are the physical aspect of an individual's design cognition.
3. Research that explores the development of theories of design cognition that are coherent with post-positivist psychological theories relating to creativity, consciousness, and altered states of consciousness.

6. Appendix 1: Annotated bibliography relating to definitions of the term ‘design’ 1962–1995.

6.1 Introduction

Within the disciplines of design research and the disciplines in which designing takes place, there have been many attempts to define design, designing and design process. The first wave of publications in this area in English was not seen until the early 1960s, although the groundwork for this interest in design as a focus for research and theorymaking occurred earlier (Jones 1970; Pahl and Beitz 1984). In this appendix, the focus is on how ‘design’ is conceptualised and defined by researchers and theorists. This overview is not intended to be exhaustive, but it is, however, intended to be extensive and to give an adequate representation of the thoughts and writings of those researching into or theorising about engineering design throughout this period. Judgement has been made at various points as to the importance of texts relative to their accessibility. Simaqi (in Shah, 1979, p. 166) offered the following advice around a thousand years ago to those involved in design,

If you take what is relative to be what is absolute, you may be lost. Take nothing, rather than risk this.

Bearing in mind Simaqi’s advice, a relativist perspective on concepts and terminology is used in this review. That is, this review allows that other researchers use terms and concepts in a variety of ways, but analyses the work of others by using the terminology defined in Chapter 1 of this thesis.

The literature being reviewed is from the period 1962 to 1995. The review is undertaken historically, commencing with 1962, and is divided into the periods 1962-1969, 1970-1979, 1980-1989 and 1990-1995. The only significance in this division is that there appear to me to be phases in the literature which change approximately as the decades change. This is supported by Cross (1984, 1993) who also sees trends in design research that change at around the same times. By separating the review at these points it offers the opportunity to comment on any obvious changes in research direction.

6.2 The 1960s: systematic methods, design as a process and the world of the 'artificial'

The first UK conference on design methods in 1962 included papers on many different aspects of the study of designing (Jones and Thornley, 1963). In this first conference there was little attention paid to clarifying basic issues such as what different participants meant by design and it appears to have been considered sufficient, by the participants and organisers, to have established some kind of discussion at whatever level, with whatever content, provided it was related to the designing or planning of technology (Jones and Thornley, 1963). As Jones (1970) was to comment later, 'it was sufficient to know that designing was what architects, engineers, industrial designers and others did in order to produce the drawings needed by their clients and by manufacturers'. In a foreword to the proceedings, Slann (1963) argued that the collected papers might be seen as 'a collection of works of exploration, to test the existence and quality of the "bedrock" on which it is hoped to construct a sound system for design'. There was obviously enough common ground to be built upon by the researchers, although there was little to indicate that the participants of the 1962 conference were addressing problems of epistemology and semantics.

In the same year as this groundbreaking conference, Matousek's (1963) German text on systematic design was translated and edited for the English-speaking market. Unlike the speculative proposals of most English-speaking design theorists, Matousek's text arrived with its theoretical proposals full blown – due to the length of time that the systematic technological design paradigm had been gestating and developing on the Continent and particularly in Germany (Pahl and Beitz 1984). Matousek's work fits coherently with the work of other German researchers in this idiom (see, for example, Eder 1966; Hubka 1985; Hubka and Eder 1988; Pahl and Beitz 1984).

In the following year in Northern America, Alexander (1964) published a detailed description of a deterministic computational method of design that was based on his earlier analysis of the design of an Indian village (Alexander 1963). Alexander viewed design as the activity necessary to match 'form' to its 'context' and used the 'misfit' between form and context as the basis for a

probabilistic computer assisted procedure to decompose a problem into well conditioned sub-problems.

In the UK, research into design proceeded apace after the 1962 conference. There was sufficient progress for another conference in 1965 bringing together the work of design theorists and researchers to provide a 'state of the art' description of this new field (Gregory 1966a). This conference was no small scale academic affair. According to Gregory (1966a), theorists and researchers presented their work at the University of Aston at Birmingham in the UK to an audience of around two hundred persons who were 'drawn from the most diverse branches of technology and design'. The title of the proceedings, 'The Design Method', reflects the focus on method of theorists and researchers at that time (Cross 1984, 1984b, 1993). The papers of this conference show that both design researchers and design theorists were, on one hand, developing techniques aimed at improving design outcomes and, on the other, hoping to discover a theoretical basis for automating design in a way which would replace human designers (Gregory 1966a).

Jones (1966) reviewed design research and his review offers a basis for grouping the definitions of design of that time into the following categories:

- Design as creative activity (see, for example, Broadbent 1966; Jones 1966; Reswick 1965).
- Design as a template for replicating goods or services (see, for example, Asimow 1962; O'Doherty 1966).
- Design as simulation and modelling (see, for example, Booker 1964)
- Design as working in the future with elements of the present (see, for example, Esherick 1963; Jones 1966).
- Design as working with complexity and uncertainty (see, for example, Alexander, 1964; Asimow 1962; Mann 1963; Matchett 1963,).
- Design as scientific activity (see, for example, Broadbent 1966; Eder 1966; McCrory 1966).
- Design as a process (see, for example, Eder 1966; McCrory 1966; Watts 1966)

The definitions of design that emerged in this 1965 conference were often multifaceted. For example, McCrory (1966) defined design in terms of ethics, science and technology:

Design is considered as the process of selectively applying the total spectrum of science and technology to the attainment of an end result which serves a valuable purpose.

Like McCrory, Eder (1966) also implicated science and defined design as,

the use of scientific principles, technical information and imagination in the definition of a mechanical structure, machine or system to perform pre-specified functions with the maximum economy and efficiency.

At the same time, however, Eder also emphasised the human aspect of design stating that 'in essence, it is this human power of imagining something that did not exist before that is termed "design"'. Concluding his review, Jones argued that it is necessary to view design and science as different activities, and suggested that the most promising definition of designing is an artistic one.

As editor of the proceedings of the 1966 conference on 'The Design Method', Gregory provided much of the material linking the work of other contributors and addressing obvious conceptual shortfalls. For example, Gregory's definition of design brought together the work in different domains by proposing that, 'to design is to plan for the fulfilment of human satisfaction' (Gregory, 1966b). The difficulties that researchers found in defining design at this time are indicated by Gregory asking 'What is design?', before circumscribing it without attempting to define it. Later, Gregory showed a preference for a process-based definition of design by focusing on 'design itself as a process', 'design as a psychological process' and design as a sociological process'.

In 1969, MIT Press published Simon's re-envisioning of technological creation, titled *The Sciences of the Artificial*. Grounded in research in the field of artificial intelligence, Simon addressed issues in engineering design theory in a new way, bringing topic areas from the social sciences into centre stage in design theorymaking. In apparent contrast to the vigorously expressed informatic rationalism which underpins the bulk of Simon's work, his definition of design here extended beyond the purely technical (see, for example, Newell and Simon 1972; Simon 1982).

In arguing for a science of the artificial, a science of making artifices, Simon claimed that the activity of design is the core of professional training in all fields and marks out the professions from the sciences. Further, 'everybody designs who devises courses of action aimed at changing existing situations into preferred ones.' This latter definition of design implied that design is essentially a human activity that spans domains and supported arguments for a domain-independent basis for design research.

The role of domain dependency and independency is extensively implicit in the literature in this decade and one obvious attribute of the literature is the way that design is described in similar terms and concepts to those used in the field with which it is associated. This understandable tendency for designers from particular domains, especially engineering domains, to envisage design theory in concepts drawn from those domains is indicated in Eder (1966) and illustrated by Beck's (1966) use of a 'breadboarding' model of designing as the basis for the planning and organisation of the 1965 conference on electronics design. 'Breadboarding' is the colloquial terminology for the development of an ad hoc functional mock-up of an electronic circuit on generic circuitboard material.

In this first decade of modern design research, many authors, in addition to those already mentioned, made important contributions both in rejuvenating traditional engineering design practice with the newfound design methods and in promoting a new perspective on design (see, for example, Archer 1965, 1968; Asimow 1962; Booker 1962; Duggan 1970; Gordon 1961; Mann 1963; Matchett 1963; Middendorf 1969; Moore 1970; Page 1963; Pye 1964; Rapoport 1969; Rittel 1967a, 1967b; Roe, Soulis and Honda 1966). Many of these also created definitions of design as part of developing their new design methods and theories. For example, Middendorf (1969) claimed to define design in the broadest terms as,

The activity wherein various techniques and scientific principles are employed to make decisions regarding the selection of materials and the placement of these materials to form a system or device which satisfies a set of specified and implied requirements.

Middendorf's 'broad' definition appears restrictive and dated compared to the definitions of Jones (1970) and Simon (1969), but underlying it was the assumption that designers should

consider the whole life of a product when designing; that is, raw materials, finished product, product in use, and scrap (salvage) or waste. This perspective predated the contemporary focus on environmentally conscious design through Life Cycle Analysis by a quarter century.

6.3 *The 1970s: domain dependency and independency, 'wicked' problems, intuition*

During the 1970s the terminological and conceptual 'free for all' in engineering design theory continued, but, in England at least, there were differences between the 1970s and the 1960s. In the tertiary teaching of engineering, there were signs of a confidence in the idea of design as a separate subject of study, and several universities changed their syllabi to reflect this change of attitude. For example, Lancaster University offered a 'thin sandwich' engineering course which was multidisciplinary and held together by its focus on designing. This enthusiasm was relatively short-lived, however, and many of these design-based courses evolved back into separate traditional courses in civil, mechanical and electrical engineering. This was perhaps due to problems related to professionalism, along with the difficulties of maintaining the accreditation required by engineering institutions (Langrish 1988; French 1991). This greater credibility of design led eventually, however, to the establishment in the 1980s of tertiary design centres whose focus is mainly postgraduate research relating to engineering design (see, Hills 1995; Sharpe 1993, 1995; Tovey 1995; Wallace and Burgess 1995). The most obvious feeling of the decade of the 1970s was that researching design and developing design methods, although unusual, was, academically at least, a respectable thing to do.

This academic respectability did not, however, extend to the detail of design theory, particularly to a widely-agreed definition of design. There were changes as the decade progressed, and the best choice of boundaries for the discipline of design became more evident. A clear separation started to emerge between those definitions of design that related to design as a human activity and those that defined design as an ahuman process. Much of the research and theorymaking of this decade does not specifically define the term design, and hence it must be inferred from the context. This is difficult because much of the literature of this decade is marked by an epistemological looseness and lack of consistency. These problems are addressed in this review by focusing on the analysis of individual contributions rather than by comparing and

contrasting different aspects of the definition of design across the field. By reviewing individual contributions, the internal inconsistencies in the perspectives that underpin the definitions of design of each can be explored and the outcomes of these explorations can then be classified as the main themes of the decade.

The start of the 1970s was marked by the publication of Jones' *Design Methods*, an influential systematic overview of the design research field from the perspective of method that Gasparski (1995) referred to as the development of a 'methodics' of design (Jones 1970). In Part 1 of *Design Methods*, Jones analysed the activity of designing, discussing how it might be improved, and in Part 2 he collected together the design methods developed up to that time, classified them and discussed their use. In Part 1, Jones argued that there was a diversity of opinion as to what design is, and quoted some definitions:

- *Finding the right physical components of a physical structure*
- *A goal directed problem solving activity*
- *Decision making, in the face of uncertainty, with high penalties for error*
- *Simulating what we want to make (or do) before we make (or do) it as many times as may be necessary to feel confident in the final result*
- *The conditioning factor for those parts of a product which come into contact with people*
- *Engineering design is the use of scientific principles, technical information and imagination in the definition of a mechanical structure, machine or system to perform pre-specified functions with the maximum economy and efficiency*
- *Relating product with situation to give satisfaction*
- *The performing of a very complicated act of faith*
- *The optimum solution to a set of true needs of a particular set of circumstances.*
- *The imaginative leap from present facts to future possibilities.*
- *A creative activity - it involves bringing into being something new and useful that has not existed previously.*

Jones noted the variety in the definitions and surmised that it may be better to look outside them and try to define designing by its results. In a similar manner to Simon (1969), he concluded that design is a means of changing the artificial aspects of the world and devised his 'ultimate' definition of design on the basis that:

The effect of designing is to initiate change in man made things.

Taking this definition, Jones then explored how the definition implicates additional issues and suggested that research into design and the consideration of the implications of that research involve many other disciplines. Jones concluded that,

As soon as we think about this ultimate definition, we see that it applies not only to the work of engineers, architects and other design professionals but also to the activities of economic planners, legislators, managers, publicists, applied researchers, protesters, politicians, and pressure groups who are in the business of getting products, markets, urban areas, public services, opinions, laws, and the like, to change in form and content.

Like Simon (1969) before him, Jones is defining design not in terms of the domain-centred focus of specific professional actions, but in terms of the wider creation and management of the 'artificial' world. In Pacey's (1983) terms, both Jones' and Simon's definitions place design in the wider scenario of human technology practice.

It was at the start of the 1970s that design researchers began to get the measure of the phenomenon of designing and reviewed their use of the simpler systematic outlooks. Researchers began to comment on the complexity of design as a concept. For example, Duggan (1970) pointed out that, 'engineering design is a complex activity which is not easy to define comprehensively'. Taking an overview of designing from what Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin (1992) refer to as a 'Romantic' position on design, Duggan suggested that,

Design is essentially a creative activity, requiring a certain amount of what might be termed native wit. It is this creative aspect which makes it different from most other subjects of engineering science, for it means that there is no unique answer to a specific problem.

Whilst moving from an overview to a more limited specific view, however, Duggan changed direction with his definition, placing it firmly into a framework emphasising analysis,

It (design) requires a systematic and scientific approach (drawing on the engineers knowledge of mathematics, mechanics, stress analysis, manufacturing processes, and mechanical behaviour and properties of materials) and an appreciation of aesthetics and ergonomics . . .

Bringing all of the above aspects of his inquiry together, Duggan moved towards a materialist position and concluded that:

Engineering design is of a complicated nature, involving making decisions based on sound knowledge and good judgement, and the application of analysis and synthesis in transforming an idea into a manufactured component or machine.

Duggan's conclusion echoes Simon's (1969) definition of 'ill-structured' problems and foreshadows the influential, and better argued ideas of Rittel and Webber (1972, 1974, 1984) on 'wicked' problems.

During 1972 and 1973 Rittel and Webber published descriptions of some practical design situations in planning which were not obviously amenable to any amount of 'applying of a systematic perspective' (Rittel and Webber, 1972, 1973). They named this type of problem 'wicked' and described its general characteristics (Rittel and Webber, 1974, 1984). By drawing attention to these 'wicked' problems they effectively extended the definition of design beyond the well-defined and well-structured circumstances that were implicit in many formal theories of design. This outlook, therefore, challenged a discipline of design research based on the development of design methods because it implied that the more designerly problems lay outside what can be addressed via deterministic or systematic design methods. Rittel avoided this crisis, however, by proposing that wicked problems require a new generation of design methods that would be different to those developed during the 1960s (Rittel, 1972a, 1972b, 1984). That is, although the first generation of design theories (i.e. the systematic methods for dealing with fairly well-defined or well-understood engineering problems and the simple process models of design) did not address some design problems, the second (or a later)

generation may well do so. This generational idea was supported by researchers because not only did it free them from attachment to prior methods, it also allowed the focus of design theory-making to remain methodological (Cross 1993). The avoidance of this early crisis in the development of design theory meant that researchers and theorists could also avoid the necessity of reviewing the epistemological and ontological basis of research and theory making relating to the phenomenon of design with all that that implied for defining design. Instead, this generational perspective allowed them to avoid defining design, skirt the philosophical questions, and continue viewing design and design process in terms of the development of design methods based on positivist perspectives.

Rittel and Webber's concept of 'wicked' problems had additional benefits in bounding definitions of design because it differentiated between 'the routine mechanistic definition of determinable solutions to design problems via systematic methods' and 'the human activity of designing that addresses wicked problems that are ill-defined and ill-structured'. This differentiation leads to the possibility of discussing how much the concept of design should encompass each of these situations. Whilst it is almost universally agreed that dealing with 'wicked' problems is an essential aspect of designing, it is not clear that it is appropriate for the term 'design' to also include the routine identification of information that results in the technical definitions needed to produce appropriate artefacts. If this were so, then a stock management system would be a designer.

During the next few years the main trend in the literature of design research was the consolidation of the systematic position. Although Jones, Rittel, Webber and others were already seeing the limitations of systematic methods there remained an almost universally held hope amongst design researchers and theorists for the development of a mathematically definable representation of a design process which would enable the automatic production of optimal design solutions. The following definitions of design from the 1970s show both sides of this situation. On one hand, the theoretically constricting process models of the 1960s and earlier were used as a theoretical base, and, on the other hand, researchers were attempting to define design in a way that offered possibilities for new theory in the future. This combination, whilst providing a conceptual stepping stone, laid the basis of much of the conceptual and

terminological confusion that was forecast by O'Doherty (1963) and identified as an ongoing problem by Hollins (1994), Pugh (1990) and Ullman (1992).

Sensing that the study of designing was being seen as theoretically problematical, that many researchers were attempting to address some of these problems, and that the concept of design was broadening, Spillers (1974) attempted to bring the questions and answers together in 1974 by holding a symposium on the basic questions of design theory at Columbia University, New York. The contributors to this symposium were drawn from diverse technical design domains, but, surprisingly, many of them proposed definitions of design from within the domain of chemical engineering, a field not otherwise renowned for its level of output on design theory. Difficulties were still surfacing, however, in relation to epistemological issues and terminology in particular. These issues were not in the main seen as important in the field, but rather they were viewed as troublesome and unnecessary complications to developing theories of design. For example, Mullen (1974) suggested that it was not necessary to specifically define the term 'design' because,

...the word design is in fact a convenient label, a Lewis Carroll portmanteau, for the early stages of that very complex process which takes place whenever a perceived need is consciously turned into a fulfilled need.

It is not obvious, however, that the use of a word as a label is very different from the ordinary use of a word. The purpose of a label is to describe or classify, and it is necessary to know what a label includes in its description and what it does not. Denigrating the mode of use of the term 'design' does not mean that it becomes semantically insignificant. Similarly, a lack of care about well argued coherent epistemological foundations is found, for example, in Himmelblau (1974) and Director (1974). On one hand, their research focused on developing mathematically based theories of design and design optimisation, whilst at the same time referring to the importance of human creativity and intuition in the resolution of complex design issues.

Himmelblau (1974) focused on process and equipment design in Chemical Engineering and claimed that suitable procedures oriented towards computer implementation of conventional design had been proposed, but not fully tested, in that domain. He addressed the problem of

defining design by circumscribing its context and looking at it from several perspectives, including attempting to identify all the underlying common features of design theory among different disciplines. It appears that Himmelblau was seeking a 'scientific' model of design because firstly, he expressed concern that there did not appear to be a theory of design, in any discipline, which was analogous to the physical theory of conservation of momentum, and, secondly, he discussed mathematically-based optimisation analyses in detail. Himmelblau was also interested in non-routine design problems, and he separated design methods which were used to produce novel designs from those which had more conventional or prosaic results. He concluded, however, that, as far as he could ascertain, no acceptable theory had been suggested for creative or innovative design. Thus, Himmelblau's underlying definition of design is one that has a scientific epistemology for routine design, but, beyond identifying a class of design outcomes as novel, is not otherwise epistemologically or terminologically defined.

Director (1974), from the domain of Electronic Engineering, followed much the same journey as Himmelblau on possible advances in automating design. He suggested that, because there is a uniform mathematical framework in which the analysis of engineering systems can be undertaken, it seemed reasonable that a common mathematical and numerical basis existed for design. By this, Director, like Himmelblau, set his definition of design in a scientific, mathematical, rationalist, empiricist framework. He ignored difficulties of the sort identified by Motard (1974) relating to the phenomenological issues associated with human designers learning about a problem as they synthesise a solution to it. Epistemological contradictions are found in Director's position. Firstly, contradictions exist between his intention to develop scientific, deterministic methods and his understanding that design procedures are not always clearly defined but based on intuition and experience to a large extent. Secondly, his assumption that designing can be computationally modelled is contradicted by his observation that,

Even in automated design the human designer must be actively involved in the design process to make those engineering decisions based upon reasoning which computers are incapable of doing.

The above contradictions imply that Director is using several definitions of design because his implicit definition of design must otherwise be simultaneously deterministic and relativistic, and scientific and imbued with human values. One explanation of Director's position is as follows. Integrated circuit design is concerned with discrete electronic elements whose characteristics and forms can be almost fully modelled mathematically. Hence, electronic devices can be synthesised using one or more of a variety of mathematically-based methods. This provides some practical justification for a mathematical basis for a definition of design in this domain in spite of the epistemological problems.

Graham's (1974) background was in the design of computer-programming languages, which is similar to that of Director in that integrated electronic circuit elements and computer programming elements are both mathematically definable. However, her view of design was very different from Director's. She described programming-language design as very much more an art than a science and emphasised human skills in design rather than the mathematical and quantifiable aspects of design information. For Graham:

Good language design is a somewhat subjective characteristic and even objective criteria are more qualitative than quantitative.

By referring to 'good' design, Graham introduced aesthetic and ethical issues into her definition of designing. Hence, her definition is not only based on design as a human activity but is also underpinned by a qualitative and relativist epistemology.

Although much of the design research in the 1970s is positivist and aims at developing deterministic design theory, Graham's human-centred perspective is also found explicitly or implicitly in almost all of the literature relating to design research in the 1970s. Most commonly, it is allied to a view of designing as 'problem solving'. For example, Wong (1974) discussing bio-engineering design, stated that,

Bio-engineering design . . . is a purposeful activity stemming from our technological culture, with the fulfilling of the ever increasing human needs as its ultimate teleological goal.

and that,

Design may be described simply as a progression from the abstract to the concrete, but it is often thought of as a goal-directed heuristic problem-solving process.

Making problem-solving one of the main aspects of a definition of design automatically brings in issues relating to the characteristics of problems. For example, the picture of design as a human problem-solving activity sketched out by Akin in 1979 segregated designing into 'intuitive' and 'non-intuitive' processes and his separation of the intuitive from the non-intuitive has many connections to 'wicked'/'routine'/'ill-defined'/'ill-structured' classifications of problems.

Thomas and Carroll (1979) focused on design as human problem-solving because of their backgrounds in cognitive psychology. Unlike Akin, they restricted their definition of design to dealing with problems in which 'the goal, the initial condition and the allowable transformations were 'ill-defined'. Their concept of ill-definedness was attributed to Reitmann (1965) and is somewhat similar to the idea of 'wickedness' of Rittel and Webber (1972, 1973, and 1974), but they appear to use the term 'ill-structured' to mean much the same as ill-defined. An important aspect of their definition is the way that they chose to separate 'what is design' from 'what is not design' by considering the implications of how designers look at problems. In defining design Thomas and Carroll argued that,

Much of what we call technological progress may be viewed as a process of rendering ill-structured design problems as more well structured procedures for accomplishing the same ends – without requiring design.

Thomas and Carroll concluded that design is a type of problem solving and that whether it is design or not depends on how the problem-solver treats the situation. That is, design happens when a problem-solver

views his/her problem or acts as though there is some ill-definedness in the goals, initial conditions or allowable transformations'.

This particular outlook leads to a definition of design that is human centred, individualistic and relativistic: a constructivist definition. In addition, and at least as significant, this position leads

to the conclusion that much of what is at present considered design and design research is inappropriately classified as such.

From an architectural perspective, Bazjanac (1974) followed a similar path towards a human centred vision of design that avoided many of the philosophical difficulties associated with both the positivist 'analysis/synthesis/evaluation' models of design process, and the early 'systems' based models of the design (see, for example, Alexander 1964, 1971; Broadbent 1973; Dasgupta 1991; Page 1963; Rittel 1967a, 1967b, 1972b). Bazjanac proposed a definition of design as a learning process in which problem definition, problem solution and documentation cannot be separated. Bazjanac believed that it was Rittel's definition of 'wicked' problems which best casts light on what is wrong with the early models of the design process. In Rittel's terms, Bazjanac saw his learning model of design process as a second generation model. This puts Bazjanac's outlook in the same class as the perspectives that underpin the 'wicked' models of Rittel and Webber (1973) and the later 'Pattern Language' models of Alexander and associates (Alexander et al. 1977; Alexander 1979). This definition of 'design as learning' is one of the early pointers to the later 'reflective' definitions and theories of design of Schön (Schön 1983, 1984, 1987, 1992; Schon and Wiggins 1992).

Motard (1974) assumed a human perspective on design and differentiated between routine and inventive design. He suggested that successful routine designs emanated from imaginative and informed people steeped in the technological state of the art in which they operate. Inventive design he regarded differently and echoing Bazjanac stated that,

Design by invention is a learning process design as a human activity includes behavioural phenomena as well as cognitive inputs.

Motard also differentiated between design and analysis. He regarded design as innovation or invention where, 'design as an engineering art is certainly more than the application of scientific and technological concepts'. By contrast and where analysis is an essential but different activity that is part of evaluation. He suggested that the benefits of computers in design lies not in their potential for generating new designs, but as a means of emphasising and developing human

professional judgement. Motard's discussions relating to these side issues confirm his position on design as an essentially human phenomenon.

Powers and Rudd (1974) took a similar human-centred position to Motard and also differentiated between routine and non-routine design. They based their position on research into improving design outcomes in chemical engineering, reporting that the outcomes of this research had been more successful when applied to automating the analysis of processing systems rather than improving understanding of the design of the basic configuration of such systems. At that time, this latter problem of the choice of processing system and its basic configuration was not a routine problem, and depended on human intuition and judgement.

The management of design, particularly in commercial situations, formed the basis of several definitions of design. For example, Leech (1972) took an instrumental view of the role of the designer within a business perspective, and emphasised the commercial situation of designing. He suggested that the best designer is one who makes the most profit for the employer. Leech avoided defining design directly and instead characterised it in terms of the following circumstances,

- *Having a customer who wants something and is prepared to pay for it.*
- *A manufacturing organisation which will make what the customer wants and sell it to him.*
- *A designer who supplies the manufacturer with what instructions are necessary to manufacture his product.*

The definition of design implicit in the above circumstances is one that is instrumental and informatic. Essentially, Leech's definition of design is whatever process produces the information necessary to manufacture a product for which a customer pays. In Leech's sense of design, the activity of designing overlaps with market research.

Contrasting with Leech's commercial view is the management view of design proposed by Siddall (1972). From this perspective, Siddall inferred that design consists of four main components; identification of need, innovation, decision making and detail design. The domain-

based nature of Siddall's view is shown by the way that these four components reflect the roles of departments in many organisational structures.

Three years later, in the area of planning and management, Ostrofsky (1977) argued for a similar view of design to that used by Jones (1970) and Simon (1969). He used the following definition drawn from Webster's International Dictionary:

Design is defined as purposeful planning as revealed in, or inferred from the adaptation of a means to an end or the relation of parts to a whole...

Ostrofsky suggested that designing and planning should be considered synonymous, and proposed the title of designer-planner. In Ostrofsky's words,

The lack of interchange between planners and designers is anomalous. If planning and designing include the same basic processes, the methods of each should be applicable to the other.

Ostrofsky's definition of design is filled out by his picture of the designer-planner as one who moves to meet a need in the most effective manner possible. He argued that the designer-planner must have much the same mastery over disciplinary content as a scientist but must have additional skills.

The designer-planner must achieve a useful solution to meet the needs within his resources even though absolute rigour may be (and often is) sacrificed for the good of overall performance.

This predates Pugh (1989) in trading scientific correctness for pragmatic gains and extends Ostrofsky's definition of design beyond the scientific. The underlying definition of design that is found in Ostrofsky's proposals is human-centred problem-solving and includes an ethical element via the 'purposefulness' of the planning.

In summary, the main points that emerged in the explicit and implicit definitions of design found in the design research literature of the 1970s relate to:

- Human aspects of designing including creativity, inventiveness and intuition.

- Characteristics of problems including 'wickedness', ill- defined and ill-structured.
- Routine and non-routine aspects of designing.
- Commercial and management aspects of design theory.

The end of the decade of the 1970s marked a new phase for design research in the UK. In 1979 the Design Research Society started the journal *Design Studies*. It was intended to be the international forum for research into technological design. The first edition marked another new beginning: that design should be a discipline itself rather than being seen as a subsidiary aspect of many other disciplines. Gregory (1979), as editor, argued that,

One of the principal assumptions behind the launching of this new journal is that Design can be identified as a subject in its own right, independent of the various areas in which it is applied to practical effect.

Yet all this was proposed without a definition of design that was epistemologically coherent and well-agreed across the field.

In essence, the literature of the 1970s shows that design researchers made token efforts to define the concept of design whilst they explored the practical aspects of building theories but neglected epistemological and terminological difficulties relating to fundamental concepts.

6.4 The 1980s: design as information processing, design as problem-solving, design management, designing as an aspect of being

The start of the 1980s was the start of the public face of the study of design as described in the first edition of *Design Studies* (Editorial 1979). Computer assistance for designers was now well known if not available on many designer's desktops. Later in the decade, with the widespread proliferation of personal computers, computer aided drafting (CAD) became de rigeour for many designers, particularly in Engineering and Architecture. The onset of the computerisation of drawing, together with use of computers for computationally complex tasks and for managing large amounts of data, led to changes in the direction of research into engineering design towards a focus on manipulating and transforming information. These areas became the 'preoccupations of the scientific research community' at that time (Lera, Cooper and Powell

1984). Those involved in research into design in this period were to see the implementation of expert systems, knowledge based systems, design decision support systems and a burgeoning connection between the 'design of the artefact' and its manufacture through the bringing together of CAD and computer aided manufacturing (CAM) into the catch all 'computer aided engineering' (CAE). Many of these systems were implemented on readily available computers at prices that were acceptable to most technical organisations. These developments are most readily found in the literature of engineering design research, perhaps because engineering design lent itself more readily to the application of computers. The proceedings of two of the more significant design research events in the 1980s, the *International Symposium on Design and Synthesis* in 1985 and the *International Conference on Engineering Design* in 1989 illustrate the breadth of this trend towards informatic computational perspectives on design.

The International Symposium on Design and Synthesis (ISDS) of 1985 in Tokyo was a milestone in the collecting together of the state of the art in design theory in the 1980s. Although restricted in its outlook, it captured the mood of technological design theory at that time. An overview of the topics indicates that the proceedings were drawn from around one hundred and twenty papers of which more than one hundred described advances in engineering theory and technological advances. Although most of the remaining papers related to engineering design theory, the majority of these described technical aids for designers. Few were concerned with epistemological issues relating to design research or developed design theory in the sense that it is defined in Chapter 1 of this thesis. In part, this imbalance towards engineering issues appears to be due to the domain distribution of the contributors to this symposium because they were drawn almost exclusively from the field of mechanical engineering. This is considerably different to the *Symposium on Basic Questions of Design Theory* in 1974 in which the papers reflected a wider range of technological domains. According to Yoshikawa (1985), this bias towards mechanical engineering is a consequence of the interests of organisations that sponsored the conference, in which case, it may have been academically more satisfactory if the title of the symposium had reflected this limitation.

The proceedings of ISDS provide strong evidence of the trend in the 1980s towards an information-processing focus for research into designing. Yoshikawa (1985), chairman of the

symposium, noted that information-processing had become an issue in design by the mid-1980s because, by then, designers needed to use computers, or, more specifically, to process information. He suggested that those involved in information-processing had begun to view designing as one of the typical intelligent processes of the brain, and many of the papers at this symposium came from perspectives that were closely related to those used in research into artificial intelligence. That is, they either proposed that design is information-processing or they described techniques developed from this field for use in designing. What was not evident in the papers of this symposium, however, was an understanding that there are important epistemological differences between viewing information-processing as a tool to be used by designers, and viewing designing as information processing. Hegemonic analysis of the situation suggests that the development of information-processing techniques by those most involved in design research leads, in turn, to defining design in a manner which supports the acceptance of these information-processing techniques.

Another major element of the literature on engineering design of this period is the proceedings of the International Conferences on Engineering Design. These international conferences, which started in Rome in 1981, are organised by the WDK (Workshop-Design-Konstruktion) group founded by Hubka with support from Eder and Andreasen (Wallace and Burgess 1995).

Although WDK organise the ICED conferences and the main publisher for the WDK group is Heurista in Zurich, the proceedings of ICED are published by a variety of organisations, for example, ICED 87 was published by the American Society of Mechanical Engineers; ICED 1989, which Hollins (1994) considers the best of these conferences, was sponsored by Institution of Mechanical Engineers, UK and the proceedings were published by MEP Ltd, their publishing arm. There were ninety seven papers included in the proceedings of ICED 89 which were grouped by the organisers into seven main categories,

- Keynote papers (4 papers).
- Management (27 papers).
- Methods (27 papers).
- Computer Application (9 papers).

- Education (19 papers).
- Reliability (3 papers).
- Information (7 papers).
- Late papers (1) by Hubka, on 'quality in design', which would otherwise have been placed either in 'Management' or 'Methods'.

As can be seen from the above list of categories there were no papers dealing specifically with the philosophy of design, design theory or epistemological issues in design theory. There was a considerable amount of theorising of one form or another in the proceedings, but the confusion between engineering theory and engineering design theory was widespread. The term 'design theory' was not only loosely applied to engineering theory, but was also applied to a variety of theories from other disciplines that had a connection with designing. For example, theories of management relating to design situations became design theories, and, similarly, 'information theories', 'marketing theories', 'psychological theories' and even 'social theories' were passed off as design theories.

In spite of the wide variety of disciplines involved with the creation of technological artefacts, ICED 89, like the *International Symposium on Design and Synthesis* was dominated by papers with a mechanical engineering focus. This cannot be attributed to a possibility that it is only mechanical engineers who are interested in engineering design because engineering design research from other domains was being published elsewhere (see, for example, Altshuller 1984; Cross 1984; Langrish 1988; Lera 1981a, 1981b; McDermott 1982; Nadler 1989; Parnas and Clements 1986; Wilde 1983). What it does indicate is that the organisers, WDK and the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, were unable or unwilling to attract papers on design from other technological domains. This is unfortunate on two counts. Firstly, some other domains have a strong history of design theorisation and, secondly, the rich picture offered by the contrasts in the paradigms of design research of differing domains was not available. In the following reviews, the focus is on the definitions of design that underpin the arguments, research and theoretical proposals of the authors.

Haugen (1980) took a socially beneficent view that to design was 'to formulate a plan for the fulfilment of a human need'. He focused on mechanical engineering design and regarded it as being concerned particularly with component strength, stiffness, thermal behaviour and economic factors. Implicit in his perspective was the assumption that theories of mechanical engineering design should be based on physics, mathematics, engineering science and engineering theory. Haugen's main proposal was probabilistic theory of design which required that all design factors be expressed in quantitative form, and assumed that structural design is the most significant aspect of designing in the mechanical engineering domain. Haugen's theory is suited, for example, to analysing the probabilities relating to the difference between the stresses in a component and the actual strength of that component. In terms of the definitions of Chapter 1 of this thesis, Haugen's theory is an engineering theory rather than a design theory.

Dieter (1983) noted that there are numerous definitions of design, and argued that Webster's dictionary definition 'design is to fashion after a plan' is incomplete as it does not include the temporal idea that to design is to create something that has never been. That is, that,

Design establishes and defines solutions to and pertinent structures for problems not solved before, or new solutions to, problems which have previously been solved in a different way.

Dieter's definition is positivist and deterministic because of its dependence on analysis and synthesis.

Clausing and Ragsdell (1985) also emphasised 'synthesis' in the sense of 'the assembling of separate or subordinate parts into a new form' (*Webster Comprehensive Dictionary* 1986) in describing their understanding of what design is. This position on synthesis led them naturally to a definition of design which implied that all products are assemblies of independent sub-systems and, consequently, that design is a constructive activity where previously disassociated elements are brought together to form that which previously did not exist.

Spur, Krause and Dassler (1985) defined the *act* of designing as the processing of geometry under functional and physical demands to find an optimal solution under the given

circumstances. There are, however, epistemological difficulties about equating the concept of an 'act' – presumed to be human from its context – and the idea of a 'complex processing of geometric data'. An important difference is that 'complex processing' is something that may be undertaken in a variety of ways by a variety of means but an 'act' must be done by a human being. To co-join them in the sense that an 'act' is identical to a 'process' is to take away or ignore some of the difference in meaning that the terms 'act' and 'process' indicate. This difference in meaning reveals the hidden and inappropriate epistemological shift that enabled Spur, Krause and Dassler to equate 'the human act of designing' and the potentially mechanisable 'design as processing of geometry' to support the development of a computerised model of designing.

Hubka (1985) defined engineering design from an information-processing perspective as 'a process in which the designed problem (based on demands) is transformed into a description of technical systems (technical product)'. Hubka also assumes that designing is an activity undertaken by humans and therefore his process based definition of designing is subject to the same epistemological criticism as that laid against Spur, Krause and Dassler above. This epistemologically inconsistent situation in which researchers assume or define design as both a human activity and a mechanisable process is widespread. It depends on a positivist approach to design research that excludes many of the epistemologically and conceptually essential aspects of designing. The arguments as to why the positivist position is insufficient and inappropriate to design research are described in detail in Chapters 1, 2 and 3 of the thesis. For brevity, these issues are not discussed further in this appendix and it is assumed that they apply whenever design is defined in positivist, scientific or deterministic terms.

In 1981 Yoshikawa proposed a mathematical theory of design which he called 'General Design Theory' (GDT). GDT moved the focus of the definition of design to the finite attributes of the designed object rather than the activity of designing, and thus effectively excluded human action from the definition of design. GDT has practical benefits as an information theory or an engineering theory in terms of adding value to information and supporting the development of computerised engineering assistance for designers. The main theoretical benefit of the ahuman perspective of GDT is that it offers an intimate correspondence between the concepts and

theories of artificial intelligence, knowledge engineering, computer aided design and design, but its claim as a theory of designing is epistemologically limited by being unable to address the more human issues of design cognition (Reich 1995; Tomiyama and Yoshikawa 1985).

Wallace and Hales (1989) identified research areas in engineering design on the basis of the information-processing paradigm described by Yoshikawa (1984). For Wallace and Hales, designing was seen as transforming information and from this point of view the purpose of design research was to provide 'structured knowledge which can be used by design engineers'. Their perspective on design was that of a mechanically-defined rational designer applying transformations that are definable in prescriptive and normative terms to descriptive information about 'specifications of needs' in order to create 'specifications of solutions'.

Wallace and Hales' model of design did not include the role of human valuing in conceptualisation, interpretation, creation, evaluation or decision-making. The definition of design that underlies Wallace and Hales' work is positivist, mechanistic and informatic in the sense that design is the logical and deterministic transformation of objectively defined information.

The description of design proffered by Hongo (1985) echoed that of Tomiyama and Yoshikawa (1985) and Hubka (1985) with respect to design as knowledge processing and the use of a model of design based on mathematical set theory. Hongo's analyses place him firmly in the logical positivist camp because he defined 'theory of design' as design science or the scientific study of design activities, and claimed that he identified his theory of design as a description of truth from (sic) design activities. There are many parts of Hongo's paper which are written in a manner which requires interpretation, and some parts which appear not to make sense. For example, defined within his 'design science' is the sub-category 'technical information of design science' which tautologically includes the 'theory of design processes'. Hongo's position presents some epistemological inconsistencies. Firstly, his observation that intuitive designing is a very powerful method which should not be disturbed by forced methodologies does not accord with his insistence on an all-inclusive scientific paradigm of design research that does not include intuitive designing. Secondly, a further contradiction exists between his argument that designing consists of unconscious and conscious activities because it is not obvious how

Hongo proposed to define these scientifically. In summary, Hongo's definition(s) of design are contradictory and reflect the underlying epistemological difficulties with trying to simultaneously recognise that design is a human activity, with all that that entails about human values and the internal workings of the human psyche, and hold that design can be described as logically definable in mathematical or scientific terms

In contrast to the mathematical theorisation of Hongo, Andreasen's (1985) underlying definition of design was based on Danish designers' practical experience with systematic methods of design. In Denmark, according to Andreasen, design is seen as both problem-solving and, unusually, as an integrated product development process. This combination necessitates a broader definition of design than otherwise. Definitions that relate purely to problem-solving can more justifiably adopt a mechanistic and deterministic approach, but integrating design into the product development process implies the inclusion of those human considerations that enable value judgements to be made. This latter corresponds with Lyle (1985) who contrasted science and design, and claimed that, unlike science, 'design is ultimately an integrative activity'. Andreasen's description of the Danish perspective on design has many similar characteristics to the concept of Total Design developed by Pugh (1991) which emerged fully developed some five years later but which is apparent in Pugh and associates earlier work at about the same time as Andreasen's text (see, for example, Hollins and Pugh 1989; Pugh 1985; Pugh and Morley 1989).

Dittmayer and Sata (1985) also described the use of systematic product development that was integrated to some extent into the product-development process, in this case, at the University of Tokyo. They used an axiomatic model of design similar to that later described by Suh (1990), but ascribed it to Glegg (1971), and linked it to a model of planning to provide a system to support decision-making in design by choosing the details of the design process. This is an unusual theoretical step because in this Dittmayer and Sata allowed that there might be many different design processes that could be used in designing, whereas most authors define a particular model of design process that relates to their particular definition of design. Their inclusion of 'planning the design process' introduces a meta-analysis, and adds additional conceptual and cognitive levels to their model. The 'design process planning model' Dittmayer

and Sata used resembled many of the design process models of the previous twenty years, but was differentiated from them by the inclusion, of a data or 'a-priori knowledge' store. The inclusion of this store moves the emphasis of their model towards the cybernetic system and information-processing perspectives on design. By the above means, however, Dittmayer and Sata avoided treating all aspects of design in the same way and thus pioneered the clarification of epistemological issues via meta-theoretical analysis in order that each of these different aspects might be addressed in an epistemologically appropriate manner. In essence, Dittmayer and Sata's definition of design is primarily rationalist and consequently has the contradictions described earlier in relation to the human aspects of designing. It divides design into epistemologically different aspects, however, and this points to the possibility of resolving some of the conceptual contradictions.

The outlooks developed by Dittmayer and Sata above fit well with Slusher, Ebert and Ragsdell's (1989) proposals for improving the management of design. They suggested classifying design situations into incremental design, complex design, creative design and intensive design, and argued that these situations should be managed differently because they represent different creative contexts of artefact and problem situations. Dittmayer and Sata's approach is useful because it provides the basis for developing appropriate design processes that suit each situation. From a perspective of design research, however, if Slusher, Ebert and Ragsdell address these situations differently it implies that they are using different theoretical perspectives on design. Hence, definitions of design that are different in detail.

The most comprehensively developed systematic basis for designing is the German VDI 2221 design guidelines. Ehrlenspiel and Dylla (1985, 1987) used these as the basis for their theories of design. They based their theories on the analysis-synthesis-evaluation definition of design implicit in VDI 2221, and identified, collected and classified their experimental data in terms of the same definition. By using this experimental process they excluded the possibility of identifying and collecting information that would contradict their thesis about what design is. It is not obvious that Ehrlenspiel and Dylla identified this difficulty. Similar underlying epistemological problems relating to the definition of design can be found in the work of Salminen and Verho (1989), which was also based on the German model of systematic design.

The broad picture of engineering design, as what happens between identifying a potential need and supplying it profitably, was synchronistically developed by several design researchers in the late 1980s. Neilsen and Valbak (1989) developed a means of defining design by classifying design activity. They used a wide ranging industrial perspective and, from this perspective, derived a model of design that focused on the dynamics of the design situation and included,

- The areas of design and production.
- Strategic, tactical and operational levels.
- The positioning of any act with respect to what it depends on in the past and what it influences in the future.
- The way that 'actors', consumers and those passively involved result in co-ordinated joint activity and its consequences.
- The way that development acts on and in the environment.

By opening out the perspective of what is involved in designing and drawing attention to the temporality of the relationships involved, Neilsen and Valbak offered a new perspective on designing which sits on the boundary between positivist and post-positivist positions. The above perspectives imply a constructivist definition of design as a human activity, yet, at the same time, focus on the details of problems, solutions, contexts, situations and processes. These factors suggest that their position has internal contradictions on the lines argued by Dilnot (1982) (see Chapter 2). There are some similarities between Neilsen and Valbak's view, and Stauffer's (1989) emphasis on the domain-independent nature of design in that the 'dynamic approach' of Nielsen and Valbak and the idea of 'domain independence of designing' both depend on dealing with aspects of designing which cannot easily be described, or manipulated by mechanistic models of design activity.

Eder (1989) continued the 'design is information processing' theme and proposed the following definition of engineering design that connects needs to solutions from that standpoint:

Engineering design is a process performed by humans aided by technical means through which information in the form of REQUIREMENTS is converted into information in the form of descriptions of TECHNICAL SYSTEMS, such that this technical system meets the needs of mankind.

The model of design process on which he based this premise relegates other factors involved in design to sub-systems acting as operators on the above forms of information. Eder defined design as a 'process performed by humans' and his focus was on identifying the external details of that process as perceived from an informatic perspective. This view of design, however, neglects all those aspects of designing that are internal to the human designer and on which externally observable process depends. That is, Eder has focused on what happens to information, an engineering issue, rather than the human activity. In this sense, it may be more appropriate that Eder's theories are classified under engineering research rather than design research.

A pragmatic definition of engineering design that was based on planning and management considerations was provided by Coplin (1989):

Engineering design is essentially a detailed planning process backed by analysis and demonstration. It is used to control the means by which we satisfy both customer and shareholder.

Coplin's definition is instrumental in that it defines design as a process that is used to control. By this, Coplin does not exclude human participation in that process but he has defined engineering design in terms of that a human process rather than the human activity.

Rhodes and Smith (1989) provided an almost identical definition of design in their work and although both the theories of Coplin (1989), and Rhodes and Smith (1989) predate Pugh (1991) and his development of 'Total Design' they are obviously similar in direction and content. Phrases characteristic of Pugh's work on Total Design occur frequently and diagrams of a similar structural format are used. Rhodes and Smith viewed design as,

The total activity necessary to provide an artefact to meet a market need that commences with the identification of that need and is not complete until the product is in use, providing an acceptable level of performance.

This definition precludes any inclusion within the design process of disposal of the used artefact or for full life-cycle design within a wide-scale ecological framework. That is, their definition, although providing a basis for the definitions of 'Eco-Design' and similar environmentally focused developments in design theory, has insufficient scope to include their implementation.

French (1985) offered a definition of design that focused on the form of the product and this reflects his mechanical engineering background.

'Design' is taken to mean all the process of conception, invention, visualisation, calculation, marshalling, refinement, and specifying of details which determines the form of an engineering product.

In spite of this focus on form and the 'needs' that necessitate its creation, French's definition has a similar conceptual breadth to the theories of Andreasen (1985) and Pugh (1991), but does not extend into the detail of the manufacturing, sales and management arenas in the way of those other proposals. French discussed the role of conceptual design 'schemas' in design theory and tied the values of these schemas to the overarching commercial purpose of design, maintaining that:

A scheme should be sufficiently worked out in detail for it to be possible to supply approximate costs, weights and overall dimensions, and the feasibility should have been assured as far as circumstances allow.

French's definition of design is functional and pragmatic. From his position, the purpose of defining design is to develop conceptual and mathematical tools and analyses that can aid designers, and it is sufficient for these purposes to define design in terms of 'needs' and 'solutions' (see, for example, French 1985, 1988). In this sense, French's definition of design does not directly relate to the concepts of design theory and design research as defined in Chapter 1 of the thesis because in most cases French's focus is on information about the physical attributes

and behaviour of objects. French's outlook was later to form the basis of a well-funded research program to develop 'Schemebuilder', a computerised expert system intended to assist with the conceptual design of mechanical and mechatronic devices (French 1990; Oh, Langdon and Sharpe 1994; Sharpe 1995).

In a similar manner to French (1985), Starkey (1988) put the focus on design as dealing with problems and 'needs'. He defined design as follows,

It [design] is the recognition and understanding of a basic need and the creation of a system to satisfy that need. Put more simply, design is problem finding followed by problem-solving.

Later, Starkey changed tack to an educational model of design in which 'design is a learn-by-doing activity'. Starkey's definition of design is essentially human-focused and tightly tied to the problem-based theories of cognition.

Lewis and Samuel (1989) followed Starkey (1988) in focusing on 'problem-solving' and 'needs' as the main characteristics of their view of engineering design. Their definition echoes that of Duggan (1970) with respect to its mention of the complexity of design, and extends to a stance very close to that proposed by Coplin (1989) above. Lewis and Samuel concluded that, in general, design is 'directed towards satisfying some human want or need' and defined engineering design as follows:

Engineering design is a complex problem-solving activity. In essence it comprises the planning of engineering systems, devices, products and components in order to satisfy some human need.

The 1980s focus on information in design research necessitated and allowed advances in mathematics as the 'needs', processes and technical outcomes of design became specified in quantitative physically measureable terms. In 1989, Arora created 'Optimum Design', a mathematically based design method for optimising the design outcomes of engineering systems. For Arora, the formulation of an optimum design problem involves,

Transcribing a verbal description of the problem into a well defined mathematical statement.

This mathematical vehicle for modelling engineering design activity constrained his theoretical picture, or definition, of what design is because all variables or constraints which impinge on the specification of the designed object must be defined in a numeric manner. There are epistemological problems with this perspective because many aspects of situations are not only difficult or impossible to quantify. These are problems that apply to any perspective on design based on positivism. Arora's method also has problems with satisfying its main aim, design optimisation, because multi-attribute and multi-objective optimisation become problematic with more than one optimisation parameter, especially if they are dependent. In Arora's words,

In other situations, there may appear to be two or more cost functions. These are called 'multi objective design optimisation problems'. There is no general and reliable method for solving such optimum design problems . . .

Further epistemological contradictions in Arora's view of design exist between his quantitative method and his conviction that engineering design depends on human designers: 'The designer's experience, intuition and ingenuity are required in the design of systems in most fields of engineering'. Arora's design theory is an engineering theory and by classifying it as such many of the epistemological difficulties disappear.

Corrigan and Morris (1989) had a similar interest in finding optimal solutions to problems, an area of endeavour that, like Arora, they called 'Optimum Design'. Their methods were explicitly directed at providing better information to the designer by using mathematical modelling techniques. Their methodic perspective lay in systems theory and from a systems standpoint they stated that, 'design is an iterative process'. To this point, they are epistemologically consistent in defining design as a process that does not exclude the possibility that humans undertake it and that design methods are aimed at adding value to the information that designers use. This epistemological consistency is disturbed when they apply a value-free systems engineering model to their interpretation of the design process. This 'value-free'

assumption was contradicted by the inclusion of human values that is implicit in their view that,

Engineers strive to design the best systems and, depending upon the specifications, best can have different connotations for different systems. In general it implies cost effective, efficient, reliable and durable systems.

Therefore the definition of design that underlies the position of Corrigan and Morris is systematic, human, and informatic but excludes those aspects of human functioning that Rosen (1980) viewed as fundamental to creativity and synthesis.

Langrish (1988) discussed similar epistemological difficulties to those that underlie the proposals of Arora and Corrigan and Morris with respect to design and technology transfer. 'Technology transfer' is used by Langrish to describe the adoption of new or different technology by any society or individual, sometimes also referred to by others as 'innovation' (see, for example, Beitz 1989; Roy 1993). From the perspective of chemical engineering, Langrish defined design as the creative and synthetic aspect of technology development. He argued that design was often mistakenly regarded as being analytical, and that this was due to societal and professional hegemonic pressures promoting analysis in such a manner that it discouraged the development of synthetic or creative approaches. Langrish's definition of 'synthesis' as 'building out of elements' is exact for design in the chemical industry, and this explains his inclusion of creativity alongside synthesis in his definition of design.

The dichotomies of value-free/value-laden, human activity/ahuman process, and creative/routine are part of the difficulties in establishing an epistemologically coherent structure for an independent discipline of design. A seasoned campaigner in the problems of design theory, Cross (1989) avoided defining design directly. He circumnavigated the difficulties of definition by reviewing common properties of design problems which is, however, tantamount to proposing that design problems should be the focus of design theory. He suggested that most design problems are similar because,

- *They have a goal.*

- *Some constraints within which the goal is to be achieved.*
- *Criteria for recognising successful designs.*

Later, Cross (1989) had design as 'working with ill-defined problems' and characterised it in similar manner to Rittel and Webber's (1972, 1973, 1974, 1984) analyses relating design to 'ill-structured problems'. For Cross, the characteristics of ill-defined problems are,

- *No definite problem formulation.*
- *Any problem formulation may embody inconsistencies.*
- *Formulation of the problem is solution dependent.*
- *Proposing solutions is a means of understanding the problem.*
- *There is no definitive solution to the problem.*

Implicit in Cross' analyses is a definition of design as a human intentional activity that uses essentially human attributes along with intellectual and practical tools to solve problems that are not readily determinable in that situation. In this sense, Cross' perspective is a development of that expressed earlier by Thomas and Carroll (1979).

For a variety of reasons, many researchers followed the pattern of the 1960s and 1970s and did not define design or defined it in part. For example, Waldron (1989), using a critical methodology in a similar way to that proposed by Franz (1994), avoided defining design in his experimental investigation into how human designers interpret design specifications.

Biggioggero and Rovida (1985) offered to describe a means of dealing with qualitative factors in mechanical design but did not do so, and in part this was due to an inadequate underlying definition of design. Eversheim, Abolins and Buchholz, (1985) changed the scope of their definition of design in mid-stream from meaning 'everything to do with designing' (when they speculated on their CAD system's potential) to 'design is drafting' when they reported what had actually been developed.

The foregoing presents the mainstream of definitions of design in the 1980s. In this period, however, a few researchers presented arguments that suggest that the mainstream was

misdirected. In outline, these arguments are that it is inappropriate to define design in terms of objects, problems and processes, and that design can only be defined and researched in terms of its human situation. For example, Dilnot (1982) argued that the subject of research, i.e. designing, is lost to view and epistemologically neglected or excluded from the research investigation when design is defined in terms of information about a designed object, or a problem that is being solved, or a process of designing. For Dilnot, 'design is a social activity' and designing must be seen as a human activity that is essentially socially situated.. The structural conclusion implied by Dilnot's arguments is that the relationship between design and technology must be reversed, and that technology is a subset of design. That is, instead of viewing design as a technological activity, technology practice should be viewed as but one of the activities of designing. The substance of Dilnot's arguments are supported in parts by a variety of sources (see, for example, Abel 1981; Alexander 1980; Daley 1982; Holt, Radcliffe and Schoorl 1985; Jones 1984; Robinson 1986; Thomas and Carroll 1979). Jones (1984) suggested that design can be seen as an activity of designing 'without a product', and pointed to a post-positivist future for design research in which he sketched a definition of designing as a way of being. This definition includes and extends Dilnot's definition of design as a social activity because it is claiming that designing is an essential aspect of being human. The difference between the two positions is similar to that between defining an activity as (say) 'running', and defining an activity as 'movement'. 'Running' is a particular human activity that is happening or not, and this parallels Dilnot's position. 'Movement', however, is something intrinsic to humans in that humans only stop moving when dead, and this parallels Jones perspective that designing is an undercurrent in all human action. Both point foreshadowed to the 1990s when, for example, Coyne and Snodgrass (1993) argued that Continental philosophy provides a better basis for design research and theory-making.

In summary, the 1980s continued the lack of attention of the 1970s and 1960s to the epistemological and conceptual foundations of design research. The term 'design' was explicitly and implicitly defined in many different ways. When it was defined, it was done opportunistically in the sense that researchers addressed the conceptual confusion by including in their work a definition of design that supported it. The systematic outlook on design

remained strong and it is clear that much engineering design research was grounded in definitions of design that were based on engineering rather than human designing. A similar situation existed where design was viewed in terms of its management and its commercial context. The informatic perspective on design evolved in the 1980s to become the dominant view, yet the epistemological justification of this informatic outlook was contradicted in many cases by researchers simultaneously acknowledging that designing depended on humans or was a fundamentally human activity. This epistemological contradiction between definitions of design as a human activity and definitions of design based on other premises exists in most of the literature, and in most cases remained unresolved. The exceptions pointed to design being a fundamental aspect of social and individual human functioning, and consequently implied that research into design that is based on informatic premises or the details of the relationships between problems and solutions is more appropriately viewed as engineering or science research.

6.5 1990–1995: the computer in design, artificial intelligence in design, Total Design, Eco-Design, the philosophy of design

In the half decade between 1991 and 1995, the publishing of papers and books related to engineering design proceeded apace. In the first half of the 1990s much of the design research was developed with computerisation in mind, and this research direction was supported by extensive contributions from the areas of artificial intelligence and architecture (see for example, Adelman, Gualtieri and Riedel 1994; Adie 1994; Akin 1992; Akin and Lin 1995; Beñares-Alcántara 1991; Bullock, Denham, Parmee and Wade 1995; Brown and Hwang 1993; Chakrabarti and Bligh 1994; Chandrasekaran 1990; Coyne 1990b, 1991a; Coyne and Newton 1990; Coyne, Newton and Sudweeks 1993; Coyne, Rosenman, Radford, Balachandrian and Gero 1990; Coyne and Snodgrass 1993; Coyne and Yokozawa 1992; Cross 1991; Cross, Dorst and Roozenburg 1992; Dasgupta 1991, 1992; Dym 1994; Faltings 1991; Fenves and Grossman 1992; French 1990; Gero 1991; Gero and Maher 1993; Hertz 1992; Hillier and Penn 1994; Hills 1995; Hoover, Rinderle and Finger 1991; Hubka and Eder 1990; Konda, Monarch, Sargent and Subrahmanian 1992; Logan, Millington and Smithers 1991; Lowe 1994; Mitchell 1993; Mullins and Rinderle 1991; Oh, Langdon and Sharpe 1994; Otto and Antonsson 1994; Oxman 1990,

1995a; Purcell and Gero 1991; Quadrel, Woodbury, Fenves and Talukdar 1993; Reich 1992, 1995; Reich, Konda, Monarch, Levy and Subrahmanian 1996; Rinderle 1991; Sharpe 1995; Sharrock and Anderson 1994; Steinberg 1994; Suh 1990; Tomiyama 1994; Ullman 1993; Visser 1991, 1995, 1996; Wallace and Burgess 1995; Will 1991; Woodbury 1993; Wong and Shriram 1993; Zeng and Cheng 1991).

Few authors, however, included a description of the model of design or design process that they were using, and fewer still discussed why they chose to use a particular perspective on design or addressed the epistemological issues relating to their choice. The research trends of the 1980s and their underlying definitions of design continued into the 1990s, especially the view of design as problem-solving, although this view was often overlain with other design definitions, for example, by the view of design as searching in a solution space (Chandrasekaran 1990; Fenves and Grossman 1992).

In 1990, Suh published his axiomatic theory of design. In this theory he did not define design directly but much of the detail of his definition can be inferred from his proposals. In particular, he assumed that design was a matter of problem-solving. His definition is human based and reflexive because he claimed that 'design involves a continuous interplay between what we want to achieve and how we want to achieve it'. This human-centred reflexive view of design is, however, contradicted by the way that Suh describes his theory in terms of the information relating to the functional and physical domains of design problem and solution. For example,

The objective of design is always stated in the functional domain, whereas the physical solution is always generated in the physical domain . . . These two domains are inherently independent of each other. What relates these two domains is the design.

Suh's theory axiomatically relates the functional attributes of the design problem to a definition of the physical characteristics of an optimal design solution. In this sense, Suh's definition of design is informatically focused on the characteristics of the designed object and hence positivist. This points to a contradiction between the human-centred aspects of his definition of design activity and the positivist informatic outlook that underpins his axiomatic theory. Whilst Suh's axiomatic analyses were obviously carefully undertaken, his overall epistemology was

marked by a lack of linguistic and conceptual clarity relating to the 'actors' or agents involved in designing. An example of this lack of clarity is his use of 'the design's objectives' to refer to the 'objectives of the designer' in order to attribute purpose to the axiomatic process.

Chandrasekaran's (1990) view of design as problem solving was based on research paradigms of neo-behaviourism and computerisation. From this perspective, Chandrasekaran saw design not as any type of problem solving, but as problem solving by searching in a 'solution space of sub assemblies' in which the design problem lies: formally, a search problem in a large space of objects that satisfy multiple constraints. Chandrasekaran's view of design equated creativity with synthesis which was viewed as 'assembling new artefacts from discrete preformed elements'. He used this definition of synthesis to introduce a new definition of design as 'doing tasks' which in turn provided the theoretical basis for the development of a computerised system design that was intended to automatically 'choose' which methods it would use to assist a designer. In this sense, Chandrasekaran's definition is positivist because it relies on all of the aspects of the design problem and its situation being defined informatically, and takes little account of the role of human values.

Zeng and Cheng (1991) also defined design as a problem-solving process, but with an emphasis on logic, or more specifically 'types of logic', in order to support the development of a computer based system concept of automatic design. They proposed a new type of logic, 'recursive logic', and claimed that this is the logic of design. Their view of 'design as recursive logic' was connected with the more general view of 'design as problem-solving' by arguing that problem-solving processes consist of the logic of the process and the knowledge based on that logic. By this means, they imply a model of creativity in designing that parallels the linguistic concept of a sentence (creative statement) that consists of 'verbs' (the logic of the process) and 'nouns' (the logic based knowledge). A similar outlook is found in linguistic and grammar-based syntactical definitions of design (see, for example, Alexander 1977; Lawson 1993; Mullins and Rinderle 1991; Rinderle 1991; Stiny 1980). Zeng and Cheng's definition of design as logic manipulation is at odds with definitions of design that relate to ill-structured or ill-defined problems, and in which it is assumed that designing involves elements that are unknown or unknowable. What Zeng and Cheng's proposals do, however, is make a short, direct connection between a

particular, logically limited synthetic activity, whether seen as design or not, and a means of replicating or automating that activity using electronic logic.

Fenves and Grossman (1992) used an underlying definition of design as problem-solving to describe tertiary engineering courses in the synthesis aspect of design. In line with the preoccupation in the field for computer design assistance or computer automatization of design, Fenves and Grossman viewed 'design problem-solving' as equivalent to 'searching in a solution space'. This perspective may account for their surprising suggestion that the two main methodologies of synthesis in design are mathematical programming and knowledge based expert systems. This suggestion is unusual in that there exists an extensive and readily available literature of methods pertaining to synthesis in design (see, for example, Andreasen 1985; Clausen and Ragsdell 1985; Jones 1970; Westerberg, Stephanopoulos and Shah 1974). Fenves and Grossman identified that one of the epistemological difficulties associated with defining design synthesis in terms of the above two methodologies is that many aspects of design information or knowledge are qualitative and the above two methods are unsuited to dealing with qualitative information, mainly because qualitative information cannot be adequately represented quantitatively in an information-processing perspective. This description of the situation is over simplified, however, because Fenves and Grossman used the term 'qualitative', in a similar manner to Faltings (1991), to refer to the application of a quantitatively defined label to a qualitative property. This does not accord with the commonly accepted interpretation of 'qualitative' as pertaining to qualities whose meanings depend on social, economic, cultural, ecological, legal, and historical context, and on continuously changing individual human values. Fenves and Grossman's underlying definition of design does not include these qualitative aspects of what it is to synthesise a design.

Ferguson (1992a) regarded 'engineering' as the same as 'engineering design', and focused on those aspects of design that were not adequately epistemologically addressed by Fenves and Grossman's perspective on design synthesis. As an historian, Ferguson (1992a) took a historical view in which engineering design is a culturally-placed problem-solving activity. Like Bassalla (1988) and Thring and Laithwaite (1977), Ferguson grounded his argument on a long temporal view of design and technology rather than arguing axiomatically from principles and theory.

This historical basis for developing engineering design theory has the advantage of helping researchers avoid the possibility of propagating misconceptions due to basing new theory on faulted old theory, and in addition it allows the possibility of identifying historical data that challenge existing theory. From Ferguson's perspective (expanded upon in Ferguson (1992b)), a designer invents by solving ill-defined problems in a contingent manner. Ferguson's definition of design moves the focus away from the analytical activity that features prominently in contemporary engineering courses and courses on engineering design such as that described by Fenves and Grossman (1991) towards a view of design that depends more on human intuition and valuing. The essence of Ferguson's definition of engineering design is human-centred, creative, intuitive, and based on a problem-solving metaphor in which problems are incompletely defined and are not expected to have a deterministic relationship to their solutions.

Visser (1995) also took an historical perspective on design, but focused on each individual designer's history and argued that designing is based on knowledge of prior solutions. This is an epistemologically more specific position than generalised assertions such as 'designing is based on knowledge', or 'designers use information'. The subtlety of Visser's argument is similar to Hamlyn's (1990) analysis of the inadequacies of information-processing theories of mind that attempt to explain the extraction from memory of elements that are 'something like' another element. Visser viewed design as problem-solving in a manner that was grounded in his earlier work on integrating research from behaviourally-based cognitive psychology, and the application of research outcomes and methods from the field of artificial intelligence to engineering design (Visser, 1991). His main proposal in 1995 was that designers re-use problem-solving elements drawn from episodes in their experience: hence, 'episodic' knowledge. Conceptually, this is similar to the research into cognitive re-use by Purcell and Gero (1996) concerning the role of fixation in how experts review prior information. Purcell and Gero's work broadly supports Visser and vice-versa. The definition of design that underlies Visser's analyses of the role of episodic knowledge is human-centred, yet he did not adequately address the role of human valuing, or ethical and aesthetic considerations in design cognition.

In addition to the problem-solving perspective on design, the first half of the 1990s was marked by contributions from the field of artificial intelligence and attempts to automate design through the use of computers. These contributions depended on design being viewed as the transformation of one type of information into another, and this informatic perspective led to designing being viewed as an ahuman process that did not include the qualitative aspects of human designing (see, for example, Quadrel et al 1993).

Many of these informatically-based contributions to design research were found in the usual design research publications, but others were disseminated via specialist channels such as the journal *AIEDAM* which publishes refereed papers relating to the application of artificial intelligence techniques and theories to engineering design and manufacturing. The first international conference on artificial intelligence in engineering design was held in Edinburgh, Scotland in 1991. In his preface to the forty seven papers in the proceedings, the editor, Gero (1991), suggested that a two-way flow of paradigm had occurred in which, on the one hand, the computational, symbolic paradigm had provided a basis for new models and processes which might be used in designing, and, on the other hand, the activity of designing had provided a new challenge for artificial intelligence researchers because of its nature as a complex activity that is essentially based on intelligence.

One example that fits the above genre closely is the work of Dasgupta (1991, 1992, 1994).

Dasgupta's (1992) perspective on engineering design was tied to the cognitive science/behaviourist outlook developed in the field of artificial intelligence and design research by theorists such as Simon (1969) and Newall and Simon (1972). For Dasgupta:

- Design is one of the most ubiquitous human activities.
- Design is the means of creating the 'artificial'.
- Design is a cognitive process.
- Design has a significant domain-independent component.

In the above, Dasgupta's use of the term 'cognitive' was based on a central-processing model of computer architecture similar to, for example, its use by Newall (1990) and Simon (1982). This

definition of 'cognitive' contrasts with human-centred definitions that include the specifically human aspects of thinking and knowing (see, for example Hamlyn 1990). Dasgupta argued for a new start in developing a science of design, and suggested two 'laws of design' as an initial basis for the development of epistemologically well-justified foundations for such a science (see also Dasgupta 1994). These proposals are grounded in Dasgupta's detailed development of the relationships between design theory and computer science in 1990. The explicit and implicit aspects of Dasgupta's position on design in these texts indicate an underlying positivist definition of design whose purpose is the computer-based automation of designing. This positivist definition of design assumes a behaviourist metaphor of design cognition which is intended to define determinable relationships between quantitative information about design problems and their solutions.

In 1995, Steinberg investigated research methodologies that were appropriate to both design research and artificial intelligence research. He emphasised decomposition and a structural analysis of his position indicates that he viewed research into design as similar to research into physics and mathematics. The main focus of his study was for the development of a complete prescriptive model of design process. For Steinberg, designing was a collection of tasks that can be defined in a scientific manner such that it is possible to choose from a range of well-established methods to complete them.

Yoshikawa (1981) proposed a theory of design which he referred to as 'General Design Theory' (GDT) that was founded on the 'design theory' that is a sub-discipline of mathematics and which relates to group theory, graph theory, coding theory, geometry and statistics (Hughes and Piper, 1985). GDT was reviewed in detail by Reich (1995) with respect to epistemological and methodological issues. He suggested that GDT attempted to cast design in the framework of set theory, and argued that it did not live up to Yoshikawa's claims, especially that 'as a model of design it did not clarify the human ability to design'. Reich concluded that GDT provided a useful prescription for the development of CAD systems because it started with assumptions about the nature of objects and used them to prove theorems about the nature of design, but his analysis implied that it is not appropriate to use GDT for anything other than well-defined and well-structured routine problems. It may be of especial assistance in situations where routine

problems become massively complex. Reich's review of GDT and his earlier discussion of design research methodologies in 1994 apply to many computational, knowledge, information or artificial intelligence based models of design. Implicit in Reich's analyses is not that these models of design are faulty per se, but that their claims of applicability and validity are too extensive.

Mullins and Rinderle (1991) proposed a grammatical representation of mechanical engineering design based on the work of Stiny (1980) which was supported and extended by Rinderle (1991). Their argument for defining engineering design in grammatical terms was:

- Design can be viewed as a transformation of functional requirements to a physical device. This claim is based on Mostow (1985), and Rinderle (1987) and is also found in Suh (1990).
- Formal grammars are also based on a transformational paradigm.
- Formal grammars are the basis for computer languages and therefore are an efficient means for the computerised representation and manipulation of design information.

Rinderle (1991) argued that the most appropriate set of formal grammars for this purpose are the attribute grammars. In theory, attribute grammars are useful for computerising a topic because they offer a way out of the semantic 'contextuality problems' associated with language because they allow contextual meaning to be attached to symbols in the grammar. It is not obvious, however, how this avoids the epistemological difficulties associated with the role of human values in the interpretation and construction of individuals' realities that is detailed in Chapter 3 of this thesis. The use of attribute grammars offers a means of controlling the computational demands of inferential processes associated with representing aspects of design, but they do this by what Logan, Millington and Smithers (1991) describe as being 'economical with truth'.

The use of attribute-based grammars of design also points to a subtle epistemological problem with respect to engineering design theory in that the contextual information fixed to grammatical symbols is also temporally fixed, whereas the contextuality of meaning in many

aspects of design is more temporally fluid. An example of this in everyday language is the contextually-based nature of a phrase like 'Should I put the cat out?'. Obviously, the exact meaning attributed by my partner to this question of mine depends on a 'history' which gives it context and which may be seen as a contextual attribute. The meaning also depends on things which may change, such as what time it is, or how long the cat has been locked in the house, or what we are doing. Hence, it would seem that the attribute grammars are only appropriate to model design elements whose meaning is temporally unchanging with respect to context.

In 1992, Konda and his associates differentiated between 'engineering' and 'design', arguing that if something fails because it violates known engineering principles it is an *engineering* failure, but that it is a *design* failure if it fails for contextual reasons which lie outside engineering analysis, for example, due to economic, social, political, legal, ecological and firm-specific factors. Konda et al (1992) used this contextual perspective on design to propose a new unifying paradigm for engineering design research and theory-making that emphasised the role of the shared memories of different aspects of a design problem, its solution and its context. Konda et al argued that the role of shared memories is central to design theory because these shared memories provide the social and individual contexts of information and of designing itself. This shared memory model of engineering design and its associated contextual perspective are supported, superficially at least, by arguments relating to the importance of considering cognitive artefacts 'in context', that is, in interaction with the user, and the role of episodic knowledge in designing (Norman 1992; Visser 1995).

This social constructivist outlook on which Konda and associates have based their concept of shared memory is, however, insufficient to adequately address the epistemological issues relating to individual contexts and interpretations, and the role of context and interpretation in human cognition (Hamlyn 1990). Human memory consists of information that is interpreted and constructed on the basis of an individual's human values and ontological assumptions, and these ethical and aesthetic bases vary temporally depending on prior circumstances. That is, how an individual conceives and values a particular piece of information depends on what experiences and thoughts precede it. This means that adequately encapsulating the nuances of shared memory in theoretical or practical terms is dependent not only on placing designing in a

socially constructed context but also on an adequate constructivist theory of how individuals interpret and utilise knowledge. These problems with the epistemology of individual memory and context are the same as those found in respect to Rinderle and Mullins' (1991) proposals for defining design in terms of formal grammars because they are both attempts to find a way of encoding context to enable contextual matters to be manipulated mechanically without addressing qualitative issues.

The definition of design that is implicit in the model of shared memory developed by Konda and associates has several dialectical contradictions; it is obviously human-centred, yet it is essentially informatic, because it is intended to be computerisable; it includes qualitative issues, yet it is intended to do so in a quantitative manner; it is based on social constructivism, a post-positive perspective, yet it includes aspects of individual cognition in a positivist manner.

Chakrabarti and Bligh (1994) focused on conceptual design and abstract functionality: a similar focus to French (1985, 1990) and Suh (1990). They saw conceptual design as,

The activity of transforming the functional requirements of a design into a solution concept or concepts for fulfilling requirements.

From this perspective on conceptual design, it appears that all that is left is to add a few dimensions to the solution concept for it would be ready for manufacture. Their use of 'transform' echoes the writings of researchers working within a computational, information-processing paradigm. This indicates that their underlying definition of design is positivist, informatic and deterministic.

The procedural view of engineering design described by Hubka and Eder (1992) was a natural extension of their theory of technical systems (Hubka and Eder, 1988). Their viewpoint on design is scientific and, as is perhaps inevitable with a procedural model, they focused on 'process' and 'systems'. They emphasised that design is a 'transformation process' and formulated their subsequent theory from a perspective of information management.

In theory, it should not be possible to develop a theory of design without consideration of what design is. Bieniawski (1993), however, attempted this by building up a theory of design for

excavation in geologic media on the paradigmic bases of the General Theory of Design of Yoshikawa (1981), the Theory of Technical Systems of Hubka (1987), and the Axiomatic Design theory of Suh (1990). His underlying perspective was a process-management view of design, that is, his model and axioms were guides for managing information for use by designers. Bieniawski's design process was deterministic in direction and this results in his view of 'synthesis' being equivalent in his model to 'the application of state-of-the-art heuristics'. The mathematical mechanistic outlook on design presented by him is, however, in conflict with his assertions about the ill-defined nature of many aspects of designing in geologic media.

In this period, human-centred perspectives on research into design provided some contrast to the widespread informatic perspective that was intended to automate designing. For example, Petroski (1992), as guest editor of *Research in Engineering Design*, defined engineering design in human terms and argued against those proposing theories of design which do not include some provision for a human aspect to designing. He maintained that:

Engineering design is an endeavour of, by, and for human beings. In both principle and practice it has incontrovertibly human characteristics . . . no understanding of engineering design can be expected to be complete without an appreciation of its uniquely human dimensions and attributes . . .

He further argued that there are many sides to the human aspect of designing engineering artefacts, and claimed that 'the contents of no single issue [of *Research in Engineering Design*] could in any way be expected to present a definitive array of topics covering the breadth and scope of the human context in which design takes place'. In essence, Petroski's view of design is that of a socially-situated activity that results in change. The engineering aspect of Petroski's definition refers only to the domain in which designed artefacts would be classified or whose technical information is used by the designer.

Similarly, Piela, Katzenberg and McKelvey (1992) argued that, although it was not the norm in engineering design research, it was important to include human behaviour in explanations of design:

Engineering design research has historically been evaluated in terms of its computational performance. However, in many cases this research implies hypotheses about human behaviour are ignored.

Piela, Katzenberg and McKelvey viewed design as a social process involving many participants, and argued that computer based systems that are built with the intention of supporting non-routine design would be improved by considering how people use designed artefacts and what the users could contribute to the design of those artefacts. The definition of design that underpins their approach to design research is essentially human-centred and participatory. It moves away from a view of designing as an activity undertaken only by specialised designers at the behest of sponsors and looks towards a theory of designing that includes users' information, knowledge and creativity.

In contrast to the social constructivism that underpins the definitions of design implicit in the work of Konda et al (1992) and Piela, Katzenberg and McKelvey (1992), Schön (1992) focused on individual designers' internal cognitive landscapes and, in particular, how these cognitive activities and perceptions change and are changed as a result of experience. Schön's view of designing is as a human activity of learning and self education. That is, Schön explores how designers move from the unknown, the design situation, to the known, the design itself, as a process of individual research and learning. This view of design in educational terms points to the importance of the role of the immediate environment of the designer including the internal environment of the designer's mental content. Schön's analysis of design and his theoretical proposals are a part of a much broader research program on reflective professional action (see, for example, Schön 1974, 1983, 1987; Schön and Wiggins 1992). The definition of design, therefore that underlies Schön's (1992) analyses is of design as a learning activity that results from an individual's reflection on the outcomes of their design proposals. For Schön, the process of designing is via small steps that involve investigating, proposing solutions and reflecting on outcomes and the changes in knowledge about the design situation. Schön implied that phenomenology offered the most appropriate research methodology for investigating design as a reflective human activity. The view of designing as a reflective activity is also found in an

earlier work of Cross (1983) that relates to explaining the differences in cognitive styles between expert and novice designers and the implications for the education of designers.

Love (1995a, 1995b), like Petroski and Schön, regarded designing as a contextually placed activity undertaken by humans with individually constructed and interpreted realities. That is, design is a human, socially situated experience. He argued that the historical dependence of engineering design theory on systems theory has led to epistemological difficulties because the way that systems theories and the systems perspective has underpinned design theory does not adequately include many of the qualitative, subjective or contextual matters which are essential aspects of successful engineering design. Love drew attention to the fact that researchers in the area of systems are struggling with similar epistemological issues relating to making theory about human creative activities and cognition (see, for example, Flood 1990; Flood and Jackson 1991). Love's underlying definition of design is human-centred, constructivist and domain-independent.

Design practice is the practical aspect of designing, and defines the overlap between design as an individual pursuit and design as a social phenomenon. Whitney (1990) brought attention to the praxeological nature of design, claiming that general or universal theories about designing will come out of research into design which focuses on practice. Whitney's position on defining design was pragmatic; that the term 'design' needs only to be defined well enough that design research can support designers by theory generation and practical aids. From this pragmatic perspective, he suggested two definitions of design. The first focuses on the individual designer and the second focuses on the social aspects of designing:

- Design is a technical process to be accomplished
- Design is an organisational process to be managed.

Whitney claimed that to develop practice-based unified theories of design it was also necessary to view design in the following ways:

- Design is the technical component of a product-realisation process.

- Design is the process of attaining wide latitude and narrow variance. Where 'latitude' is tolerance to departures from specification or envisaged use, and variance refers to the standard of performance of the product.
- Design is the process of recognising, consensualising and resolving conflict during creation of an entity that meets a set of goals.

Whitney's perspectives and definitions raise many issues and define several areas of research relating to design. The definitions themselves, however, have several internal contradictions. For example, by defining design as the technical component of the product-realisation process Whitney is implying that there are other components that are not design and his human-centred perspective suggests that it is the human aspects that are excluded. Yet, by defining design as a 'process of recognising, consensualising and resolving conflict', Whitney is including human aspects of designing. These epistemological difficulties are eased if Whitney's definitions are viewed as cumulative. That is, if Whitney's intention is to define design as all of the above, then he is free to add to the definition at anytime. In this case, it is necessary for Whitney to bound the scope of this accumulation of definition unless he intends it to be all encompassing, and furthermore it would be helpful to identify the research perspective that each definition is formulated within to avoid inconsistencies between them. In summary, Whitney suggested a variety of pragmatically useful definitions of design but in a manner which implied a lack of epistemological coherence between them.

Will (1991) gave an industrial perspective on product design. He did not define design or design process directly but placed them as phases within Hewlett-Packard's Phase Review Process. This is Hewlett-Packard's term for what is otherwise known as a product realisation process or product development process. How Will saw design must be inferred from the text, and his position appears to have internal contradictions. On one hand he had 'design is an intuitive art' as opposed to a science, but he also argued that the education of design-skilled engineering graduates depends on a science base for design. It appears that Will does not know exactly what design is, but when a Hewlett-Packard Phase Review Process has been implemented it will tell him whether the designing has been done successfully.

The overall position in the design research field as to whether design should be viewed as an activity that is independent of the domains in which it is undertaken is not yet clear. On one hand, design may be viewed as a generic activity which may be applied to any information or knowledge, but, on the other hand, it is clear that the practice of designing is different in each discipline and topic area, and it is in this latter sense that theories of design are domain dependent. The domain-dependent view of design dominates the literature of design research, but the human-centred view of designing points more towards the domain independent perspective. The main argument for the domain-dependent position is that the knowledge content of different domains has led to different theories of design being developed in those domains, and because the answer to the question 'What is Design?' is different in each domain (Lawson 1990, 1993, 1994; Sargent 1994). Lawson (1993) argued against domain independency in design theory because,

Design refers to an enormous range of activities from the highly constrained, numerical and well defined problems of say electronic engineering to the under constrained, nebulous and ill-defined problems in say fashion or textiles.

The differing theories of design and domain-based models of design process are explainable, however, as a consequence of the different paradigms of research that are due to different domain cultures and technical knowledge. The argument for design to be viewed as a domain-dependent activity is also undermined by Dilnot's (1982) conclusion that using information about the design problem and its solution as the basis for design research results in design theory that does not epistemologically include many fundamental aspects of designing. If design information is viewed as the material on which designing acts, a position that accords with both informatic and human-centred perspectives on design, then epistemologically, the role of domain-based information is no longer fundamental to defining design. Together, these imply that, in the interests of epistemological coherency, it may be better for the field to move towards viewing design as domain-independent activity.

In 1991 Pugh published the details of an all-encompassing engineering design paradigm, theory and methodology which he called 'Total Design'. In the short period since its inception, Total

Design has become one of the best accepted contemporary methods in product design, by both researchers and practitioners (Hollins, 1994). Pugh proposed Total Design as a process which contains all the factors contributing to the development of a product from conceptual 'cradle' to physical 'grave'. He contrasted 'Total Design' with 'partial design' where 'partial design' was seen as any designing which is undertaken from a specialist or narrow viewpoint. Pugh concludes that this 'partiality' leads to design decisions being made which are not the best when seen from a wider perspective. From this position, he argued against engineering attitudes dominating product development, and suggested that 'misdirected engineering rigour will always give rise to bad total design'.

Pugh's conception is based on a systems outlook and geared to a commercial value base. He defined Total Design as,

The systematic activity necessary, from the identification of the market/user need, to the selling of the successful product to satisfy that need - an activity that encompasses product, process, people and organisation.

One of the most distinctive features of the Total Design model is its 3-D pictorial representation which Pugh uses and which is echoed at different levels of detail and abstraction to fill out the Total Design concept. In conceptual terms, Total Design has a core consisting of its main elements in Pugh's words:

Total Design may be construed as having a central core of activities . . . this core, the design core, consists of market (user need), product design specification, conceptual design, detail design, manufacture and sales.

Thus, the Total Design core includes the epistemologically different entities of 'needs' (information), product design specification (information), conceptual design (internal activity), detail design (internal activity), manufacture (external activity), sales (internal and external activities).

Total Design is based on the concept of satisfying needs – which may exist independently of the product or be generated by the product because Pugh maintains that, 'All design starts, or should start, with a need that, when satisfied, will fit into an existing market or create a market

of its own'. Total design does not take engineering design theory into new country. It has a theoretical base in the systematic design theories of the 1960s and 1970s, and some German theorists might argue that it goes back further. What Pugh and his associates did, however, was to combine into one coherent system different aspects of design theories and methods together with well-established methods from other disciplines. More than that, Pugh demonstrated the worth of the system in practical, non-trivial commercial design situations.

Two other themes in the 1990s have been an increased focus on including environmental issues into design, and a renewed interest in the epistemology of design theory. The focus on environmental aspects of designing is a consequence of public pressure for technology to have less harmful environmental effects. The level of publication relating specifically to the inclusion of environmental issues in design research is low but increased awareness of environmental considerations in designing is evident in many texts (see, for example, Beder 1990; Engineering Council 1993; Goggin 1994; Hillier and Penn 1994; I.E. Aust. 1992; Somers 1992; Woolley 1992). Research into the design aspects of environmentally conscious manufacture is also found in many small European research groups, such as those individual researchers affiliated to the ongoing ECO2-IRN electronic conference organised from the CAE Centre at Cranfield in the UK.

The interest in epistemological aspects of design theory is evident in the increase in publications relating to research methodology and research perspectives in design (see, for example, Coyne 1991b; Coyne and Newton 1992; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992a, 1992b; Dorst and Dijkhuis 1995; Franz 1994; Reich 1992, 1994a, 1994b, 1995). The renewed interest in epistemological issues is also found in the increase in papers concerning structural issues in design theory such as design taxonomies (see, for example, Hubka and Eder 1990; Konda et al 1992; Ullman 1992).

Ullman (1992) argued that design has different meanings to different theorists, and advanced a comprehensive taxonomy for classifying different methods and theories of mechanical engineering design. Although Ullman did not make it explicit, he used an 'artefactual' paradigm of design theory-making to develop his taxonomy. This may be seen, on one hand, by

the fact that the most detailed and comprehensive levels of his taxonomy are dedicated to artefact definition, and, on the other hand, by the attention he gives to,

- The environment that the *artefact* is designed in.
- The problem that the *artefact* is a solution for.
- The process which leads to that *artefact*.

This artefactual focus contrasts with, for example, Schön's emphasis on the phenomenon of designing, or Petroski's focus on design as human endeavour, or Zeng and Cheng's logic-based view of design. Since taxonomies of design theory could be developed from each of these perspectives, it would be expected that each of these other taxonomies would have differences in category types and taxonomic structure from that of Ullman.

Together, these interests in the structure and dynamic of design theory, and in methodological issues of design research suggest that a 'Philosophy of Design' is being established.

6.6 Summary

By 1995, the focus of design research had changed from improving 'traditional designing' via systematic design methods to automated designing with computer assistance transforming information about the design problem into a detailed specification of a physical solution. The balance and volume of the literature associated with research into design reflects the magnitude of this change in research direction. The recent focus on computer assistance has led to a change in the privilege and dominance of the different metaphors used in design theory, and in the mid 1990s the predominant theoretical metaphor of engineering design has become the concept of 'design as information processing'.

Some of the main characteristics of the definitions of design that have been used explicitly and implicitly in the texts analysed in this review are listed below:

- That designing is a process.
- That designing involves transforming or processing information.
- That design is a human activity.

- That designing involves creativity and synthesis.
- That designing is similar to problem-solving, managing, learning and planning.
- That designing is a scientific rational process.

There are many other definitions of design in the reviewed literature, relating to, for example, futurism, working with uncertainty, integration and construction. None of the definitions of design is adequately justified in epistemological terms. In most cases, different aspects of theory and definition in the same text are epistemologically contradictory or are not epistemologically justifiable.

In summary, the literature of design research of the period 1962–1995 that was reviewed in this appendix contains a variety of conflicting definitions of design most of which are poorly justified and inappropriately used.

7. Appendix 2: Annotated bibliography relating to the definition of the term 'design process' 1962–1995

7.1 Introduction

There are two main themes within the literature on design process. In the first, design is a structured process in which information is processed and activities managed. The language of this outlook consists of morphologies, taxonomies, block diagrams, flow charts and system analyses. The second theme on design process is concerned with the human creative activity of designing and all necessary associated activities.

The literature on design contains a wide variety of proposals for the structure of the process together with morphologies and taxonomies of different aspects of designing and design theory. French (1985) commented on the extent of this variety whilst proposing his own block diagram representing the engineering design process:

Constructing block diagrams is a fashionable pastime, especially in fields like design where boundaries are imprecise and interactions legion, so that any ten experts will produce ten (or a hundred). They will all be different, and all valid. . . . They express only truisms, and yet they have a value for all that.

Parnas and Clements (1986) argued that it is helpful for communication between designers and design researchers to use rational and logical descriptions of design processes even though designing is not essentially rational or logical. Sargent (1990) expressed similar sentiments:

In a sense it does not matter whether any such classification is true, but only whether it is an aid to talking

The above comments point to a hidden epistemological difficulty in this area of design research. Both of the above positions indicate that a relativist position is appropriate to addressing the variety of different ways that design process can be conceived, yet they stop short of including those matters of theoretical perspective and metaphor that clarify relativist situations because of their inherent absolutism. That is, the impossibility of classifying definitions of design process

in terms of objective 'truth' precludes being able to analyse the epistemological correctness of individual proposals if no attempt is made to analyse or take account of the assumptions on which particular models of design process are based (Indurkha 1992; Stegmüller 1976).

Some researchers have addressed the epistemological issues on which their definitions depend. For example, Coyne and his associates have consciously focused on the epistemology that underpins design definitions and theory (see, for example, Coyne 1990c, 1991b; Coyne and Newton 1990, 1992; Coyne, Newton and Sudweeks 1993; Coyne and Snodgrass 1992b; Coyne, Snodgrass and Martin 1992). Other researchers have addressed the epistemological issues concerning relativism in design theory in other ways. For example, Jones (1970) explained his model of design process in terms of a means of classifying the information relating to a particular design; Siddall (1972) tied his model of design process to a definition of good decision-making based on value; and Ullman (1992) described his taxonomy of design process as an attempt to classify an evolving field. Each of these researchers has stated the perspective on which their model of design process is based, and made it possible, therefore, to analyse whether their model is consistent with its underlying assumptions.

The second theme in the literature on design process is concerned with design as human creativity. In many cases the literature in this area is epistemologically confused because defining design as a process assumes that design can be defined as a sequence. In essence, this means that to define design as a process depends on assuming that the design outcome is determinable. The concept of creativity, however, is dependent on the design outcome not being determinable, and hence there is an implicit epistemological contradiction. The origins of this difficulty lie in the early systematic models of design process, for example, the analysis-synthesis-evaluation model, which consisted of a sequential process that included a stage that was given the attributes of creativity or invention. These systematic sequential process models make sense from the perspective of managing designing or managing the flow of information, but as theoretical descriptions of designing as a human creative activity they are epistemologically incoherent because most of the elements included in the design process model refer to associated supporting activities rather than creative human designing.

These characteristics of the two different themes on 'design process' have already emerged in relation to definitions of 'design' in the first appendix where many texts that include 'design process' have already been discussed. This second appendix, therefore, focuses mainly on those details and texts that have not already been addressed.

7.2 1962 - 1969: design as a systematic process, epistemological difficulties, practice based process models

In 1962 at the Conference on Design Methods, Jones (1963) proposed a method of 'Systematic Design' that was aimed at reducing the amount of design error, re-design and delay, and, in addition, making possible more imaginative and advanced designs. His method was aimed at design problems where considerable departures from existing designs are called for, where large quantities of information are available, and where the design team has well defined responsibilities for development, free of routine design work.

Jones' built his Systematic Design Method around a framework of Analysis - Synthesis - Evaluation (ASE) and by this separated the intuitive aspects of design from the mathematically rigorous aspects of design with the intention of integrating the two into a more effective process. Jones' ASE framework has been widely accepted and used as the basis for models of design process. More recently, however, the ASE framework has been subject to practical and theoretical criticism in terms of its internal inconsistencies and its lack of coherence with real design situations (see, for example, Dasgupta 1991; Dietterich and Stauffer 1988; Stomph-Blessing 1989; Ullman 1992). The way that the ASE framework has been adopted by the field is rather different to the ways that Jones originally proposed, and few who based their theory on his ASE framework seem to have identified these differences.

Jones (1963) used the analysis-synthesis-evaluation framework for two purposes:

- To help designers distinguish whether their minds were acting logically, creatively or practically.
- To provide a system of notation to help designers record every item of design information *outside* their memories [emphasis in original]. In Jones' view of design, the mind moves from problem analysis to solution-seeking whenever it feels the need, and

then the data can be recorded under the three categories of analysis, synthesis and evaluation.

The ASE framework has been mainly used in the design research literature, however, to describe or prescribe a sequential process of activities, and this is a different purpose to those epistemologically more justifiable purposes envisaged by Jones.

In the early 1960s, Alexander developed a different systematic design process based on probability and graph theory, and needing a computer for its application to anything more than trivial problems (Alexander 1963, 1964). In 1963, Alexander introduced this design process in relation to designing an Indian Village, and then expanded on his explanation of it in 1964 in *Notes on the Synthesis of Form*. Alexander's design process focused on the relationship between form and its context, and used a decompositional method that identified which aspects of a design problem are best considered as sub-problems on the basis of a weighted analysis of the relationships between all the design variables. His process was hailed as a major step forward in systematic design, but, although this design process appears to be almost completely automatic, it depended on a designer's ability to identify the relevant variables and the relationship between design elements. This meant that the human creative aspects of designing had become peripheral to Alexander's design process. Alternatively, if human creativity is viewed as essential to the concept of designing, then Alexander's process was peripheral, in the sense that it is a means of providing improved information to designers. Hence, it has much the same role with respect to a designer, and to design theory, as, for example, a mathematical means of calculating the stress in a bearing. Alexander recognised the underlying epistemological and ontological difficulties with his deconstructional design process, and in the mid 1970s, published an epistemologically and ontologically more sophisticated design process (Alexander 1977, 1979).

Roe, Soulis and Handa (1966) described the content but not the mechanism of a design process that included:

- Planning
- Systems

- Innovation and creativity
- The role of information
- Decision-making
- Value and utility

They regarded intuition or creativity to be a matter of four measurable psychological personality characteristics:

- That the designer is open to experience
- That the innovator must have a creative imagination
- That the innovator must exhibit detachment when necessary
- That the innovator must have confidence in his or her evaluations

Decision-making was seen as a matter of using probabilistic and weighting methods similar to multi-criteria or multiattribute optimisation methods. The aspect of design process to do with value and utility was viewed as problematic because of a lack of consensus in society about value and utility, and because of the difficulties of including issues of value and utility in a decision-making system. They suggested the use of a quantitative economic theory of value, and noted problems with regard to representing qualitative factors.

There are inconsistencies in Roe, Soulis and Handa's proposals, particularly in how they reconciled issues concerning intuition and value with mechanistic methods. They avoided these problems to some extent by claiming that issues of intuition and value are not very relevant to technological design decisions.

Middendorf (1969) created a model of design process based on process management that was grounded in the day to day practices of engineering designers of that time. He noted that individual engineering designers each worked according to some iterative pattern, procedure or process, and suggested that this behaviour might be approximately described by the following steps carried out in an iterative fashion, but in more or less the following sequence:

1. Determine the specifications
2. Make a feasibility study
3. Search for patents
4. Develop possible alternative design concepts which are likely to meet the specifications.
5. Determine the criteria for making a selection and select the most promising of the alternative design concepts for further concentrated effort.
6. Develop a mathematical and/or a physical model of the selected design concept.
7. Use the model(s) to determine the relationship among the basic dimensions and materials of the product and the specifications.
8. Optimise the design with respect to as many of the selection criteria of step 5 as possible.
9. Evaluate the optimised design by extensive analysis on the mathematical model and tests on physical models.
10. Communicate the design decisions to engineering administration and manufacturing personnel by reports, drawings and verbal explanation.

Middendorf's model of design process had the advantage that if it were read aloud to experienced designers they would understand and probably concur. It represented, in a simplified manner, the idealised progression of activity that a designer might engage in but it lacked universality. That is, although many designers might agree that that is how designing might happen in a particular circumstance, it is by no means obvious that this description would apply to all designers in all circumstances in all engineering domains. Middendorf's design process is in effect a map that is useful for the management of designing.

In summary, in the period 1962 to 1969, the ways that design process was defined by the researchers reviewed here were based on the new systems perspectives that emerged in the 1960s. Researchers used these systematic concepts in a variety of ways to create models of

design process that accorded with the design practices of the time but paid little attention to epistemological considerations and validity.

7.3 1970-1979: Design as methodological process, decision-making and optimisation

The 1970s started with Jones (1970) publishing his comprehensive collection of design methods which included discussion and analysis of many aspects of design theory. In *Design Methods*, Jones maintained a flexible position as to what might be the best model of design process, and expected it to depend upon circumstance and the individuals involved. Jones put forward the view that designing should not be confused with art, with science, or with mathematics. He claimed that it is a hybrid of all three, and pointed out that one of the differences between them is a matter of timing: that artists and scientists work in present time, that mathematicians work on abstract relationships that are independent of historical time, and that designers treat as real that which exists only in an imagined future. Developing the systematic perspective that he proposed in 1962, Jones expanded the 'analysis-synthesis-evaluation' model into: 'breaking the problem into pieces', 'putting the pieces together in a new way' and 'testing to discover the consequences of putting the new arrangement into practice', three aspects of designing that he called 'divergence', 'convergence' and 'transformation'. This new proposal may have been conceptually and epistemologically appropriate in, for example, Architecture where it is building form that is both taken apart and reassembled, but in most disciplines the pieces that are taken apart using analysis are not the pieces that are put together in synthesis. For example, in Engineering it is forces, masses, inertias and stresses that are the theoretical entities that are analysed, but it is gears, beams, shafts and cams that are the physically based concepts that are put together using synthesis.

Jones reconfirmed his position in 1963 that the main role of these terms is not as a representation of design process (as other theorists have taken it) but that the terms are more useful as a means of categorising information, design theories and methods for discussion and analysis. In addition, Jones was suggesting these categories as a conceptual framework on which to hang future theory. To quote,

The three stages . . . do not necessarily fit together to form a universal strategy composed of ever more detailed cycles. They are more elementary than that, being merely categories into which the many loose ends of design theory, as it now exists, can be discussed at the inexact, or fanciful, level that our partial knowledge and partial ignorance permit.

The three stages are here named divergence, transformation and convergence. These names are meant to refer more to the new problems of system designing than to the traditional procedures of architecture and of engineering design.

This emphasis by Jones on the use of Analysis - Synthesis - Evaluation (or divergence, transformation and convergence) as categories for managing design theory-making is epistemologically and conceptually different from the way that they are used by many other researchers as prescriptive stages of design process.

In addition, Jones' proposals for viewing design as a systematic process tied his theoretical design process to business process in real organisations and included proposals for changes to organisational structures. He proposed that design processes should include marketing, design, production and sales and should contain several separate small-scale departments which act together within a product development department to realistically model a business's main operations. This concept of viewing design activity in its wider business context predates, by at least a decade, the view that design process is a central activity of commercial institutions (see, for example Andreasen 1985; Beitz 1989; Hollins and Pugh 1989; Pugh and Morley 1989).

The collection of papers relating to the *Symposium on Basic Questions of Design Theory* that Spillers edited in 1974 provides an insight into researchers' positions on design process in the years immediately after Jones' publication of *Design Methods*. For example, Purcell, Mallen and Goumain (1974) developed models of design process that were intended to utilise the increased availability of computers. Hence, like Alexander (1964), their models are neither based directly on some understanding of the theoretical and practical necessities, nor on whatever was best practice at the time, but on the possibilities defined by computer hardware and software development.

Motard (1974) suggested that creativity proceeds on two planes:

- The first plane relates to the inner state of the individual in which the creative outcomes are discovered via an internal symbolic language.
- The second plane is the external communication of those concepts formulated in the inner language, and this external communication helps the designer marshal and refine the internal concepts.

Thus, for Motard, the design communication media of charts, drawings, calculations and reports have a dual role as both a means of external communication with others and as part of an internal design process. If this is true, it has implications for the choice and design of the media used in developing, communicating and recording artefact or system details. Motard's proposals fit well with the observations of Booker (in Duggan (1970)) who concluded that:

Languages in general are not only useful for communication; they play an inherent part of our very thinking, for we tend to think in terms of the language we know. Drawing is of this nature, and he who can draw can think of, and deal with, many things and problems which another man cannot.

These proposals about to the role of language and designerly methods of communication in design processes foreshadow research in the 1980s and early 1990s that came to similar conclusions (see, for example, Cross, Cross and Glynn 1986; Goldschmidt 1994; Tovey 1992a).

Harrison (1974) also used language as the basis for model of design process that automated design but, in his case, he based his design process model on linguistic theory. He demonstrated his outlook by applying it to the design of finite automata using the language of regular expressions, and concluded that this model of the design process could automatically produce the desired result for a client's specification. The main drawback of his design process, however, was that clients must always state their specifications in a complete manner and in the mathematically-based language of regular expressions. This means that the effort, and perhaps the process, of designing has been moved from the designer to the client. Harrison also suggested that predicate calculus, inductive inference and fuzzy logic were other possible

approaches to a unified symbolically representable design process, but noted that these methods when applied even in the most constrained situations produced solutions which were unrealistic.

Wong (1974) based his view of design process on design practice in the domain of bioengineering and suggested that the typical design processes of bioengineering design is representative of design processes in most domains. He described his model of design process as follows:

It starts with a set of consistent principles capable of expansion and extension but bounded by the rules of logic, involves an operational discipline which leads to predicted action, and requires a feedback apparatus that makes meaningful evaluation and improvement possible.

Wong used an hierarchical model that spanned between living systems and abstract concepts via what he referred to as the 'mathematical formalisation of representation'. In essence, Wong's description of his model supports the observation made earlier in Appendix 1, that definitions of design process depend on the concepts and theoretical perspective that are available in the domain in which they are conceived and expressed.

Altman (1974) suggested a model of design process aimed at organisational change as one of the consequences of design output. From this perspective, Altman argued that design process must include a consideration of human factors, and that this requires a qualitative means because the quantitative perspective that underpins most models of design process is limited in its ability to include human behaviour. He observed that most models of the design process implicitly assume quantitative logical procedures for modelling, evaluation and optimisation, and that including a qualitative perspective would necessitate fundamental changes to the way that the design process is seen and would have implications in terms of choice of the value system(s) to be used in the models, evaluative structures and optimisation methodologies.

Altman's analyses, though sketchy and with little epistemological and ontological justification, pointed to the conclusions that have emerged as a result of the application of post-positivist perspectives in this thesis and predated them by a quarter century.

Westerberg, Stephanopoulos and Shah (1974) viewed the design process in chemical engineering as one partitioned into the sub-tasks of 'analysis', 'optimisation' and 'synthesis', and used these three terms in an industry-specific manner. Their design process starts with the synthesis of a design of an engineering system (the invention) which may be appropriate to the desired outcomes (presumably tested against some perceived needs). Then this engineering system is analysed to find out if it is suitable, and evaluated to determine its worth. They suggested an evolutionary means of automating the synthesis component by taking an initial process, modifying it then testing it for improvement. Their model of design process is strongly influenced by the modus operandi of chemical industries in that the focus – what is being designed – is an efficient means of synthesising the manufactured product, rather than the product itself. This leads to confusion between their use of the term 'synthesis' and its use elsewhere in the literature because in, for example, mechanical engineering design, the term 'synthesis' refers to the elements of the designed outcome.

Brotchie and Sharpe (1974) proposed a design process based on viewing urban planning design as design decision-making. They used a systems approach and included qualitative as well as quantitative data, but restricted the role of qualitative data to descriptive or labelling functions because all decision-making in their design process was done via a quantitative mathematical model. This meant that decisions involving qualitative data such as community attitudes or environmental issues could be included only by attributing quantitative weighting factors to them. The authors noted that there are problems with this approach because the factors which are weighted may not have a simple relationship with each other or with the system as a whole. Brotchie and Sharpe did not address the epistemological difficulties relating to value systems under which the weighting process is undertaken but their description implied a utilitarian model of value.

Gero (1974) focused on the limits of usefulness of systems analysis and mathematical modelling in a perspective on computer aided design process which included ethos and value judgements. He noted the symbiotic relationships between the developments in computer systems, systems methods and mathematical techniques. He suggested that, whilst researchers in these areas are happy to limit the scope of a problem by studying it in isolation, they rarely put the problem

back into its fuller context to test the validity of their definitions of variables as either endogenous or exogenous or to test their assumptions about those variables. He suggested that the crux of one of the fundamental problems in computer aided design research is that the definition of problems is over-influenced by the means of resolving or analysing them. That is,

In order to manipulate the problem with a particular set of tools, the problem is so constrained that it allows no feedback to the ethos from which it was extracted.

Gero argued that existing mathematical and computer-based tools of analysis force the definition of problems to be well-bounded regardless of whether or not this is their state in a larger system. He suggested that the failure, within the strict notions of scientific systems analysis, of attempts to include the contextual ethos of a problem or the range of potential value judgements pertinent to the view of the solution in its wider context is because the analytical tools that have been used are inappropriate or inadequately developed. Gero concluded that ethics formed the epistemological boundary for any model, and what was necessary was to extend the detail of models to that boundary. In summary, Gero was pointing to the role of ethics as an exogenous condition for models of design process, and arguing that those models must be able to unite systemic and ethical considerations. In terms of the philosophy of knowledge, Gero was suggesting that design theories must be coherent and well coordinated with their epistemological and ontological foundations.

Nevill and Crowe (1974) considered conceptual design as a process in which a designer is asked to generate a novel, highly optimal solution to a tentatively constrained problem. They viewed this design process as being represented by the stages of 'divergence' and 'transformation' of Jones' (1970) definition of design, and suggested that the conceptual design process is an optimum search through a maximally expanded problem space which consists of all the information which is known to or by the designer. They viewed their definition of conceptual design as better than other definitions that included concepts such as inspiration, insight and incubation, because the process was more compatible with computers.

Ostrowski's (1977) model of design process was based on a systems approach with a tree structure of discrete sub-processes, and assumed that designing and planning were equivalent.

The measure of success for elements of his process was based on satisficing the needs of what he referred to as 'the production/consumption cycle'. Ostrofski's design process was also aimed at finding optimum designs that satisfied the above design constraints, and to this end he proposed using Criterion Function Synthesis as a method of quantitative weighted criteria evaluation for the comparison of candidate optimal systems. This method maps the design criteria onto probability space and enables the comparison of multiple criteria which are not necessarily independent. Ostrofski noted, however, that the proposed system depends upon human expertise and value judgements. That is,

Those who are evaluating the criterion performance and its relative value are experts to the extent that their decisions are rational, representing the maximum level of accuracy and knowledge at the respective stage of development.

Ostrofski's model of design process was defined to enable the application of Criterion Function Synthesis as a method of quantitative weighted criteria evaluation for choosing optimal design outcomes. In essence, Ostrofski's design process is designed to create multiple designed outcomes that are quantitatively defined in the most appropriate manner to enable the efficient application of his preferred decision-making method.

In summary, the models of design process that emerged in the 1970s followed from the systematic definitions of the 1960s, but extended them in a variety of directions, in most cases with little regard for epistemological and ontological justification or coherency.

7.4 1980-1989: Mechanistic, mathematical, informatic and commercial models of design process, design as product development

In the early 1980s, some of the world's most prominent design methodologists expressed their dissatisfaction with the systematic design methods they had developed. This is seen in Jones' change of direction in *Essays in Design* (Jones, 1984a) and his discussion of design methodology in Jones (1984b). Similarly, Alexander (1980) argued for the importance of human values in designing, and, in 1984, spoke out against models of design process and methodology of the sort that he had devised in the mid 1960s. In spite of these criticisms the design research field

continued in a positivist direction building rigid models of design process that were intended to result in the automation of design.

As in the 1960s and 1970s, many of these definitions of design process were couched in the concepts and terminology of the parent domain from which they emerged. For example, Furman (1981) an engineering design researcher, suggested a definition of design process similar to that of Haugen (1980) that was mechanistic and defined by forces, geometry and movement. Like Haugen, in parts he confused engineering theories that are used to provide useful information for designers with engineering design theory. Yet, Furman did not totally equate design theory with engineering theory because he argued that, in engineering, playing games with words, numbers, diagrams, graphs and computer programs had become an end in itself and that, 'the fact that they are models (approximations) only of the real physical world has often been lost sight of'.

Fukuda's (1983) description of the design process used in the design of large scale structures echoed Rittel's (1972a, 1972b) concepts of wicked design. He claimed that:

- *There are many 'difficult to quantify' factors involved in design and fabrication.*
- *Most structures, especially large ones, are produced to order. Therefore there is almost always the problem of lack of data.*
- *Various conditions in design and manufacturing change remarkably from structure to structure.*
- *Influencing factors are too many and too diverse, and furthermore the relations among these factors are too complicated.*
- *The quality does not depend upon a single manufacturing process alone, so that the interacting effect of processes must be taken into account*

Fukuda suggested that in a design process for large-scale structures it is important to fully utilise the limited amount of information and experience, and to extract the common and unvarying conditions of design and manufacturing. Fukuda's outlook on design process was pragmatic, and included humans as a way of addressing the particular difficulties in designing in this domain. Domain issues influenced Fukuda differently from Furman (1981) or Haugen

(1980) in that his model of design process is directly tied to practice whereas the descriptions of design process from Furman and Haugen are built from the concepts and language that are a part of engineering analysis in their domains.

Biggioggero and Rovida (1985) presented a logical schematic model of design process based on the cataloguing of mechanical functions in order of increasing complexity. This is another example of a model that has its roots in the theoretical concepts of its associated domain. They noted that characterising the required mechanical functions had two distinct phases: qualitative choices and quantitative determinations. Their logical model of design process was well-suited to quantitative determinations or choices, but it is unclear how qualitative choices were incorporated into their design process.

Milacic and Polopovic (1985) defined a process for conceptual design in terms of the application of the theory of automata. They viewed conceptual design as a knowledge-based activity and, using a taxonomy of conceptual design information, they applied the theory of automata to these building blocks of knowledge. They concluded that the combination of theory of cybernetics, mathematical linguistics and theory of automata may be a basis for a general theory of conceptual design. They noted, however, that there are problems in defining a programming language for such a purpose and that optimisation methods must be performed through derivatives of regular expressions or other methods for converting non-deterministic automata into finite state deterministic automata. In essence, Milacic and Polopovic's model of design process is intended to facilitate the application of their mathematical methods, and, like the proposals of Harrison (1974), transferred much of the effort, intuition and creativity, and perhaps the designing, into defining the problem in the correct way.

Kuno, Kawagoe and Managaki (1985) also suggested the mathematical representation of design knowledge as the basis for a computerised design process. It appears however that, their proposals were tested only on design problems which were trivial or well defined. Their design process consisted of a two part sequence of 'primary' design and 'detailed' design. 'Primary' design is where designers collect together user's requirements and arrange and analyse them into specifications which the designers then use iteratively to determine reasonable objectives

corresponding to the user's requirements, until a satisfactory design solution is reached. 'Detail' design referred to the design activities of determining geometry and other specific information in detail and was mainly concerned with properties such as size, heat flow and stress. Kuno et al noted that in real design situations 'primary design knowledge is undertaken within design paradigms whereby the design knowledge moves from concrete to abstract and vice versa in a dynamic fashion', whereas 'detailed design involves more practical directly related information'. They suggested that this is the reason why it was found difficult to model the primary design process. Kuno et al produced a view of design process that separates those essentially human aspects of designing from the mechanical determinable process relating to the manipulation of information. By assuming that knowledge and information are equivalent and that the essence of designing is the identification of correct information they failed to identify the epistemological and practical difficulties involved in attempting to devise a mechanistic process that includes human creativity.

The computer aided version of the engineering design process devised by Eversheim, Abolins and Buchholz (1989) had it as a linear flow chart relating to the stages of product development. In an epistemological sleight of hand they defined design process so as to exclude most of those elements which have proved intractable to other researchers. Their stages of product development are:

- Planning
- Conceptual (sic) Design
- Design
- Detailing

They excluded, however, 'Planning', 'Conceptual Design' and 'Detailing' from their model of design process. The design process was defined in terms of design activities that are separated into 'object neutral' activities and 'object specific' activities. 'Object neutral' design activities were data collection and calculations which might relate to any machine, for example, choices of bolt sizes or bearings. 'Object specific' design activities included the collection of data and

calculations which are specific to the particular artefact being designed. In effect, they defined design process in terms of engineering calculations and the collection of engineering data, and, in this sense, their model of design process is engineering theory rather than design theory.

Dittmayer and Sata (1985) developed a mathematically based design process aimed at optimising product development. Their design process was divided between algorithmic and axiomatic approaches. Their algorithmic approach included the methods of mathematical analysis, and their axiomatic approach was based on axiomatic rules of thumb which have corollaries and which formed a decision-guiding structure. Dittmayer and Sata used a 'Universal Model of a Planning Process' to manage a design process defined in terms of their 'Product Development Model' (PDM). The PDM was divided into elements containing sub-elements of solution/evaluation/decision that could be arranged in series or parallel. Arranging the elements serially enabled modelling to be done firstly, at an abstract level and then at a more detailed level. Arranging the elements in parallel allowed the possibility of dividing the problem into units whose design might proceed in parallel. They concluded their analysis with four pieces of advice on using their systematic process of product development:

- Analyse existing products critically.
- Apply personnel resources to developing a large number of alternative solutions at an abstract level - without concrete detail.
- If final solutions have been developed using systematic procedures then the final choice is less critical.
- Do not use algorithmic methods when dealing with complex problems. Proceed iteratively.

In summary, Dittmayer and Sata's underlying perspective on design process was of making the best choice between a number of possible options that each satisfied the initial 'needs' or design constraints. Their algorithmic and axiomatic approaches were both to this end. The use of the term 'synthesis' implied the assembly of permutations of solution elements in the manner of the

structure of their model of design process, and if this is the case then their model avoided all consideration of issues of human creativity and intuition.

For Arora (1985), iteration was the main characteristic of his mathematically based model of Optimum Design Process. His model, which was grounded in the domain of systems engineering, consisted of:

- System Specification.
- Preliminary Design.
- Detailed Design.
- Prototype System Fabrication.
- System Testing.

The model had feedback and feed forward paths, and was used to facilitate the application of algorithmic optimisation methods to the evolution of a design. There were other differences in the detail between Arora's Optimum Design Process and more conventional models of design process, particularly in the areas of needs analysis and evaluation of potential solutions. For example, the initial 'needs analysis' of traditional design processes was replaced in the Optimum Design Process by the 'identification of design variables, the cost function and constraints'. Similarly, the evaluation stage of the traditional design process, which involved assessing whether the solution performs satisfactorily, was replaced in the Optimum Design Process by comparing the design solution with its constraints and checking whether it satisfied convergence criteria. In addition, the traditional optimisation of design solutions via experience and heuristics was replaced in Arora's model by the mathematical optimisation of design variables in relation to the cost function. Arora claimed that the main gains of Optimum Design were that the designer needed to explicitly identify: the relevant set of design variables, a cost minimisation function and the constraints on the system. Arora's proposals are relevant to design situations that have a singular optimisation function, are well constrained and have quantitative variables whose relationships are well defined. It is not obvious, however, how well they are suited to design situations in which the variables, relationships and constraints are

not related by simple mathematical functions, or not realistically expressible in numeric form, or where the optimisation process requires minimisation of many interrelated functions.

Dieter (1983) argued that, although optimisation procedures in a design process are intellectually pleasing and technically interesting, they often have limited application in a complex design situation. He stated that there is no universally acclaimed set of steps which leads to a workable design and claimed that design process is best represented by a chain of simple feedback loops of elements of 'information'/'design operation'/'evaluation'. Dieter suggested an arbitrarily chosen model of design process consisting of the following steps:

- Recognition of need.
- Definition of problem.
- Gathering of information.
- Conceptualisation.
- Evaluation.
- Communication.

He noted that sometimes the above steps might be carried out in parallel, and that feedback leading to iteration is expected. The underlying metaphor of Dieter's proposals was that design is problem-solving, and, from this perspective, Dieter identified that the final design depends on the viewpoint of whoever formally defines the problem situation. Dieter understood that qualitative issues involving human values have an important role in designing, and suggested that evaluation be performed by an impartial external reference panel. His overall preference for a quantitative perspective is evident from his proposals that human values and/or other qualitative issues should be expressed in terms of a quantitative measure of utility, ranging from 1 to 10, and that a multiattribute utility function should be used where necessary to combine individual utility functions. The core epistemological characteristics of Dieter's model of design process are those of pragmatism, problem-solving and positivism.

In 1982, Newell proposed an additional level in the hierarchy of system design which he called the 'knowledge level'. The significance of Newell's proposal for design research was that it appeared to address many of the conceptual difficulties relating to the representation of information and knowledge and their relationships with other aspects of design process. Newell explained the role of his 'knowledge level' in relation to the following hierarchy of electronic systems:

- Computer program (symbolic level).
- Register level.
- Logic circuit level.
- Circuit level.
- Electronic device level.

Newell's 'knowledge level' lies above the symbolic level and is characterised by knowledge as the medium on which rationality acts. From a positivist perspective, the 'knowledge level' integrated easily into models of human cognition provided that the human brain was viewed as a computer system and it was assumed that humans behave rationally. In effect, however, Newell's proposal simply moved the epistemological difficulties relating to the representation of the creative aspects of designing to a different theoretical nexus, because this computer based model of human cognition did not adequately include the phenomenological and contextual issues related to the way that creative thought depends on human values. These phenomenological and contextual issues challenge the basis of Newell's assumptions about the characteristics of knowledge and human rationality. Newell identified and attempted to address the challenge to rationality via Simon's (1982) concept of 'bounded rationality', but the difficulties relating to the dependence of knowledge and human cognition on human valuing remain. Newell's proposal of a 'knowledge level' was, and is, significant for those establishing positivist models of design process because it provided epistemological foundations for a quantitatively expressed relationship between design information and a rational basis for decision-making, and was well suited to situations in which designing is viewed as equivalent

to searching through a solution space filled with quantitatively expressed objects. The weaknesses of Newell's proposal are those that can be attributed to its positivist outlook on cognition.

Clausing and Ragsdell (1985) argued that different models of design process are appropriate to different cultures and to different product development processes. In support of this position they cited the differences between models of design process in the USA and Japan. They claimed that it is difficult to separate design from other parts of product development, and produced a three-dimensional sequential and iterative model of the product development process that included the categories of : Needs, Concepts, Design, Parameter Design, Tolerance Design, Data Transfer, Produce, Test, Review, Improve. They defined design process as decision-making in a manner that they attributed to Harrisburger:

The design process is a trial and error sequence of choices among a number of alternatives, in which each decision is affected by compromise between a number of conditions and constraints. It demands meticulous attention to detail, co-ordination of a wealth of information, the search for ideas at each stage, and an overall necessity to achieve the best performance at the lowest cost in the shortest time.

In short, Clausing and Ragsdell's model of design process was informatic and focused on decision-making, search and optimisation.

Hein (1985) viewed the design process as part of a concurrent model of product development in which the design of the product happened in parallel with the collection of market information, the establishment of a sales structure and the development of the production facility. He argued against a serial model of product development, and claimed that it is important to avoid a situation where the responsibility and information relating to a new product is developed and handed over from marketing to design to production and then sales. Hein's model of design process was participatory and commercial in the sense that all stakeholders or contributors to the design of the product contributed during the design process to maximise the potential profits.

Pugh (1985) argued that the conceptual development of designs occurs differently under static and dynamic conditions, and these differences are important in terms of business development and require two different models of systematic design process. He claimed that the ultimate success of a product arrived at by systematic means depends also on harnessing the creative ability of a multidisciplinary design team within a systematically structured design activity. It is not clear how exactly Pugh used the term 'multidisciplinary', and whether and how he differentiated it from 'interdisciplinary' and 'cross-disciplinary', or whether his use of 'multidisciplinary' would extend to an unrelated collection of experts from different disciplines. Pugh's model of design process was pragmatic, well-structured and addressed practical issues that are not included in other models of design process. Epistemologically, however, Pugh's models of design process were neither well-justified nor coherent, particularly because they depended on addressing a variety of different theoretical entities in an epistemologically similar manner.

Hubka (1985) took an economic rationalist outlook on design stating that,

The design process, like all other human activity, has to achieve the best possible results with the aim of increasing economic benefit for humanity.

He suggested that the aim of engineering design research is to increase the efficiency of engineering design, and tied this argument to the emphasis on rationalisation proposed by Taylor and Gilbreth in the early twentieth century. Hubka noted, firstly, that rationalisation had not been the main aim of design research, and, secondly that although rationalisation had resulted in industrial productivity improvements of over 1000% from 1900 to 1960, productivity of design work increased only 20% in the same period. Hubka argued that further rationalisation should be possible in design practice. In essence, Hubka was proposing that the overriding priority for design research was to prescribe appropriate rational design processes and methods in order to increase the economic benefits. Hubka's analysis did not, however, extend to the necessary political and economic analyses that would, on one hand, indicate in which directions that economic benefit would be distributed and, on the other hand, provide the basis for the development of design processes.

Martyn's (1985) model of design process was also tied to commercial values, but his perspective on design process was societal – a perspective similar to that argued by Dilnot (1982):

The design process involves applications of technology for the transformation of resources, to create a product that will satisfy a need in society. The product must perform its function in the most efficient and economic manner within the various constraints that may be imposed. The major restraint is cost, although other factors such as safety, pollution and legal requirements will have to be considered....The sociological view of a product's place in society must also be considered. This will require an understanding of the structure and needs of society, and any changes that may occur, e.g. occupational changes or wealth, during the lifetime of a product.

Martyn's design process was needs based and socially focused and, in terms of design theory, took an instrumental view of the role of engineering in the manner described in Chapter 1 of this thesis.

For Cross (1989), models of design process are descriptive or prescriptive. 'Descriptive' models of design process are those that describe what typically occurs in designing, whereas 'prescriptive' models are those that prescribe how designing should be undertaken. Cross claimed that prescriptive models are often better regarded as design methodologies because of their focus on algorithmic, systematic procedures. This algorithmic emphasis means that prescriptive models are also mainly concerned with well-defined and well-bounded quantitative problems which are more amenable to numerical definition and a classical mathematical treatment. In the main, Cross took a human-centred focus and regarded designing as a process of solving ill-defined problems. Although he did not state his stance clearly and definitively, it is apparent that Cross regarded a designer as a person who is able to synthesise solutions to problems which do not succumb to algorithmic analytical techniques and also able to perform multi-criteria evaluations of qualitative data. From this perspective, Cross also regarded design as a learning process in which a designer proposed solutions and in the evaluation of these solutions gained further knowledge about the design problem situation. Cross proposed a six stage model of design process that was symmetrical in terms of its attention to the design problem and its solution. The six stages were chosen to assist in the

generation of solutions, to help redefine the problem and to decompose the problem and its solution into sub-problems and sub-solutions. These six stages were:

- Clarifying objectives
- Establishing Functions
- Setting Requirements
- Generating Alternatives
- Evaluating Alternatives
- Improving Details

Cross claimed that it was necessary to have a design strategy to manage the general plan of action for a particular design project and the sequence of particular activities and design methods used. He suggested that a design strategy should assist the designer by providing:

- A framework of intended actions within which to operate.
- A management control function enabling the designer to adapt their actions as they learn more about the problem.

He claimed that designers consciously and unconsciously used a variety of design strategies that included divergent, convergent, prefabricated and random search strategies.

To recap, Cross separated descriptive models of design process from prescriptive models and implied that prescriptive design processes are better regarded as design methodologies. This latter point accords with many of the analyses of this thesis in terms of improving both the terminology of design research and its disciplinary structure. Cross' perspective on design process was that designing is an essentially human activity that involves solving 'wicked' problems and that this also defines it as a learning activity. He did not claim that there is a universally applicable model of design process, and consequently he suggested that managing and planning the design process is an important aspect of designing. In this sense, Cross' position is pragmatic and embraces human, organisational and informatic perspectives.

In summary, the main focus of design research in the 1980s was the automation of designing via either rigid prescriptive processes, mathematical means, or the computerised manipulation of information. Alongside this focus on automatic design, and using the same algorithmic means and positivist perspective, was a strong drive towards developing automatic design optimisation processes. These prescriptive models of design process aligned well with the view that design was a part of a larger, commercially, organisationally and economically defined product development process. The systematic outlook on design process persisted in the background alongside the limited amount of research that maintained an assumption that design should be viewed as an essentially human activity.

7.5 1990-1995: Design process as design method, Total Design, design as reflection-in-action, histories of design intent, grammatically based design processes

The main themes in design research in the first half of the 1990s followed smoothly from the 1980s and moved the mainstream of design research further along the path towards the computer based automation of design. Most models of design process were based on a metaphor of design as transforming quantitatively expressed information, and most research avoided including any analyses relating to specifically human aspects of designing or epistemological correctness. Oxman (1995b), like Cross (1989) above, suggested that research into design process is essentially research into design methodology. From a methodological perspective, the lack of attention by the field to epistemological issues relating to theories of design process is surprising.

The metaphor of design as problem-solving still underpinned much of the research into design process especially in new areas such as software design. For example, Budgen (1995) described several design processes that utilised a problem-solving perspective alongside the conceptual tools of computer programming that focused on manipulating data. The systematic outlook on design process was also evident in many other publications but was used mainly to provide an outline on which to report other research (see, for example, Foqué and Lammineur 1995; Johannes 1992). Pugh (1991) combined the problem-solving and systematic perspectives in a comprehensive three-dimensional prescriptive model of design process that he called 'Total

Design'. His 'Total Design' model covered all aspects of the development of products within an organisation. It included all inputs to the design process from market analysis through design and development to sales, and included output issues such as end of life analysis and recycling. He placed emphasis on the development of a complete product design specification (PDS) prior to any design work being started. The framework that he provided for developing PDS in theory allowed social, ethical and environmental factors to be incorporated via market forces. There appeared, however, to be an assumption that non-technical qualitative factors would be included in a quantitative manner using an economically rational theory of value and utility.

Ullman's (1992) taxonomy of mechanical design characterised the process and the research which accompanied it from much the same perspective as Pugh (1991), but he used a two dimensional hierarchical structure because the purpose of his taxonomy was descriptive. Unlike various other taxonomies of design process, Ullman not only classified information about the designed artefact but also classified information about the environment in which the design was undertaken and the characteristics of designers. The underlying perspective of Ullman's design process taxonomy was positivist and informatic, although his inclusion of considerations relating to design environment and designer characteristics point to the necessity of a post-positivist epistemology.

Dorst and Dijkhuis (1995) contrasted different outlooks on design and claimed that the two main explanations of design process were 'design as a rational problem-solving process' and 'design as a process of reflection in action'. They viewed the rational problem-solving approach as being based on Simon's (1969) theories and the reflective approach as being based on Schön's (1983) *Reflective Practitioner*. They concluded that viewing design as problem-solving was appropriate where design problems were clear cut and strategies were available for solving them, particularly with respect to information and the embodiment phases of designing. They regarded the reflection-in-action model as being better suited to the conceptual design stages, and suggested that Schön's (1983) model could be extended to including the rational problem-solving model. Lloyd and Scott's (1994) analysis of the models of design process used in architecture, engineering and computer science points to similar conclusions. They suggested that it is important to include the active agenda of the designer along with the designer's

behaviour in developing a description of design process and that rational models of design process that were based on information about the design problem were insufficient to that task. In epistemological terms, the above perspectives do not appear to take account of the necessity for epistemological coherency in developing structural relationships between theoretical elements.

In 1992, Schön and Wiggins extended the reflective model of human activity and argued that viewing design as a reflective process strongly implicated the medium that designers used to record their designs. On the basis of observations of designers, they concluded that definitions of design process must take account of the fact that designers work in a medium, particularly that most designers work in a visual medium which conditions how they design. Their conclusions are supported by Goldschmidt (1994) and Tovey (1992a).

Ganeshan, Garrett and Finger (1994) also emphasised the role of the human designer but focused on providing a framework for design process for documenting the history of the designer's intentions through the course of designing a product. This outlook on design process is similar to that expressed by Jones (1970) and argued by Parnas and Clements (1986). This conceptualisation of design process as 'what designing happened in this situation' rather than 'how design should happen', or 'how designing happens in general' is essentially informatic. It contains information about the sequence in which design decisions were made, along with information about what decisions were made and why. In theory, the design process might include reference to qualitative phenomenological considerations, but, if Parnas and Clements advice was followed, the model of design process would be a rational and logical explanation that would filter out the arrationally of intuition and creativity. This makes sense from many viewpoints, but rationalisation of the design process record is likely to be unhelpful in the case where a design process history must be reviewed in detail, for example, in searching for new ideas or investigating a design failure.

The epistemological difficulties that relate to the research drive to automate designing were eased in the 1990s by greater agreement that the role of informatic design research developments was to assist human designers rather than to result in automatic design activity.

This separated the epistemological issues relating to information about the design problem and solution from the epistemological issues relating to the human aspects of designing, and helped reduce the scope for epistemological, terminological and conceptual confusion. An example of research of this form was the development of a practical model of design process for the design of tubular steel trusses by Tizani and Davies (1994) Tizani and Davies developed a model of design process that was grounded in the current design practice in this domain. Their model of design process and its associated design methods was aimed at improving the quality of information that was available so that it enabled a human designer to make better informed decisions that would improve economic performance. A similar outlook underpinned Platt and Blockley's (1994) research into the development of an integrated computer based system that was aimed at improving the information available to both engineers and business managers in an organisation. The cultural theory that Platt and Blockley used as a basis for their design process was very different from the practical basis of Tizani and Davies' process, and led to an integration of models of product, process and organisation. This integration of the models of design process and design product was based on the earlier analyses of Dias and Blockley (1994) who divided process and product-based models of design into generic elements, and then identified extensive structural equivalence between both sorts of models. The reasons for the similarity between product and process design theories is also found in the meta-theoretical analysis that is defined in Chapter 3 of this thesis. The meta-theoretical perspective suggests that the similarity is due more to the epistemological structure implicit in any human theory-making than any actual similarity between products and processes.

The above models of design process that are aimed at supporting human designers also assist with the management of design and point to the change of emphasis in the early 1990s from 'trying to identify a universal design process' to 'providing the means to choose and manage an appropriate design process'. This can be seen in Whittaker et al's (1995) proposals for the development of an integrated design system (design process) for software design in which 'object-oriented' methods are used via different design process models to develop aids for designers. Similarly, Sivaloganathan et al (1995) identified four different groupings of design processes for use within product development situations, and suggested that models from these

four groups could be incorporated and managed under the 'Design-Function-Deployment' design system.

The final theme analysed in this review of the literature of the period 1990 to 1995 is the linguistic approach to design process. This language-based outlook was found earlier in Harrison (1974) and is supported by the analyses of Cross, Cross and Glynn (1986), Goldschmidt (1994) and Tovey (1992a). The metaphor of design process that underpins the linguistic perspective on design research is that design elements can be regarded as nouns and adjectives and that operations on those elements are regarded as verbs. Examples of the computerisation of design in this manner are found in Coyne (1991a) and Coyne and Yokozawa (1992) in relation to architectural forms. Mullins and Rinderle (1991) extended this outlook into the mechanical arena, and proposed a grammatical approach to engineering design in which the design process consisted of the grammatical transformation of the characteristics of the design requirements, described in a formal language, into the characteristics of the designed solution. They argued that the application of formal grammars within a transformational paradigm opened the way for the computerised automation of design. Rinderle (1991) developed these concepts and demonstrated how a component based design artefact language can be parsed to check conformance to design specifications. One limitation of the grammatical outlook is that all aspects of a design and its context must be expressed in whatever formal language is used regardless of whether it is epistemologically appropriate. In addition, for the process to be epistemologically consistent with other design theory, it is necessary for the underlying assumptions to be consistent with theories relating to human design behaviour.

7.6 Summary

The main trends in the development of definitions of design process during the period 1962 to 1995 follow the development of definitions of design over the same period described in Appendix 1. There is a significant epistemological divide between those definitions of design process that are based on managing and transforming information relating to a design problem and its solution, and those definitions that are based on behaviour of designers. The epistemological differences between these two types of design process models were echoed in

Cross' (1989) differentiation between prescriptive and descriptive models. In most cases, prescriptive models of design process provided a defined sequence through which the design problem was transformed into its solution, and in this respect were mainly concerned with design situations that were well defined and could be rationally, quantitatively and deterministically expressed (Dorst and Dijkhuis 1995). This means that there is little epistemological difference between a prescriptive model of design process and a design method as some researchers have noted (Cross 1989; Oxman 1995b). This has led to the evolution of 'design systems' that include prescriptive models of design process and have essentially the same explanatory and conceptual role as the term 'design process' used to have (See, for example, Sivaloganathan et al 1995; Whittaker et al 1995). Descriptive models of design process that focused on designer behaviour were not as numerous as prescriptive models, but, in most cases, descriptive models used a similar positivist perspective to prescriptive models and this is clearly evident in the recent application of protocol analysis to building descriptive models of design process.(Dorst 1995; Oxman 1995b). An epistemologically helpful change that has occurred in the last decade has been the move towards viewing prescriptive and automated design processes as technical aids for designers. This brings the role of the human designer back to centre stage, but, more importantly, it reduces the epistemological and terminological problems that are associated with the conflation of analyses relating to human activity and the transformation of information.

8. Appendix 3: List of Dewey Call Numbers relating to literature of design research and engineering design research.

The books associated with design research referred to in this thesis were, in the main, found under the Dewey call numbers in Table 32.

Table 32: Dewey call numbers and categories for the focal and background literature of this thesis relating to design.

Dewey Call Number	Dewey Category
003	Generalities; systems
004	Generalities; data processing
005	Generalities; computer programming
006	Generalities; special computer methods
007	Generalities; no longer used
094	Printed books
153	Psychology; mental processes and intelligence
191	Modern Western Psychology; <i>ZZZZ</i>
300	Social Sciences
301	Social Sciences; sociology and anthropology
307	Social Sciences; communities
309	Social Sciences; social science
363	Social Services; other social problems and services
368	Social Services; insurances
371	Education; school management special education
501	Mathematics; philosophy and theory
512	Mathematics; Algebra and number theory
517	Mathematics
519	Mathematics; probabilities and applied mathematics
532	Physics; fluid mechanics; liquid mechanics
541	Chemistry and allied sciences; physical and theoretical chemistry
550	Earth sciences
573	Life sciences; physical anthropology
601	Technology (Applied Sciences); philosophy and theory
604	Technology (Applied Sciences); special topics

606	Technology (Applied Sciences); organisations
607	Technology (Applied Sciences); education, research, related topics
608	Technology (Applied Sciences); invention and patents
609	Technology (Applied Sciences); historical, areas, persons treatment
615	Medical Sciences Medicine; pharmacology and therapeutics
616	Medical Sciences Medicine; Diseases
620	Engineering and Allied Operations
621	Engineering and Allied Operations; applied physics
624	Engineering and Allied Operations; civil engineering
627	Engineering and Allied Operations; hydraulic engineering
629	Engineering and Allied Operations; other branches of engineering
636	Agriculture; animal husbandry
658	Management and auxiliary services; general management
660	Chemical engineering
709	The Arts; historical, areas, persons treatment
711	Civic and landscape art; area planning (civic art)
720	Architecture
725	Architecture; public structures
727	Architecture; buildings for education and research
729	Architecture; design and decoration
745	Drawing and decorative arts; decorative arts

The literature relating to design can also be found under the Dewey call numbers and categories of Table 33.

Table 33: Additional Dewey call numbers and categories that apply to aspects of the literature of design research

Dewey Call Number	Dewey Categories
100	Philosophy and psychology
101	Philosophy and psychology; theory of philosophy
120	Epistemology, causation, humankind
121	Epistemology, causation, humankind; epistemology (theory of knowledge)
126	Epistemology, causation, humankind; the self
127	Epistemology, causation, humankind; the unconscious and the sub

	conscious
140	Special philosophical schools
142	Special philosophical schools; critical philosophy
144	Special philosophical schools; humanism and related systems
148	Special philosophical schools; Liberalism, eclecticism, traditionalism
149	Special philosophical schools; other philosophical systems
150	Psychology
152	Psychology; perception, movement
154	Psychology; subconscious and altered states
158	Psychology; applied psychology
160	Logic
161	Logic; induction
162	Logic; deduction
165	Logic; fallacies and sources of error
167	Logic; hypotheses
168	Logic; argument and persuasion
169	Logic; analogy
170	Ethics
171	Ethics; systems and doctrines
174	Ethics; economic and professional ethics
178	Ethics; ethics of consumption
179	Ethics; other ethical norms
190	Modern Western Philosophy
400	Language
401	Language; philosophy and theory
410	Language; linguistics

Table 32 and Table 33 above indicate the wide range of categories that different elements or aspects of design research have been or can be classified in.

9. Appendix 4: *DesignWeb Researchers' Database 1996* [on-line]

The following is a screen capture of the text of the *DesignWeb Researchers' Database 1996*. Available WWW: http://www.bath.ac.uk/Depart-ments/Eng/design/dweb/offer/resint_form.html.

Researchers' Database

Add Yourself to DesignWeb Database

(With an experimental taxonomy)

To add yourself to the Researchers' Database simply fill-out the following form.

UK Data Protection Act (1984): This information is held on a computer. Any information held here may be distributed (electronically or otherwise) to other parties.

Please: DO NOT use any HTML within the first two sections of this form (ie Personal Details and Contact Points).

1. Personal Details

Full Name:
Position:
Organisation:

Address:

Telephone:
Fax:
e-mail:
www:

2. Current Research

Please brief describe of your current research interests, your research group and your academic background. You can say anything you like about yourself in this box however your entry may be edited in the future.

Note: You CAN use HTML, including links, within this section.

3. FIELDS OF INTEREST

Please select from the following fields those which you feel best describe your interests and expertise.

3.1 Broad Areas of Design:

Design Theory Paradigms Design Process
Design History Design Archive Design Methods
Methodologies Simulation Design Hardware
Integration Representation Design Environments
Human Factors Technical Systems Design Management
AI in Design Des. Analysis Product Development

3.2 Design Phase:

Innovative Specification Conceptual
Configuration Adaptive Variant
Routine Embodiment Detailed
Verification Maintenance

3.3 Product Realisation Process:

Life-cycle Design Concurrent Engineering
Agile Manufacturing Rapid Prototyping
Virtual Prototyping Virtual Manufacturing
Sequential Engineering Systematic Design
Team-Based Other

3.4 Design Domain:

Industrial Engineering Architectural
Structural VLSI Electronic
Electrical Mechanical Hydraulic
Kinematic Control System Mechatronic
Software Hardware Co-Design
Systems Offshore Aerospace
Aeronautical Robot Vision Systems
Manufacturing Cell Manufacturing Process
Manufacturing Plant Assembly Cell
Assembly Process Assembly System
Man-Machine Interface Instruments

3.5 Design for X:

Function Manufacture Assembly
Maintenance Service Environment
Cost Safety Reliability
Recycling Ergonomics Quality
Production Fabrication Control
Inspection Construction Continuous Improvement

3.6 Product Types:

Large One-off Products Small One-off Products
Large-Batch Products Small-Batch Products
Virtual Products Real Products

3.7 Design Tools/Aids for:

Computer Aided Design Design Optimisation
Decision Support CAD Logic
Group Design Support Concurrent Engineering
Design and Manufacture Intelligent Design Systems

3.8 Application of Mathematical and Computational Techniques:

Expert System Geometric Modelling
Neural Networks Simulated Annealing
Machine Learning Genetic Algorithms
Adaptive Search Symbolic Computing
Numerical Analysis Statistical Analysis
Pattern Recognition Relational Databases
Obj-Oriented Databases Distributed Databases
Data Modelling Information Modelling
Artificial Intelligence Optimization
Finite Elements Data Fusion
Scientific Visualisation Data Mining
Human-Computer Interface Communication in Design Groups
Graphic Modelling Design Grammars/Languages
Shape Grammars/Languages Formal Methods
Data Exchange Feature Grammars
Bond graph Operations research
System science Cybernetics
Dynamic programming Qualitative physics
Statistical optimisation Multi-media systems

3.9 Specific Activities/Sub-problems in Product Development

Feature Modelling Product Modelling
Material and Process Selection Material Selection
Process Selection Component Selection
Process Planning Assembly Planning
Requirements Engineering Specification
Verification Validation
Visualisation Layout Design
Decision Support Optimization
Reliability Engineering Design Education
Quality Engineering Value Engineering
System Simulation Cost Estimation

3.10 Manufacturing Materials

Materials Selection Materials Databases
Materials Design Polymers
Advanced Composite Materials Process Selection

Polymer Processing Polymer Composite Materials
Metal Matrix Composites Structural Brickwork

3.11 Specific Artefact Design:

Bolted and other connections Shaft-hub connections
Mechanical Power Transmission Plastic gears
Solid Lubrications for Bearings Ultra-high performance systems
Construction machinery Machines
Standard parts design Selecting Standard Components
Modelling of assemblies Optimization of assemblies
Thermodynamic systems Land vehicles
Noise and vibration Friction and wear in machines
Mobile Robots Programmable electro-mechanical products
Precision engineering Mechatronics
Aerospace crew system Sensors
Impact loading and dynamics Machine parts
Machine design Mechanisms
High speed machinery Seawave energy converters
Gas turbines Thermal design
Impact buffer modelling Biomedical equipment design
Offshore equipment design User Interface
Engineering design in plastics Hydraulic machines and systems
Machine elements Prosthesis design
Tool manufacturing Rapid prototyping
Interdisciplinary systems Engineering systems

3.12 Miscellaneous Topics in Product Development

(In broad groupings)

Computer-Aided Design (CAD)
CAD System Architectures CAD Frameworks
CAD Methods CAD Management Systems
Intelligent CAD CAD/CAM/CIM
CAD Integration CAD tools for early design stages
Documentation problem in CAD Documentation problem in design
Drafting

Group Design

Design team coordination Design coordination
Teamwork in engineering design Multi-function design teams
Interaction in design Cooperative design
Collaborative design Group design
Cooperating expert systems Communication in distributed groups
Team design protocol analysis CSCW
Cooperative problem solving Team communication
Virtual Co-location

Social Aspects of Design

Social design process Ethnographic studies of CAD
Behavioural models Anthropology of engineering RandD

Cognitive psychology Cognitive processes in design
Question-asking and design Product Aesthetics
Development studies Psychology of technical creativity

Quality Issues in Design

Engineering design and quality Quality function deployment (QFD)
Total quality management(TQM) Working Environment and Quality
Quality of design Design function deployment (DFD)
Taguchi's methods Quality control
Quality assurance

Form-Function Issues

Form and function Geometric reasoning
Form-generation theories Tolerance theories
Geometric Tolerances Tolerance analysis

Information Management

Information science Information processing
Manufacturing info systems Design info systems
Design information flow Data management
Electronic catalogues Engineering catalogues
Design databases Engineering databases
EDA and EDI standards Enterprise modelling
Enterprise integration Logistics
Life-cycle modelling Life-cycle analysis
EDIF STEP
CAL S EDI
VHDL CFI

Design Science

Robust design Structured methodology
Methodical design Systematic design
Systems methods Parametric design
Incremental design Iteration in design
Optimal design Meta-design theory
Domain-independent design Praxiology
System theory Theory of technical systems
Engineering design science Design research bibliography
Terminology for design Design taxonomy
Design logic Design thinking
Design architectures Design rules
Design axioms Axiomatic design
Design guidelines Function-based design
Descriptive studies Prescriptive studies
Design for production Structural identification
Design evaluation Imprecision in design
Uncertainty Incompleteness
Total design Integration with engineering science
Design diagnostics Design repair
Design curriculum Reverse engineering
Configuration design Configuration optimisation
Configuration evaluation Circuit simulation

Design analysis Evaluation in design
Design languages Generative systems
Constraint languages Constraint models
Constraint processes Constraint management
Design reasoning

Machine Learning Issues

Machine learning in design Case-based reasoning
Design knowledge capture K-Based design systems
K-Based design selection Structure of Knowledge
Knowledge reuse Domain ontologies
Design archives Design reuse
Design automation Design support environment
Agent-based design Actors model
Design rationale Corporate memory

Innovation Issues

Innovation strategies Creative thinking in design
Creative design process Design creativity
Creativity in design Management of innovation
Product planning Computational processes for creative design
Structured planning Categorization and analogical reasoning
Sketching Experimental design

Design Process

Abstraction in designing Theory of planning and design
Design models Engineering design process
Design process models Design process theory
Design process analysis Designing design process
Planning of design activities Organisation of design activities

Industrial Implementation and Management

New product search Design Economics
Design change management Productivity in engineering design
Trade-off analysis Methodologies for better productivity
Case studies Yield maximization
Virtual processing Control patterns in production chain
Adaptive architectural systems Industrial implementation
IT in design Design systems for production facilities
Product realisation models Architectures for product realization
Design automation Management of technology transfer
Product lines RandD-Design Interface
Tendering and Cost estimation Business Processes and BPR
Team cultures Version management

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Pravir Chawdhry (P.K.Chawdhry@bath.ac.uk)

10. Appendix 5: Four lists of the characteristics and skills of human engineering designers

10.1 Cross (1989)

Cross (1989) defined the necessary skills of designers as,

- Creativity.
- Intuition.
- The use of technical drawing conventions.
- The ability to associate mental concepts of artefacts with technical drawings and other representations.
- The ability to think subjectively.
- The ability to refine by iteration.
- Analysis.
- Knowledge.
- Skills with methods of engineering science.
- The ability to deal with problem and solution together.
- The ability to sketch and model to externalise and clarify complex situations.
- To be able to evaluate against design criteria.
- The ability to live or function in an area of uncertainty.
- The ability to communicate with specialists.

10.2 Eder (1995)

Eder (1995) claimed that creativity in design depended upon designer's being able to draw on all the following skills simultaneously,

- An adequate knowledge of relevant objects and principles (including tacit knowledge).

- A knowledge of processes - especially design and problem-solving processes. These should be intuitively or consciously available to the designers.
- Adequate judgement.
- An open minded attitude along with a sense of care and attention.
- Sufficient motivation.
- An ability to communicate appropriately.
- An appropriate level of stress.
- Recognition and ownership of the existence of a problem.

Eder argued that the characteristics and skills that he listed were prerequisites for creativity but that they did not guarantee it. He claimed that creativity occurs as a natural tension between the intellectual and intuitive mental modes and suggested that a problem is first recognised in the rational aspects of the mind, then a sense of dissatisfaction in the intuitive mental mode causes a rational solution to be found. Although Eder brings feelings into his argument, via dissatisfaction and satisfaction, he does not include physical feeling – for Eder, ‘feelings’ are totally cerebral.

10.3 Glegg (1971)

For Glegg (1971) the mind of a designer had three realms of activity:

- The inventive: which can be encouraged by filling the mind and the imagination with the context of the problem and then relaxing and thinking of something else.
- The artistic: which is to do with style.
- The rational: disciplined thinking applied over the entire field of design from theoretical analysis to economic realities.

10.4 Nevill and Crowe (1974)

For Nevill and Crowe (1974) human engineering designers had the following main characteristics,

- A very large (in fact, the principal) source of information regarding the problem space, (perhaps stored in long term memory as a list structure).
- A very flexible capability for extensive processing of small quantities of information.
- The ability to concentrate on only one thing at a time.
- The ability to utilise illogical thoughts, to pretend, to dream, to fantasise.
- The ability to operate with incomplete information, draw inference, make intuitive leaps.
- A large set of experiences indicating how things can and 'should' be done.
- Certain strong habits, inhibitions or patterns of thinking and designing.
- A significant number of conceptual blocks including those of perceptual, emotional, cultural and environmental nature.
- Many prejudices and preconceived ideas about the world, most of which are subconscious.
- Performance significantly dependent upon emotional state.
- Highly stimulated and motivated by interactions with others.
- A finite quantity of energy, limited attention span and availability, gets tired, bored, frustrated, sleepy.
- Very broad communicative abilities, sensitive to realm of beliefs and feelings.
- Finds it basically enjoyable to use a large powerful machine which has the characteristics of a personal friend who offers unconditional acceptance and support.